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Zamfara International Journal of Science Technology Education and Mathematics (ZIJSTEM) is the official Journal of the Department of Science Education, Faculty of Education Federal University Gusau Zamfara State, Nigeria. The Journal publishes articles of diverse fields of interest in Sciences, Technology, Education and Mathematics. Papers reporting original research and extended version of already established conference and journal articles are welcomed. Papers for publication are selected through peer review process to ensure originality, relevance and readability. ZIJSTEM is published quarterly which spans throughout the year i.e. March, June, September and December, respectively.

The aim and scope of the journal is to provide an academic medium and an important references for the advancement and dissemination of information that supports high level learning, teaching and research in the fields of Sciences, Technology, Education and Mathematics.

The articles in this volume are academic and professional discourse written by reputable scholars in their area of specialization.

Professor Bashir Suleiman

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FORWARD

On Behalf of the staff and students of the Department of Science Education, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara state, Nigeria, we humbly acknowledge and thank Allah (S.W.T) the most beneficent, the most merciful for without his will, collection and computation of this journal publication would not have been possible. May all praise be ascribed unto Him. The department is sincerely grateful to its accommodating mentor Prof. M.G. Abubakar, Vice Chancellor, Federal University, Gusau and his management team for giving the department enabling environment for academic activities. The department's profound gratitude goes to Dr. Umar Sodangi who doubled as the Dean, Faculty of Education, Federal University, Gusau and Associate Editor of Zamfara International Journal of Science, Technology, Education and Mathematics (ZIJSTEM). Furthermore, Special gratitude goes to our contract and visiting Professors, the staff and students of the Department of Science Education, Federal University, Gusau, for their supports and foresight towards actualizing the dream of the department.

The Zamfara International Journal of Science, Technology, Education and Mathematics (ZIJSTEM) is a brain child of Department of Science Education with the aim of bringing science and technology education into global and well recognized journals of science and technology education research. This is first of its kind, among Science Education Departmental Journals in Northwest, Nigeria and by extension one of the highly placed departmental journal in Nigeria, considering its online visibility and originality, based on well-known global best practices.

Dr. Nuhu Ishaq Lawal

Associate Editor/Head of Department,
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The Zamfara International Journal of Science, Technology, Education and Mathematics (ZIJSTEM) calls for scholarly articles for review and possible publication in its next edition (Volume 2, Number 1.), ZIJSTEM publishes articles that emphasizes on research development and application within the field of Sciences, Technology, Education and Mathematics. All manuscripts are reviewed by editorial review committee. Contributions must be original, not previously or simultaneously published elsewhere, and are critically reviewed before they are published. Papers, which must be written in English language, should have good grammar and proper terminologies.

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Effects of Computer-Assisted Instruction on Performance in Programming Concepts among College of Education Computer Science Students in North-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the Effects of Computer Assisted Instruction on Performance in Programming Concepts among Colleges of Education Computer Science Students in North-West, Nigeria. The population of the study consists of 1204 (Male 695 and female 509) NCE II computer science students during 2024/25 academic session among colleges of education in Northwest, Nigeria. A sample size of 120 (60 male and 60 female) were selected from the target population using a multi-stage sampling technique. 60 students were used for Experimental and the remaining 60 for Control groups. Experimental group were taught using Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) package while control group were taught using lecture method of instruction. Four research questions and hypotheses respectively, were formulated to guide the study. Research questions were answered using descriptive statistics while hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics at 0.05 level of significance. Results obtained showed that students taught with CAI perform better than those taught with lecture method and CAI is also gender friendly. The study concluded that CAI should be encouraged as an effective assistance to both teacher and students for effective teaching and learning.

Keywords: Gender, Programming Concept, Performance and Computer Science Students

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Introduction

The concept of “gender” has attracted the attention of many researchers; biologist, mathematicians, psychologist and others. Gender difference is one of the factors affecting learning; studies on the influence of gender on students’ academic performance have not produced conclusive results. Some findings indicated that significant differences existed between the achievement of male and female students while other findings showed that gender factor has no influence on students’ achievement (Yusuf, 2004). In this study, the differential gender performance of computer science students in programming language skill using concept of “LOOP” is considered. Programming Languages according to French (2006), are languages used to program computer. They are computer languages designed to communicate instructions to a machine, particularly a computer.

This work therefore was conducted to investigate the gender difference in Programming concepts and Performance among Computer Science students in colleges of Education, north-west, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Several studies like Iwendi, 2009, Michael, Omiola and Mohammed (2014), Muchiri (2018), Achuonye (2018), Julious (2018), have been conducted in the area of gender-related differences in academic performance of students in sciences; some noted that males perform better (Iwendi, 2009, Muchiri, 2018), while another study reported females’ superiority in science subjects (Julious, 2018). Some claim no difference among gender (Michael, Omiola & Mohammed (2014), Achuonye, 2018). Poor performance of students in science related courses has also been of a thing of concern for decades of which most researchers claim that poor performance by students mostly, have to do with teaching method and strategies used by the teacher (Eze, Ezenwafor & Molokwu (2015), Ogunniyi, Akerele & Awoyemi, 2021); the concern in recent times is to have science classrooms that are student-centered, activity oriented and focuses on understanding rather than rote-learning and simple recall of knowledge. Again, our students, graduates from school without demonstrating high entrepreneurial skill in their various professions without undergoing serious training and/ or retraining (Ndukwe, P.E. 2016). The contradictive evidences in academic performance due to gender among others, had resulted in the need to verify how Computer Science Programming Test (CSPT) can influence students’ academic performance in computer

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programming concept by gender in computer science. The problem of the study is therefore, to find the Effects of Computer Assisted Instruction on Performance in Programming Concepts among Colleges of Education Computer Science Students in North-West, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study was to investigate the Effects of Computer Assisted Instruction on Performance in Programming Concepts among Colleges of Education Computer science students in North West, Nigeria. Specifically, to:

1. Ascertain the computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education students when taught using Computer Assisted Instruction.
2. Investigate the computer programming skill level of male and female students of Federal Colleges of Education when exposed to Computer Assisted Instruction.
3. Determine the performance of Federal Colleges of Education students when taught using Computer Assisted Instruction.
4. Compare the performance of male and female students of Federal Colleges of Education when exposed to Computer Assisted Instruction.

Research Questions

1. What is the difference between the computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education students taught computer science using the Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using the lecture method?
2. What is the difference between the computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education male and female students taught computer science using the Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught by the lecture method?
3. What is the difference between the mean performance score of Federal Colleges of Education students when taught computer science using Computer Assisted Instruction and when taught by lecture method?
4. What is the difference between the mean performance score of Federal Colleges of Education male and female students when taught computer science using Computer Assisted Instruction and when taught by the lecture method?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at $P \leq 0.05$ level of significance.

(Effects of Computer-Assisted Instruction on Performance ... Ndukuwe, P. E., Et. al. 2025)

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education students when taught Computer Science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught by the lecture method.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between computer programming skill level of male and female Federal Colleges of Education students when taught Computer Science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught by the lecture method.

Ho₃: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students of Federal Colleges of Education taught Computer Science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using the lecture method.

Ho₄: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of male and female students of Federal Colleges of Education taught Computer Science using the Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using the lecture method.

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was the quasi-experimental research design, involving two groups, one experimental and one control. Both groups were pretested each on Programming concept and performance before the administration of treatment to ensure equivalence in level of performance in the experimental groups only; while students in the control group were taught using the lecture method and a Posttest administered after treatment to all groups of students to determine their performance

Population of the study

The population of the study comprised of NCE II Students of Computer Science Education in five Federal Colleges of Education in North West, Nigeria.

S/NO	COLLEGES	NCE 2 MALE	COMPUTER SCIENCE FEMALE	TOTAL
1	Federal College of Education Kano	173	78	251
2	Federal College of Education Katsina	74	75	149
3	Federal College of Education Zaria	232	170	402

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4	Federal College of Education (T) Bichi	216	108	324
5	Federal College of Education (T) Gusau	0	78	78

TOTAL		695	509	1,204
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Departmental records, 2023/2024 academic sessions

Sample and Sampling Techniques

Two (2) colleges were selected using simple multi-stage sampling technique from the five (5) Federal Colleges of Education: they are Federal College of Education, Zaria (FCEZ) and Federal College of Education (Technical) (FCE(T)), Bichi. Five Subject combinations were sampled by the simple random sampling (balloting) from the seven combinations available in the colleges namely: Mathematic/Computer, Chemistry/Computer, Physics/Computer, Biology/Computer and Economics/Computer. Six students were then selected using the simple random sampling comprising of three male and three female computer Science students from each of the five computer combinations. This gives sixty (60) students per selected college; thirty (30) male and thirty (30) female students. This gives a total of 120 students and according to Tuckman (1975) and Sambo (2008), the Central Limit Theorem recommended a minimum of 30 ($N \geq 30$) subjects for experimental study of this nature. Hence the sample of 120 students is viable for this study. Equal number of male and female students, (60 for both male and female) for the research was used to avoid gender bias.

Instrumentation

Two validated instruments were used to collect data for the study; Computer Science Performance Test (CSPT) with reliability coefficient of 0.83 when subjected to Pearson Product Moment of Correlation and the Computer Science Computer Programming Concept Inventory (CPLSI) with a Cronbach value of 0.75 which ascertained their reliabilities. The instruments were validated by two senior Computer Science lecturers who have taught Programming Languages for over ten years in colleges of Education.

Data Analysis

Research questions were answered using descriptive statistics while hypotheses were tested using inferential statistics at 0.05 level of significance

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Presentation of Result

Research Question 1

What is the difference between the computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education students taught computer science using the Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method?

Table 1: Mean Rank scores of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean Rank		Mean Rank Difference
		Pretest	Posttest	
Experimental	60	40.95	77.43	36.48
Control	60	40.05	43.57	3.52

From Table 1, the experimental group had a higher mean rank (posttest) Computer Programming skill level score of 77.43 compared to that of the control group who had 43.57. Also, it was observed that the mean rank difference of the experimental and control groups was 36.48 and 3.52 respectively.

Null Hypothesis 1

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education students when taught Computer Science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method.

This hypothesis was analyzed using Mann-Whitney U-test as presented in Tables 2.

Table 2: Summary of Mann-Whitney U-Test of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean Rank	Sum of Ranks	U-value	P-value	Remark
Experimental Group	60	77.43	4921.50	508.50	0.001*	S
Control	60	43.57	2338.50			
Total	120					

*Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Table 2 revealed that the Mann-Whitney U-value of 508.50 produced a corresponding P-value of 0.001 which was significant at $P \leq 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. This implies that there is significant difference between the Computer Programming skill level of students taught computer science using the Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) and those taught using the lecture method.

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Research Question 2

What is the difference between the computer programming skill level of Federal Colleges of Education male and female students taught computer science using the Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method?

Table 3: Mean Rank Skills Scores of Male and Female Students in the Experimental and Control Groups

Group	Sex	N	Mean Rank		Mean Rank Difference
			Pretest	Posttest	
Experimental	Male	30	41.95	85.32	43.37
	Female	30	40.55	84.62	44.07
Control	Male	30	43.23	65.95	22.72
	Female	30	42.90	57.18	14.28

The summary of mean Computer Programming skill Level score presented in Table 3 revealed a mean rank (posttest) score of 85.32 and 84.62 respectively for male and female students in the experimental group. In the control group, the mean rank (posttest) score for male and female students was found to be 22.72 and 14.28 respectively. However, the mean rank difference Computer Programming skill level score for the male and female students in both groups was higher for the experimental group (43.37 and 44.07). The control group was observed to have lower mean rank difference (22.72 and 14.28).

Null Hypothesis 2

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between computer programming skill level of male and female Federal Colleges of Education students when taught Computer Science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method.

Table 4: Summary of Kruskal-Wallis H-test for Gender between Experimental and Control Groups

Groups	Sex	N	Mean Rank	H-value	p-value	Remarks
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Experimental	Male	30	85.90	46.97	0.001*	S
	Female	30	84.62			
Control	Male	30	65.95			
	Female	30	57.18			

*Significant at $P \leq 0.05$

Table 4 revealed that a Kruskal-Wallis H-value of 46.97 has a corresponding P-value of 0.001 which was significant at $P \leq 0.05$. Hence, the hypothesis 4 was rejected. This implied that there was a significant difference in the Computer Programming skill level of the groups with respect to gender. In order to ascertain where the difference lied, the data was subjected to the Dunn-Bonferroni post hoc test of multiple comparisons and presented in Table 5.

Table 5: Dunn-Bonferroni post hoc test of Multiple Comparison for Gender between the Experimental and Control Group

Group	Mean Difference	Std Error	P-Value	Remarks
Female control group - Male control group	0.917	8.956	0.918	NS
Female control group - Male Exp. Group	39.633	8.956	0.001	S
Female control group - Female Exp. Grp	47.383	8.956	0.001	S
Male control group - Male Exp. Group	38.717	8.956	0.001	S
Male control group - Female Exp. Group	46.467	8.956	0.001	S
Male Exp. Group - Female Exp. Group	-7.75	8.956	0.387	NS

Table 5 showed that the difference in computer science students Computer Programming Concept was not significant for male and female students of control group and male and female of experimental group. This implied that Computer Assisted Instruction Method of Instruction and lecture method are all gender friendly.

Research Question 3

What is the difference between the mean performance score of Federal Colleges of Education students when taught computer science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method?

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Table 6: Descriptive Statistics of Performance of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Mean	S.D
Experimental group	60	56.25	13.62
Control group	60	45.13	7.44
Total	120		

From Table 6, experimental group had a mean score of 56.25 with a corresponding standard deviation score of 13.62 and the control group had a mean score of 45.13 and standard deviation score of 7.44 respectively.

Null Hypothesis 3

Ho₃: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of students of Federal Colleges of Education taught Computer Science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method.

Table 7: t-test Analysis of Performance between Exp. Group and Control Group

Group	N	Mean	SD	df	t-value	p-value	Remarks
Experimental Group	60	56.25	13.62	58	5.55	0.001*	S
Control Group	60	45.13	7.44				

*Significant at P ≤ 0.05

From Table 7, the p-value 0.001 with its corresponding t-value of 5.55 showed that there is significant difference between experimental group taught with Computer Assisted Instruction and the control group taught with lecture method at P ≤ 0.05 level of significant. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This showed that there was significant difference between the performance of students taught computer science with Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught with lecture method of instruction.

Research Question 4

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What is the difference between the mean performance score of Federal Colleges of Education male and female students when taught computer science using Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method?

Table 8: Descriptive Statistics of Gender of Experimental and Control Groups

Group	Sex	N	Mean	SD
Experiment Group	Male	30	55.20	15.63
	Female	30	57.30	11.45
Control	Male	30	44.50	7.71
	Female	30	45.77	7.23
Total		120		

From Table 8, the mean score and standard deviation of male students of Experimental group were 55.20 and 15.63 while the mean score and standard deviation of the female students of the experimental group were 57.30 and 11.45. For the control group, the mean score and standard deviation score of the female students taught with lecture method were found to be 45.77 and 7.23 respectively while the mean score and standard deviation of their male counterpart were 44.50 and 7.71.

Null Hypothesis 4

Ho₄: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of male and female students of Federal Colleges of Education taught Computer Science using the Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught using lecture method.

Table 9: Analysis of variance for Gender between Experimental and Control Groups

	Sum of Squares	Mean Square	Df	t-value	P-value	Remark
Between Groups	3797.63	8877.58	3	10.39	0.001*	S
Within Groups	5232.25	68.85				
Total	31864.99					

*Significant at P ≤ 0.05

From Table 9 the p-value 0.001 with its corresponding t-value of 10.39 showed that there is significant difference between the experimental group taught with Computer Assisted Instruction and control group taught with lecture method at P ≤ 0.05 level of significant. Hence the null hypothesis was rejected. This showed that there was

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significant difference between the performance of computer students taught with Computer Assisted Instruction and those taught with lecture method of instruction.

To ascertain where the difference lied, the data was subjected to Scheffes post hoc test.

Table 10: Scheffes Post hoc comparison test of Gender of Exp. and Control Group

(I) Gender	(J) Gender	Mean Difference (I-J)	Std. Error	P-value	Remark
Male Exp. Group	Female Exp. Group	-2.10	2.849	0.909**	NS
	Male Cont. group	10.70	2.849	0.004*	S
	Female Cont. group	9.43	2.849	0.015**	NS
Female Exp. Group	Male Exp. Group	2.10	2.849	0.909**	NS
	Male control group	12.80	2.849	0.001*	S
	Female control group	11.53	2.849	0.002*	S
Male control group	Male Exp. Group	-10.70	2.849	0.004*	S
	Female Exp. Group	-12.80	2.849	0.001*	S
	Female control group	-1.27	2.849	0.978**	NS
Female control group	Male Exp. Group	-9.43	2.849	0.015**	NS
	Female Exp. Group	-11.53	2.849	0.002*	S
	Male control group	1.27	2.849	0.978**	NS

*Significant at $P \leq 0.05$, **Not Significant at $P \leq 0.05$,

From Table 10, it was observed that there was no significant different between performance of male and female computer science students of Experimental group (0.909). It was also observed that the performance of male and female computer science students of control group was not significant. This means that CAI and Lecture method of Instruction are gender friendly.

Discussion of Findings

The result in Table 1 showed that there is a difference between the mean ranks of the Programming skill level of experimental and control group in favour of the experimental group. The result was then subjected to Mann-Whitney U-test; it was observed that there was significant mean Computer Programming skill level difference between the students taught with Computer Assisted Instruction method and those taught with

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lecture method of Instruction. This confirms Ifeakor (2005) finding that level of activities involved in learning can improve students learning outcomes; she suggested that manipulating the computer involve some activities and also interesting. Muoneme (2012) opined that instructional package usage in learning motivates students and is a key variable in education as supported by Okoroma (2000), Moris and Aggawal (2007) who added that computer-based instructions not only motivate students' interest but also stimulates several senses thus making the learner more involved consequently setting the students excitement and desire to put in their best during learning.

In Table 3, the respective mean ranks and sum ranks of experimental group compared with that of control group showed that there was higher gender Computer Programming skill level in favour of the experimental group. This was further subjected to Kruskal Wallis H-Test in Table 4. The findings showed that the observed difference in Computer Programming Concept was significant within the two groups. This is supported by research conducted by Balogun (2004), Michael and Rahman (2001) that showed higher skill acquisition when Computer Assisted Instruction is used as learning strategy. This also is in line with the study carried out by Gongden and Gongden (2019), who observed that using CAI in learning improve both male and female learners.

From Table 6, which sought to answer research question three, the students exposed to CAI mode of instruction had a higher mean gain compared with that of the control group. This was found to be in favour of the experimental group which implied that the use of Computer Assisted Instruction learning strategy improved students' academic performance in computer science. The finding was in line with that of Tabassum (2004) who revealed that overall performance of students taught by lecture method, supplemented by Computer Assisted Instruction package, is higher than those taught with lecture method only. It was also supported by Akour (2008) and Ndukwe (2016), who revealed the fact, that lecture method together with computer Assisted Instruction enhances performance.

Table 8 revealed that female students of the experimental group performed better than the male students when CAI was administered. Comparison within the groups was carried out using Analysis of Variance and was subjected to Scheffes post hoc test to ascertain where the difference lied. There was no significance difference in the performance of male and female students taught Computer Science using CAI. This implies that CAI is a gender friendly method for Computer Science Pedagogy. This is in

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line with the findings of Michael, Omiola & Mohammed (2014), Achuonye (2018) who found from their research that Computer Assisted Instruction is gender friendly.

Conclusion

It can be adduced from the findings of this study that in the area of performance, experimental group with use of CAI model (CSPT) of instruction performed significantly better compared with those exposed to Lecture mode of instruction. CAI was observed to improve students Computer Programming skill in Computer Science better than the lecture method only. Hence, CAI should be encouraged as an effective assistance to both teacher and students for effective teaching and learning irrespective of gender.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are offered based on the outcome of this study:

1. Colleges of Education in Nigeria as well as other institutions of higher learning should endeavour to incorporate the development and use of CAI for effective teaching and learning to enhance students' performance in computer science and science related courses in colleges of education.
2. Curriculum planners and school managements should rely on flexible home-based CAI packages as a gender friendly strategy for learning. for better development of education and other sectors in Nigeria.

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Effect of Youtube-Video-Learning Strategy on Performance in Algebra Concepts among Secondary School Students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study explored the effects of YouTube Video-Learning Strategy on the performance in Algebra among senior secondary school students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria. The study adopted a pretest-posttest quasi-experimental design with a single experimental group. The population comprised of 4,001 SS2 Mathematics students from 22 public senior secondary schools during the 2024/2025 academic session in Funtua Educational Zone. A sample of 88 students was selected from target population using multi-stage sampling technique. The experimental group were taught Algebra instruction using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy, while there was no separate control group as the study focused on the effects within the experimental group only. The Algebra Performance Test (APT) was used to collect data. The instrument was validated by experts at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria, and had a reliability coefficient of 0.70, calculated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). Two research questions and two null hypotheses were formulated. Data analysis involved calculating the mean, standard deviation, and mean difference to answer the research questions, while hypotheses were tested using paired sample t-test at a 0.05 significance level. The findings showed no significant gender-based differences in performance within the experimental group. Based on the results, the study concluded that YouTube Video-Learning Strategy are effective for improving performance in Algebra and are gender-neutral. It is recommended that secondary school mathematics teachers incorporate YouTube Video-Learning Strategy in teaching complex concepts like Algebra.

Key words: YouTube Video-Learning Strategy, Algebra, Academic Performance

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Introduction

Mathematics is taught at various educational levels in Nigeria, including the basic, secondary, and tertiary levels, and is considered essential in many aspects of life, as noted by Olanrewaju (2023). De Vera and Balgua (2023) describe Mathematics as the foundation and essence of science and technology. In Nigeria, the formal education system plays a critical role in imparting scientific and mathematical knowledge, developing essential skills, shaping attitudes, and fostering a mindset that values science, particularly Mathematics. Blåsjö (2021) views Mathematics as the cornerstone of all true sciences, asserting that no scientific field can thrive without mathematical principles. Agah (2020) emphasizes the interconnection between Mathematics, science, and technology, stating that without Mathematics, science would not exist, and without science, technology would be impossible—ultimately leading to the absence of modern society. As a result, Mathematics is universally recognized as a core subject, taught in every country around the world, although the language of instruction may vary depending on the official language of each nation (Acharya, Kshetree, Khanal, Panthi, & Belbase, 2021).

Hillmayr, Ziernwald, Reinhold, Hofer, and Reiss (2020) emphasized that Mathematics is a crucial tool for the advancement of science and technology. A nation cannot develop scientifically and technologically without prioritizing the teaching and learning of Mathematics, as it is fundamental for understanding and interpreting concepts in these fields. The National Policy on Education of the Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) recognizes Mathematics as a core subject, mandating that all students, regardless of their discipline, gender, or ability, must study and pass it at a credit level, particularly at the secondary school level. To achieve the goals of Mathematics education, Nigeria, as a developing country, requires modern innovations in teaching and learning processes, which necessitate skilled mathematicians who can help realize these goals. Despite the critical role of Mathematics in development, studies by Ndidi and Effiong (2020) and Eyong, Ugada, and Aminu (2020) show that Nigerian students often perform poorly in Mathematics, citing factors such as lack of teaching materials, Mathematics anxiety, ineffective teaching methods, and inadequate teaching facilities, including equipment and instructional resources. To address these challenges, researchers such as Pattier (2021) and Nabayra (2022) have recommended the use of modern teaching methods, including YouTube videos.

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According to Maziriri, Gapa, and Chuchu (2020), YouTube videos are valuable educational tools that stimulate student engagement and enhance learning by allowing for repetitive viewing, enabling students to fully grasp the concepts being taught. Pratama, Arifin, and Widianingsih (2020) highlighted the influence of television and video materials on learners, noting that they enrich classroom experiences with resources that may not typically be available in traditional settings. Mayer (2021) noted that instructional videos do more than present factual information; they illustrate and contextualize it, enhancing students' understanding by providing visual and auditory elaborations. This combination of sound and images strengthens students' retention of key information. Similarly, Alpizar, Adesope, and Wong (2020) found that the use of multiple sensory channels and rich elaboration of information supports learning and aids in the retention of verbal information. Additionally, Moreno-Guerrero, Rodríguez-Jiménez, Gómez-García, and Ramos Navas-Parejo (2020) emphasized that instructional videos in education are designed to achieve specific objectives, which should positively influence students' attitudes toward learning. According to scholars, Video-Learning Strategy can make learning more permanent and offer valuable experiences for students. When used effectively, Video-Learning Strategy can significantly enhance students' academic performance.

Academic performance is typically measured by the quality of students' test or examination scores, especially in comparison to other students at the same level. Jomuad and Paclipan (2020) describe academic performance as the scholarly standing of a student at a particular point in time. Wang, Hofkens, and Ye (2020) define academic performance as the result produced by students, reflected in the quality of their examination scores. Similarly, Ariastuti and Wahyudin (2022) suggest that academic performance is an indicator of how much a student has learned. Another key variable in this study is gender, which is defined as a set of characteristics that distinguish between males and females (Shahzad, Hassan, Aremu, Hussain, & Lodhi, 2021). Depending on the context, these distinguishing characteristics can range from biological sex to social roles to gender identity. Siddiqi and Shafiq (2017) view gender as a socio-cultural construct that assigns specific roles, attitudes, and values deemed appropriate for each sex. Research by Rodriguez, Regueiro, Piñeiro, Estévez, and Valle (2020) highlights that gender is an important factor influencing academic performance in Mathematics. They argue that the belief that Mathematics is a subject primarily for boys can result in lower motivation among girls, contributing to a wider gender gap in Mathematics achievement, with boys performing better. This disparity often leads to

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lower performance in Mathematics and Mathematics-related subjects among female students. The present study seeks to investigate whether a difference exists in the performance of male and female SS II students in the Funtua Education Zone when taught using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy.

The research study draws upon Dual Coding Theory (DCT), a cognitive framework developed by Allan Paivio in the 1960s. DCT suggests that humans process and represent information both verbally and non-verbally, with mental imagery playing a crucial role in the formation of memory (Paivio, 1991). According to Paivio's theory, the development of verbal understanding is heavily reliant on a strong non-verbal foundation, with both systems working in tandem to process linguistic and visual information. In the context of investigating the impact of YouTube Video-Learning Strategy on algebra performance among senior secondary school mathematics students in Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria, DCT offers valuable insights into how students assimilate mathematical concepts. The incorporation of visual tools such as YouTube videos allows educators to engage both verbal and non-verbal cognitive systems, potentially enhancing students' understanding and retention of algebraic principles. The theory's emphasis on mental imagery aligns with the use of multimedia resources, which have been shown to facilitate learning, especially in abstract subjects like algebra (Reiber, 2000). Additionally, by considering the range from concrete to abstract in knowledge representation, educators can adjust their instructional materials to match students' cognitive preferences, thus potentially improving their performance in algebra. This application of DCT highlights its relevance in educational settings and its potential to inform teaching practices aimed at maximizing student learning outcomes.

Statement of the problem

In recent years, the integration of technology in education has been heralded as a means of enhancing students' academic performance, particularly in abstract and challenging subjects like algebra. However, there is a growing concern regarding how gender differences may influence the effectiveness of technology-based learning tools, such as YouTube Video-Learning Strategy, in secondary school mathematics education (Aliyu, Tijjani & Usman, 2025). Despite the increasing use of multimedia tools in classrooms, limited research has explored how these resources impact male and female students differently, especially in terms of their academic performance in algebra. In

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the context of Funtua Educational Zone, Katsina State, Nigeria, the existing educational strategies may not fully address the potential of digital resources to engage both male and female students equally. Therefore, this study seeks to explore the effects of YouTube video-based learning resources on the performance of male and female senior secondary school mathematics students in algebra. The problem lies in the gap in knowledge regarding whether these resources contribute equally to improving algebra performance across genders, or whether they have a differential impact on male and female students. This study aims to address this gap and provide insights into how gender might influence the efficacy of YouTube Video-Learning Strategy in enhancing algebra performance among secondary school students.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of this study is to:

1. Examine the effect of YouTube Video-Learning Strategy on performance of SS II Mathematics students in algebra by gender.

Research Question

The following research question guided the study;

1. What is the difference between the mean performance scores of male and female SS II students taught algebra using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypothesis were formulated and tested at $p \leq 0.05$ level of significance:

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of male and female SSII students taught algebra using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy.

Methodology

The research design for this study is quasi-experimental, utilizing a pre-test, post-test approach with an experimental group. The study involves only one experimental group, where YouTube Video-Learning Strategy are used to teach algebra, with no

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control group in the analysis. Two intact classes, one designated as the experimental group and the other as the control group, were selected for the study.

The target population for this study includes all SS2 students from 22 public senior secondary schools in the Funtua Educational Zone of Katsina State, with a total of 4,001 students. This group is composed of 2,050 male students and 1,951 female students, with an average age of 17 years. The population includes 18 co-educational schools and 4 single-sex schools, two of which are male-only and two are female-only, all managed by the Katsina State Government. The schools are either day schools or boarding schools.

To select the sample, multi-stage sampling technique was employed. A total of 88 SS2 students were selected as the study sample from one public co-educational school in the Funtua Educational Zone. For data collection, the researcher utilized a single instrument, the Algebra Performance Test (APT), which was created specifically for this study. The APT consists of 40 multiple-choice questions derived from algebra topics, using a table of specifications based on Bloom's taxonomy (1970). The test was evaluated for construct, criterion, and content validity by professors from the Department of Science Education at Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria.

Before the main study, the instrument underwent pilot testing at Kurami Government Senior Secondary School, which is part of the larger population but not included in the sample. A group of 30 students from this school participated in the pilot testing. Following the pilot, the data was analyzed to determine the reliability of the instrument. The reliability coefficient of the APT was calculated using Pearson Product Moment Correlation through SPSS Version 20.0, yielding a reliability coefficient of 0.70. This result indicates a strong positive correlation between the initial and subsequent administrations of the test, demonstrating that the instrument is reliable for the study.

Presentation of Results

Results obtained from the data collected were analyzed as follows:

Research Question One: What is the difference between the mean performance scores of male and female students taught algebra using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy?

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To answer the research question two post test scores from APT for experimental and control groups were subjected to mean and SD. Summary of the findings is in Table 1.

Table 2: Mean, Standard Deviation Statistics of Posttest APT scores for Male and Female Students in Experimental Group

GENDER	N	Mean	STD	Mean difference
Male	51	34.59	1.63	0.39
Female	37	34.19	1.87	

Result of the descriptive Mean statistics showed that there is no difference between the mean performance score of male and female SSII students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy. Their computed mean performances are 34.59 and 34.19 of Male and female SSII Secondary school Mathematics students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy respectively. This shows that both male and female students have the same level of mean performance when taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy

Testing Null Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance score of male and female SSII students taught algebra using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy.

To test null hypothesis two, the post test scores from APT for male and female of the experimental group were subjected to independent sample t-test. The summary is presented in Table 2.

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Table 2: Summary of Independent Sample t-test of Mean Posttest APT Scores for Male and Female in Experimental Group.

GENDER	N	Mean	STD	Mean diff.	Df	T comp.	t crit.	p
Male	51	34.59	1.63	0.39	86	1.07	1.96	0.289
Female	37	34.19	1.87					

P > 0.05, t-computed < 1.96 at DF 86

Result of the independent t-test statistics showed that there is no significant difference between the mean performance score of male and female SSII students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy. Reasons being that the calculated p-value of 0.289 is greater than the 0.05 alpha level of significance and the computed t-value of 1.07 is lower than 1.96 t-critical value at df 86. Their computed mean performances are 34.59 and 34.19 of Male and female SSII Secondary school Mathematics students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy respectively. This shows that both male and female students have the same level of mean performance when taught with students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy Therefore the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant difference between the mean performance score of male and female SSII students taught Algebra Concept using YouTube Video-Learning Strategy, is hereby accepted and retained.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that there was no significant difference in the performance of male and female students when exposed to YouTube Video-Learning Strategy. This suggests that YouTube Video-Learning Strategy are a gender-neutral tool in terms of their impact on academic performance, as both male and female students benefited equally from the intervention. This outcome aligns with the research conducted by Khan, Saeed, Anwar, and Kanwal (2023), who found that boys did not outperform their female counterparts in heterogeneous group settings. Similarly,

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Onasanya et al. (2022) and Sharma (2024) found in their independent studies that gender did not have a significant impact on student performance when video-based resources were used as instructional tools. These findings suggest that YouTube Video-Learning Strategy can serve as an inclusive and effective teaching strategy for all students, regardless of gender.

However, contrasting results were observed in the study by Kutigi et al. (2023), where male students outperformed female students in various areas when exposed to flipped classroom instructional models. The differences in findings between this study and the one by Kutigi et al. (2023) may stem from the different instructional approaches used in each study, with flipped classrooms potentially providing more opportunities for male students to excel. It is important to note that these discrepancies underscore the importance of considering instructional methodologies and their varying effects on students across genders.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it can be concluded that the use of YouTube Video-Learning Strategy significantly enhances the academic performance of both male and female students, demonstrating that these resources are gender-neutral. The study revealed that YouTube video-based learning not only provides a more engaging and interactive method of teaching algebra but also fosters equal participation and achievement among male and female students. This suggests that YouTube Video-Learning Strategy offer a flexible and accessible learning platform that accommodates the diverse learning styles of students, irrespective of gender. The positive impact on both male and female students' performance highlights the potential of technology-based tools like YouTube videos to bridge any gender-based gaps in educational outcomes, offering a more inclusive approach to teaching complex subjects such as algebra. Therefore, it is recommended that educators incorporate YouTube Video-Learning Strategy regularly into their teaching strategies to improve student engagement and learning outcomes, benefiting all students regardless of gender.

Recommendations

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1. School administrators should invest in providing adequate technological infrastructure, including internet access and multimedia tools, to ensure that YouTube Video-Learning Strategy can be effectively integrated into the teaching of Algebra and other mathematical concepts.
2. Teachers should be encouraged to develop and share a repository of quality YouTube Video-Learning Strategy that align with the curriculum, enabling students to access supplementary learning materials beyond the classroom and reinforce their understanding of algebraic concepts.
3. Educational stakeholders, including the Ministry of Education, should promote the use of YouTube video-based learning as part of the national curriculum, advocating for its adoption as a valuable tool for improving students' comprehension of challenging mathematical topics and encouraging gender-equitable learning environments.

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Assessment of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Practical Skills Acquisition in Computer Science among Undergraduate Students in Usmanu Danfodio University Sokoto

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Abstract

This paper assessed laboratory instructional strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS Affiliated Programme. Three (3) objectives and research questions each were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted descriptive survey design and population of the study comprised of all 300 level UDUS students of 2022/2023 academic session (of the formerly affiliated Federal College of Education, Zaria). Since the population (361) is not as large as in other researches, the researchers have decided to use same as sample size using purposive sampling technique. Questionnaire was the sole instrument used for data collection in this study from the respondents (students). Data analysis was undertaken using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and simple percentages. The study revealed that the use of laboratory instructional strategy by teachers has assisted UDUS B.Ed students in the practical skill acquisition of computer science in FUE, Zaria to a great extent. FUE, Zaria have the required facilities that supports the use of laboratory instructional strategy towards the practical skills acquisition in computer science for UDUS B.Ed students. The effects of the use of laboratory instructional strategy on the practical skills acquisition in computer science among UDUS B.Ed students in FUE, Zaria, is relatively positive and high. Thus, the study recommended the need for education managers to advocate for the strong use of this strategy in teaching science related subject. Finally, this strategy is student - centeredness and should therefore be encouraged in all teacher training institutions when teaching computer science students.

Keywords: Computer Science, Instructional Strategy, Practical Skills Acquisition

Introduction

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The use of computers today is key to the activities of individuals, groups and organizations at achieving a certain goals or the other. Thus, as important as it is, the practical knowledge of how to effectively use it is still in dilemma. This is because, there are those who could not afford it (aside their mobile phones), others have it for the mere sake of the time they would be asked if they have it or not. The other category are those who could not use it for so many things even as a student in the institution under study aside phone calls and/or short messages. Although, it is a known fact that computer science has become a useful “tool in different sectors of the economy. In fact, there is no discipline at the moment where knowledge of computer science is not being used for one operation or the other. Computers are being used in the airports to control flights.

It is equally being used in the hospitals to diagnose, treat and manage diseases. In the field of communication, networking and internet connectivity has turn the whole world into a global village. Marketing Robot is also being developed to take care of sales in big marketing organizations. In a nutshell, computer science has become so useful and popular to the extent that all countries are training and developing her citizens to be at least computer literate. Meanwhile, the Nigerian government via her educational system has introduced computer science otherwise referred to as information and communication technology (ICT) or data processing as a subject in all schools including primary, secondary and tertiary institutions. But despite all the efforts of government, the performance of students is abysmal as wide gap exist between their theoretical and practical knowledge (Omoniwa nd).

This was suspected to be as a result of the teaching method so adopted by those saddled to teach the subject (or course) at the different levels. Many teaching methods have so far been employed such as discussion, assignment, lecture, laboratory among others. The focus of this study however, is to assess laboratory instructional strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students of UDUS Affiliated Programme in the former Federal College of Education, Zaria. Laboratory method of teaching according to Akuto, Aduloju and Odeh (2012) in Chibabi, Umoru, Onah and Itodo (2018) is a process where the students are in direct contact with the concept or processes they are learning. This includes any activity involving students in real situations using genuine materials and properly working equipments.

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The authors added that the use of laboratory method of teaching aids the development of visual, perceptual and manipulative skills and also makes learning permanent (retention) among students. In using this method, the teacher does not take recourse to lecturing nor to demonstration of experiment. Rather, the students are encouraged to derive the laws and principles of science themselves by actually performing the experiments. The students are given all necessary materials and equipments in the laboratory along with their proper instructions for carrying out their experiments with their own initiative and effort. The observations are recorded and the results are inferred. It helps the students to understand complex abstract ideas and gives students an opportunity to participate in the process and have an appreciation for the methods of science.

It is further considered that the knowledge and skills gained through laboratory method is more lasting and permanent as they learn by their own experience, observation, testing and verification. In all these, the teacher is expected to guide the trainee teachers on what to do during the session and at achieving worthwhile results. For this reason, it is believed that constant practice leads to proficiency in what the learners learn during classroom instruction hence, the dictum “practice makes perfect”. This has given rise to the expectation that laboratory facilities should be adequately provided to schools for effective teaching and learning. Important areas of literature reviewed in this paper are sub - titled below as:

Use of Laboratory Strategy by Computer Science Teachers

Laboratory experiences provide opportunities for teachers to model best practices in the study of scientific concepts, including application of scientific methodologies, respect for life and the environment, inclusion of learners of all abilities, and consistent adherence to safety standards. Thus, study in a laboratory is an integral and essential part of science courses (Odubunni, and Balagun in Gonca, Aytakin, Burckin and Umut, 2016). This being the case, is with expectations that this method be used as much as possible to assist the students to understand the practical aspect of the course of study. Tobin (1990) quoted by Hamidu, Ibrahim and Mohammed, 2014 wrote that: “Laboratory activities appears as a way to learn with understanding and, at the same time, engage in a process of constructing knowledge by doing science”. He also suggested that meaningful and quality learning is possible in the laboratory if students are given opportunities to manipulate equipment and

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materials in order to be able to construct their knowledge of phenomena and related scientific concepts.

Availability of instructional Facilities for Laboratory Strategy

There is usually a strong move to emphasize the dependence of science (computer class) teaching on the existence of a well - equipped laboratory. With the laboratory experience, students will be able to translate what they have read in their texts to practical realities, thereby enhancing their understanding of the learnt concepts. Farombi (1998) in Yara (2010) argued the saying that seeing is believing is the effect of using laboratories in the teaching and learning of science and other science related disciplines as students tend to understand and recall what they see more than what they hear.

Effects of Laboratory Strategy on Practical Skills Acquisition in Computer Science

Science educators have believed that the laboratory is an important means of instruction in science since late in the 19th century. Laboratory instruction was considered essential because it provided training in observation, supplied detailed information, and aroused pupils' interest. These same reasons are still accepted almost 100 years later. In a laboratory, students work individually or in small groups on a question, problem or hypothesis. The distinction between laboratory and traditional classroom learning is that activities are student - centered, with students actively engaged in hands-on, minds - on activities using laboratory techniques. (Lazarowitz and Tamir, 1994 cited by Hamidu, Ibrahim and Mohammed, 2014).

Laboratory is very important and essential to the teaching of science and success of any science course is much dependent on the laboratory provision made for it. Lending credence to this statement, Yara (2010) in Hamidu, Ibrahim and Mohammed, 2014) said that there is a general consensus among science educators that laboratory occupies a central position in science instruction. It could be conceptualized as a place, where theoretical work is practicalized and practicals in any learning experiences involve students in activities such as observing, counting, measuring, experimenting, recording and carrying out fieldwork.

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Preference of Laboratory Strategy for Practical Skills Acquisition in Computer Science

There are a number of teaching methods available for teacher's use in teaching Computer Science. These methods are classified into two major groups namely traditional (teacher - centered) and contemporary methods (students - centered). The preference for this method of teaching (laboratory) is to enable students to be actively involved in knowledge acquisition and retention over a period of time. As in the case of traditional method, students are rarely exposed to practical work because science teachers do not place much value and attention on the process of science through laboratory activities since they feel it takes time away from teaching to cover the prescribed examination - driven curriculum (Abamba, 2012).

This has also encouraged teachers and students to depend on external examination instructional manuals instead of preparing students through student - centred methods. It is quite obvious from the aforementioned, that practical knowledge of the use of computers for multifaceted tasks in the different nation's industry will be a lot more achievable if laboratory method is adopted in schools. However, there are many issues with the use of laboratory method in teacher colleges for practical knowledge of computer science. In his contribution, Kofo (2012) pointed out that science teachers do not usually find it convenient to make laboratory method the center of their instruction. They usually complain of lack of materials and equipment to carry out practical work.

At the same time, it is possible that some of these materials and equipment may be locked up in the school laboratory store without teachers being aware of their existence. The conditions under which many teachers function do not engender any enthusiasm to use the laboratory method of teaching computer science even where they know that these materials and equipment are available. To cap it all, higher institutions in Nigeria charged with the responsibility of training computer science teachers at all levels, are increasingly turning out teachers without requisite laboratory experience. A common reason usually given is shortage of laboratory facilities. Such trained computer science teachers usually lack the necessary confidence to conduct practical classes with their students.

Objectives of the Study

The following specific objectives guided this study:

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1. Assess the extent of use of laboratory strategy for practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS.
2. Find out if the required instructional facilities are available in UDUS for the use of laboratory strategy for practical skills acquisition in computer science.
3. Examine the effects of laboratory strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS.

Research Questions

This study shall be guided by the following research questions:

1. To what extent does the use of laboratory strategy assist undergraduate students in practical skills acquisition in computer science in UDUS?
2. Do UDUS have the required instructional facilities for the use of laboratory strategy for practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students?
3. What are the effects of laboratory strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS?

Methodology

This study adopted descriptive survey research design. Yin (2014) argues descriptive survey research design is useful for providing a comprehensive understanding of a phenomenon or population. Population for this study was comprised of all year III UDUS students of 2022/2023 academic session (of the formerly affiliated Federal College of Education, Zaria). Since the population is not as large as in other researches, the researchers have decided to use same as sample size. Therefore, a sample size of three hundred and sixty - one (361) students was selected at random for this study using purposive sampling technique. In any research as this, purposive sampling technique which is also judgment sampling is a non - probability sampling method where participants are selected based on the researchers' judgment and expertise. It allows for selection of sample that is representative of the population, but not necessarily randomly selected (Creswell, 2014).

The sole instrument used for data collection in this study was questionnaire and titled "questionnaire on assessment of laboratory strategy on practical skills

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acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students” (QALSPSACS). Pilot study was conducted in Kaduna State College of Education, Gidan Waya an affiliate institution to Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and a reliability co-efficient of 0.89 was obtained. Data analysis was undertaken using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and simple percentages on the reseach questions formulated for this study.

Presentation of Results

Research Question One: To what extent does the use of laboratory strategy assist undergraduate students in practical skills acquisition in computer science in UDUS? The respondents questionnaire was adopted alongside Likert four point rating scale of strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A), disagreed (D) and strongly disagreed (SD) respectively. There are five (5) item statements in the table below which the respondents had responded to.

Table 1: Respondents’ opinion on the use of laboratory strategy as it assist in practical skill acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students

S/N	Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	STD
1.	Laboratory method helps a lot in the acquisition of knowledge of computers, its use and functions.	162	80	90	29	3.038	1.010
2.	Laboratory method helps in the retention of knowledge	168	68	77	48	2.986	1.101
3.	It is a less suitable method in the teaching of practical oriented subject like computer.	129	110	70	52	2.875	1.055
4.	It is a suitable method of teaching which has attracted students’ interest in the subject.	196	115	33	17	3.357	0.834
5.	The use of laboratory method will further assist the students to earn a living for themselves to support their studies.	161	130	30	40	3.141	0.977
Cumulative Mean						3.079	

Source: Field work (2024)

Decision/threshold mean =2.500

The extent to which the use of laboratory method by teachers assisted UDUS B.Ed students in the practical acquisition of knowledge in computer science in FUE, Zaria is quite high. This is as the cumulative mean response of 3.079 is higher than the 2.500 decision/threshold mean. Specifically, most of the students asserted that the method in question is suitable for teaching and has attracted students’ interest in the subject. This view attracted the highest mean agreement level of 3.357 as details showed that a combined total of 315 were in agreement and 50 others disagreed.

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Also, most respondents believed that the use of laboratory method will further assist the students to earn a living for themselves in order to support their studies. As this view attracted the second highest mean of 3.141 as details showed that while a combined total of 290 were in agreement the rest 70 were in disagreement.

Research Question Two: Do UDUS have the required instructional facilities for the use of laboratory strategy for practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students? The respondents questionnaire was adopted alongside Likert four point rating scale of strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A), disagreed (D) and strongly disagreed (SD) respectively. There are five (5) item statements in table 2 below which the respondents had responded to.

Table 2: Respondents’ opinion on instructional facilities for the use of laboratory strategy in practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students

S/N	Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	STD
1.	Electricity supply to the University is constantly available whenever this method is to be used.	108	96	104	53	2.717	1.047
2.	There is inadequate computers and other accessories for use whenever this method is to be used.	164	74	80	35	3.022	1.033
3.	Adequate manpower with requisite knowledge of computers and method to use can be found in FUE, Zaria	177	128	36	20	3.279	0.857
4.	Learning environment where laboratory method can be use to teach and acquire knowledge in computers are unavailable in FUE, Zaria.	141	112	64	44	2.969	1.028
5.	Laboratory method is mostly used by experienced lecturers at the expense of their inexperience counterparts.	165	132	32	32	3.191	0.930
Cumulative Mean						3.035	

Source: Field work (2024)

Decision/threshold mean =2.500

In the table above, it was evident showed that FUE, Zaria have the required facilities for the use of laboratory method towards the practical acquisition of knowledge in computer science for UDUS B.Ed students. This is as their cumulative mean agreement level of 3.035 is greater than the 2.500 decision/threshold mean. Specifically, most of the respondents believed that adequate manpower with requisite knowledge of computers and method can be found in the study area. This view attracted the highest mean agreement level of 3.279 as details showed that while a combined total of 305 were in agreement only 56 were in disagreement. They also asserted that laboratory method is mostly used by experienced lecturers at the expense of their inexperience counterparts. This viewpoint attracted the second

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highest mean agreement level of 3.191 as details showed that while a combined total of 297 were in agreement the rest of 64 respondents were in disagreement.

Research Question Three: What are the effects of laboratory strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS? The respondents questionnaire was adopted alongside Likert four point rating scale of strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A), disagreed (D) and strongly disagreed (SD) respectively. There are five (5) item statements in the table below which the respondents had responded to.

Table 3: Respondents’ opinion on the effects of laboratory strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS

S/N	Variables	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	STD
1.	Exposes the students to what they need to know in computers and how to manipulate it for diverse use.	161	73	90	37	2.091	1.052
2.	Allows for group participation in the class activities which perhaps may take place in the school laboratory.	163	133	33	32	3.182	0.930
3.	Knowledge sharing among the students is difficult where laboratory method is used.	141	112	64	44	2.969	1.028
4.	Interest of slow and un-serious learners are of less concern when laboratory method is put to use.	182	124	35	20	3.296	0.858
5.	The use of laboratory method is incapacitated by poorly trained personnel, lack of adequate materials and say, poor electricity supply in school.	105	94	107	55	2.689	1.050
Cumulative Mean						2.845	

Source: Field work (2024)

Decision/threshold mean =2.500

Table 3 above showed that the effects of the use of laboratory method on the practical acquisition of knowledge in computer science among UDUS B.Ed students in FUE, Zaria is relatively positive and high. This was because the cumulative mean of 2.845 is above the 2.500 decision/threshold mean. Specifically, most of the respondents believed that this method allows for group participation in class activities which perhaps may take place in the school laboratory. This view attracted the highest mean agreement level of 3.182 as details showed that while 296 were in agreement the rest 65 were in disagreement. In the same vein, interest of slow and un-serious learners are of less concern when laboratory method is put to use. The corresponding mean was 3.296 with details showing that while 55 were in agreement the rest 306 were in disagreement.

Summary of the Findings

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The study revealed the following as its findings from the analysis carried out:

1. That the use of laboratory strategy assists in practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students of UDUS to a great extent.
2. UDUS affiliated college in Zaria have the required instructional facilities for the use of laboratory strategy in the practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students. This was in terms of manpower, support facilities like computers and its accessories among others.
3. The effects of use of laboratory strategy in the practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate UDUS students, is relatively positive and high.

Discussion of Findings

Three (3) research questions were formulated and tested in this study titled assessment of laboratory instructional strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS Affiliated Programme. In research question one, extent to which the use of laboratory strategy has assisted undergraduate students in practical skills acquisition in computer science in UDUS was tested. Respondents unanimously agreed that the use of this strategy has helped undergraduate students to acquire practical skills in computer science. This was evident in the aspect of retention of knowledge, attraction of students' interest and in the knowledge of what is computer as well as its workings. The position of Lazarowitz and Tamir cited by Hamidu, Ibrahim and Mohammed, (2014) concur with the findings of this study. This was carefully captured in the distinction between laboratory and traditional classroom learning. They believed that this strategy is student - centered, with students actively engaged in hands-on, minds - on activities using laboratory techniques.

The availability of required instructional facilities for use of laboratory strategy in practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students was tested in research question two. The outcome of this analysis revealed that required instructional facilities are available for use of laboratory strategy in the acquisition of practical skills in computer science among the students. To this end, respondents believed that adequate manpower, computers and its accessories as well as constant electricity are available whenever this instructional strategy is to be used.

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Research question three tested the effects of laboratory strategy on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students in UDUS. The effect of use of laboratory strategy is noticeable in the practical skills acquisition among the undergraduate students of UDUS in computer science. This was reflected in the responses of respondents that the use of laboratory strategy has effects on exposing the students to what they should know and how to manipulate the computers. It also has the effect of promoting group participation and knowledge sharing amongst the UDUS students. Tobin quoted by Hamidu, Ibrahim and Mohammed (2014) as saying that “laboratory activities appears as a way to learn with understanding and, at the same time, engage in a process of constructing knowledge by doing science.

Recommendations

The following recommendations have been put forward in this study:

1. The need by education managers to advocate for the use of this method by teachers in science related subjects have become essential. Where possible too, they collaborate with policy makers to ensure adequate legislation and strong use of this method in schools to help learners acquire practical knowledge where necessary.
2. This method is student - centeredness and should therefore be encouraged in all teacher training institutions when teaching computer science students. More so, it is more suitable than any other methods in the acquisition of practical knowledge which computer is known for.
3. There is need to carefully monitor the teaching of computer practical by making available all the packages that are necessary with the correct operating system.

Conclusion

The success of the teaching of any school subject lies in the teaching strategy so adopted and how well it is put to use viz-a-viz its purpose. It is therefore imperative to note that there are many instructional strategies, laboratory is thus one of them. Laboratory can thus be considered as one of the most useful teaching strategy in schools that can be applied in computer science as a subject as well as in other science subjects. Vividly, the use of laboratory strategy has positive effects on practical skills acquisition in computer science among undergraduate students of UDUS. This strategy when used effectively will boost the nation’s economy and help

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reduce the rate of unemployment in the society by producing graduates or graduates to - be who will be self-reliance.

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(Correlation between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge ... Idris, I. O. Et. al. 2025)

Correlation between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Performance in Mathematics among Secondary School Students in Kogi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated Correlation between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Performance in Mathematics among Secondary School Students in Kogi State, Nigeria. The study was a survey research of the correlational type and sample consisted of twelve mathematics teachers and three hundred (300) SS II Mathematics students during the 2023/2024 academic session in Kogi central senatorial zone selected by stratified random sampling techniques from ten (10) senior secondary schools in five (5) local government areas of Kogi Central Senatorial zone. Two research questions and two null hypotheses were raised and formulated respectively to direct the study. Mathematics Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge Assessment Rating Form (MTPKARF) was used to collect data with respect to Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge while students' scores from end of school term examination of the classes taught by the observed mathematics teachers were collected from documentary source in the sampled schools with respect to their academic performance. Data collected were analyzed using regression and multiple regression analysis. The result indicated that: There was significant relationship: between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Academic Performance of students in Mathematics and between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and male and female Students' Academic Performance in Mathematics. Based on the research findings, it was concluded among others that Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge relate directly with and predict students' academic performance. It is recommended among others that the three tier of government in Nigeria should employ qualified mathematics teachers with required education background to teach mathematics in senior secondary schools.

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Keywords: Pedagogical Knowledge, Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge, Student's Academic Performance and Mathematics.

Introduction

Mathematics is one of the school subject that have application to every facet of human endeavor. Shulman (2010) described it as the precursor of scientific discoveries. No Nation, over the world can hope to achieve any measure of scientific or technological advancement without a proper foundation in school mathematics. Gatbonton (2018) opined that mathematics is an indispensable medium by which science expresses, formulates, continues, and communicates itself. It was emphasized that Mathematics has turned into something more than simple calculations; it has become a powerful tool for practical sciences like engineering, industry, and others to mention but a few. It has entered into the development of technology and a great variety of inventions. Thus, the lack of basic mathematics knowledge and skills in any society may isolate such society from the global scientific trend. It is in recognition of the important of mathematics that it is studied as a compulsory subject at both primary and secondary school levels in Nigeria so that every school child will acquire appropriate basic scientific and mathematics knowledge.

However, students' academic performance in Mathematics at the Nigerian secondary school level in WASSCE has improved for the past few years as reported by the WAEC Chief Examiner's Report (2021, 2022, and 2023) based on the statistics of students with A's, B's, and C's. With this development in terms of performance, more is needed to be done to maintain the standard. However, this does not mean that success has been attained in teaching mathematics as there are lots of factors that still militate against teachers' effort to achieve the primary objectives of teaching and learning of mathematics at the secondary school level that must be addressed. Prominent among these factors are teachers' Motivation level, students' interest in mathematics and teachers' Competency (i.e. Teachers' pedagogical knowledge, Content knowledge and acquisition of Skills). The focus of this study is on teachers' pedagogical knowledge as a component of teachers' competency.

According to Rodgers and Raider-Roth, (2010), many a teacher is knowledgeable of his or her subject matter without necessarily being able to decompress it in a way that he or she will make it accessible to his or her students. However, having pedagogical knowledge is the way to decompress the subject matter knowledge. In this respect, teachers' pedagogical knowledge is the ability of a teacher to adopt diverse suitable

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strategies and teaching methods while impacting knowledge of the subject matter in a manner that makes sense to the students. Shulman (2010) define it as any theory or belief about teaching and the process of learning to plan and the process of learning that a teacher possesses that influences that teacher's teaching. This process includes the implementation, problem solving and teaching strategies, questioning techniques and assessment (Hudson, 2017). Tak-wah and Yiu-Chi (2019) also described it as knowing the ways of representing and formulating the subject-matter and making it comprehensive to students.

Furthermore, Elit and Sibel (2017), indicated that pedagogical knowledge includes the ways of representing content that make it comprehensible to learners and an understanding of what makes the learning of specific topics easy or difficult. Monica and Helen (2017) on the other hand emphasize that pedagogical knowledge includes: knowledge of multiple ways of representing content to students which relies on the teacher's understanding of the content and has its purpose in the transformation of the content into a form that students will understand such as illustration, examples, explanations and demonstrations; an understanding of what makes topics easy or difficult; knowledge of students' typical preconceptions and misconceptions; strategies for helping students reorganize their understanding; knowledge of student thinking and knowing the relationships among topics procedures and concepts. The study therefore see pedagogical knowledge of mathematics teachers as the knowledge of how to teach mathematics.

To cope with the problem of maintaining/keeping and improving upon the standard already attained in academic performance in mathematics in senior secondary school in Nigeria, there is need to produce and have competent teachers who can effectively teach and motivate students to learn mathematics. Thus, education courses offered in Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE), University undergraduate programme, Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE), Masters and Ph. D, are meant to help develop teacher's knowledge about teaching. Also, several years of teaching experience will also help build upon that knowledge to make it more specialized and useful. Mathematics teachers must therefore, possess pedagogical knowledge of their content area in order to facilitate students' learning. This study carried out investigation to determine if teachers' pedagogical knowledge is a predictor to students' academic performance in mathematics.

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Moreover, a growing body of research has shown that students' academic performance is influenced by teachers' pedagogy knowledge and yet, others are in contradiction. The study conducted by Baumert et al (2010), Bayer and Davis (2011) and Olorunsola (2019) pointed out that there was significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and students' academic performance in mathematics including students' academic performance on gender bases. But contrary results were obtained by Ladipo, (2013); Olabisi, Alabi and Henry (2017) whose study indicated that there is no significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and students' academic performance in mathematics and that the former is not a predictor of the later. Thus this study examined whether teachers' pedagogical knowledge significantly relate with and predict senior secondary school students' academic performance in mathematics in Central Senatorial Zone, Kogi State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

It has been noted that students' academic performance in Mathematics at the Nigerian secondary school level in WASSCE has improved for the past few years as reported by the WAEC Chief Examiner's Report (2021, 2022, and 2023) based on the statistics of students with A's, B's, and C's. With this development in terms of performance, more is needed to be done to maintain the standard. However, this does not mean that success has been attained in teaching mathematics as there are lots of factors that still militate against teachers' effort to achieve the primary objectives of teaching and learning of mathematics at the secondary school level that must be addressed. Prominent among these factors are teachers' Motivation level, students' interest in mathematics and teachers' Competency (Teachers' pedagogical knowledge, Content knowledge and acquisition of Skills). It was on this note that the study investigated, 'Correlation between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and performance in mathematics among secondary school students in Kogi State, Nigeria.'

Objectives of the Study

The study investigated Correlation between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Performance in Mathematics among Senior Secondary School Students in Kogi State, Nigeria. Specifically, the study determine if:

1. Teachers' pedagogical knowledge predict students' academic performance in mathematics.
2. Teachers' pedagogical knowledge predict male and female students' academic performance in mathematics.

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Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

1. What is the relationship between Teachers' pedagogical knowledge and students' Academic performance in mathematics?
2. What is the relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and male & female students' academic performance in mathematics?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and students' academic performance in mathematics.

Ho₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and male & female students' academic performance in mathematics.

Methodology

The study used survey research design of the correlational type which according to Launer (2006), establish relationship between two or more variables that has manifested already hence, no manipulation of existing phenomenon is required. The variables in this research work has manifested already hence, no manipulation of existing phenomenon is required and emphasis is on association between the variables. The researcher used assessment rating for teachers' pedagogical knowledge and the students' performance scores were collected from the examination administered to the students by the observed mathematics teachers in the sample schools. The researcher observed the sampled mathematics teachers in the sample classes in each sample schools each on three occasions while teaching throughout a whole school term and take the average of their pedagogical knowledge rating. Also, the end of term mathematics examination scores of the students they taught were collected which form the data for the study.

The target population for this study embraced all the Senior Secondary two (SSII) Mathematics teachers and SS II students in Kogi Central Senatorial Zone for 2023/2024 academic session. This consisted of 55 teachers teaching Mathematics at SS II classes and 2,139 SS II Students (1080 males & 1059 females) respectively from forty four senior secondary schools in Kogi Central Senatorial Zone. Sample consisted of fifteen mathematics teachers and three hundred (300) SS II students selected by stratified random sampling techniques from ten (10) senior secondary schools in five (5) local government areas of Kogi Central Senatorial zone.

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Data collected for the study was through the use of 20 items Mathematics Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge Assessment Rating Form (MTPKARF) and students' examination scores conducted by the observed mathematics teachers at the end of the school term. The Mathematics Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge Assessment Rating Form was adapted from (Eric Zhi Feng LIU^a and Chun Hung LIN, 2010) used in this study to collect information about teachers' pedagogical knowledge in teaching mathematics. The rating ranged from 0 to 5, where 0 stand for lowest score while 5 for the highest score. For each item the teachers were scored from 0 to 5 and the maximum obtainable score for the 20 items is 100%. The scoring was done by the researcher through observation while the teachers were teaching. Students' scores from end of school term examination of the classes taught by the observed mathematics teachers were collected from documentary source in the sampled schools with respect to their academic performance.

The MTPKARF was field tested on a sample of 5 SSII mathematics teachers in a school that was not part of the study. The instrument have reliability coefficient of 0.83 using test retest method and Pearson Product Moment Correlation for data analysis. Examination questions set by mathematics teachers were internally moderated by the head of department and some senior colleagues. Marked examination scripts were vetted by an internal examiner to ensure internal quality controls. Data collected were analyzed using regression and multiple regression analysis to address the research questions and test the null hypothesis

Presentation of Results

The data collected from the study were analysed to address the research questions and test the null hypotheses using regression and multiple regression analysis as follow:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and students' academic performance in mathematics.

To test the null hypothesis and address the corresponding research question, regression analysis was used as shown in Table 1a and 1b.

Table 1a: Regression Analysis of Prediction between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Students academic Performance in Mathematics

Model	R	Change Statistics
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	R square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the estimate	R Square Change	F Change	Df1	Df2	Sig. Change	F	Durbin-Watson
1	.716	.465	.458	19.132	.385	37.845	1	56	.000	1.973

Predictors: (Constant). Pedagogical Knowledge

Dependent Variable: Students' Academic Performance

The results of the Regression analysis as shown in Table 1a, revealed F ratio of 1.973 and df of 1, 56 and computed p value of 0.000 is less than the 0.05 alpha level, indicating that teachers' pedagogical knowledge significantly related with and predicted the students' academic performance in mathematics. This implies that the null hypothesis H_{01} was rejected and alternative hypothesis retained. The predictor factors for the relationship are: $a = 20.234$ and $b = .716$ as presented in Table 1b. The regression equation is $y = 20.234 + .716x$. Table 1b contains the summary of the test of the contribution of each predictor in the regression analysis.

Table 1b: Coefficients^a of Correlation between Teachers' Pedagogical, Knowledge and Students' Performance in Mathematics

Model	Unstandardized Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Constant	20.234	5.011		4.318	.000
Pedagogical Knowledge	.644	.102	.716	6.241	.000

As shown on Table 1b, the unstandardized regression coefficient of pedagogical knowledge was 0.644 and Standardized regression coefficients was 0.716 which were higher than the Regression critical value of 0.4. Hence, the relationship between the two variables is a high direct relation.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between teachers' pedagogical knowledge and male & female students' academic performance in mathematics

To test the null hypothesis and address the corresponding research question, multiple regression analysis was used as presented in Table 2a and 2b.

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Table 2a: Multiple Regression Analysis of Prediction between Teachers' Pedagogical Knowledge and Male and Female Students Academic Performance in Mathematics

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of estimate	tChange Statistics					Durbin-Watson
					R Change	Square Change	Df1	Df2	Sig. Chang	
1	.834	.798	.791	6.989	.898	105.971	3	54	.001	1.498

Predictors: (Constant), Pedagogical Knowledge

Dependent Variable: Male and Female Students Academic Performance

The results of the Regression analysis as shown in Table 2a, revealed F ratio of 1.498 and df of 3, 54 and computed p value of 0.001 is less than the 0.05 alpha level, indicating that teachers' pedagogical knowledge significantly related with and predicted the male and female students' academic performance in mathematics. This implies that the null hypothesis H_{02} was rejected and alternative hypothesis retained. The predictor factors for the relationship are: $a = 11.329$ and $b_1 = .634$ and $b_2 = .595$ as presented in Table 2b. Table 2b contains the summary of the test of the contribution of each predictor in the regression analysis.

Table 2b: Coefficients^a of Correlation between Teachers Pedagogical Knowledge and Male and Female Students' Performance in Mathematics.

Model	Unstandardised Coefficient		Standardized Coefficient	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error			
Constant	11.329	4.318		-1.324	.005
Male Studentrs' Axademic Perfomance	.513	.121	.634	.296	.006
Female Students' Academic Performance	.499	.153	.595	3.134	.002

As shown on Table 2b, the unstandardized regression coefficient of male and female students' academic performance were 0.513 and 0.499 respectively, their Standardized regression coefficients were 0.634 and 0.595 respectively which were higher than the Regression critical value of 0.4. Hence, the relationship between the teachers'

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pedagogical knowledge and male and female students' academic performance in mathematics is a high direct relation.

Discussion of Findings

The results of the study as presented in Table 1a and 1b and likewise in Table 2a and 2b showed that mathematics teachers' pedagogical knowledge had a direct relationship on and is a good predictor of students' academic performance in mathematics. This implies that the level of teachers' pedagogical knowledge in teaching mathematics determine how well the students performed academically irrespective of the students' gender. It can however be deduced that for a mathematics teacher to be successful in the classroom, be able to impart mathematics knowledge to the students adequately and to achieve the require result better (student's performance) he/she must be well grounded in the methodology of teaching the subject. This could only be ensured if the person delivering mathematics instruction is a trainee teacher. These result agreed with the outcome of what is obtained in the study of Baumert etal (2010) and Olorunsola (2019) but contradicts the finding of Ladipo (2013) and Olabisi, Alabi and Henry (2017) who reported that teachers' pedagogical knowledge did not significantly relate with and predict students' academic performance in mathematics including male and female students' performance on gender bases.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that Mathematics Teachers' pedagogical knowledge has direct relationship with and is a predictor to students' academic performance in mathematics irrespective of their gender. This implies that the more sound Mathematics Teachers' pedagogical knowledge is the better their students' academic performance in mathematics.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this research work, the following recommendations are made:

1. The Government should endeavor to employ only qualified trained mathematics teachers to teach mathematics in senior secondary schools in Kogi Central Senatorial zone.
2. Unqualified mathematics teachers in senior secondary schools should be provided opportunity of in-service training for them to be train as a professional teacher in programmes such as institute of Education's Professional Diploma in Education (PDE) Ahmadu Bello University Zaria or Post Graduate Diploma in Education (PGDE) offered in the Nigeria Universities.

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3. The Federal and State government should engage in training and retraining of senior secondary school mathematics teachers in service in their domain through seminar, workkshop or conference to update their pedagogical knowledge in order to move along with the current trend of information and communication technology as it relates to teaching and learning.

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(*Sunflower Extractions Potential to Reduce Lead-induced Toxicity ... Aminu, N., Et. al., 2025*)

Sunflower Extraction's Potential to Reduce Lead-Induced Toxicity in Lead-Contaminated Soil

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Abstract

The presence of Lead (Pb) in the environment has become widespread, mainly due to human activities and it's becoming a major concern globally. This study aimed to determine the responses of Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus L.*) to varying concentrations of lead and to evaluate its bioaccumulation potentials. Sunflower seedlings (4-weeks old) were spiked once with different concentrations (0, 100, 200 and 500 mM) of lead oxide solutions and observed weekly for 2 weeks. The growth, biomass and lead (Pb) content of sunflower in different treatments was measured. The results revealed that lead significantly ($p < 0.05$) reduced plant height, number of leaves, biomass of shoot and roots. The control had the highest plant height of 35cm while 500 mM treatment had the shortest length of 25cm. For shoot and root biomass, the control had the highest biomass of 13.2g and 3.5g respectively while 100 mM treatment had the lowest biomass of 10.8g and 1.1g respectively for shoot and root. The lead (Pb) concentrations in shoot of Sunflower significantly ($p < 0.005$) increased with increasing concentrations with the highest content (0.478 mg/kg) in 500 mM treatment while the control (0 mM) had the lowest (0.006 mg/Kg) lead concentrations. Lead uptake in the roots showed that 500 mM treatment had the highest (0.515mg/Kg) lead content while the control (0 mM) had the lowest (0.006mg/Kg) lead content. Overall, Sunflower showed differential response and uptake of lead to varying concentrations of lead. Sunflower can serve as a sentinel and good candidate in cleaning lead polluted soils.

Keywords: *Helianthus annuus*, Phytoremediation, Lead, Bioaccumulation, Lead Oxide

Introduction

Sunflower (*Helianthus annuus L.*) is the most potential oil seed crop for edible oil production in the world. Besides, the third most important oilseed crop in Pakistan after the Rapeseed and Mustard. The first decade of this century had perceived a substantial improvement in the crop yield of sunflower; however, the average crop yield has gradually decreased since 2010 (Altaf et al., 2020). This decrease could be ascribed

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to the shorter availability of mineral fertilizers, overexploitation of marginal land and toxic heavy metals pollution in the soil (Rehman et al.,2022). Thus, it needs to adopt modern and sustainable approaches to fulfil fertilizer resilience and improve plant growth and soil health. Lead (Pb) is a widely distributed trace element with severe health impacts such as brain damage and central nervous system disorders (Ashraf et al.,2021; Liu et al.,2022). Several sources of Pb exposure to the environment, particularly rock weathering, extensive use of pesticides, leaded gasoline, molting paint chips, batteries, and wastewater irrigation have been overwhelmed (Xie et al.,2020). Most countries around the world, including the United States, China, India, Japan, and Pakistan, have reported that Pb concentration in soils has gradually increased and become a key factor in reducing crop yields (Lyu et al.,2016). Normally, Pb makes stable complexes such as phosphates, carbonates, sulfates, and hydroxides, which deteriorate soil fertility and crop yield. Najeeb et al. (2017) reported that Pb toxicity induces oxidative stress (ROS) that inhibits seeds germination, nutrients assimilation, enzyme activity, and the photosynthetic rate in plants, ultimately affecting the crop yield. In view of this circumstance, the U.S, Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) and the Ministry of Ecology and Environment have settled down the maximum Pb concentration limits (400 mg/kg Agro–field area) for controlling the Pb pollution in the soil (Zhang et al.2019). In recent years, numerous sustainable and environmentally safe techniques have been used to remediate the metals polluted soils (Ashraf et al. 2019; Hou et al.,2020) At present, the adsorption technique is regarded as the most useful and inexpensive approach for Pb-contaminated soils (He et al.2021; Hong et al.2022).In recent decades, sunflower (*Helianthus annuus* L.), as a plant of the family Asteraceae, has attracted much attention for use in phytoextraction, as it could be grown under stressful conditions, such as heavy metal stress. Sunflower can accumulate relatively large amounts of metallic contaminants, besides translocating a good amount of the same from roots to shoots, and producing large quantities of biomass. Ashraf et al.,2021 found that *Helianthus annuus* L. was a robust and suitable plant that could be used for extracting and repairing cadmium, lead, and zinc from soil under certain conditions. Moreover, the success of phytoextraction partially relies on the solubility and availability of metal in soil for root uptake. Usually, heavy metals adsorbed in soil particles are difficult to be integrated by plants.

Statement of the problem

Environmental contamination due to heavy metals have become a matter of great concern over few decades as it poses toxic effects on plants and animals inhabiting the

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affected region. These pollutants are added in soil and water through industrial discharge, mining, pesticides, fertilizers and automobile exhausts. High contamination of heavy metals in soil and water also pose a potential threat to ecosystem; while their toxic effects limit the agricultural yield, their uptake by plants incorporates them in the food chain causing hazardous health effects (Chen et al., 2020). Trace amounts of heavy metals are potential enough to damage the vital functions of plants such as seed germination, seedling growth, photosynthesis and other physiological events. Heavy metals enter the human body through the gastrointestinal tract, skin, or via inhalation. Toxic metals have proven to be a major threat to human health, mostly because of their ability to cause membrane and DNA damage, and to perturb protein function and enzyme activity.

Materials and methods

Plant Materials and their Sources

The seeds of the selected plant species was collected from matured plants (*Jatropha curcas* L.) and (*Helianthus annuus* L.) growing in the Biological garden and taken to the Herbarium of the Department of plant science, Faculty of Chemical and Life Sciences, UDUS for further identification. The seeds were sorted to remove soil particles, dirt and debris before placed in an oven (at 600C) for 2 days to break the possible dormancy of the seeds. The seeds are stored in air tight containers until used.

Soil Analysis

The soil sample is transfer to a plastic tray for air-drying. Large clods are break up to speed up drying. Large plant residues are removed. The soil is not placed in direct sunlight. After drying, the total sample is weighed, Sieve through a 2 mm sieve, Clods not passing through the sieve are carefully crushed by a pestle and mortar and sieved again. Special features such as coarse concretions are picked out as quantitatively as possible and their content is determined separately. The fraction <2 mm (air-dry fine earth) is homogenized and constitutes the sample that is subjected to the usual laboratory procedures. The soil is analyse to know the heavy metals, toxins that is cyanide derivatives. present before planting the seeds. Soil samples are analyse for physico chemical properties such as texture, colour, pH, nitrate-nitrogen, calcium, magnesium etc. by using soil analysis kit. Respective extraction procedures are followed for analyzing the above properties. Reagents necessary for the analysis were provided in the kit. Physico-chemical properties of the soil are measured, heavy metals constituents and contaminants present are analyse (Farmaha et al., 2020).

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Solution Formulation and Spiking

Laboratory grade lead oxide (PbO₃) was dissolved in distilled water to make varying concentration of 0, 100, 250 and 500mm concentration of the respective contaminants. The solution is stored in air tight containers until required for use. (Ghani, 2011).

Experimental setup and description

The study was carried out at Tissue Culture in the main campus of Usmanu Danfodiyo University Sokoto (UDUS). A pot experiment was conducted in a Completely Randomized Design (CRD) Seeds were grown in plastic pots filled with 7kg of soil, 5 seeds were sown at equal distance and one inch deep in soil of corresponding pots, thinning to one-plant after 14 days from sowing. Lead oxide concentrations of 500 mM, 200 mM, 100 mM and 0 mM are used to spike the plants using 100 mL volume of each solution. Lead treatments were added to the soil at one-month seedling age. Stressed induced for two weeks, replicated three times (Hinkelmann and Kempthorne, 2008).

Determination of Leaf Spectroscopy and Pigment Indices

The plants are subjected to spiking with lead after 6 weeks of germination from mild concentration, average concentration to high concentration. After one week of spiking the measurement start using CID (CI-710) leaf spectra machine model CI 710s (spectra View) (CID Bio Science, Inc. Felix Instruments Applied Food Science 1554 NE 3TM Ave, Camas, WA 98607). According to the manufacturer manual there are two ways to take measurement, the live measurement and single measurement mode; previewing live measurement procedure are; place leaf inside of the leaf clip, enable display live measurement in the graph menu and select chosen mode in the home screen, then the start button and save button to record the measurement. Then the red box will be pressed to stop previewing. To take single measurement; leaf was placed inside of the leaf clip, disable display live measurement in the graph menu and the chosen mode will be selected in the home screen, press the start button to take/ save a measurement. All the growth markers are measured (leaf senescence, leaf colour, leaf pattern, leaf fluorescence, leaf pigmentation, chlorophyll contents and carotenoids) on the machine. Measurement continues weekly same day and time (Falcioni et al., 2023).

Analysis of Biomass and Heavy Metals

Plant samples were collected every 7 days and the shoot and roots were separated by stainless blade. All parts were washed with distilled water. Plant samples, including

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shoots and roots, were dried in an oven at 50°C, and the weights of samples were recorded by a weighing balance. The method develops by Awofolu (2015) was use in digesting the plant samples. A 0.5g sample of plant part in a beaker. 2ml of chloric acid (HClO₄) and 4ml concentrated (65%) nitric acid (HNO₃) will be added and heated on a hot plate until plant parts are digested. It will be allowed to cool and thereafter filter through the Whatman filter paper into a 50 cm³volumetric flask of 50 cm³. The filtrate collected and dilute with 50 cm³ with distilled water. All the filtrate both soil and plant parts will be analyse for heavy metals using microwave plasma atomic emission spectrophotometer (MPAES) (Black,2015). using acetylene/air as a gas mixture.

Statistical analysis

The results obtain was presented as Mean + SD of the 3 replicates used. The data generated on growth, morphology and pigment indices were analysed using two – way analysis of variance (ANOVA) using SPSS version 20 statistical package at 5% level of significance ($p \leq 0.05$) and 10% ($p \leq 0.01$). The difference between means was determine using Least Significance Difference (LSD) test.

Results

Growth and Morphological response of Sunflower to varying Concentration of Lead In lead, the results for plant growth parameters, involving plant shoot length (SL), root length (RL)and number of leaves. The height of plant decreased with increasing concentration of lead. The control 0mM recorded the highest height (51cm in week 1and 74cm in week 2) followed by 100mM and 200mM, (29cm in week 1and 62cm in week 2) and (25cm in week 1 and 67cm in week 2) and 500mM had the least value of height (24cm in week 1 and 45cm in week 2) respectively, there is statistical difference between the treatment $p < 0.05$ (Fig. 1).

The number of leaves per plant of sunflower is affected by various concentration of sunflower, the control (0mM) had the highest number of leaves in both weeks (27 in week 1 and 39 in week 2). Followed by 100mM (25 in week 1 and 33 in week 2) and 200mM (24 in week 1 and 32 in week 2). And subsequently 500mM had the least number of leaves (21 in week 1 and 31 in week 2). There is no significance statistical difference between the treatment $p > 0.05$ (Fig. 2). In addition, the result of root height shows no significance statistical difference $p > 0.05$, the control 0mM had the highest height (35cm in week 1 and 29cm in week 2), followed by 100mM and 200mM (25cm

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in week 1 and 26cm in week 2) and (27cm in week 1 and 24cm in week 2) and 500mM had the least height (25cm in week 1 and 21cm in week 2) respectively (Fig. 3)

Figure 1: plant height with varying concentration of lead

Figure 2: Number of leaves with different concentration of leaf

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Figure 3: Root length with different concentration of lead

Plant Biomass Determination

The result on the effect of lead on biomass of sunflower in shoot fresh water (SFW) shows that there is no statistical significance difference between the treatment $p > 0.05$, control (0mM) has the highest weight (week 1 86.8g and week 2 73.0g) followed by 100mM and 200mM, (77.1g in week 1 and 42.2g in week 2) and (67.1g in week 1 and 40g in week 2) and 500mM had the least weight (50.7g in week 1 and 38.3g in week, 2) respectively, (Fig. 4).

Furthermore, result on shoot dry weight (SDW) shows that there is no statistical significance difference $p > 0.05$, the control 0mM shows the highest dry matter 13.2g in week 1 and 13.3g in week 2 followed by 100mM and 200mM 11.0g in week 1 and 9.8g in week 2, 10.9g in week 1 and 9.2g in week 2 and 500mM had the least weight 10.0g in week 1 and 7.0g in week 2 respectively, (Fig. 5). The result on the effect of lead on biomass of sunflower in root fresh weight (RFW) shows that there is no statistical significance difference $p > 0.05$, control 0mM has the highest weight (week 1 14.6g and week 2 13.4g) followed by 100mM and 200mM, (11.0g in week 1 and 9.8g in week 2) and (9.9g in week 1 and 9.2g in week 2) and 500mM had the least weight (9.0g in week 1 and 7.8g in week 2) respectively, (Fig. 6). Root dry weight (RDW) shows that there is no statistical significance difference $p > 0.05$, the control 0mM shows the highest dry matter 3.5g in week 1 and 4.2g in week 2 followed by 100mM and 200mM 2.5g in week 1 and 2.3g in week 2, 2.3g in week 1 and 2.3g in week 2 and 500mM had the least weight 1.1g in week 1 and 1.7g in week 2 respectively, (Fig. 7).

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Figure 4: Fresh weight of shoot with varying concentration of lead

Figure 5: Dry weight of shoot with different concentration of lead

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Figure 6: Root fresh weigh with varying concentration of lead

Figure 7: Root dry weight with different concentration of lead

Leaf Spectroscopy and Pigment Indices In lead the results revealed that contaminated soils affect all plants survival rates and growth. The result with $p\text{-value} = 0.003 < 0.05$ for PSRI implies that there is significant difference between the effect of lead levels on PSRI of the sunflower at 5% level of significance. The results revealed that the effect of lead level 200mM with average value $-0.80 \pm 0.15\text{mM}$ is significantly lesser than lead levels 0mM, 100mM and 500mM with average values $-0.06 \pm 0.01\text{mM}$, $-0.07 \pm 0.02\text{mM}$ and $-0.07 \pm 0.04\text{mM}$ respectively. The result with $p\text{-value} = 0.042 < 0.05$ for CRI1 implies that there is significant difference between the effect of lead levels on CRI1 of the sunflower at 5% level of significance. The results revealed that the effect of lead level

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200mM with average value 0.30 ± 0.15 mM is significantly higher seconded by lead level 100mM 0.24 ± 0.12 mM and lastly are lead at levels 0mM and 100mM with average values 0.03 ± 0.12 , and 0.03 ± 0.13 respectively which equally significant. However, the p -value = $0.392 > 0.05$ for WBI, p -value = $0.705 > 0.05$ for SPAD, p -value = $0.699 > 0.05$ for G, p -value = $0.980 > 0.05$ for CHPLT, p -value = $0.379 > 0.05$ for CPHLA, p -value = $0.317 > 0.05$ for CPHLB, p -value = $0.994 > 0.05$ for ARI1 and p -value = $0.790 > 0.05$ for CCI implied that effects of lead contents at 0mM (control), 100mM, 200mM and 500mM on WBI, SPAD, G, CHPLT, CPHLA, CPHLB, ARI1 and CCI of sunflower are not statistically significant at 5 % level (Table1).

Table 1: Effects of Lead on Some Parameters of Sunflower

Group	WBI	SPAD	PSRI	G	CRI1	CHPLT	CPHLA	CPHLB	ARI1	CCI
0mM	1.14±0.08	19.7±3.53	0.06±0.01 ^b	2.20±0.26	0.03±0.12 ^c	27.5±5.56	10.6±1.23	16.8±3.25	0.003±0.002	6.52±1.62
100mM	1.14±0.15	19.6±2.79	0.07±0.02 ^b	2.33±0.27	0.03±0.13 ^c	26.8±3.97	10.3±1.38	16.4±4.31	0.003±0.002	6.39±1.24
200mM	1.14±0.01	18.97±4.95	0.80±0.15 ^a	2.28±0.25	0.30±0.15 ^a	26.9±3.98	10.4±1.34	16.5±6.08	0.002±0.003	6.27±2.29
500mM	0.980±0.38	17.01±5.14	0.07±0.04 ^b	2.20±0.38	0.24±0.12 ^b	24.9±4.73	9.65±1.70	15.2±3.02	0.002±0.004	5.43±2.12
S.E	0.78	1.859	0.11	0.131	2.012	1.806	0.631	1.174	0.002	0.078
F-stat	0.164	0.473	3.509	0.482	2.947	0.98	0.82	1.065	0.124	0.35
P-value	0.392	0.705	0.003	0.699	0.042	0.337	0.379	0.317	0.994	0.79
Sig.	NS	NS	*	NS	*	NS	NS	NS	NS	NS

Means followed by the same letter along the columns are not significantly different
 * = significant at 5%, NS = Not Significant, Values=Mean ± SD, SD= Standard deviation

Heavy Metal Analysis and Uptake Bioaccumulation of lead in sunflower shoot and root, the result with p -value = $0.000 < 0.05$ for lead bioaccumulation on sunflower' shoots

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in the presence of heavy metals implies that there is significant difference between the effect of lead levels of sunflower's shoots at 5% level of significance. The results revealed that the effect of lead level 500mM with average value 0.4549 ± 0.0264 mM is significantly higher seconded by lead levels 200mM with average value 0.3545 ± 0.0199 mM, followed by 100 mM with average value 0.2412 ± 0.0253 mM and lastly 0 mM level with average value 0.0098 ± 0.0043 mM (Table 2).

The result $F=10.526$ with $p\text{-value}= 0.000 < 0.05$ for lead bioaccumulation on sunflower's roots in the presence of heavy metals implies that there is significant difference between the effect of lead levels at 5% level of significance. The results revealed that the effect of lead level 500 mM with average value 0.5384 ± 0.0307 mM is significantly higher seconded by lead levels 200 mM with average value 0.4637 ± 0.0746 mM, followed by 100mM with average value 0.3417 ± 0.0176 mM and lastly 0 mM level with average value 0.1196 ± 0.2726 mM

Table 2: Bioaccumulation of Lead in shoot and root of Sunflower

Concentrations	Parameters	
	Shoot	Root
0mM	0.0098 ± 0.0043^d	0.1196 ± 0.2726^d
100mM	0.2412 ± 0.0253^c	0.3417 ± 0.0176^c
200mM	0.3545 ± 0.0199^b	0.4637 ± 0.0746^b
500mM	0.4549 ± 0.0264^a	0.5384 ± 0.0307^a
S.E	0.006	0.056
F-stat	970.557	10.526
P-value	0.000	0.000
Sig.	*	*

Total uptake of lead by sunflower by measuring the amount left in soil

The result with $p\text{-value}= 0.000 < 0.05$ for lead accumulated in soil after harvesting implies that there is significant difference between the lead levels left in the soil at 5% level of significance. The results revealed that the 500mM treatment with average value 0.6428 ± 0.0577 mM is significantly higher seconded by lead levels 200 mM with average

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value 0.5619 ± 0.0250 mM, followed by 100mM with average value 0.4465 ± 0.0338 mM and lastly 0mM level with average value 0.0065 ± 0.0028 mM (Table3)

Table 3: Lead accumulated in soil after harvesting with different conc. of lead

Concentrations	Parameter Soil
0mM	0.0065 ± 0.0028^d
100mM	0.4465 ± 0.0338^c
200mM	0.5619 ± 0.0250^b
500mM	0.6428 ± 0.0577^a
S.E	0.014
F-stat	398.857
P-value	0.000
Sig.	*

Discussion

Plant growth, physiology, and antioxidant enzyme activities are susceptible to metal toxicity and elucidated through cell injury and plant tolerance levels against metal stress (Aslam et al.2021). In this present work, the plant height was rigorously affected when plants were exposed to lead contamination. Soares et al. (2001) reported that higher concentration of heavy metal has been reported to retard the cell division and differentiation, reduce their elongation and effect plant growth and development. The root and shoot length of the treated seedlings were also found to be considerably reduced at all levels of the heavy metals applied, except the control, where root length was more or less comparable with those of untreated seedlings (Figure 1 and 3). The adverse effects on root and shoot growth were much more pronounced at the higher concentration (500mM), which may be one aspect of the role of metabolic inhibitors in the overall phenomenon of plants growth. Many studies had reported an inhibitory effect of various heavy metals, including Cd and Pb, on plant growth (Sharma and Dubey 2005; Mishra et al., 2006). The result on number of leaves revealed that heavy metal affect the number of leaves, plants with the highest concentration of lead has the lowest number of leaves in both weeks. Same pathological changes in ultra-structure level were testified on other plant species by Goyal et al. (2020). Leaves are considered as one of the most important plant organs because of their role in capturing light and making food by the process of photosynthesis.

Farooqi et al. (2009) made a study on soybean which indicated that heavy metal toxicity induced a histological change in leaves, and made a thin leaf blade, minified the xylem and phloem in the vascular bundles, and also reduced the diameter of the xylem vessels. At the same time, all these damages could disrupt many plant activities including anti oxidative system, photosynthesis, respiration, mineral nutrition,

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membrane structure and properties and gene expression (Figure 2). Furthermore, the observed negative impacts on sunflower physiology (Table 1) confirmed that lead concentration in the soil above tolerable limits poses a threat to plant physiological machinery, which results in chlorosis, necrosis, rolling and twisting of leaves, eventually impeded the plant health (Shabaan et al.,2020; Ahmed et al.,2022). My results are similar to previous studies that revealed severe adverse effects on plant growth and physiology under lead stress Carotenoids serve as antioxidants against free radicals and photochemical damage (Sengar et al., 2008). Result of current study reveal no significant ($p < 0.05$) change in chlorophyll a, and b and carotenoids. (Table 1), indicated that sunflower plant may has a high ability to tolerate lead stress. The deterioration of chlorophyll synthesis due to lead toxicity resulting in chlorotic leaves, changed ratios of chlorophyll a and b (Viehweger and Geipel, 2010) and photosynthetic activity. The exposure to lead decreased the dry matter significantly in experimental plants (Figure 5 and 7). The considerable reduction in dry matter yields of the plants under the influence of high concentrations of heavy metals is in agreement with significant reduction reported in dry biomass of *Albizzia lebbek* under the toxic effect of lead and cadmium Farooqi et al. (2009).

The growth-development, fresh-dry biomass and growth tolerance index of root, shoot and leaves were negatively altered by increasing lead concentrations in sunflower (Figure 4 and 6). Same results were obtained by some other studies at the calculated lead concentration: root, shoot and leaf growth, fresh and dry biomass were critically reduced *Zea mays* (Wang et al., 2021). The weight of the shoot was significantly higher than that of the roots. Other authors (Ashraf et al., 2019; Alaboudi et al.,2018) found reductions of dry matter production in many plant species as a function of the application of increasing doses of heavy metal in experiments with soil and nutrient solution. Based on the results in Table 3, it is clear that sunflower can uptake heavy metals to the plant tissue as previously reported by Spirochova et al., (2003). From the experimental data it was clear that the largest portion of lead taken up by the plant was stored in the roots rather than in stem and leaves. This is because heavy metals are absorbed by roots from soil solution and later on translocated to leaves (through xylem vessels) where they are deposited in vacuoles (de Abreu et al., 2017). Lead accumulation in roots is considered to be a factor that increases plant tolerance to lead toxicity, because it prevents the metal translocation to leaves (Azad et al., 2011). Based on the experimental data it is clear that as the concentration of lead in the soil increases the amount of metal taken up by the plant also increases.

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From Table 3 it is clear that the lead concentration in the whole plant is less slightly than the metal concentration in the soil after harvesting. Based on lead accumulation in roots more than other parts of the plant, it could be concluded that roots play a very significant role in extra lead storage. The high lead concentration, found mainly in roots, suggested that sunflower tend to avoid toxicity in the physiologically most active portions of the plants by reducing lead translocation to the epigeous portion.

Conclusion

The problem of heavy metal pollution is continuously worsening due to a series of human activities, leading to intensification of the research dealing with the phytotoxicity of these contaminants and with the mechanisms used by plants to counter their harmful effects. Heavy metal pollutants like lead, undoubtedly cause deleterious effects in plants. In this study, the tolerance limits and mechanisms of heavy metal tolerance of sunflower were assessed against three levels each of lead exposure. All the growth parameters were affected at different concentration. These findings are relevant to evaluate the effect of heavy metal pollutants on sunflower and assess the tolerance levels of the plant. The results from this study would certainly be useful to find strategies to alleviate sunflower from heavy metal stress and also to explore and enhance its phytoremediation potential.

Recommendations

1. The level of potentially toxic heavy metals and metalloids in water, sediments, soils and the resident biota should be assessed and monitored regularly
2. The public should be educated about the harmful effects of toxic heavy metals on human health and the environment.
3. The native plant proposed in this research can be effectively used in practical applications of phytoremediation with the aim of remediating soil contaminated by heavy metals around metal smelting factories and mining sites etc.

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Impact of E-Learning Machine Model on Achievement in Mathematics Concepts among Secondary School Students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the Impact of E-Learning Machine Model on Achievement in Mathematics Concepts among Secondary School Students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria. A pre-test post-test quasi experimental research design was adopted for the study. Simple Random Sampling technique was used to select two co-educational schools from the target population. The sample of the study consisted of 122 students, in which 60 are male while 62 are female Senior Secondary class two students during 2024/2025 academic session in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State. The instrument used for data collection was E-Learning Machine Model Test (EMMT). The EMMT had a reliability index of 0.88 using Test-retest reliability test which implies that the instrument is significant. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while the null-hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Independent Sample t-test statistics. The results of the study revealed that students taught mathematics using E-Learning machine model performed significantly better than those taught the same contents using the conventional method. The study also revealed that both male and female students in the experimental group performed significantly better. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that teachers should be trained on how to use e-learning machine model effectively in their teaching practices through workshops and seminars.

Keywords: E-learning machine model, achievement, mathematics concepts.

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Introduction

Mathematics provides a fundamental framework for comprehending the intricacies of the physical world, enabling the interpretation of spatial and temporal relationships. Its significance extends to underpinning scientific and technological advancements, which in turn drive socio-economic development. Consequently, mathematics education is mandatory in Nigerian primary and secondary schools. Furthermore, proficiency in mathematics is a prerequisite for admission into esteemed university programs, including engineering, medicine, and accounting, highlighting its crucial role in academic and professional pursuits. Mathematics is a vital subject that extends beyond academic qualifications, as it equips students with essential skills for future success, regardless of their chosen career path (Davies & Hersh, 2012). This notion is reinforced by Mefor (2014), who succinctly emphasizes that mathematics relates to everything across the universe, from the smallest scales to the vast expanse of the universe.

Despite its pivotal role in societal development, mathematics is often a source of anxiety, failure, and disdain among students (Areelu, 2014). The subject has long been perceived as the most challenging component of the school curriculum, fostering a pervasive negative attitude among learners that transcends generations. This entrenched mindset, which extends to adults who have previously struggled with mathematics, can lead to a devaluation of the subject's importance, ultimately influencing the effectiveness of educators' teaching efforts (Ajani & Konku, 2012).

Mathematics education is a multidisciplinary field that focuses on the development and implementation of effective methods, tools, and approaches to teach and learn mathematics. At the higher education level, mathematics education aims to equip students with advanced mathematical skills, quantitative reasoning, and symbolic manipulation through various programs, including general education, services, majors, and graduate studies. According to Odili (2012), mathematicians can be broadly classified into two categories: mathematics educators and professional mathematicians. Mathematics educators specialize in curriculum design, instructional development, and pedagogical innovation, whereas professional mathematicians focus on advancing mathematical knowledge and applications.

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Mathematics education fundamentally aims to cultivate innovative instructors who can effectively communicate mathematical concepts to learners across various levels. Mathematics educators perceive mathematics as a dynamic field of practice, rather than merely a static body of knowledge or academic discipline. As Lester (2002) notes, this perspective emphasizes the importance of understanding how mathematics is learned, interpreted, and applied, as well as how individuals conceptualize and utilize mathematics in their daily lives. Furthermore, educators seek to bridge the gap between mathematical concepts taught in schools and their real-world applications. The rapid evolution of technology has significantly impacted the educational landscape, enabling unprecedented opportunities for learning and interaction, even in remote and underserved regions.

The widespread adoption of Information Communication Technology (ICT) necessitates the evolution of education through e-learning platforms. As underscored by Adeyinka and Olusola (2009), the integration of ICT into educational settings enhances the learning experience, organisational structure, and administrative efficiency of institutions. Furthermore, the internet has emerged as a transformative force, significantly contributing to the advancement of educational development and bridging the knowledge gap. The integration of technology in education has transformed the way students learn and teachers teach. E-learning leverages information and communication technology (ICT) to facilitate a seamless exchange of knowledge between educators and learners across all educational levels, thereby marking a significant milestone in the advancement of education.

E-learning machine models are computational models that utilise machine learning algorithms to analyse learner's behaviour, preferences, and performance, and adapt the learning content, pace and style to meet individual learner needs (Kotsiantis, 2012). Research by Stephen (2023) has demonstrated that the integration of e-learning machine models in education improved outcomes, enhanced student engagement, and increased support for teachers. E-learning machine models can significantly improve teaching and learning outcomes in mathematics education for sustainable development in secondary schools in several ways which include, Adaptive Learning, Learning Pathways, Interactive Simulations, Real-world applications and Learning analytics among others (Koedinger et al., 2013).

Adaptive Learning: E-learning machine models can adjust the difficulty level of mathematical problems and provide real-time feedback, catering to individual

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students' needs and abilities (Koedinger et al., 2013). Furthermore, in terms of learning pathways, Machine learning algorithms can create personalized learning pathways for students, recommending relevant mathematical concepts and resources based on their learning history and performance (Romero & Ventura, 2010). Interactive simulations: E-learning machine models can provide interactive simulations and games that make mathematical concepts more engaging and accessible, promoting active learning and exploration (Hansen et al., 2016). Real-world applications, Machine learning models can help students connect mathematical concepts to real-world sustainable development challenges, making learning more relevant and meaningful (Ernest, 2012). Efficient assessment and feedback to automated grading, E-learning machine models can automate the grading process, freeing up instructors' time to focus on providing feedback and support (Baker et al., 2016). Real-time feedback, Machine learning algorithms can provide immediate feedback to students on their performance, helping them identify areas of improvement and track their progress (Koedinger et al., 2013).

Learning analytics: E-learning machine models can provide instructors with valuable insights into student learning behavior, helping them identify knowledge gaps and adjust their instruction accordingly (Siemens, 2013). Moreso in the area of predictive modelling, machine learning algorithms can predict student performance and enabling instructors to provide targeted support and interventions (Romero & Ventura, 2010). E-learning machine models have emerged as a promising tool for improving teaching and learning outcomes in mathematics. This study therefore, investigates the impact of e-learning machine model on teaching and learning in mathematics education for sustainable development in senior secondary schools in Zaria, Kaduna State, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the crucial role of mathematics education in sustainable development, students continue to show weakness in attempting Mathematics examination questions. WAEC Chief Examiner's report 20223 pointed out eleven (11) areas of students' weaknesses against three (3) areas of strength in answering mathematics examination questions which is worrisome. The traditional teaching methods, which emphasize lecturing and rote memorization, have been criticized for failing to promote deep understanding, critical thinking and problem-solving skills (Nwafor, 2017). Furthermore, the absence of adequate instructional materials, including e-learning resources, has hindered the effective teaching and learning of mathematics. Researchers have explored various factors contributing to the poor

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performance in mathematics, Impact of E-Learning Machine Model on Achievement in Mathematics Concepts among Secondary School Students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State, Nigeria remain understudied, highlighting the need for an investigation into the potential benefits of integrating e-learning machine model into mathematics education in secondary schools. The use of e-learning machine model has the potential to address these challenges and improve teaching and learning outcomes in Mathematics (Ahn & Edwin, 2018). Based on these factors, the researcher wishes to investigate Impact of E-Learning Machine Model on Achievement in Mathematics Concepts among Secondary School Students in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State.

Objectives of the Study

The study has the following objectives:

1. To determine the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics concept using E-learning machine Model and those exposed to lecture method among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State
2. To determine the mean achievement scores of Male and Female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State

Research questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What are the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model and those exposed to lecture method among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State?
2. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State?

Research Hypotheses

The following research hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model and those exposed to lecture method among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State

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Methodology

The study adopted a quasi-experimental control group design employing pre-test and post-test. Quasi-experimental design was adopted because the researcher has no total control over the study subjects. The study involved two groups; one experimental group and one control group which were drawn from the population of senior secondary class two (SSII) in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State. The experimental group was taught mathematics using E-learning Machine Model while the control group was taught mathematics using the conventional method. The population of the study consisted of 7,550 students from all the senior secondary schools in Zaria Metropolis. Then a sample of 122 was randomly selected from two senior secondary schools, in which 60 are male and 62 are female students. The instrument used for the study was E-Learning Machine Model Test (EMMT). The face and content validity of the instrument was vetted by the experts in Mathematics department, experts in the department of Test and Measurement evaluation. The reliability of the instrument was determined by using Test-retest reliability test which was analysed using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation analysis that yielded the reliability coefficient of 0.88. The data collected were subjected to both descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions were answered with the use of mean and standard deviation while the research hypotheses were tested using t-test statistic at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Result

The results of the study were obtained from the research questions answered and hypotheses formulated for the study;

Research question one

What are the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model and those exposed to lecture method among secondary schools in Zaria Metropolis, Kaduna State?

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Achievement Scores in Mathematics of both the Experimental Group and Control Group after the Treatment.

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Experimental	64	50.18	9.07	

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Control	58	39.53	12.54	10.65
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The result in Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of the students' achievement scores in mathematics between the experimental group and the control group. The results revealed that the experimental group had the mean score of (50.18) while the control group had the mean score of (39.53). The mean difference between the experimental and control group was 10.65. This implies that the experimental group that was taught mathematics with e-Learning machine model performed significantly better than the control group that was mathematics using lecture method.

Null Hypothesis One:

There is no significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model and those exposed to lecture method among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State. This was analysed using Independent Sample t-test, the summary of the result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Independent sample t-test analysis on the students' post-test in the Experimental and Control group after treatment

Group	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Remark
Experimental	64	50.18	9.07	120	20.05	0.001	*
Control	58	39.53	12.54				

* Significant at $p \leq 0.05$

The independent sample t-test result in Table 2, shows that the difference in the test scores between the experimental group (N=64, M=50.18, SD=9.07) and control group (N=58, M=39.53, SD=12.54) were statistically significant. t-value = 20.05 and the p-value of 0.001 was less than $\alpha \leq 0.05$. Based on this result, the null hypothesis was rejected, which shows that there is significant difference in the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model and those exposed to lecture method. Since the mean score of the experimental group is higher than the control group it therefore implies that the mean achievement scores of students taught mathematics with e-learning machine model enhances the academic achievement of secondary school students in mathematics than the conventional method.

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Research question two

What are the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State? Summary of the mean and standard deviation is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' Achievement Scores in Mathematics for both Male and Female students in the Experimental Group

Group	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean Difference
Male	33	43.05	20.20	1.04
Female	31	42.01	20.10	

The result in Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of both male and female students' achievement scores in mathematics within the experimental group. The results revealed that the male students had the mean score of (43.05) while the female students had the mean score of (42.01). The mean difference between the male and the female students in the experimental group was 1.04. This implies that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model in the experimental group.

Null Hypothesis Two:

There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State. This was analysed using Independent Sample t-test, the summary of the result is presented in Table 4:

Table 4: Independent sample t-test analysis on male and female students' achievement in mathematics within the Experimental group

Gender	N	Mean	SD	Df	t-value	P-value	Remark
Male	33	43.05	20.20	62	0.19	0.79	**
Female	31	42.01	20.10				

** Not significant $p > 0.05$

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The result in Table 4, showed an independent sample t-test of the difference in the test scores between the male students (N=33, M=43.05, SD=20.20) and the female students (N=31, M=42.01, SD=20.10) were statistically not significant. t-value = 0.19 and the p-value of 0.79 was greater than $\alpha \leq 0.05$. Based on this result, the null hypothesis was retained, this means that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female students taught mathematics concept using e-learning machine Model among secondary schools in Zaria metropolis, Kaduna State. Thus, e-learning machine model enhances the academic performance of both male and female students in mathematics.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study revealed that the experimental group who were taught mathematics using e-learning machine model performed significantly better than those taught mathematics using the conventional method. The difference was in favour of the experimental group; this could be due to the fact that e-learning machine model allows active participation of students than the conventional method which is teacher centre method. Several studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of e-learning machine models in improving student learning outcomes in mathematics. For instance, a study by Koedinger et al. (2013) found that students who used an intelligent tutoring system (ITS) for mathematics performed better than those who received traditional instruction. Similarly, a study by Ritter et al. (2017) found that students who used a computer-based mathematics tutor outperformed those who received traditional instruction.

Furthermore, the result of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in the academic achievement of both male and female students in mathematics when taught with e-learning machine model. This shows that e-learning machine model is gender friendly and improves the performance of both male and female students in mathematics. This is in accordance with the findings of Wang et al. (2016) who found that girls who used a computer-based mathematics program performed as well as boys, suggesting that technology-based instruction can help reduce the gender gap in mathematics achievement. More so, the use of e-learning machine models has been shown to promote sustainable development in education. A study by UNESCO (2017) highlighted the potential of technology-based instruction to promote sustainable development in education. Overall, the findings of this study contribute to the growing

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body of research that supports the use of e-learning machine models to improve teaching and learning in mathematics education.

Conclusion

This study concludes that e-learning machine models have a positive impact on students' achievement in mathematics concepts among senior secondary school students in Zaria. The use of e-learning machine models enhances students' achievement in mathematics, promotes student-centered learning methods, and improves overall teaching and learning outcomes. Both male and female students performed relatively equally when taught using e-learning machine models. Therefore, teachers should be encouraged to integrate e-learning machine models into their teaching practices for both boys and girls, while conventional learning methods should be supplemented to enhance learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are made:

1. Schools should invest in e-learning technologies to enhance the teaching and learning of mathematics, ensuring accessibility for both teachers and students.
2. Teachers should receive continuous professional development through workshops and seminars on the effective integration of e-learning tools into their instructional practices.
3. Policymakers should formulate and implement strategic policies that support the adoption and sustainability of e-learning technologies in secondary schools

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(Effects of jigsaw Instructional Strategy on Performance and Retention ... Sani, M., Et. al., 2025)

Effects of Jigsaw (iv) Instructional Strategy on Performance and Retention in Mensuration Concept Among Secondary School Students in Katsina State

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Abstract

This study examined the Effect of Jigsaw (IV) Instructional Strategy on Performance and Retention in Mensuration Concept among Secondary School Students in Katsina State. A quasi-experimental design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of 77,117 (44,113 Male & 33,004 Female) senior secondary school class two (SS II) mathematics students during the 2024/2025 academic session in Katsina State. A sample size of 159 (84 Male & 75 Female) students were selected from the target population using a multistage sampling technique. Data were obtained using the Mensuration Performance Test (MPT), which was validated and a reliability coefficient of 0.89 was obtained. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, and hypotheses were tested using ANCOVA at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that students taught mensuration using jigsaw (IV) instructional strategy (J4IS) significantly outperformed and retained the concept better than those taught using the lecture method (LM). Based on these findings, J4IS was more effective in teaching mensuration concept than LM and recommended that mathematics teachers should adopt the J4IS to enhance students' engagement, performance, and retention in mensuration and related topics.

Keywords: Jigsaw IV, Performance, Retention, Mensuration

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Introduction

Teaching strategies have a significant impact on students' academic performance and retention in the classroom, especially in subjects that call for both conceptual knowledge and real-world application. While retention refers to the long-term storage and retrieval of learnt data for future application, performance, as an indication of accomplishment, represents students' capacity to understand and apply concepts effectively. Since students frequently need to apply abstract ideas like mensuration to address real-world situations, these dependent variables are essential in mathematics education (Valderama & Oligo, 2021). However, there is also disagreement about how well teaching strategies work to achieve these goals, with conventional lecture-based techniques frequently falling short in terms of student engagement or fostering deeper comprehension (Armstead & Gragg, 2022).

The requirement for creative teaching tactics is shown by the connection between teaching strategies and students' academic performance. By actively engaging students in the learning process, effective teaching strategies not only improve retention but also make comprehension easier. Cooperative learning techniques, for instance, have been demonstrated to promote engagement, accountability, and interaction while promoting a better comprehension of challenging subjects (Khan, 2019). Because mensuration is abstract and depends on geometric concepts, it poses special difficulties as a crucial subject of mathematics. Research has shown that lack of use of teaching strategies that neglect the interactive and practical components of the topic are frequently associated with poor performance and retention in mensuration (Yakubu, 2016).

The Jigsaw IV strategy, a cooperative learning approach, has demonstrated potential for improving students' academic outcomes, particularly in challenging subject areas. This strategy engages students in collaborative activities where they learn specific material, teach it to peers, and collectively synthesize knowledge through group discussions and presentations (Aronson, 2023). The Jigsaw IV technique is particularly useful for complex topics like mensuration in mathematics because of its organized stages, which include expert group discussions, quizzes, and re-teaching sessions. These phases enable deeper investigation of the material and close learning gaps (Gonzalez, 2015).

As a dependent variable, performance refers to students' ability to demonstrate their understanding of mensuration through measurable academic outcomes such as test scores, problem-solving accuracy, and application of concepts in real-world scenarios.

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Another critical dependent variable is retention, which involves students' ability to store and recall mathematical knowledge, ensuring they can retrieve and apply it when needed. Effective memory of mensuration concepts such as calculating geometric forms' areas, volumes, and perimeters is critical for laying the groundwork for advanced mathematical topics and real-world applications (Valderama & Oligo, 2021).

Geometric qualities such as area, volume, and perimeter are studied and calculated in mensuration, a basic field of mathematics. However, it is frequently viewed as abstract and challenging, which results in ongoing difficulties with students' performance and retention. Yakubu (2016) found that low performance in mensuration is mostly caused by a lack of understanding of fundamental geometrical concepts and an inability to apply them to problem-solving activities. Similar to this, Armstead and Gragg (2022) pointed out that students find it difficult to remember important concepts when traditional, lecture-based teaching techniques fail to appropriately handle the interactive and practical character of mensuration.

According to research, these difficulties may be lessened by using cooperative learning techniques like the Jigsaw IV approach. Cooperative learning strategies enhance performance by encouraging active involvement, group responsibility, and peer-to-peer teaching, according to studies like those by Khan (2019) and Gonzalez (2015). For example, Gonzalez (2015) showed that students taught using the Jigsaw IV technique recalled more knowledge than their peers exposed to standard teaching methods, while Khan (2019) highlighted that collaborative assignments improve conceptual comprehension. Additionally, Yakubu (2016) reported that students who were exposed to cooperative learning strategies outperformed their peers in mensuration tasks, demonstrating the efficacy of these approaches in tackling subject-specific difficulties.

The study's focus on Katsina State secondary school students is especially warranted given the region's ongoing difficulties with mathematics instruction. Studies have shown that traditional teaching approaches, a lack of interactive learning methodologies suited to the local educational environment, and a lack of instructional resources all contribute to Katsina State students' low performance in mensuration. For example, Yakubu (2016) found that low performance in mensuration is mostly caused by a lack of understanding of fundamental geometrical concepts and an inability to apply them to problem-solving activities. Similarly, research by Kankia (2011) showed that students find it difficult to remember important ideas since traditional, lecture-based teaching approaches do not sufficiently handle the

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interactive and practical aspect of mathematics. Therefore, carrying out the study in this setting guarantees that the results are relevant to similar places with comparable educational issues and provide insightful information about how to improve mathematics education.

Statement of the Research Problem

Failure in mathematics is still a major problem worldwide, but especially in Nigeria, and more especially in Katsina State. The WAEC Examiners' Reports (2019, 2021) pointed out that students showed deficiencies in resolving mensuration-related issues, highlighting mensuration as one of the troublesome mathematical concepts. Additionally, the 2024 WASSCE report showed that applicants' performance in English language and mathematics had decreased by 7.69% from 2023 (Omisakin, 2024). Accordingly, Wasagu and Kabir (2022), Ibrahim et al. (2023), and Dauda et al. (2024) identified a number of factors that contribute to this low performance, including inadequate laboratories and instructional materials, students' lack of geometrical background, and teachers' improper implementation of the curriculum. These problems are made worse by the widespread adoption of lecture teaching method, which do not actively involve students in the learning process. Furthermore, students find it difficult to use their mathematical understanding to resolve practical issues, especially those involving mensuration. To address these issues, appropriate teaching strategies for mensuration concepts must be developed. This study aims to investigate the effectiveness of the Jigsaw IV instructional strategy in enhancing students' performance and retention of mensuration in Katsina State, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives of the study:

1. To examine the effect of jigsaw IV instructional strategy on performance in mensuration among secondary school students in Katsina State;
2. To investigate the effect of jigsaw IV instructional strategy on retention of mensuration among secondary school students in Katsina State.

Research Questions

The following questions were drowned to guide the study:

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1. What is the difference between the mean performance scores of students taught mensuration using jigsaw IV instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture method?
2. What is the difference between the mean retention scores of students taught mensuration using jigsaw IV instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture method?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught mensuration using jigsaw IV instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture method.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught mensuration using jigsaw IV instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture method.

Methodology

The study adopted Quasi-experimental research design in order to establish a cause-and-effect relationship between the variables. The population of the study consists of 77,117 (44,113 Male & 33,004 Female) senior secondary school class two (SS II) mathematics students during the 2024/2025 academic session in Katsina State. A sample size of 159 (84 Male & 75 Female) students were selected from the target population using a multistage sampling technique.

The instrument used for the study data collection was Mensuration Performance Test (MPT) which was validated by three experts in mathematics education with a reliability coefficient of 0.89 tested using Cronbach's Alpha. It was used to test the students' performance and retention abilities on mensuration which was administered three times as pretest, posttest and post-posttest. All the research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation, while the hypotheses were tested using ANCOVA at 0.05 significance level.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

(Effects of jigsaw Instructional Strategy on Performance and Retention ... Sani, M., Et. al., 2025)

What is the difference between the mean performance scores of students taught mensuration using jigsaw IV instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture method?

To answer the research question 1, MPT marks of students taught mensuration using jigsaw IV instructional strategy and those taught using Lecture method were subjected to descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation in table 1

Table 1

Means and Standard Deviations Performance Scores of J4IS and LM

Strategy	N	Mean	SD	Mean Diff.
J4IS	75	51.40	13.27	9.61
LM	84	41.79	10.81	

From table 1 the mean and standard deviation performance scores of students taught mensuration using J4IS ($M = 51.40$, $SD = 13.27$) was greater than that of those taught using LM ($M = 41.79$, $SD = 10.81$) with difference of 9.61 mean score. To investigate whether the difference is significant or not, null hypothesis one was tested and the result presented in Table 3.

Research Question 2

What is the difference between the mean retention scores of students taught mensuration using jigsaw IV instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture method?

Table 2

Means and Standard Deviations Retention Scores of J4IS and LM

Strategy	N	Mean	SD	Mean Diff.
J4IS	75	53.07	14.70	7.72
LM	84	45.35	12.82	

In table 2 the mean and standard deviation retention scores of students taught mensuration by the J4IS ($M = 53.07$, $SD = 14.70$) was higher than that of LM ($M =$

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45.35, $SD = 12.82$) with difference of 7.72 mean score. To investigate whether the difference is significant or not, null hypothesis two was tested and the result presented in Table 4.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean performance scores of students taught mensuration using jigsaw IV instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture method.

The hypothesis was tested using ANCOVA in the table 3.

Table 3

Analysis of Covariance on Mean Performance Scores of J4IS and LM

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	4200.183 ^a	2	2100.091	14.776	.000
Intercept	44419.361	1	44419.361	312.524	.000
Pretest	537.684	1	537.684	3.783	.054
Treatment	3520.664	1	3520.664	24.771	.000
Error	22172.459	156	142.131		
Total	367525.000	159			
Corrected Total	26372.642	158			

Note. R Squared = .159 (Adjusted R Squared = .148)

The ANCOVA result in table 3 showed that there was significant difference in the mean performance scores of the students taught mensuration using J4IS and those taught through LM, $F(1, 156) = 24.77, p < .001$. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant difference between the mean retention scores of students taught mensuration using jigsaw IV instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture method.

The hypothesis was tested using ANCOVA in the table 4.

Table 4

Analysis of Covariance Result on mean Retention Scores of J4IS and LM

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
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Corrected Model	16469.893 ^a	2	8234.947	59.375	.000
Intercept	3212.490	1	3212.490	23.163	.000
Posttest	8007.395	1	8007.395	57.735	.000
Treatment	2705.919	1	2705.919	19.510	.000
Error	21636.081	156	138.693		
Total	365050.000	159			
Corrected Total	38105.975	158			

Note. R Squared = .432 (Adjusted R Squared = .425)

Table 4 revealed that there was significant difference between the mean retention scores of the students taught mensuration using J4IS and those taught using LM, $F(1, 156) = 19.51, p < .001$. Hence, the null hypothesis was rejected.

Discussion of findings

Tables 1 and 3 showed that there was significant difference in the mean performance of students taught mensuration using jigsaw IV instructional strategy and those taught through LM and the difference is in favour of those taught using Jigsaw IV instructional strategy. This agreed with the findings of Yakubu (2016) on “Impacts of Jigsaw II Co-operative learning strategy on academic performance and retention in mensuration among senior secondary school students in Kano State”. The findings showed that the mean performance of students taught using jigsaw II co-operative learning strategy is higher than that of lecture method. Other corresponded research finding include that of Abdullahi and Salisu (2017) whose finding showed that experimental group had higher mean score than that of control group, and suggested that cooperative instruction was the best approach to enhance students learning of Arabic language. This could be attributed to the fact that in cooperative learning as in the case of jigsaw IV strategy, students were actively involved in the learning process. Therefore, in this study jigsaw IV instructional strategy improves the students’ performance in mensuration.

Tables 2 and 4 revealed that the students’ mean retention scores of the two groups were different, the students taught mensuration using jigsaw IV instructional strategy retained significantly higher than those taught using lecture method. The findings are in line with that of Jamilu et al (2022) whose finding revealed that students taught with Jigsaw IV strategy retained higher in geometry than those taught using lecture method. Also, the findings of Nwankwo and Okigbo (2021) whose revealed that the students taught chemistry using jigsaw strategy retained significantly higher than those taught using traditional method. According to Valderama and Oligo (2021), learners’ retention is increasing due to use of good and effective instructional method

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by the teachers. Thus, treating students through jigsaw IV instructional strategy could increase their retention abilities on mensuration.

Conclusion

Based on the study findings, it could be concluded that jigsaw IV instructional strategy was better and more effective in teaching mensuration and could enhanced the students' performance and retention ability more than the lecture method commonly used in the study area. Since, the students were actively involved into the lesson activities of the strategy. Thus, the strategy could be used in place of lecture method for better achievement.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings and conclusion of the study, the following recommendations were made:

- 1) Secondary school mathematics teachers should be encouraged in using jigsaw IV instructional strategy in teaching mensuration and other related concepts.
- 2) Jigsaw IV Strategy should be incorporated into the curriculum for effective teaching of mensuration concept and other aspects of Geometry concept in all Senior Secondary Schools in Katsina State.
- 3) Professional bodies such as Mathematics Association of Nigeria (MAN), Science Teachers Association of Nigeria (STAN) and Nigerian Educational and Research Development Council (NERDC) should encourage the use of the alternative strategy in all educational levels especially at junior and senior secondary schools.
- 4) Seminars, workshops and conferences should be organized for mathematics teachers on how to adopt strategy in teaching their students for effective and better achievement of the designed objectives.

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(Assessment of Students' Perception on STEM Education ... Usman, G. & Hassan, M. N. 2025)

Assessment of Students' Perception on STEM Education Implementation among Pre-service Mathematics Teachers' in Sokoto State University, Sokoto

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Abstract

The integration of Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) education is receiving attention globally where many countries are adopting it into their system of education. Therefore, the present study investigated the perceptions of Pre-service Mathematics teachers on STEM education. A correlational survey research design was used to collect data from 39 Pre-service mathematics teachers at Sokoto State University in Sokoto. A questionnaire titled pre-service mathematics teachers' perception on STEM with reliability index of 0.73 was used to collect data, about their views on STEM-related activities. Descriptive statistics were used to analyze data using mean and standard deviation. Whereas, partial correlation statistics was used to obtained the correlation among the variables. The results showed that there is moderate level of awareness, readiness, and experience, but a high level of confidence in implementing STEM education. Also, a higher correlation of confidence with another variable was found. The study recommends faculties and college of education should provide more awareness to pre-service teachers and give opportunities to the teachers to gain experience of STEM education in real-world contexts.

Keyword: STEM, Perception, Pre-service Mathematics Teachers, STEM Education

Introduction

In 21st century, Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) education is receiving more and more attention and it becoming a global phenomenon, with many countries incorporating it into their education systems. STEM is a term that had its origins and first coined the use of an acronym in the 1990s at the National Science Foundation (NSF) in the United States of America (USA). Hence, today the term is used

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as a common label for any event, program, policy and practice that involves one or numerous STEM fields (Galadima, 2024; Galadima, et.al 2019a). Accordingly, STEM is best understood as a discipline by removing the boundaries between the disciplines and taught as one discrete entity. The disciplines are combined into a single class focused on the connection between them and the idea for solving the real-world problem (Breiner *et al.*, 2012).

Also, STEM is considered as a unified amalgamation of concepts and content from multiple STEM disciplines in the curriculum through increasing focus on students' persistence in STEM (Kelley, & Knowles, 2016). Consequently, the connection between the STEM disciplines increases preparation and careers in developing the STEM-capable workforce that improves STEM literacy needs. The need for more engineers, technicians, scientists, and mathematicians (such as Software developers, Information security analyst, Architect, Actuarial Scientist, Cost estimators, Statistician, Web Developers, etc.). This necessitate for more innovative and creative workforce needed to compete and spar in a global marketplace (National Research Council. 2011). Taking together, this rationale supports the continually growing demand for the required STEM skills to meet the present and future global economic and social challenges. In view of this teacher institution need to develop and implement curricular for developing STEM skills to pre-service teachers.

Pre-service mathematics teachers are education students at the university levels who are receiving training to become the certified mathematics teachers for schools within a formal teacher education program (National Research Council, 2011). According to the study conducted by Koirala and Bowman (2003), indicated that pre-service teachers are much more likely to implement integrated teaching strategies within and during their teaching method course, particularly within their university methods courses. Due to limited researches in Sokoto State on pre-service mathematics teachers' preparation for STEM education, indicates the need for using PMTs who have yet to venture into the field to be at the forefront of the STEM movement. As the future leaders of the field, PMTs who are the novice to the field should be prepared for STEM education because they are the future leaders in the field who will play a vital role in steering the route of STEM education (Atkinson, & Mayo, 2010). This study provides meaningful learning opportunities for pre-service mathematics teachers to participate in STEM education to develop STEM competencies.

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STEM education competencies are prominent topic of discussion among educators since they involve in the processes of incorporating the four STEM disciplines. These competencies involve the awareness of the level of understanding and familiarity with STEM education concepts, principles, and practices (Abdioglu, et, al. 2021). While, experience as the extent of hands-on experience and engagement with STEM education activities, projects, and programs (Margot, & Kettler, 2019). Also, readiness is the level of preparedness and willingness to integrate STEM education into teaching practices (Sulaeman, et, al. 2022) and then confidence as the level of self-assurance in teaching STEM education subjects and integrating STEM education into teaching practices (Hoon, et, al. 2022; Stohlmann, et, al. 2012).

While, Pre-service teachers learn a variety of innovative and cutting-edge technologies and how to handle new pedagogical aspects, such as 21st century skills. This will enable the pre-service teachers to become familiar with 21st century STEM technologies. The question is whether the courses or trainings attended at universities to gain experience were sufficient to promote STEM practices in their future school career. To help PMTs implement STEM disciplines effectively and not only provide them with a positive understanding of STEM education but also improve their knowledge of STEM careers (Jiang, et, al. 2024). STEM awareness can be expressed as awareness of the relationships between STEM fields and the ability to draw logical conclusions. Subsequently, Abdioglu, et, al., (2021) defines STEM awareness as the promotion of higher-order thinking skills in individuals through STEM education, the ability to use STEM disciplines together, the understanding that a problem can be solved in different ways, and self-confidence and awareness that provide the ability to collaborate and build effective communication. Instead, STEM awareness is considered a prerequisite for interaction, self-efficacy and development (Abdioglu, et, al., 2021). Consequently, studies in the literature on STEM awareness show how important comprehensive STEM awareness of the individual is in addition to STEM education.

On the other hand, it is learned that experience is not acquired by learning; rather, it is evoked through collaboration to improve as the learner reflect and make judgement on their practices (Hoon, et, al., 2022). For this reason, experiences can be used as a guide for future STEM practices (Şenyiğit, & Bakırcı, 2025). In this respect, pre-service teachers found the experience they gained from other activities related to STEM were lesser (Dost, 2024). The year of experience confirm that novice teachers have a less positive view of STEM education than experienced teachers. In contrast, Srikoom, et,

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al., (2017); Margot, and Kettler, (2019), explain that teachers' year of experience appears to be inconsistent with teachers' perceptions of STEM education and that teachers' engagement in STEM education may mediate this inconsistent relationship. Likewise, Theo, et, al., (2024) added that as teachers gain more experience, their readiness to implement STEM subjects also increases, but only if they place a high value on STEM education.

In contrast, increasing number of experiences does not influence teachers' readiness to teach STEM subjects. Also, Margot and Kettler (2019) confirmed that pre-service teachers who valued STEM education not only increases their level of readiness to teach STEM, but also their desire to teaching STEM education. However, pre-service teacher who did not value STEM education did not demonstrate higher level of readiness with more years of experience (Ramli, et, al., 2017). Perhaps valuing this type of pedagogy will lead to an improvement in pre-service teachers' readiness, and this variable should be considered more frequently. With the spread of STEM education, teacher readiness has become an essential component, especially in how they train teachers (Margot & Kettler, 2019) and build their readiness in STEM education (El-Deghaidy, et, al., 2017; Sulaeman, et, al., 2022). Other researchers argue that readiness refers to the extent to which teachers demonstrate willingness and confidence to take responsibility for their own teaching (Hung, 2016). Stohnlmann et al. (2012) found that teachers' passion for STEM education influenced their confidence and comfort in implementing the curriculum. The PMTs confidence is generally defined as a belief in one's own abilities or the degree of confidence a person has in his or her abilities or, in the case of STEM, a person's ability to learn well and perform well in STEM education (Şenyiğit, & Bakırcı, 2025). Confidence has further been defined in this study as the teacher's belief in assessing to establish their perceived capabilities in STEM education. In view of the present study deem it imperative to investigate the per-service mathematics teachers' perception after engagement with STEM activities in their methodology course.

Statement of the Research Problem

STEM education is an important area that help towards actualizing the 21st century skills and continue to receive more concern globally. Despite the importance of STEM skills toward national development, the reality in Nigeria, STEM education are taught as single subject, and that the perception of pre-service mathematics teachers on STEM education is not well understood due to lack of a clear curriculum that combines

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the science, technology, engineering and mathematics (Galadima., 2023; 2024). Still, each of the STEM disciplines is considered as a separate and distinct field of study (Galadima, et.al, 2019b). In this regard, the use of STEM approach would provide opportunities with a more relevant, more meaningful learning experience and less fragmented knowledge (Furner & Kumar, 2007). In relation to solving real-world problems, single disciplines prevent the PMTs from building the needed competencies and connection between and among the four fields of STEM (Kalolo, 2016). Subsequently, real-world problems are not fragmented and isolated in single disciplines as they are taught in the school's curriculum of Sokoto State Nigeria.

Thus, to solve the problems of teaching in a single discipline, people need skills that make sense of learning content cut across the disciplines. literature affirmed that the learners need prepare for the global demands of the 21st-century through STEM education (Thibaut et al., 2018). The 21st-century demand needs for workers to have the knowledge of mathematics skills and science, creativity, expertise in communication and information technology, and the capability to solve complex real-world problems (Jayarajah, et, al., 2014). The STEM practices help to determine whether Sokoto State Nigeria will be able to solve tremendous challenges in teaching individual STEM disciplines without connection between and among the disciplines per se. In bridging this gap, this study investigated the perception of pre-service mathematics teachers on STEM education at Sokoto State University, Sokoto, with a focus on awareness, experience, readiness, and confidence.

Objectives of the study

The following objectives were developed to guide the study

1. Assess the mean response of level of awareness of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University.
2. Assess the mean response of level of experience of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University.
3. Assess the mean response of level of readiness of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University.
4. Assess the mean response of level of confidence of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University.
5. Find out the Preservice Mathematics Teachers' level of confidence and its relationship with awareness, experience, and readiness on STEM education.

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Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

1. What is the mean response of level of awareness of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?
2. What is the mean response of level of experience of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?
3. What is the mean response of level of readiness of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?
4. What is the mean response of level of confidence of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?
5. Are there any relationships between the Preservice Mathematics Teachers' perceptions of confidence and its relationship with awareness, experience, and readiness to teach STEM education?

Hypotheses

1. There is no any relationships between the Preservice Mathematics Teachers' level of confidence and its relationship with awareness, experience, and readiness on STEM education.

Methodology

A correlational survey research design design was adopted in this study. The design will help to explain the relationship between both independent and dependent variables. Participants in the present research were selected from pre-service mathematics teachers at Sokoto State University, Sokoto, Nigeria. A total of 39 students were involved, using intact class. Thus to ensure the ethical standard all the participants (Mathematics pre-service teachers) were told that their names would be kept confidential and anonymous. As such all the participating pre-service teachers agreed to participate. However, to assess the pre-service mathematics teachers' perception a 20 items questionnaire based on STEM competencies was developed. After expert validation, modifications were made, pilot tested and reliability index was obtained with a Cronbach's 0.73, the acceptable Cronbach's alpha value is ranging

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between 0.7 to 0.95. The results obtained were analysed using descriptive statistics to describe the perception of the respondents about the implementation of STEM education and partial correlation were used to analyze the relationship among the variables.

Presentation of Results

In this section the result of five research questions and one hypothesis were answer as explained in methodology using tables as follows.

Research Question 1

What is the mean response of level of awareness of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?

Table 1: PMTs Perception on the Awareness to Teach STEM Education

S/N	Questionnaire Items	N	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)
1	I am familiar with the concept of STEM education	39	3.87	0.83
2	I have a clear understanding of how to integrate mathematics with other STEM subjects.	39	3.23	0.91
3	I am aware of the various teaching strategies used in STEM education.	39	4.03	0.67
4	I am familiar with the use of technology in STEM education.	39	3.46	0.85
5	I have knowledge of the resources and materials available in teaching STEM education.	39	3.92	0.76

Table1 shows the results of 39 PMTs level of awareness on STEM education. The mean and the SD of 3.87(0.83); 4.03(0.67) and 3.92(0.76) indicated that the respondents tend to agree that they are familiar with the concept, aware with the various teaching strategies and have the knowledge of resources and materials in teaching STEM education. Whereas, the mean and the SD of 3.23(0.91) and 3.46(0.85) indicated that the respondents tend to be neutral about having a clear understanding of how to integrate mathematics with other STEM disciplines and their familiarity with the use of technology in STEM education.

Research Question 2

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What is the mean response of level of experience of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?

Table 2: PMTs Perception on the Experience to Teach STEM Education

S/N	Questionnaire Items	N	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)
1	I have experience in teaching mathematics in a way that integrates with other STEM subjects.	39	2.85	0.92
2	I have used technology to support student learning in mathematics and other STEM subjects.	39	3.38	0.81
3	I have experience in designing and implementing STEM-based projects in the classroom.	39	2.59	0.95
4	I have experience in assessing student learning in STEM subjects using a variety of methods.	39	3.08	0.88
5	I have experience in collaborating with other teachers to develop and implement STEM education programs.	39	2.82	0.93

Table 2 shows the results of 39 PMTs level of experience on STEM education. The mean and the SD of 2.85(0.92); 2.59(0.95), and 2.82(0.93) indicated that the respondents tend to disagree that they have experience in teaching mathematics in a way that integrates with other STEM subjects; designing and implementing STEM-based projects in the classroom; and that they have experience in collaborating with other teachers in developing STEM education programs. Whereas, the mean and the SD of 3.38(0.81) and 3.08(0.88) indicated that the respondents tend to be neutral about using technology to support student learning in mathematics and other STEM subjects and about having experience in assessing student learning in STEM subjects using a variety of methods.

Research Question 3

What is the mean response of level of experience of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?

Table 3: PMTs Perception for their Readiness to Teach STEM Education

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S/N	Questionnaire Items	N	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)
1	I am ready and prepared to teach mathematics in a way that integrates with other STEM subjects.	39	3.59	0.81
2	I have the necessary skills to use technology to support student learning in STEM subjects.	39	3.85	0.74
3	I am ready in my ability to design and implement STEM-based projects in the classroom.	39	3.31	0.89
4	I am prepared to assess student learning in STEM subjects using a variety of methods.	39	3.54	0.83
5	I am ready in my ability to teach STEM subjects in a way that promotes critical thinking and problem-solving.	39	3.67	0.79

Table 3 shows the results of 39 PMTs level of readiness on STEM education. The mean and the SD of 3.59(0.81); 3.85(0.74); 3.54(0.83) and 3.67(0.79) indicated that the respondents tend to agree that they are ready and well prepared to teach mathematics in a way that integrates with other STEM subjects; having necessary skills to use technology to support student learning in STEM subjects; prepared to assess student learning in STEM subjects using a variety of methods; and their confidence in their ability to teach STEM subjects in a way that promotes critical thinking and problem-solving. Whereas, the only mean with SD of 3.31(0.89) indicated the respondents tend to be neutral about their readiness in designing and implementing STEM-based projects in the classroom.

Research Question 4

What is the mean response of level of confidence of STEM education implementation among pre-service Mathematics teachers in Sokoto State University?

Table 4: PMTs Perception of their Confidence to Teach STEM Education

S/N	Questionnaire Items	N	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)
1	I am confident in my ability to teach mathematics in a way that integrates with other STEM subjects.	39	3.92	0.71
2	I am confident in my ability to use technology to support student learning in STEM subjects.	39	4.03	0.65
3	I am confident in my ability to design and implement STEM-based projects in the classroom.	39	3.62	0.81

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4	I am confident in my ability to assess student learning in STEM subjects using a variety of methods.	39	3.85	0.73
5	I am confident in my ability to teach STEM subjects in a way that promotes critical thinking and problem-solving.	39	3.97	0.69

Table 4 shows the results of 39 PMTs level of confidence on STEM education. The mean of all the items indicated that the respondents agreed that they are confident in their ability to teach STEM education. Whereas, the SD of all the items indicated relatively low level of variability in the participants responses.

Research Question 5

Are there any relationships between the Preservice Mathematics Teachers' perceptions of confidence and its relationship with awareness, experience, and readiness to teach STEM education?

Table 5 : Mean and Standard Deviation of the Perceived Levels of STEM Education

S/N	Perceived Levels	N	Mean (M)	Std. Deviation (SD)
1	Awareness	39	3.70	0.81
2	Experience	39	2.94	0.89
3	Readiness	39	3.59	0.81
4	Confidence	39	3.88	0.72

Table 5 presented the results of 39 PMTs regarding their level of awareness, experience, readiness, and confidence on STEM education. The PMTs awareness was rated with the mean of 3.70 and (SD=0.81). Nonetheless, they rated comparatively higher than their experience and readiness with mean of 2.94 and 3.59 (SD=0.89 and 0.81). With these, the PMTs were more confident with the mean of 3.88 (SD=0.72) in their ability to teach STEM subjects.

Hypothesis 1

There is no any relationship between the Preservice Mathematics Teachers' level of confidence and its relationship with awareness, experience, and readiness on STEM education.

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Table 6. Partial Correlation of Confidence with Awareness, Experience, and Readiness

Confidence		
Awareness	Partial Correlation	0.53**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.01
	N	39
Experience	Partial Correlation	0.41**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.01
	N	39
Readiness	Partial Correlation	0.68**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.01
	N	39

Table 6 highlights the results of partial correlation of confidence and its relationship with awareness, experience, and readiness. The results indicated that the confidence has significant positive correlation with awareness ($r = 0.53$, $p < 0.01$), experience ($r = 0.41$, $p < 0.01$), and readiness ($r = 0.68$, $p < 0.01$). The results show all the factors are essential in ensuring achievement of knowledge in STEM education. Interestingly, the results indicated the highest correlation between readiness and confidence balanced in STEM education.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that pre-service mathematics teachers recognize the value of STEM education and its relevance to the modern world. Their awareness and intention towards STEM education promote higher-order thinking skills and influenced collaboration to build effective communication (Abdioglu, Çevik, & Kosar, 2021). Thus, Jiang, Zhang, and Zhang, (2024) stated that awareness of STEM disciplines effectively and not only provide them with a positive understanding of STEM education but also improve their knowledge of STEM careers. On the connection between awareness and confidence it can be seen in table 6 the PMTs who are more aware of the importance of teaching STEM education tend to be more confident in their ability to teach it, independent of their experience and readiness.

However, the results also show that pre-service mathematics teachers lack experience in teaching STEM education. This is not surprising, given that many teacher education programs may not provide adequate opportunities for pre-service teachers to gain practical experience in teaching STEM subjects (Baptista, Conceição, & Filipe, 2025).

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The experience is exceptionally essential since the result also shows that there is a relationship between experience and confidence (Şenyiğit, & Bakırcı, 2025). Nevertheless, the pre-service teachers found the experience they gained from other activities related to STEM were lesser (Dost, 2024). PMTs year of experience confirm that novice teachers have a less positive view of STEM education than experienced teachers (Galadima, Ismail, & Ismail, 2019). Even though PMTs were less experienced, they responded positively to the level of confidence. (Şenyiğit, & Bakırcı, 2025).

In terms of readiness, the findings revealed that pre-service mathematics teachers are moderately ready to teach STEM education. This indicates that while they may have some knowledge and skills, they may still require additional support and training to feel fully prepared (Ramli, Ibrahim, Surif, Bunyamin, Jamaluddin, & Abdullah, 2017). The analysis focused on understanding teachers' opinions on their readiness to teach STEM education. In this study, results showed that moderate respondents were ready to teach STEM and showing interested in STEM. With the spread of STEM education, teacher readiness has become an essential component, especially in how they train teachers (Margot & Kettler, 2019; Sulaeman, Efwinda, & Putra, 2022) and build their readiness in STEM education (El-Deghaidy, Mansour, Alzaghibi, & Alhammad, 2017).

Finally, the results show that pre-service mathematics teachers are moderately confident in their ability to teach STEM education. This suggests that while they may have some doubts and uncertainties, they are generally positive about their ability to teach STEM subjects (Hoon, Aris, Ibrahim, & Isa, 2022). The confidence level provides a direction on the PMTs plans and ability to conduct lessons with STEM elements in schools or other institutions. According to the findings of this study, students require more experience to gain confidence in guiding the next generation through school activities. All parties benefit from the activities, which support and respond to the growing STEM activities (Solanki et al., 2019).

Conclusion

From the finding of this study, we can conclude that teachers' readiness in implementing STEM education is still at a low level. The present study indicated that pre-service mathematics teachers' have high level of confidence in in their ability to STEM education was highly associated to experience, even though the level of experience was rated lower when compared to readiness and effort. On the other hand, there are positive correlation between the confidence and awareness, experience, and readiness to teach STEM education. Also, the study showed that awareness,

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experience, and readiness are interconnected and influenced one another, which in turn affect confidence. Therefore, it is essential to address these variables simultaneously to enhance pre-service teachers' confidence on STEM education.

Recommendations

The following recommendations could be useful based on the findings of this study:

1. Regular workshops and seminars should be organized to enhance pre-service mathematics teachers' awareness of STEM education, such as its importance, and its implementation strategies.
2. Pre-service mathematics teachers should be provided with opportunities to participate in hands-on STEM education activities, such as internships, volunteer teaching, to gain practical experience.
3. A readiness program should be developed and implemented to prepare pre-service mathematics teachers for STEM education implementation, focusing on developing their skills, knowledge, and attitudes.
4. Mentorship programs should be established to pair pre-service mathematics teachers with experienced teachers or mentors who can provide guidance, support, and feedback to boost their confidence in implementing STEM education.
5. Intervention should be developed to enhance pre-service mathematics teachers' level of confidence and awareness, experience, and readiness on STEM education. This could include the training programs and mentorship to address areas of concern in implementing STEM education.

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Assessment of Internet Facilities usage on Reading Culture among Wesley High School Students in Otukpo, Benue State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study assessed internet facilities usage on reading culture among Wesley high school students in Otukpo, Benue state, Nigeria. Three objectives guided the study. The research design adopted was a survey research design. The population of the study comprised of 278 SS2 and SS3 students of the school studied in 2023/2024 academic session. The sampling technique used was a complete census. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire titled: "Impact of Internet Facilities on Student's Reading Culture Questionnaire (IIFSRCQ)". The questionnaire was subjected to face and content validity. The reliability score of the questionnaire was 87.53 Cronbach Alpha Value. Data collected were analyzed using frequency counts, simple percentages and mean scores. The findings showed that majority of the students make use of the internet to study, prepare for examinations, write assignments, and chatting with friends, among others. Making the students active in class, distracting their reading, and exposing them to unimportant articles and write-ups were among the perceived impact. The study recommended that Management of secondary schools should organize seminars aimed at teaching the students the right use of the internet to improve their reading culture, among other things.

Keywords: Reading, Reading Culture, Internet, impact, Student.

Introduction

Reading is the springboard of any literacy program. It is one of the oldest habits of human civilization and has remained the passion of the greatest personalities of all times. According to Nnadozie and Egwim (2010), reading is a complex skill requiring the coordination of several inter related sources of information. It is the art of interpreting printed and written words, and the most effective process of conscious learning, which influences the extent and accuracy of information as well as the attitudes, morals, beliefs, judgement and action of individuals (Edeole & Adejoke, 2016).

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However, due to the attitude of individuals who rarely pick a book or magazine to read, there is a serious decline in reading culture. The same applies to the schoolchild for whom reading has come to mean a thing of spare time. Considering the place of creative thinking in reading, it becomes very important for one to develop the rudiments of reading and the culture of reading always. The importance of reading culture cannot be overemphasized because it is crucial for both personal and academic success. Furthermore, it is an aid to language development, socialization and civilization.

The development of good reading culture is important because society has realized the importance of information and effective communication for the survival and exploitation of their environment. Moreover, the development of reading and reading culture are basic skills, which society must confer on its students as part of their childhood education. Unfortunately, there are problems inherent in the development of proper reading culture among students because of some technological innovations. One of the technological innovations is the Internet. The Internet can be broadly defined as a worldwide network of computers communicating through an approved protocol. The Internet according to Kumar and Kaur in Jibrin, Musa and Shittu (2017), has an unlimited wealth of information resources that are readily available and easily accessible for people to use worldwide and simultaneously. Internet is a veritable tool in learning, teaching and research if effectively used. However, it has been observed that owing to this technological innovation, reading culture is being threatened, especially, among teens and secondary school students (Yusuf, 2015).

In Nigerian society today, while technology is slowly taking a steady control over individual lives, the reading culture among secondary school students is fast vanishing. Today, students rather than read to acquire new knowledge prefer to spend hours unending, surfing the net, playing with funky handsets, chatting and passing non-stop short message services (SMSs), thereby making reading a book or any other information resource in a quiet or peaceful corner of a library or home an archaic idea. The declining interest in reading among our children (especially those in secondary schools) compared to increase in hours spent on the Internet has become a cause for alarm and a challenge to all and something needs to be done to change the scenario. However, assuming or concluding that Internet use is the cause of the declining reading culture can be better regarded as an assumption until empirically proven. It is against this backdrop that the current study is assessing internet facilities usage

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on reading culture among Wesley high school students in Otukpo, Benue state, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The rapid advancement of internet technology has transformed how students access and engage with information. While the internet provides vast resources that can enhance learning, its usage also raises concerns about its impact on students' reading culture. In Wesley High School, Otukpo, Benue State, there is growing concern that students may be shifting from traditional reading habits, such as reading textbooks, novels, and academic materials, to spending more time on social media, online gaming, and entertainment websites. Despite the availability of internet facilities in the school and among students, little is known about how these resources are being utilized and whether they contribute positively or negatively to students' reading culture. Some researchers argue that the internet can enhance reading habits through access to e-books, online journals, and educational blogs, while others believe that it distracts students and reduces their engagement with academic texts (Musa & Shittu, 2017; Yusuf, 2017). This study seeks to assess the usage of internet facilities and its impact on the reading culture of students in Wesley High School Otukpo, Benue State, Nigeria. Specifically, it aims to determine whether internet access promotes or hinders reading habits, identify the types of online content students engage with, and explore possible ways to enhance the positive effects of internet usage on reading culture. Addressing this issue is essential to ensuring that the internet serves as a tool for academic growth rather than a distraction from meaningful reading practices.

Research objectives

The study is guided by the following objectives, which involve, to:

1. Find out if students of Wesley high school Otukpo make use of the Internet facilities
2. Determine the students' reasons for their use of the Internet facilities
3. Investigate the perceived impact of the Internet facilities by the students on their reading culture

Research questions

1. Do students of Wesley high school Otukpo make use of the Internet facilities?
2. What are the students' reasons for their use of the Internet facilities?

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3. What is the perceived impact of the Internet facilities by the students on their reading culture?

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the students' reasons for use of internet facilities and students on their reading culture

Literature review

Since the advent of ICT, the subject of the students' reading culture has attracted a major concern. According to Yusuf (2015), this major concern is because of the need to keep the schoolchild active and able to cope with the demands of the present day. In the same vein, Saka, Bitagi, and Garba (2012) pointed out that inculcating a reading culture should be introduced at an early age among children. This is because reading and reading culture develop over a prolonged period and an early promotion will be able to mold them into lifelong readers. The challenge is therefore to ingrain the culture of reading in children so that it is as important as sports and other hobbies. Perhaps then, the impact of negative media will be directly reduced. Furthermore, Yani (2003) observed that reading culture of Nigerians is a matter of concern in our educational and national development, stating further that in a developing country like Nigeria, the concept of reading culture should not be relegated to the background.

Fundamentally, the major way to improve the reading culture of students is through a well-equipped school library. Topo, as cited in Strong (2014) affirmed that the need today is the thoughtful integration of book reading with high technology, as it will reverse the decline in book reading among children and adults. In addition, Yusuf (2007) asserted that equipping school libraries is the first practical step in these efforts. This is because books and other information resources are the most suitable medium through which knowledge is transmitted from generation to generation.

Nonetheless, Kristy (as cited in Kolawole, 2005) reported that the prevalence of poor reading skills varies, and believed the consequential effect to include poor grades for students and difficulty trying to find or advance to a good job for adults. Saka, Bitagi and Garba (2012) in their submission were of the view that the majority of students read to pass examinations and to do assignments. The implication being that absence of examinations and assignments creates a distance between students and their books, while shifting their attention and energy to the net for frivolities. As to what these students prefer, the study of Chen, Hsiao, Chern and Chen (as cited in Almasi,

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Machumu & Zhu, 2017) reported a growing increase in the use of the Internet, which is gradually eroding reading culture among secondary school students.

The authors, however, observed that the students use the Internet also for activities related to schoolwork as well as more General activities, believing that Internet-based activities in schools may have several impacts on students` life at schools and thereafter. Besides, various studies have reported that the use of the internet can have benefits on the educational achievement of students.

Considering the influence of the use of the Internet on student learning performance or other outcomes, the studies of Davis (2001), Widyanto and Griffiths (2006), Odaci and Kalkkan (2010), and Odaci (2011) reported that it has either a negative influence or no significant influence. Furthermore, Young (as cited in Amasi et al., 2017) suggested that excessive internet usage among students have negative effects on students` academic success.

The studies of Olatokun (2008) and Nwagwu, Adekannbi and Bello (2008) reported that students chiefly utilize the Internet for academic purposes, such as preparation for assignments and examinations, rather than for leisure purposes. Though some students use the Internet much more than their school libraries, they also find the Internet as a source of general knowledge since it assists them in their reading habits as well as improving their academic performances.

Tarimo and Kavishe (2017), believed that by providing Internet access and enhancing its usage in schools, a chance to improve students` learning through access to the huge amount of information that is accessible on the internet is guaranteed.

Chen and Fu (2009) stated that the Internet has brought unparalleled opportunities to students on one hand and a major concern for parents on the other hand. This is because while online searching for information helps to boost examination scores and performances in assignments given to students, using the internet mainly for socializing and gaming results in poor reading habit and poor performance in examinations, general academic achievements as well as poor personal development. Since some internet use may seriously distract students, affect their reading habit and generally distort their academic achievements, students should employ effective use of the Internet.

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In the same vein, the studies of Adedotun (as cited in Yebowaah, 2018); Akande and Bamise (2017) reported that access to information brought about by the use of the Internet can influence the academic performance of the secondary school students. Also, Sahin, Balta and Ercan (2010) and Yebowaah (2018) believed that the use of credible Internet resources is of greater importance for academic activity, especially in high-class courses which require an academic review of the literature. This is not different from the belief of Kim (as cited in Yebowaah, 2018) who asserted that Internet use for educational purpose is the heart of adolescent academic achievement, as it helps students to broaden their academic knowledge, research and assignments by accessing information worldwide as well as enhances easy communication to the academic community.

On what needs to be done to avoid the negative influence of the Internet on the students, Chen *et al* as cited in Almasi, Machumu & Zhu (2017) noted that Internet usage is of benefit to students but believed that its negative use involves pornography addiction and excessive chat among secondary students, which have relatively negative effects on their academic success and life after school. In the same vein, Fuchs and Woessmann (2004); Kuhlemeier and Hemker (2007) believed that the Internet is used in daily life in educational settings; and as a result, its usage among secondary school students should be channeled appropriately to yield academic success.

Downes (2002) noted that if secondary-education teachers are to tailor their instruction to the needs of all students, they need to develop an understanding of the extent to which incoming students have access to and make use of the Internet at home. Campagna (as cited in Almasi *et al.*, 2017) emphasized that teachers should encourage students to come up with techniques for reading independently, which is one of the outcomes of reading habit.

In the same vein, Ngoumandjoka (as cited in Yebowaah, 2018) found that the Internet is not mostly used for academic purpose rather for recreational activities. The authors further buttressed that though students are more into the use of the Internet, in reality, they are using it mainly for non-academic purposes like emailing, gaming and social networking, which has contributed greatly to the decline in their reading culture. This brings to the fore the controversy among empirical studies on the influence of internet use on the academic performance and reading culture of secondary school students.

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Based on the literature review, it is clear that the Internet has serious effects on students and their reading culture. Students are so vulnerable to becoming addicted to the Internet to the extent that they do their homework not with their efforts but with complete dependence on Internet resources. This is to say that the influence of the Internet is in two faces, either negative or positive.

However, it would be inappropriate to conclude on the face the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State belong to. A critical look at available literature has revealed a gap in this respect, which forms the fulcrum of this research.

Methodology

The study was purely a descriptive survey because of the given large number of different sub-sets of the population involved. Thus, a descriptive survey design was adopted for the study owing to its usefulness in the field of computer Science. The population of the study was 278, which comprised senior secondary 2 and 3 classes (SS2 & SS3) in 2023/2024 academic session. Furthermore, the 278 students were sampled using the complete census sampling technique. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire titled: “Impact of Internet Facilities on Student’s Reading Culture Questionnaire (IIFSRCQ)”. The questionnaire was validated using face and content validation. The research instrument was validated by an expert in measurement and evaluation from the department of mathematics and Statistics in Federal University of Health Sciences Otukpo Benue State. Also, the instrument was distributed in Jesus College Otukpo Benue State for Pilot test among SS2 and SS3 students. A total of 50 copies of questionnaire was distributed to the students and retrieved. The data was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha. The overall Cronbach alpha value for the instrument was 87.53 which was found strong and reliable. Therefore, the instrument was used for the study. The items in the questionnaire consist of close-ended questions using four (4)-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. The data collected were analyzed using frequency counts, simple percentages and mean scores. A mid-point of 2.5 was taken as the acceptance criterion for the positive response. This implied that questionnaire items with a mean score of 2.5 and above denote “agreed” while questionnaire items with a mean score below 2.5 denote “disagreed”. Presentation of the result was done using the frequency tables.

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Presentation of Results

This section deals with the analysis of the outcomes of the data collected. A total of 278 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents but 275 copies were completed, returned and found useful for analysis. The presentation follows the order of the research objectives.

Research Objective 1: To find out if students of Wesley High school Otukpo make use of the Internet.

Table 1: Responses of the Students on the Use of Internet Facilities (N = 275)

S/N	Item statement	Yes	%	No	%
1	Do you make use of the Internet?	267	97.1	8	2.9

Source: Researcher's Field Survey

Table 1 shows the responses of the students on the use of the Internet. The result shows that the majority of the respondents 267(97.1%) indicated the use of the Internet, while few of the respondents that constitute 8(2.9%) indicated the non-use of the Internet. The result implies that students in Otukpo Local Government Area make use of the Internet.

This finding corroborates with the earlier studies carried out by Olatokun (2008), Tarimo and Kavishe (2017), which revealed the high use of the Internet among youths and secondary school students.

Research objective 2: To determine the students' reasons for their use of the Internet Facilities.

Table 2: Students' Reasons for Use of the Internet (N = 275)

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	I use the Internet for study purposes	75	120	18	62	2.76	Agreed
2	To prepare for examinations	114	126	12	20	3.21	Agreed
3	To do my assignments	92	51	90	42	2.70	Agreed
4	To chat with friends	114	96	35	30	3.07	Agreed
5	To watch movies	126	36	68	45	2.88	Agreed
6	To get information	91	114	40	30	2.97	Agreed

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7	To meet new friends	101	114	40	20	3.08	Agreed
8	To improve my reading habit	25	20	86	114	1.73	Disagreed
9	To improve my grades in school	35	50	96	94	2.09	Disagreed
10	To be like others	83	61	48	83	2.52	Agreed

Source: *Researcher's Field Survey*

Key: SA – Strongly Agreed; A – Agreed; D – Disagreed; SD – Strongly Disagreed

Table 2 showed the responses to the reasons for the use of the Internet by the students of Wesley High School Otukpo Benue State. From the analysis, majority of the students agreed with the following reasons for their use of the Internet: for studying purposes (2.76), to prepare for examinations (3.21), to do my assignments (2.70), to chat with friends (3.07), to see movies (2.88), to get information (2.97), to meet new friends (3.08) and to be like others (2.52). However, few respondents that constitute 1.73 and 2.09, respectively, indicated the use of the Internet to improve their reading habit and improve their grades in school.

Research Objective 3: To investigate perceived impact of the Internet facilities on the reading culture of the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State.

S/N	Item Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	It enhances my reading ability	20	15	173	67	1.96	Disagreed
2	It makes me active in class	77	138	40	20	2.99	Agreed
3	It increases my reading attention span	20	30	126	99	1.89	Disagreed
4	It helps me to have a better understanding of what I am reading	80	165	10	20	3.11	Agreed
5	Chatting with friends keeps me awake to read in the night	102	138	25	10	3.21	Agreed

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6	Internet articles motivate me to read	63	132	30	50	2.76	Agreed
7	The Internet distracts my reading	113	117	30	15	3.19	Agreed
8	The Internet exposes me to unimportant articles and write-ups	200	30	15	30	3.25	Agreed

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey

Key: SA – Strongly Agreed; A – Agreed; D – Disagreed; SD – Strongly Disagreed

Table 3 presents responses gotten on the perceived impact of the Internet on the reading culture of the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State. The result shows that out of the eight perceived impact investigated, six were agreed by the majority of the respondents that constitute 2.99, 3.11, 3.21, 2.76, 3.19, and 3.45, mean scores respectively. These impacts agreed by the respondents on item statements 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8, include it makes me active in class, it helps me to have a better understanding of what I am reading, chatting with friends keep me awake to read in the night, Internet articles motivate me to read, the Internet distracts my reading and the Internet exposes me to unimportant articles and write-ups. Furthermore, majority of the respondents disagreed with item statements 1 and 3, which present that, it enhances my reading ability (1.96), and it increases my reading attention span.

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the students’ reasons for use of internet facilities and students on their reading culture

Statement	N	df	Mean	S.D	R	P-Value	Decision
Students’ Reasons for Use of the Internet	275		3.0000	.60302			
students reading culture	275	274	3.1667	.71774	.210	0.512	Not Significant

***p-value is significant at <=0.05, df: degree of freedom, S.d: standard deviation, R; relationship,*

The result showed the relationship between reasons for the use of internet facilities and reading culture of students. The result showed the mean and standard deviation

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of the variables. Students' reasons for use of internet facilities: 3.00(0.603) and students reading culture is 3.167(0.718). The degree of freedom is 274. The showed that the relationship between students' reasons for use of internet facilities is linear and weak $R = 0.210 \times 100 = 21\%$. In the same vein, the result further showed that there is no significant relationship between students' reasons for use of internet facilities and their reading culture as the p-value = 0.512. Since the P-value > 0.05, the hypothesis which state that there is no significant relationship between students' reasons for use of internet facilities and students reading culture is accepted.

Discussion of findings

The result showed that students in Otukpo Local Government Area make use of internet facilities. The finding corroborates with the earlier studies carried out by Olatokun (2008), Tarimo and Kavishe (2017), which revealed the high use of the Internet among youths and secondary school students. This is because majority of the students has a mobile device with internet facilities, also majority of the schools has internet enable e-library in the school premises. Also, the results showed that students of Wesley High school Otukpo Benue State make use of the Internet for numerous purposes aside to improve their reading habit and grades in school. Consequently, preparation for examinations had the highest mean score of 3.21. The finding of this study in this regard partially corroborates with the work of Luambano and Nawe (2004), which found the use of the Internet by students particularly for academic purposes as hugely influenced by their teachers who give them assignments requiring the use of the Internet. Thus, the studies revealed that students will only use the Internet if work given to them by their teachers requires them to use Internet facilities. In the same vein, the finding has shown different perceived impact of the Internet on the reading culture of the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State. Some of the impacts are positive, such as making them active in class, understand what they are reading, keep them awake to read in the night, and motivates them to read.

However, the negative impacts include the use of the internet distracting their reading, expose them to unimportant articles and write-ups, fails to enhance their reading ability, and failure to increase their reading attention. With these findings, one can deduce that the negative impacts of the Internet outweigh its positive impacts in the case of students of Wesley High Otukpo, Benue State. This study corroborates the earlier works of Davis (2001), Widyanto and Griffiths (2006), Odaci and Kalkkan (2010), and Odaci (2011), which reported that the use of the Internet by the students

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has either a negative impact or no significant impact on student learning performance or other outcomes.

The authors believed that if these young users are educated, they will use the Internet more for educational information resources rather than leisure or entertainment purposes, which will invariably improve their studying and reading culture. The findings of the study also corroborate with the study of Luambano and Nawe (2004), which investigated the use of the Internet by students of University of Dares Salaam and revealed that many of the students were not using the Internet for issues on education but for communication purposes such e-mailing and Face booking.

The study further showed that some students were using Internet services for pornographic viewing, which is an obvious misuse of Internet facility in an academic background, which negatively affects their reading culture and overall academic performance. The negative influence of the Internet as revealed by the above studies may be attributed to the findings of Manda (2005) that majority of students are not aware that Internet is a veritable tool for searching online academic information but rather jump into the Internet for other frivolous purposes.

Finally, the result showed that there is no significant relationship between students' reasons for use of internet facilities and their reading culture. The implication of this finding is due to the fact students reasons for use internet facilities is not necessarily because of academic purposes but may be for pleasure and socialization such as the use of social media platforms. The result is supported by Luambano and Nawe (2004), which found the use of the Internet facilities by students is not necessarily for academic purposes but for socialization and pleasure while just few uses internet facilities for academic purposes through their teacher's instructions.

Conclusion

A critical look at the Internet could make one believe that it is a blessing to our generation. However, many students are becoming addicted to the Internet as they spend more time playing games or just surfing the net without any particular reasons. Consequently, the time they spend on studying is automatically reduced, which in turn causes lower academic achievement, which could all be attributed to poor reading culture.

Findings of the study have shown that the students make use of the Internet for different reasons. These reasons include for studying purposes, to prepare for

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examinations, to do their assignments, to chat with friends, to watch movies, to get information, to meet new friends, and to be like others. However, the influence of the use of the Internet is various, which include making them active in class, helping them to have a better understanding of what they are reading, chatting with friends keeping them awake to read in the night, Internet articles motivating them to read, the Internet distracting their reading, as well as exposing them to unimportant articles and write-ups.

Based on the findings, the study concludes that the use of the Internet amidst some positive impacts negatively influences the reading culture of the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made to ensure that the use of the Internet positively influences students` reading culture:

1. Management of secondary schools should organize seminars aimed at teaching the students the right use of the Internet to improve their reading culture.
2. Teachers in secondary schools should give assignments to students that will stimulate effective use of the Internet for academic purposes and improvement of reading culture.
3. School authorities and parents should closely monitor the Internet sites their students and wards visit to ensure that the utilization of the educational sites is encouraged.
4. There should be a law stipulating the age limit of the utilization of some Internet sites that are detrimental to the reading culture of the secondary school populace.
5. Secondary school students should be provided with adequate guidance on how to promote their reading culture through the appropriate use of the Internet.
6. Establishing, equipping and proper maintenance of school libraries as a means of improving the reading culture of the secondary school students should be highly considered and made a priority for all secondary schools

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Qualitative Study on Leveraging Artificial Intelligence Technology in Islam: A Historical and Philosophical Perspective

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Abstract

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) Technology into Islamic education finds philosophical and theological support through metaphors drawn from Islamic teachings, particularly in the stories of trained animals and birds in the Qur'an. The narratives of the Trained Dog, Al-Hudhud (the Hoopoe bird), and the Ant in the story of Prophet Sulaiman (Solomon) illustrate how non-human creatures serve human beings through their unique skills and intelligence. These creatures, operating under divine guidance, perform functions beyond human capability, much like AI today. The Trained Dog, for instance, reflects the collaboration between human effort and external agents, symbolizing ethical frameworks guiding the use of technology. Al-Hudhud's role in delivering critical information to Prophet Sulaiman emphasizes the value of AI as a tool for gathering and analyzing vast amounts of data for the greater good. Lastly, the Ant's communication with Prophet Sulaiman represents the importance of precision and foresight, akin to the predictive capacities of AI systems. This paper explores the philosophical grounding for AI in Islamic education through these narratives, arguing that the ethical use of AI can enhance learning and decision-making within an Islamic framework. By reflecting on the roles of animals in Qur'anic stories, it offers a theological justification for leveraging AI as a tool for education, supporting both the pursuit of knowledge and adherence to Islamic ethical standards.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence (AI), Islamic Education, Philosophical Justification, Ethical Technology.

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a transformative force in education across the globe, and its integration into various fields has raised philosophical and ethical concerns, especially in the realm of religious education. Islamic education, rooted in both the Qur'an and the Hadith, provides a holistic approach to knowledge acquisition. This article seeks to explore the use of AI in Islamic education through the lens of

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philosophical and theological underpinnings, referencing the stories of the trained dog, *Al-Hudhud* (the Hoopoe bird), and the ant in the narrative of Prophet Sulaiman (Solomon). By examining these narratives, this article will argue that AI, when aligned with Islamic principles, can serve as a beneficial tool for advancing education and knowledge in Islamic contexts.

The Trained Dog: Symbolism in Guidance and Utility

In Surah Al-Ma'idah, verse 4, the Qur'an addresses the permissibility of trained animals, specifically hunting dogs, by stating:

“They ask you, [O Muhammad], what has been made lawful for them. Say, ‘Lawful for you are [all] good foods and [game caught by] what you have trained of hunting animals which you train as Allah has taught you. So eat of what they catch for you, and mention the name of Allah upon it, and fear Allah. Indeed, Allah is swift in account’” (Qur'an 5:4).

The use of trained dogs in hunting serves as a metaphor for guided tools that assist humans in their endeavors. The trained dog, much like AI, does not act on its own volition but is rather directed and programmed by human beings to achieve a specific task. In the same manner, AI systems in Islamic education can be viewed as tools that, when properly "trained" and ethically designed, can assist educators in delivering knowledge effectively.

Moreover, just as a trained dog operates under the supervision of its master, AI in Islamic education must be controlled and guided by human intellect and moral values. This establishes the principle that AI is not an independent entity with moral agency, but a tool to be harnessed for positive outcomes, such as enhanced learning experiences, accessibility, and engagement with religious texts.

***Al-Hudhud* (The Hoopoe Bird): A Messenger of Knowledge and Wisdom**

The story of *Al-Hudhud* in Surah An-Naml (The Ants) offers profound insights into the dissemination of knowledge. Prophet Sulaiman (Solomon) is said to have communicated with a hoopoe bird, who brought him valuable information about the Queen of Sheba and her kingdom (Qur'an, 27:22-26). This narrative highlights how Allah enables even animals or creatures to serve as channels of wisdom and information.

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“But the Hoopoe stayed not long and said, ‘I have encompassed that which you have not encompassed, and I have come to you from Sheba with certain news’” (Qur’an 27:22).

Al-Hudhud’s role can be analogized to that of AI in the modern context. The bird, like AI, gathered and processed information beyond the immediate reach of Prophet Sulaiman, thus expanding his access to knowledge. AI, similarly, has the potential to enhance human capability by providing educators and students with tools to analyze vast amounts of data, access global knowledge, and create personalized learning pathways.

Furthermore, the ethical dimension in the story of Al-Hudhud demonstrates the importance of verifying and cross-checking information. Prophet Sulaiman did not immediately act on the bird’s report but rather questioned its findings to ensure their accuracy (Qur’an 27:27). This principle applies equally to AI, which should not be blindly relied upon, but critically assessed and supervised, ensuring that its outputs align with the values of Islamic education.

The Ant and Prophet Sulaiman: Cooperation and Communication in Learning

Another compelling narrative from the life of Prophet Sulaiman is the story of the ant, which reveals deeper lessons about cooperation, communication, and the broader ecosystem of knowledge. When Sulaiman and his army approached a valley, an ant warned its colony to take cover, saying:

“O ants, enter your dwellings so that Sulaiman and his soldiers will not crush you while they perceive not” (Qur’an 27:18).

Upon hearing this, Sulaiman smiled and reflected on the mercy of Allah. This verse emphasizes the value of communication, not only among humans but within creation as a whole. It also signifies the presence of complex knowledge systems in even the smallest creatures.

In the context of AI in Islamic education, the ant represents a form of collective intelligence, where communication and collaboration lead to the preservation and transmission of knowledge. AI tools such as machine learning algorithms, natural language processing, and data analytics can serve as instruments that foster collaboration among students and educators, thereby promoting a richer and more

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interactive learning environment. Just as Prophet Sulaiman harnessed his ability to understand the language of the ants, AI can help decode and disseminate knowledge in ways that were previously unimaginable.

Philosophical justification of leveraging artificial intelligence in Islamic education

Knowledge as an Obligation (Fard ‘Ayn and Fard Kifayah)

Islam places a high value on knowledge, with both individual and communal obligations to seek and disseminate it. AI can facilitate these obligations by providing widespread access to educational resources, especially in remote areas. The use of AI in Islamic education can be justified as an extension of the Islamic principle of promoting knowledge and making it accessible to all, fulfilling the communal obligation (fard kifayah) to teach and learn.

Tawhid and the Unity of Knowledge

The principle of tawhid (oneness of God) emphasizes the unity of knowledge in Islam. AI, when used within the parameters of Islamic ethics, can help integrate various branches of knowledge—religious and secular—into a unified system that serves the holistic development of individuals. By synthesizing diverse sources of information, AI can support the Islamic worldview that knowledge is interconnected and ultimately leads to the recognition of the Creator

Shura (Consultation) and Ijtihad (Independent Reasoning)

The processes of shura (consultation) and ijtihad (independent reasoning) are central to Islamic jurisprudence and decision-making. AI can be viewed as a tool that enhances these processes by providing data-driven insights and facilitating informed decision-making in educational settings. While AI does not replace human reasoning, it can serve as a consultative tool that aids scholars and educators in arriving at sound conclusions, thereby promoting ijtihad in contemporary contexts (Abdul Hakim & Pauli Anggraini, 2023)

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS IN THE USE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN ISLAM

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While AI offers numerous benefits, its use in Islamic education must be guided by ethical principles rooted in the Shariah. The following areas are considered vital points to be considered in the use of AI Technology.

Avoiding Bias and Ensuring Justice (Adl عدل): AI systems must be designed to avoid bias and ensure fairness in educational outcomes, aligning with the Islamic principle of justice (adl).

Privacy and Dignity (Hurma حرمة): The use of AI should respect the privacy and dignity of individuals, as mandated by Islamic teachings.

Human Supervision (إشراف بشري): AI must always be used under human supervision, ensuring that it serves as an aid to, rather than a replacement for, human educators and scholars.

Ethical Justifications for Artificial Intelligence in Islamic Education

Islamic ethics are primarily concerned with the moral consequences of actions. Technologies, including AI, are judged by their ability to contribute to the greater good (maslaha) and minimize harm (mafsadah). Ethical justifications for AI in Islamic education can be grounded in the following areas:

Accessibility and Democratization of Knowledge

One of the major ethical justifications for using AI in Islamic education is its potential to democratize knowledge. AI can provide access to Islamic education to millions of people who may otherwise be unable to attend traditional schools or universities. Online platforms, personalized learning systems, and AI-driven content delivery can bring high-quality Islamic education to people in remote areas and those with physical disabilities, enabling them to fulfill the religious obligation of seeking knowledge (Omar, 2020).

The Qur'an emphasizes equality in seeking knowledge, stating, "Are those who have knowledge and those who have no knowledge alike?" (Qur'an 39:9). AI can play a critical role in realizing this equality by removing barriers to education.

Efficiency in Learning

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AI has the capacity to process and analyze vast amounts of data quickly and efficiently. This can be particularly useful in the context of Islamic education, where students often engage in extensive memorization of the Qur'an and Hadith, alongside the study of complex jurisprudential texts. AI can assist in personalized learning, where students' progress is monitored and tailored teaching methods are applied to suit their individual learning styles. This technological efficiency aligns with the Islamic value of productivity and time management (Itqan) (Hameed, 2018).

Promoting Lifelong Learning

Islamic tradition encourages continuous learning throughout a Muslim's life. AI's capacity for lifelong learning systems fits into this philosophy. Through AI-based platforms, learners can access Islamic content at their own pace, contributing to personal development and spiritual growth over time (Hamid & Masoud, 2019).

Preventing Misinterpretation and Enhancing Accuracy

One significant challenge in Islamic education is ensuring the accuracy of religious teachings. AI systems, when properly developed, can help prevent misinterpretations by offering standardized and verified educational content. AI can analyze and cross-reference different Islamic texts, providing explanations consistent with accepted Islamic doctrines. This contributes to preserving the purity of Islamic teachings and minimizes the risk of misinformation (Al-Khalifa, 2021).

Theological Justifications for AI in Islamic Education

Tawhid and Technological Utilization

The principle of Tawhid (the Oneness of God) lies at the heart of Islamic theology and shapes the Muslim worldview, which emphasizes that all of creation is interconnected under the sovereignty of Allah. In this context, AI can be seen as part of the divine resources made available to humanity to fulfill its purpose of stewardship (Khilafah) on Earth. As long as AI is used in a way that serves good purposes, such as enhancing religious knowledge and promoting ethical values, its use is consistent with the concept of Tawhid (Rahman, 1982).

Stewardship and Ethical Responsibility

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The concept of *Khilafah* (stewardship) asserts that human beings are custodians of the Earth and must act responsibly in utilizing its resources, including technological advancements like AI. The Qur'an encourages humans to reflect on their responsibilities as stewards: "He raised you in ranks, some above others, that He may try you in the gifts He has given you" (Qur'an 6:165). AI, as a gift, can be used for promoting educational access and ethical learning, provided that Muslims employ it with the awareness of their moral and ethical responsibilities.

Innovation (Bid'ah)

A potential theological concern related to AI in Islamic education is the concept of *Bid'ah* (innovation). Traditional Islamic thought often distinguishes between acceptable and unacceptable forms of innovation. While AI may be viewed as an innovation, its use in education falls under the category of beneficial (*Bid'ah Hasanah*) rather than harmful innovation, provided it enhances religious understanding and knowledge without contradicting core Islamic principles (Al-Ghazali, 1991). Many contemporary scholars argue that modern technologies can be incorporated into Islamic education as long as their use is for the greater good and conforms to *Shariah*.

Conclusion

The integration of AI in Islamic education can be philosophically justified through the principles of *Ijtihad*, Islamic ethics, and theological doctrines like *Tawhid* and *Khilafah*. AI has the potential to democratize access to Islamic knowledge, enhance learning efficiency, and maintain the accuracy of religious content. When used responsibly and ethically, AI can align with Islamic principles, offering an innovative pathway to fulfill the religious obligation of seeking knowledge. However, it is essential that AI technologies be developed and implemented in ways that respect Islamic moral and ethical boundaries, ensuring that AI serves as a tool for human betterment rather than a source of harm. The stories of the trained dog, *Al-Hudhud*, and the ant in the narratives of Prophet Sulaiman offer rich philosophical insights that justify the use of AI in Islamic education. These stories highlight the role of creatures and tools as extensions of human capability, serving to gather, process, and transmit knowledge. When AI is employed within an Islamic ethical framework, it can enhance the educational experience, making knowledge more accessible and promoting a holistic understanding of the world in accordance with Islamic principles. By drawing on these

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timeless narratives, the integration of AI into Islamic education can be both philosophically justified and ethically aligned with the teachings of Islam.

The stories of the trained dog, Al-Hudhud, and the ant in the narratives of Prophet Sulaiman offer rich philosophical insights that justify the use of AI in Islamic education. These stories highlight the role of creatures and tools as extensions of human capability, serving to gather, process, and transmit knowledge. When AI is employed within an Islamic ethical framework, it can enhance the educational experience, making knowledge more accessible and promoting a holistic understanding of the world in accordance with Islamic principles. By drawing on these timeless narratives, the integration of AI into Islamic education can be both philosophically justified and ethically aligned with the teachings of Islam.

Research Suggestions and Recommendations

Research Suggestions

1. Philosophical Foundations of AI in Islamic Education
 - Explore how Islamic epistemology and ontology justify the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education.
 - Compare AI-driven educational tools with traditional Islamic teaching methods.
 - Investigate the ethical dimensions of Artificial Intelligence (AI) from an Islamic perspective, including fairness, justice, and accountability.
2. Symbolic Lessons from Trained Animals in Islamic Thought
 - Analyze how the trained dog, Al-Hudhud (Hoopoe bird), and Prophet Sulaiman's ant symbolize intelligence, communication, and structured learning.
 - Draw parallels between these animals' cognitive abilities and Artificial Intelligence (AI)'s role in problem-solving and knowledge dissemination.
 - Investigate the extent to which these creatures functioned as intelligent agents in divine narratives.
3. Theological and Legal Justifications for AI in Education

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- Study Islamic jurisprudence (Fiqh) to determine the permissibility of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in learning environments.
 - Assess how AI aligns with the objectives of Maqasid al-Shariah, particularly in preserving knowledge and facilitating ease in education.
 - Evaluate historical Islamic approaches to technology and knowledge acquisition.
4. Comparative Study with Other Religious and Philosophical Perspectives
- Compare Islamic perspectives on Artificial Intelligence (AI) with other religious and indigenous philosophical views.
 - Investigate how different traditions justify AI use in education, drawing insights from both classical and modern scholarship.

Recommendations

1. Incorporating AI Ethically in Islamic Education
 - AI should be used as an aid rather than a replacement for traditional scholars and teachers.
 - Ethical guidelines should be established to ensure Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools align with Islamic values.
 - Ongoing scholarly review is necessary to address emerging ethical and theological concerns.
2. Developing AI Models Inspired by Islamic Educational Principles
 - AI should be programmed to reflect Islamic moral and ethical teachings.
 - Developers should integrate AI-based educational platforms with classical Islamic texts to promote holistic learning.
 - AI-generated content should be monitored to ensure authenticity and accuracy in Islamic teachings.
3. Fostering Collaboration Between Islamic Scholars and Artificial Intelligence (AI) Experts

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- Establish interdisciplinary research centers focusing on Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Islamic education.
 - Encourage scholars in Usul al-Fiqh, Tafsir, and Hadith to collaborate with Artificial Intelligence (AI) developers.
 - Conduct conferences and workshops on AI in Islamic education to foster academic dialogue.
4. Addressing Potential Challenges and Limitations
- AI-generated Islamic knowledge should not replace human scholarship and ijtihad (independent reasoning).
 - Safeguards should be implemented to prevent AI misinterpretation of religious texts.
 - Further studies should be conducted on Artificial Intelligence (AI)'s impact on the traditional teacher-student relationship in Islamic learning.

These suggestions and recommendations provide a structured approach for further research into the philosophical, theological, and practical aspects of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in Islamic education, using the trained dog, Al-Hudhud, and Prophet Sulaiman's ant as case studies for Intelligent Learning Systems.

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Comparative Analysis between Guidance, Emotional Wellbeing, Social Skills and Career-Decision-Self-Efficacy among Electrical/Electronic Education Students in Federal Universities in Southwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the levels of guidance, emotional well-being, social skills, and career decision self-efficacy (CDSE) among electrical/electronics education students in southwest Nigeria, and examined how these factors relate to each other. The study was guided by four research questions and one hypothesis. Using a correlational design, the study surveyed 168 students from six universities with a questionnaire measuring these four areas. The questionnaire was validated by three experts. Data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation (SD) and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance. Results showed a low level of guidance (Mean = 2.36), but high levels of emotional well-being (Mean = 3.50), social skills (Mean = 3.58), and CDSE (Mean = 3.55), suggesting students are resilient despite limited help. Significant positive relationships were found between guidance and social skills ($r = .257^$), guidance and CDSE ($r = .422^*$), emotional well-being and social skills ($r = .402^*$), and social skills and CDSE ($r = .409^*$), rejecting the idea that these factors are not related. However, guidance did not strongly connect to emotional well-being ($r = .132$), nor did emotional well-being to CDSE ($r = .119$). These findings, backed by theories like Social Cognitive Career Theory, suggest that even limited guidance boosts career confidence and social abilities, but better counseling is needed to support emotional health. The study recommends improving guidance programs to help students succeed academically and professionally.*

Keyword: Career Decision Self-Efficacy (CDSE); Guidance; Emotional Well-being; Social Skills; Electrical/Electronic Education

Introduction

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The dawn of the 21st century has ushered in an era of unprecedented diversification in career paths, with emerging opportunities complicating the decision-making process for individuals worldwide. For university students, particularly those in technical fields like electrical/electronics education in southwest Nigeria, this complexity is magnified by rapid technological advancements, globalization, and a competitive educational landscape. Career decision self-efficacy (CDSE), defined as an individual's belief in their ability to successfully navigate career-related choices (Bandura, 1986; Taylor & Betz, 1983), stands as a critical determinant of academic persistence, vocational selection, and long-term professional success. Rooted in Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory, CDSE emerges from a dynamic interplay of personal experiences, vicarious learning, social persuasion, and physiological states, shaping how students approach tasks, set goals, and persevere through challenges. For electrical/electronics students, whose training bridges theoretical knowledge and practical application, fostering CDSE is essential not only for individual achievement but also for addressing regional and global shortages of skilled technical professionals (Eurofound, 2021).

Guidance serves as a foundational pillar in this context, offering structured support to enhance students' academic, emotional, and career development. Beyond its traditional role in career path selection, modern guidance encompasses a broader spectrum, including emotional counseling, academic advising, and life skills development, all of which contribute to resilience and self-awareness (Gysbers, 2001). Research underscores a positive correlation between effective guidance and heightened CDSE, as it equips students with the tools to explore career options, reduce indecision, and build optimism about their vocational futures (Rudolph et al., 2017; Stead et al., 2022). In Nigeria, where educational systems face resource constraints and guidance services are often underutilized (Egbochuku, 2008), understanding its impact on technical students is particularly pressing. Students require tailored support to navigate the unique demands of their discipline, which blends hands-on skills with theoretical rigor, yet evidence suggests that inadequate guidance may contribute to low enrollment and retention in such programs (Chireshe, 2012).

Emotional well-being, another key factor, reflects an individual's capacity to understand, manage, and express emotions constructively, fostering resilience amid academic and personal pressures (Cross et al., 2018). For university students transitioning into adulthood, emotional well-being is vital for coping with stress, maintaining a positive outlook, and building self-worth (Cowen & Keltner, 2021). These attributes directly influence academic performance and social interactions. Similarly,

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social skills, defined as learned behaviors enabling effective and rewarding interpersonal interactions (Kinnaman & Bellack, 2012), are indispensable for forming relationships, resolving conflicts, and adapting to new environments. These skills, developed through observation and experience, serve as a protective factor against psychosocial challenges like anxiety or isolation, which are prevalent among adolescents (Jensen-Campbell et al., 2002). For electrical/electronics students, strong social skills can enhance teamwork and communication, while also supporting their emotional health.

The interplay of guidance, emotional well-being, and social skills with CDSE is especially relevant in southwest Nigeria, where technical education plays a pivotal role in economic development yet faces challenges. For instance, some students pick electrical/electronics programs without really wanting to, often as a backup plan, which might mean they didn't get enough guidance early on (Veillard, 2012). This misalignment can erode satisfaction, performance, and retention, perpetuating a negative occupational image of the field and exacerbating skilled labor shortages (Veillette, 2004). Despite these issues, little research has explored how these constructs interrelate among this specific student population, leaving a gap in understanding how to bolster their holistic development. Previous studies have established broad associations between CDSE and career outcomes (Betz & Luzzo, 1996) and between social skills and emotional health (Deniz et al., 2005), but their specific dynamics within the context of Nigerian technical education remain underexplored.

This study, therefore, aimed to investigate the levels of guidance, emotional well-being, social skills, and CDSE among electrical/electronics education students in southwest Nigeria, with a focus on Ogun State, and to examine the relationships among these variables. By doing so, it sought to illuminate how guidance influences students' emotional resilience, interpersonal competence, and career confidence, offering insights into optimizing support systems. Given the theoretical foundations linking these constructs such as Social Cognitive Career Theory (Lent et al., 1994) and emotional intelligence frameworks (Goleman, 1995), the findings could inform interventions to enhance student outcomes, addressing both individual aspirations and broader societal needs for a skilled workforce. In a region where educational and career stakes are high, this research provides an exploration of how to empower technical students to thrive in a changing world.

Objectives of the Study:

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The main purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship among guidance, emotional well-being, social skill and career decision self-efficacy of electrical/electronics education students in Southwest, Nigeria. The study specifically sought to determine the:

1. Level of guidance among electrical/electronics education students in Southwest, Nigeria.
2. Level of emotional well-being of electrical/electronics education students in Southwest, Nigeria.
3. Level of social skill of electrical/electronics education students in Southwest, Nigeria.
4. Level of career decision self-efficacy of electrical/electronics education students in Southwest, Nigeria.
5. Relationship among guidance, emotional well-being, social skill and career decision self-efficacy of electrical/electronics education students in Southwest, Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the level of guidance among electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria?
2. What is the level of emotional well-being of electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria?
3. What is the level of social skill of electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria?
4. What is the level of career decision self-efficacy of electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria?

Research Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between guidance, emotional well-being, social skill and career decision self-efficacy of electrical /electronics students.

Methodology

Research Design: A correlational research design was adopted for this study. Thus, to investigate the relationship which exist among guidance, emotional well-being, social skill and career decision self-efficacy of electrical/ electronics students in Southwest Nigeria, correlational research design was seen as suitable for this study

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Population of the Study: The population for this study comprised all the 168 electrical/electronics technology education students in south western part of Nigeria. This made up of electronics technology students that are in 300 level and final year (400 level). This is because the students at this level would have already specialized in electrical/electronics technology education.

Sample and Sampling Techniques: Purposive sampling technique was adopted for this study. The electrical/electronic education students in south western part of Nigeria were purposely sampled because the study focused on electrical/electronics students. There are six universities in southwest region offering Technical Education as a course and having electrical/electronics option. However, the entire population of the study was used for the study because of the relatively small size which is manageable and accessible.

Research Instruments: Data for this study were gathered using a questionnaire, which was based on tools from earlier research but adjusted for this project. To assess participants' confidence in managing career-related tasks, the study used a modified version of the Career Decision Self-Efficacy Scale–Short Form, originally developed by Betz et al. (1996). This tool included 20 questions, such as “I think my college performance will help me succeed in finding a job” and “I want a good job, but I don't stress about it too much.” Participants rated their agreement on a 5-point scale, from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Emotional well-being was evaluated with the Schutte Self-Report Emotional Intelligence Test (SSEIT), which measures four aspects of emotional intelligence outlined by Salovey and Mayer (1990): recognizing emotions in oneself and others, expressing emotions, regulating personal emotions, and using emotions to address challenges. The SSEIT has 32 questions, answered on a 5-point scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree), where higher total scores indicate stronger emotional intelligence (Schutte et al., 1998).

For social skills, the study employed a version of the Social Skills Questionnaire (SSQ) by Gresham and Elliot (1998). This 23-item tool examines students' social behaviors and their frequency, as well as their importance in relationships. Responses were given on a 5-point scale, ranging from 5 (very often) to 1 (never). To measure the guidance students received, a custom questionnaire was created with 10 questions. It was

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designed using a 5-point Likert scale, where participants indicated their level of agreement from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree).

Validation of the Instrument: The instrument was validated by three experts who are lecturers from the Department of Industrial Technical Education, Tai Solarin University of Education, Ijebu-ode Ogun State. They were requested to carry out face validity of the questionnaire instrument which involves ascertaining the appropriateness of questionnaire items, clarity of items, arrangement and logical sequence.

Reliability of the Instrument: The reliability of the instrument was established by administering 10 copies of the instrument to respondents outside the study area. Cronbach Alpha was used to establish the internal consistency of the instrument, and it yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.73.

Method of Data Analysis: Data collected for the study were analyzed and interpreted using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation (SD) and Correlation matrix (Pearson Product Moment Correlation PPMC). The hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Decision Rule: A mean score of 4.50 – 5.00 indicates very high, 3.50 – 4.49 represents high, 2.50 – 3.49 signifies moderate, 1.50 – 2.49 reflects low, and 1.00 – 1.49 denotes very low. Correlation decisions were based on strength and direction: $r > 0.7$ (strong), $0.4 \leq r \leq 0.7$ (moderate), and $r < 0.4$ (weak), whether positive or negative. The decision rule for accepting or rejecting the null hypothesis at a 0.05 level of significance is as follows: If the p-value ≤ 0.05 , we reject the null hypothesis (H_0), indicating that there is sufficient statistical evidence to support the alternative hypothesis (H_1). However, if the p-value > 0.05 , we fail to reject the null hypothesis, suggesting that there is not enough evidence to conclude that H_1 is true.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the level of guidance among electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean responses of participants on level of guidance among electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria.

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S/N	Items	Mea n	SD
1	Guidance services (career, academic, or emotional) is accessible at my university	2.00	0.88
2	It is easy to approach a guidance counselor or advisor at my university	2.39	0.81
3	The guidance services are well-advertised to students	2.05	0.79
4	The advice and guidance I received from my counselors are of high quality	2.91	0.94
5	The guidance provided is personalized to my specific needs	2.31	0.79
6	I am satisfied with the response time when seeking guidance services	2.28	0.68
7	I feel more emotionally resilient after seeking guidance	2.46	1.18
8	The guidance services I received has helped me manage stress or anxiety	2.67	1.02
9	The guidance provided helped clarify my career goals	2.04	1.08
10	I am satisfied with the guidance I received as it covers the important areas where I felt I needed guidance	2.53	0.81
Average Mean		2.36	

The table presents the mean responses of respondents on the level of guidance among electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria. The table revealed the level of agreement of the respondents to the items with means of 2.00, 2.39, 2.05, 2.91, 2.31, 2.28, 2.46, 2.67, 2.04, and 2.53. However, with an average mean of 2.36, it was established that the level of guidance received by electrical/electronics education students is low.

Research Question 2: What is the level of emotional well-being of electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean responses of Participants on level of emotional well-being of electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD
1	I know when to speak about my personal problems to others	3.99	0.80
2	When I am faced with obstacles, I remember times I faced similar obstacles and overcame them	3.69	1.12
3	I expect that I will do well on most things I try	3.81	0.89
4	Other people find it easy to confide in me	3.85	1.01
5	I find it hard to understand the non-verbal messages of other people	3.56	1.19
6	Some of the major events of my life have led me to re-evaluate what is important and not important	3.94	1.00
7	When my mood changes, I see new possibilities	3.77	0.90
8	Emotions are one of the things that make my life worth living.	3.91	1.07
9	I am aware of my emotions as I experience them	3.72	0.90
10	I expect good things to happen	3.99	0.77

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11	I like to share my emotions with others	3.66	0.96
12	When I experience a positive emotion, I know how to make it last	2.91	0.78
13	I arrange events others enjoy	3.11	1.09
14	I seek out activities that make me happy	3.38	1.06
15	I am aware of the non-verbal messages I send to others	3.04	1.11
16	I present myself in a way that makes a good impression on others	3.94	1.17
17	When I am in a positive mood, solving problems is easy for me	3.90	1.10
18	By looking at their facial expressions, I recognize the emotions people are experiencing	2.86	1.00
19	I know why my emotions change	3.97	0.90
20	When I am in a positive mood, I am able to come up with new ideas	3.91	1.07
21	I have control over my emotions	3.72	0.90
22	I easily recognize my emotions as I experience them	3.94	1.19
23	I motivate myself by imagining a good outcome to tasks I take on	2.79	1.44
24	I compliment others when they have done something well.	3.94	1.19
25	I am aware of the non-verbal messages other people send.	2.35	1.31
26	When another person tells me about an important event in his or her life, I almost feel as though I have experienced this event myself	2.90	1.32
27	When I feel a change in emotions, I tend to come up with new ideas	2.55	1.34
28	When I am faced with a challenge, I do not give up because I believe I will succeed	3.95	1.30
29	I know what other people are feeling just by looking at them	3.88	1.21
30	I help other people feel better when they are down	2.79	1.44
31	I use good moods to help myself keep trying in the face of obstacles	3.98	1.19
32	I can tell how people are feeling by listening to the tone of their voice	2.35	1.31
Average Mean		3.50	

The table presents the mean responses of respondents on the level of emotional well-being of electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria. The table revealed the level of agreement of the respondents to the items. Out of the thirty-two (32) items, twenty-four (24) of the items were above 3.0 while eight (8) of the items is below 3.0. However, with an average mean of 3.50, it was established that the level of emotional well-being of electrical/electronics education students is high.

Research Question 3: What is the level of social skill of electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean responses of Participants on level of social skill of electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	Mea n	SD
1	I make friends easily	4.08	1.23
2	I say nice things to others when they have done something well	3.79	1.16
3	I asked adult for help when other children try to eat me or push my heart.	3.44	1.22
4	I try to understand all my friends free when they are angry or upset	3.22	1.35
5	I listen to adults when they are talking with me	3.68	1.18

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6	I asked what I put my problems	3.58	1.23
7	I asked before using other people's things	3.41	1.30
8	I disagree with adults without fighting or argue	3.01	1.01
9	I do my homework on time	3.96	1.01
10	I keep my desk clean and neat	3.23	1.41
11	I am active in school activities such as sports and clubs	3.23	1.41
12	I finished classroom work on time	3.27	1.25
13	A compromise with parents or teachers when we disagree	3.54	1.08
14	I listen to my friends when they talk about problems their face	3.58	1.23
15	I tell other people when they have done something well	3.51	1.03
16	I smile with or not at others	3.94	1.08
17	I use my free time in a good way	4.20	0.75
18	I fight others to join in social activities	4.14	0.85
19	I control my temper when people are angry with me	4.09	1.04
20	I follow teachers' directions	3.94	1.08
21	I start talks with classroom members	4.23	0.90
22	I talk things over with classmates when there is problem or an argument	3.20	0.75
Average Mean		3.58	

The table above presents the mean responses of respondents on the level of social skill of electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria. The table revealed the level of agreement of the respondents to the items. It was revealed with all the means higher than 3.0 that the respondents agree with all of the items. However, with an average mean of 3.58, it was established that the level of social skills of electrical/electronics education students is high.

Research Question 4: What is the level of career decision self-efficacy of electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria.

Table 4: Mean responses of Participants on level of career decision self-efficacy of electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria.

S/N	Items	Mean	SD
1	I see other students like me get good jobs after college	3.10	0.88
2	Based on my performance in college, I believe I'll be successful at searching for a job	3.73	0.44
3	I feel really great when I am doing things to find a career	3.43	0.56
4	People tell me that I should find a job easily	3.00	1.14
5	I get a sinking feeling when I think of working on my job search	3.17	0.91
6	I have done well in the past in finding jobs	3.03	0.80
7	I care about getting a good job, but I don't worry too much about it	3.23	0.77
8	People in my family have been successful in their job searches, and it has paid off for them in their careers	4.33	0.71
9	My teachers or advisors encouraged me to apply myself towards getting a job	3.40	0.67
10	Job searching always makes me nervous	3.47	0.68
11	I see people like me overcoming career challenges in getting jobs	3.40	0.67

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12	People who know what it takes to get a good job, tell me they believe I will be successful	3.47	0.68
13	I feel a sense of satisfaction when I work on looking for a job	4.23	0.67
14	I see my peers doing well in their job searches	3.97	0.49
15	I get so anxious about my job search that my mind often goes blank or I am too distracted to think clearly	3.77	0.86
16	I believe I am bright enough to do what is necessary to find a job	3.33	0.92
17	When I am working on my job search my heart beats fast and my palms get sweaty	3.47	0.57
18	Parents of my friends have praised or recognized my job search efforts	3.99	0.60
19	I have strong positive feelings when I work on my job search	3.47	0.62
20	Based on my past experience, I feel I have the necessary skills to find a good job	3.93	0.67
Average Mean		3.55	

The table above presents the mean responses of respondents on the level of social skill of electrical/electronics education students in southwest, Nigeria. The table revealed the level of agreement of the respondents to the items. It was revealed with all the means higher than 3.0 that the respondents agree with all of the items. However, with an average mean of 3.55, it was established that the level of social skills of electrical/electronics education students is high.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship among guidance, emotional well-being, social skill and career decision self-efficacy of electrical /electronics students.

Table 5: Relationship among guidance, emotional well-being, social skill and career decision self-efficacy of electrical /electronics students.

Variables	M	SD	1	2	3	4	5
1. Guidance	3.90	0.44	1				
2. Emotional well-being	3.13	0.32	.132	1			
3. Social skill	3.57	0.39	.257*	.402*	1		
4. Career decision self-efficacy	3.90	0.40	.422*	.119	.409*	.424*	1

The table above shows the relationship among guidance, emotional well-being, social skill and career decision self-efficacy of electrical /electronics students. The table revealed electrical /electronics students' guidance ($M = 3.90$, $SD = 0.44$), emotional well-being ($M = 3.13$, $SD = 0.32$), social skill ($M = 3.57$, $SD = 0.39$), and career decision self-efficacy ($M = 3.90$, $SD = 0.4$). The results of these correlation analyses are presented in Table 5. Guidance shows a weak, non-significant positive relationship with emotional well-being ($r = .132$), but a moderate, significant positive relationship with

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social skill ($r = .257^*$) and a moderately strong, significant positive relationship with career decision self-efficacy ($r = .422^*$). Emotional well-being has a moderately strong, significant positive relationship with social skill ($r = .402^*$), yet only a weak, non-significant positive relationship with career decision self-efficacy ($r = .119$). Meanwhile, social skill and career decision self-efficacy exhibit a moderately strong, significant positive relationship ($r = .409^*$).

The null hypothesis is rejected for the relationships between guidance and social skill, guidance and career decision self-efficacy, emotional well-being and social skill, and social skill and career decision self-efficacy, as these correlations are statistically significant. However, the null hypothesis is not rejected for the relationships between guidance and emotional well-being, and emotional well-being and career decision self-efficacy, as these correlations are not statistically significant. Conclusively, the hypothesis that there is "no significant relationship among" all four variables is rejected, as significant relationships exist among several pairs of variables, though not universally across all combinations.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of this study among electrical/electronics education students in southwest Nigeria provide shed light into the levels of guidance, emotional well-being, social skills, and career decision self-efficacy, as well as their interrelationships. The results indicate that the level of guidance received by these students is low (average mean = 2.36), suggesting inadequate access to or quality of guidance services. This aligns with prior research by Egbochuku (2008), who noted that guidance and counseling services in Nigerian tertiary institutions are often underutilized or poorly implemented due to limited resources and awareness. In contrast, emotional well-being (average mean = 3.50), social skills (average mean = 3.58), and career decision self-efficacy (average mean = 3.55) were all rated as high, indicating that these students possess a strong sense of emotional resilience, interpersonal competence, and confidence in career-related decision-making. These findings are in line with Salami (2011), who found that Nigerian students often exhibit high emotional and social competencies despite systemic challenges, potentially due to cultural emphasis on communal support and personal resilience.

The correlation analysis further reveals significant relationships among several variables, and rejecting the null hypothesis. Guidance showed a moderate, significant

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positive relationship with social skills ($r = .257^*$) and a moderately strong, significant relationship with career decision self-efficacy ($r = .422^*$), suggesting that even limited guidance can positively influence students' interpersonal abilities and career confidence. This supports Lent et al.'s (1994) Social Cognitive Career Theory, which posits that external support, such as guidance, enhances self-efficacy in career decision-making. Similarly, the moderately strong, significant relationship between emotional well-being and social skills ($r = .402^*$) aligns with Goleman's (1995) assertion that emotional intelligence is the foundation for effective social interactions.. The significant correlation between social skills and career decision self-efficacy ($r = .409^*$) further corroborates Bandura's (1997) self-efficacy theory, where social competence reinforces confidence in achieving career goals. However, the weak, non-significant relationships between guidance and emotional well-being ($r = .132$) and between emotional well-being and career decision self-efficacy ($r = .119$) suggest that guidance may not have a direct impact on improving emotional health, nor does emotional well-being alone drive career confidence in this context. This could reflect contextual factors, such as the technical focus of electrical/electronics education, where career self-efficacy may depend more on practical skills than emotional states (Ogbuanya & Chukwuedo, 2017).

These results reveal a contradiction. Even though students receive little guidance, they still show strong emotional well-being, social skills, and confidence in making career decisions. This may be because they rely on other support systems, such as friends or family, as suggested by Adeyemo (2005). However, the weak connection between guidance and emotional well-being shows the need for better counseling services to support students in all areas of their lives. Improving the quality of guidance could further enhance its positive influence on social skills and career confidence, leading to better academic and career success.

Conclusion

This study investigated the levels of guidance, emotional well-being, social skills, and career decision self-efficacy among electrical/electronics education students in southwest Nigeria, as well as the relationships among these variables. The findings reveal a low level of guidance, indicating a gap in the accessibility, quality, or awareness of counseling services within the educational system. Conversely, students demonstrated high levels of emotional well-being, social skills, and career decision self-efficacy, suggesting resilience and competence despite limited formal guidance.

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Correlation analyses further showed significant positive relationships between guidance and social skills, guidance and career decision self-efficacy, emotional well-being and social skills, and social skills and career decision self-efficacy.

Recommendations

1. Educational institutions should prioritize the development of comprehensive guidance and counseling programs that cater to the emotional, social, and career development needs of students. This may include workshops, mentorship, and personalized counseling sessions that address both academic and personal growth.
2. Trainings should be organized for educators, teachers/instructors and school counselors in the aspect of identifying the diverse needs of students, especially in the areas of emotional well-being, social interactions, and career decision-making.
3. Future studies could further explore the specific types of guidance that are most effective in enhancing students' career decision-making processes.

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Qualitative Study on Significance and Threats of Integrating Artificial Intelligence Technology at Tertiary Level of Education in Nigeria: A Systematic Review

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ABSTRACT

The advent of artificial intelligence (AI) has significantly transformed various sectors, including tertiary education. This paper examines the Qualitative study on significance and threats of integrating Artificial intelligence technology at tertiary level of education in Nigeria: A Systematic Review. On the other hand, AI offers unprecedented opportunities for personalizes learning. Efficient administrative processes, and advanced research capabilities. Adaptive learning systems, intelligent tutoring and predictive analytics have potential to revolutionize the educational landscape, making learning more accessible and tailored to individual needs. However, AI also poses significant challenges and threats to education in tertiary institutions. These includes concerns over the potential for job displacement among academic staff, potentially rendering some job roles obsolete, and erosion of critical thinking skills among students due to over-reliance on automated systems. Additionally, not everyone has equal access to AI, internet, and devices, lack of AI techniques designed for a specific situation that could address the needs of a particular domain, specific learning activities, or teaching goals among others. Based on the challenges identified, the paper recommended among others that all stakeholders in education including curriculum planners and policy makers should provide a framework and guardrails on how AI should be integrated in schools to assist teachers but not to replace them, but it should be an effective learning tool that lessens the burdens of both teachers and students and offers effective learning experiences for students. The paper also recommended that there is a need to provide equal access to AI, internet, and devices to all learners at tertiary institutions.

Keywords: Threats, Integrating, Artificial intelligence and Higher Education

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Introduction

Artificial intelligence (AI) is growing, and its use spreads at a dangerous rate, and AI has become part of our daily life. The global adoption of technology in education has changed the teaching and learning method. One of the disruptive techniques to customize various learning groups, teachers and teachers experience is artificial intelligence. Mechanical learning and artificial intelligence are the main drivers of growth and innovations in all industries, and the education department is not different. According to the E-learning industry, 47% of learning management tools are operated with AI skills in the next three years. Although the AI-running solutions have been in the Education Technology's place for some time, the industry is slow to follow them. 86% of academics say technology should be the central part of education. AI can improve both learning and teaching, and the education sector helps develop the best benefit for students and teachers. AI has changed the method of learning of people in the 21st century, the century of continuous change and advancement. Everyone is equipped with gadgets; it can be mobile, VR Box, Fitness Band, etc. Moreover, every day, you find new updates or even an advanced version of gadgets. Technology acceptance has become very natural in the last few decades. Amidst all these technological revolutions, Artificial Intelligence is the most admired technology in every sector. Now, it is not limited to Sci-Fi movies or novels. The reason why AI is the most attractive tech is its human-like experience. In 2016 social humanoid robot, Sophia was launched, it got trendy among tech giants and all around the world due to its human-like appearance and behavior compared to previous robotic variants. Artificial Intelligence has entered in every sector i.e. finance, retail, law, marketing & advertising, and the health sector. It is paving its wave in the education sector also. The moment the education sector get fully equipped with AI, it will change the face of education entirely. The paper aimed at finding out the importance of AI in teaching and learning, the uses of AI in Education and its thread to tertiary institution.

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial intelligence (AI) is currently one of the hottest buzzwords in tech and with good reason. The last few years have seen several innovations and advancements that have previously been solely in the realm of science fiction slowly transform into reality (Duggal, 2024). Artificial Intelligence (AI) is the simulation of human intelligence in machines that are programmed to think and act like humans. Learning, reasoning,

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problem-solving, perception, and language comprehension are all examples of cognitive abilities. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is a method of making a computer, a computer-controlled robot, or a soft think intelligently like the human mind. AI is accomplished by studying the patterns of the human brain and by analyzing the cognitive process. The outcome of these studies develops intelligent software and systems (Duggal, 2024).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) also refers to the development of intelligent machines that can perform tasks that typically require human intelligence. These tasks include speech recognition, problem-solving, decision-making, and even learning from experience. AI has the potential to revolutionize various aspects of higher education, including teaching, learning, administrative tasks, and student support services. With AI-powered systems, institutions can automate routine processes, analyze vast amounts of data, and provide personalized learning experiences to students (AUGUST, 22, 2023).

Artificial Intelligence as a tool for educational service/delivery

AI has the potential to be a valuable resource for education. One important topic the panel discussed was how AI can be helpful for bilingual learners. Practicing a new language with other students can be intimidating, but AI can offer a safe and effective learning environment. AI can be helpful more broadly as well by saving time. If you get writers block or are stuck getting started, you can use AI to develop an initial brainstorm, and then use your own thoughts and words to develop your essay or paper.

Significance of Artificial intelligence at tertiary level of education in Nigeria

Nigeria, like many other countries, is grappling with the rising costs associated with traditional educational methods. From expensive textbooks to high overhead costs for academic materials and resources, the financial burden on both students and lecturers continues to escalate. Additionally, the challenges posed by the ongoing economic hardships further exacerbate these issues, making it increasingly difficult for individuals to access quality education. However, the integration of AI into tertiary education can presents a transformative opportunity to address these challenges effectively. Here are some compelling reasons why it is essential to embrace AI in Nigerian Universities and colleges:

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Cost reduction: by leveraging digital learning platforms, open educational resources, and AI-powered teaching tools, tertiary institution can significantly reduce the cost of education for students. E-books, online lectures, and virtual libraries offer cost-effective alternatives to traditional textbooks and physical learning materials. Moreover, AI-driven educational platforms can personalize learning experiences, allowing students to progress at their own pace and reducing the need for expensive tutoring services.

Enhanced Efficiency: AI Technologies streamline administrative processes, academic workflows, and research endeavors, thereby improving overall efficiency within tertiary institutions. Automated grading systems, online registration portals, and virtual classrooms eliminate time-consuming manual tasks, enabling lecturers to focus more on teaching and research. This efficiency translates into cost savings for both students and lecturers.

Quality Education: introducing AI education in Nigerian tertiary institutions can elevates the quality of teaching, learning, and research. Interactive e-learning modules, virtual laboratories, and simulation software enhance students' understanding of complex concepts and practical skills. Furthermore, AI-driven analytics and predictive models enable educators to identify learning gaps, tailor instructional strategies, and provide personalized feedback, leading to improved academic outcomes.

Global Competitiveness: by equipping students with AI skills, Nigerian tertiary institutions prepare them to thrive in the digital economy and compete on a global scale. Proficiency in emerging technologies such as data science, machine learning, and cyber security enhances graduates' employability and empowers them to contribute meaningfully to the knowledge-based economy. Moreover, research collaborations and knowledge exchange initiatives facilitated by AI foster innovation and drive socio-economic development.

Student Assistance

Artificial Intelligence can understand the weakness and strength of every single student. It can analyze the pace of learning and latent skills of students that will help teachers, parents to guide students in productive learning. Next generation students will have the AI companion that will know everything about them from personal to professional.

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Teacher Assistance

As AI can understand students and their capability, it is going to help teachers to work accordingly. AI can also help the teachers to guide them on the rate of lecture delivering, the right time for assessments, what type of assessment is required for a particular topic, which topic is beneficial for students which are redundant, etc. Teachers can use AI for better understanding of topics and its level of difficulties towards students. That will increase the quality of education and level of students. With the use of Artificial Intelligence, educators can outsource their targets quickly and achieve results set for each and individual performance of a student.

Personalized Learning

It is one of the best benefits of AI in the education sector. As teachers we all know there are various types of students, and every teacher has a different way of teaching methods. It is very difficult for teachers and students to meet the exact expectations. There are students with different needs and some with extraordinary capabilities. In this era of ample information, it is imperative that every student gets the same access to education and learning. AI can adapt to the individual learning related requirements of students and teachers. That will reduce the meaningless and unproductive work of teachers and will help the institution to increase the efficiency of education.

Automation of Grading

At present, artificial intelligence is able to automate grading system in multiple choice questions (MCQ) in education institutions. Can you believe how much time teachers will be able to save from the automation of the grading process? With the continuous advancement in the AI algorithm, sooner it will be able to automate standard and dynamic grading system according to the needs of institutions.

Global access to education

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Artificial intelligence is one advanced tool that can bring the global classroom for students in every corner of the world. AI can fill the gap of communication between teachers and students. Students with different language or with visual or hearing impairments can understand teachers with the help of real-time subtitles. Presentation Translator is a free-plugin for PowerPoint that does so. AI will also help students to connect on the global level for brainstorming. It will increase the spread ability of knowledge among students. Many other educational technologies are transforming the education sector and easing the life of students, teachers, and institutions.

Considering these compelling benefits, the writers recommend that the stakeholders in the Nigerian education sector to prioritize the integration of AI education into the tertiary education curricula. This endeavor require strategies investments in infrastructure, faculty development, digital literacy programs to ensure widespread adoption and sustainable impact.

Uses of AI in Education

In May 2023, the U.S. Department of Education released a report titled *Artificial Intelligence and the Future of Teaching and Learning: Insights and Recommendations*. The department had conducted listening sessions in 2022 with more than 700 people, including educators and parents, to gauge their views on AI. The report noted that constituents believe that action is required now in order to get ahead of the expected increase of AI in education technology and they want to roll up their sleeves and start working together. People expressed anxiety about future potential risks with AI but also felt that AI may enable achieving educational priorities in better ways, at scale, and with lower costs.

AI could serve or is already serving in several teaching and learning roles:

Instructional assistants: AI's ability to conduct human-like conversations opens up possibilities for adaptive tutoring or instructional assistants that can help explain difficult concepts to students. AI-based feedback systems can offer constructive critiques on student writing, which can help students fine-tune their writing skills. Some research also suggests certain kinds of prompts can help children generate more fruitful questions about learning. AI models might also support customized learning for students with disabilities and provide translation for English language learners.

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Teaching assistants: AI might tackle some of the administrative tasks that keep teachers from investing more time with their peers or students. Early uses include automated routine tasks such as drafting lesson plans, creating differentiated materials, designing worksheets, developing quizzes, and exploring ways of explaining complicated academic materials. AI can also provide educators with recommendations to meet student needs and help teachers reflect, plan, and improve their practice.

Parent assistants. Parents can use AI to generate letters requesting individualized education plan (IEP) services or to ask that a child be evaluated for gifted and talented programs. For parents choosing a school for their child, AI could serve as an administrative assistant, mapping out school options within driving distance of home, generating application timelines, compiling contact information, and the like. Generative AI can even create bedtime stories with evolving plots tailored to a child's interests.

Administrator assistants. Using generative AI, school administrators can draft various communications, including materials for parents, newsletters, and other community-engagement documents. AI systems can also help with the difficult tasks of organizing class or bus schedules, and they can analyze complex data to identify patterns or needs. ChatGPT can perform sophisticated sentiment analysis that could be useful for measuring school-climate and other survey data.

Though the potential is great, most teachers have yet to use these tools. A Morning Consult and Education Choice poll found that while 60 percent say they have heard about ChatGPT, only 14 percent have used it in their free time, and just 13 percent have used it at school. It's likely that most teachers and students will engage with generative AI not through the platforms themselves but rather through AI capabilities embedded in software. Instructional providers such as Khan Academy, Varsity Tutors, and DuoLingo are experimenting with GPT-4-powered tutors that are trained on datasets specific to these organizations to provide individualized learning support that has additional guardrails to help protect students and enhance the experience for teachers.

Google's Project Tailwind is experimenting with an AI notebook that can analyze student notes and then develop study questions or provide tutoring support through a chat interface. These features could soon be available on Google Classroom, potentially

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reaching over half of all U.S. classrooms. Brisk Teaching Is one of the first companies to build a portfolio of AI services designed specifically for teachers differentiating content, drafting lesson plans, providing student feedback, and serving as an AI assistant to streamline workflow among different apps and tools

Providers of curriculum and instruction materials might also include AI assistants for instant help and tutoring tailored to the companies' products. One example is the edX Xpert, a ChatGPT-based learning assistant on the edX platform. It offers immediate, customized academic and customer support for online learners' worldwide. Regardless of the ways AI is used in classrooms, the fundamental task of policymakers and education leaders is to ensure that the technology is serving sound instructional practice. As Vicki Phillips, CEO of the National Center on Education and the Economy, wrote; We should not only think about how technology can assist teachers and learners in improving what they are doing now, but what it means for ensuring that new ways of teaching and learning flourish alongside the applications of AI (Bailey ,2023).

The Impact of AI at tertiary level of education in Nigeria

As AI continues to advance, its impact on higher education is becoming more evident. One of the significant impacts is the potential disruption of traditional teaching methods. AI-powered platforms can provide intelligent tutoring, adaptive learning, and virtual classrooms, making education more accessible and personalized. Tertiary level of education in Nigeria can leverage AI to enhance administrative tasks, such as admissions, student support, and campus management. AI-powered chatbots can provide instant assistance to students, reducing the burden on staff and improving overall efficiency (Hamilton and Swanston, 2023). 60% of Educators Use AI in their Classrooms, AI tools for teacher and students support are growing in popularity. A Survey by found Hamilton & Swanston (2023) found that younger teachers are more likely to adopt these tools, with respondents under 26 reporting the highest usage rates.

Review on Integration artificial intelligence at tertiary level of education in Nigeria

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The emergence of big data, cloud computing, artificial neural networks, and machine learning has enabled engineers to create a machine that can simulate human intelligence. Building on these technologies, this study refers to machines that are able to perceive, recognize, learn, react, and solve problems as artificial intelligence (AI) (Kumar and Thakur, 2012). Inevitably, such smart technologies will revolutionize the workplaces of the future (Horakova, Houska, and Domeova, 2017). Thus, while AI can interact and help humans perform at higher levels, it is emerging as the next disruptive innovation (Lawler & Rushby, 2013). AI is currently viewed by many as a driver that is integral to the fourth industrial revolution, and it may trigger the fourth revolution in education. Learning about AI has also begun to be part of school curriculum (Dai, Chai, Lin & Knox, 2020). However, just as the emergence of television and computers was once touted to be game changers of education, they have been shown to in fact enhance access to information without substantially changing the core educational practices. Nonetheless, educators are obliged to review current AI capabilities and identify possible pathways to optimize learning. Given the increasing attention, it is timely to review recent AI research in education to provide educators with an updated understanding of the field as a preparation to possible changes.

AI has been increasingly propagated as having strategic value for education (Seldon & Abidoye, 2018). Loeckx, 2016) suggested that AI could be an effective learning tool that lessens the burdens of both teachers and students and offers effective learning experiences for students. Coupled with current education reforms such as the digitalization of educational resources, gamification, and personalized learning experiences, there are many opportunities for the development of AI applications in education. For example, the modelling potential of AI techniques has been exploited systematically to develop reactive and adaptive tutorials for the construction of individualized learning environments as compensation for the shortage of teachers through the use of intelligent tutoring system (ITS) (Magnisalis, Demetriadis & Karakostas, 2011). ITSs provide personalized learning experience in four main ways: monitoring student's input, delivering appropriate tasks, providing effective feedback, and applying interfaces for human-computer communication (Seldon & Abidoye, 2018). When more ITS's are created for more subjects and topics, it is likely to change the role of teachers, and hence, schooling may need to be re-conceptualized (Zhai Chu, Chai, Jong, Andreja Istenic, Spector, Bao Liu, Jing Yuan, & Yan Li, 2021).

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Interview and reviewed papers have respectively surfaced the challenges or misunderstanding of AI in education. (Lawler & Rushby, 2013), Magnisalis, Demetriadis, & Karakostas, (2011) viewed that, there is a need to articulate a holistic evaluation criterion to measure the effectiveness of AI in education. To ensure the validity and reliability of the evaluation, a multidimensional model should be adopted, which includes technique, pedagogical design, domain knowledge, and human factors. Woolf's (Jain, Gurupur, Schroeder, & Faulkenberry, 2014). However, Roadmap for Education Technology predicted that in the era of AI Educational Data Mining, the lifelong assessment of students' knowledge, their progress, and the environments where they learn, as well as the success and failure in teaching strategies, can be chronologically tracked.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a Threat to Tertiary level of Education in Nigeria

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has rapidly emerged as a transformative technology in various industries, and higher education is no exception. As the capabilities of AI continue to advance, there is an increasing concern about its potential impact on the traditional higher education system. While AI offers numerous opportunities, it also presents challenges that higher education institutions must address. One of the primary concerns is the potential job displacement caused by automation. As AI takes over certain tasks, there may be a shift in the demand for specific skill sets, potentially rendering some job roles obsolete. Furthermore, ethical considerations arise when implementing AI in education. Privacy concerns, data security, and algorithm bias need to be carefully addressed to ensure fair and equitable access to education for all students.

Morrison (2023), reports that, School leaders have warned that AI poses a real and present danger to education, leaving teachers bewildered by the pace of change. And they have cast doubt on the ability and willingness of both governments and technology companies to regulate the technology effectively to protect the interests and well-being of students. Developments in artificial intelligence have gripped the public imagination since Open AI released ChatGPT, but there is growing disquiet at the potential impact on education. The letter warns of the very real and present hazards and dangers presented by AI, alongside the potential to benefit students and staff. While much attention has focused on the risk of students using AI to cheat in coursework and

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assessment, there are also concerns about the impact on children's mental health as well as on the teaching profession.

The school leaders, led by Sir Anthony Seldon, the head of Epsom College and biographer of former Prime ministers Boris Johnson and Tony Blair, also announced the creation of an advisory body to help teachers navigate developments in AI. Sir Anthony told the Times that while AI could prove the biggest benefit to education since the printing press, the risks were more severe than any threat that has ever faced schools. Learning is at its best, human beings are at their best, when they are challenged and overcome those challenges. AI will make life easy and strip away learning and teaching unless we get ahead of it, he added (Morrison, 2023).

Prime minister Rishi Sunak told reporters at the G7 summit in Japan that guardrails would have to be put in place so AI could be introduced safely and securely, but the school leaders cast doubt on government's ability to effectively regulate the sector. AI is moving far too quickly for the government or parliament alone to provide the real-time advice schools need, said the signatories, who included Geoff Barton, general secretary of the Association of School and College Leaders, which represents many school principals.

Education Secretary Gillian Keegan told an education technology showcase in March that AI had the potential to transform education and have a significant impact on teachers' workloads. The education secretary has been clear about the government's appetite to pursue the opportunities and manage the risks that exist in this space, and we have already published information to help schools do this, the Department for Education said. We continue to work with experts, including in education, to share and identify best practice. But Professor Stuart Russell, of University of California in Berkeley and a former advisor on AI to both the U.S. and U.K. governments, cautioned that governments were not doing enough to protect the public from the impact of AI and Dr Geoffrey Hinton, regarded as the godfather of artificial intelligence, warned about the growing dangers of developments in AI when he quit Google.

AI is a promising field that faces many technology bottlenecks. The challenges would be more complex and intricate, especially when they are connected to an application in education. The challenges this review identifies could be classified into three categories: technique, teachers and students, and social ethics. Although AI

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techniques displayed and predicted smart computation in the education domain, they generally fail to bring added-value to large-scale students because of the concern of costs, and the mainstream is still occupied by basic value (Nabiyev, Çakiroğlu, Karal, Erümit, & Çebi, 2016). Specifically, some researchers found that many AI techniques were designed for a general situation that could not address the needs of a particular domain, specific learning activities, or teaching goals. This would prevent the actualization of personalized learning experiences (Loeckx, 2016 and Wegerif, McLaren, Chamrada, 2010).

Another great challenge reported in the Horizon report in 2018 is the reconceptualization of the role of educators. Teachers' attitudes towards AI have a significant influence on the effectiveness of using AI in education. Teachers may swing from total resistance to overreliance. The former could arise from inadequate, inappropriate, irrelevant, or outdated professional development. The latter may be due to teachers' unrealistic expectations. These teachers may focus too much on the emerging AI technologies rather than learning itself (Wu, Hou & Hwang, 2013). Additionally, from the perspective of students, AI technique may provide smart and efficient tools that cause -students to avoid doing the knowledge processing work that teachers expect them to do. For example, the AI translators may offer ready-made illustrations, pronunciation, fixed phrases, and even a serial of examples. Students are thus unwilling to engage in the inquiry processes that facilitate deep learning.

The ethical issues brought by AI are also challenging for both researchers and educational practitioners. It was clear that AI has made great strides over the past few years, mostly because of cheaper processing and the availability of data; however, individual student data may be exposed, shared, or used inappropriately. It is a constantly mindful challenge that educators and AI engineers will face when considering how we access, evaluate, and share the big data and the results of data analysis (Wu, Hou & Hwang, 2013 and Wang & Srinivasan, 2017). Another ethical debate was conspicuously found in gamification that emphasis should be put on learning and tend to suck the fun out of games, or on gameplay suck out the learning (Liu, Rus, & Liu, 2017).

Potential Gaps in Integrating Artificial Technology at Tertiary level of Education in Nigeria

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In order to take advantage of the benefits of AI, we also must be cognizant of the shortcomings. As an emerging edtech professional, Dr. Zeidan pays particular attention to the digital divide within technology. Not everyone has equal access to AI, internet, and devices. This became especially apparent during the pandemic when work and learning turned entirely to remote options. Moreover, AI is prone to biases. By nature of its construction, algorithms can reflect and reinforce biases that harm marginalized groups. AI is powerful, but it fails to understand cultural sensitivities and the personal experiences of users. Going forward, Dr. Zeidan stresses the importance of being aware of the gaps, strengths, and weaknesses within emerging tech. In the words of Morris (2023), he mentioned that: We do not want to widen the educational divide for already marginalized students

Potential Disruptions Caused by AI at tertiary level of Education in Nigeria

The widespread adoption of AI in higher education can lead to significant disruptions in traditional educational models. AI-powered platforms have the potential to replace certain teaching roles, such as grading assignments, providing feedback, and even delivering lectures through virtual instructors. Moreover, AI can enable personalized learning experiences for students. Intelligent systems can adapt to individual learning styles and provide tailored content and assessments, enhancing student engagement and outcomes.

Strategies to Adapt to Integration of artificial intelligence at tertiary level of Education in Nigeria

As higher education institutions navigate the evolving landscape of AI, it is crucial to develop strategies that allow them to adapt and harness the potential benefits. One strategy is to focus on up skilling and reskilling faculty and staff to ensure they possess the necessary skills to integrate AI into their teaching and administrative practices. Additionally, collaboration between academia and industry can foster innovation and help develop AI solutions that address specific educational challenges. By working together, institutions can better understand the potential applications of AI in education and develop effective implementation strategies (Zhai Chu, Chai, Jong, Andreja Istenic, Spector, Bao Liu, Jing Yuan, & Yan Li, 2021).

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Ethical Considerations in Implementing Artificial intelligence at tertiary level of education in Nigeria

While AI brings exciting possibilities to higher education, it is essential to consider the ethical implications associated with its implementation. Institutions must prioritize data privacy, transparency, and fairness when designing AI systems. Moreover, it is crucial to ensure that AI-powered systems do not perpetuate existing biases or discriminate against certain student populations. Regular audits and evaluations of AI algorithms can help identify and rectify any potential biases.

Conclusion

Based on the foregoing, the paper concludes that the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into tertiary education system can have significant impacts on students learning. AI-powered platform can provide intelligent tutoring, adaptive learning, virtual classrooms, making education more accessible and personalized learning. AI is an effective learning tool that lessens the burdens of both teachers and students and offers effective learning experiences for students. Coupled with current education reforms such as the digitalization of educational resources, gamification, and personalized learning experiences. However, too much reliance on AI tools such as ChatGPT among others can be a threats to education in tertiary institutions as it the potential for job displacement among academic staff rendering some job roles obsolete, making students to rely too heavily on AI which lead to lack of creativity and independent thinking, as well as reduced ability to analyze and interpret information without the assistance of AI.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made in the paper, that

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1. All stakeholders in education including curriculum planners and policy makers should provide a framework and guardrails on how AI should be apply in schools to assist teachers but not to replace them, but it should be an effective learning tool that lessens the burdens of both teachers and students and offers effective learning experiences for students.
2. It is crucial to practice cognitive hygiene. This involves consciously choosing when to engage AI and when to rely on your own cognitive processes.
3. There is a need to provide equal access to AI, internet, and devices to all learners at tertiary institutions.

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Effects of Cognitive Apprenticeship Instructional Strategy on Interest in Physics among Secondary School Students in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper compared the effect of the Cognitive Apprenticeship Instructional Strategy (CAIS) on secondary school students' interest in Physics in Apa Local Government Area of Benue State, Nigeria. This study also compared the effect of CAIS on the interest of male and female students in Physics. The study adopted the pre-test, post-test, control group quasi-experimental, and survey research designs. The sample consisted of 90 Senior Secondary School class One (SSS I) students selected during the 2024/2025 academic session in Apa Local government area of Benue State using a multi-stage sampling procedure. The Physics Students' Interest Questionnaire (PSIQ) was used for data collection. The Cronbach's Alpha (α) statistics were adopted to determine the reliability of PSIQ which yielded 0.81. The results showed that CAIS is an effective teaching strategy for improving secondary school students' interest (Post-test: $\bar{x} = 40.8140$, Pre-test: $\bar{x} = 16.6977$) in Physics. The findings have also shown that the CAIS is gender-neutral in improving students' interest (Male: $\bar{x} = 40.27$, Female: $\bar{x} = 41.11$) in Physics. Based on the findings of the study, it was concluded that the CAIS is effective in enhancing male and female secondary school Physics students' interest in Apa Local Government Area of Benue State. It was therefore recommended that teachers should receive training, workshops, and seminars on the use of CAIS to ensure effective implementation and to maximize its benefits.

Keywords: Cognitive Apprenticeship, Teacher Expository Teaching, Physics, interest

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Introduction

Colleges of Education (COEs) are the third tier of institutions of higher learning in Nigeria that are encumbered with the tasks of training pre-service teachers in courses that best equip such individuals for pedagogical activities in primary and secondary schools. This is intended to make them share the knowledge gained with society towards sustainable development. These institutions no doubt played critical roles in producing teachers of high moral and ethical standards to teach subjects that range from technical, science, business, social sciences, languages, and humanities at the Primary and Junior Secondary Schools (Ezugoh *et al.*, 2020).

Such contributions towards national development cannot be overstated just like the Universities and Polytechnics for they have in the past produced competent manpower for the education, economic, and social sustainability of the country. It is therefore a matter of serious concern noting that the (COEs) may no longer be meeting up to expectations, especially in rendering quality and efficient services that will lead to the achievement of educational goals due to myriads of challenges confronting the tier of Nigeria's education system. Owing to the foregoing, it is expected that COEs are meant to be functional and sustainable. Functionality and sustainability in this regard suggest that they have the required number of students in all the course combinations and an enabling environment for teaching, learning, and research.

It is a fact that Colleges of Education are faced with stark challenges in Nigeria. However, the case of the Federal College of Education, Odugbo seems to be different and in a dangerous trend due to low student enrolment. Aina and Ayodele (2018) submitted that there are many challenges confronting the Colleges of Education in Nigeria which include, teachers' inadequate pedagogical content knowledge, off-content teaching, and low teaching staff self-efficacy. According to the report, there has been a serious decline in students' enrolment among the colleges which could be attributed to the proliferation of private Colleges of Education, students' loss of interest, and inadequate infrastructure among others. Aina and Ayodele (2018) affirmed that the core of challenges confronting the Nigerian Colleges of Education is diminishing students' enrolment.

This may be traced to the loss of interest in colleges of education by the students among others. Meanwhile, interest which precedes readiness is key in whatever anyone attempts to do especially learning. Apart from a general loss of interest in learning

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among students nowadays, there seems to be a special odium for Colleges of Education which may be due partly to the social and economic status of teachers who are products of these schools in society. This may also have to do with the perception of teaching among society as an undesirably worthless profession which may likely be based on criticisms concerning the absence of professional autonomy, low wages, and poor condition of service.

Within the available students seeking admission to COEs, Sciences most especially Physics seem to be the worst hit in terms of low enrolment. Science education is one of the academic programs of the College of Education in Nigeria alongside Social Sciences, Languages, Arts, and Vocational Education. The prime challenge of this program has been low enrolment. Aina and Ayodele (2018) examined the case of five-year enrolment at Federal College of Education Technical, Lafajaji. It was observed that between 2012 and 2016, the data indicated that the enrolment trend decreased yearly. Overall, within the years under review, 3174 students enrolled in sciences where 2187 (68.9%) for Biology, 712 (22.4%) for Chemistry, and Physics had 275 (8.7%). This is suspected to be the trend in all the Colleges of Education in Nigeria to date.

The case of the Federal College of Education, Odugbo attests to this fact. In the 2022/2023 academic session which happened to be the maiden session, about 500 students applied for admission, it was a sad situation to see that no single student applied to study Physics and Chemistry. This infers that the school will not produce a single Physics teacher in its maiden convocation. Consequently, the society and most especially Apa Local Government Area Secondary School may have to contend with an acute shortage of Physics teachers shortly. This has been a source of concern for the researchers considering the impact of Physics on the individuals learning it, the society, and the world at large.

Agbaje and Alake (2014), in their study on the student variables as a predictor of secondary school students' academic achievement in science subjects, established that students' interest is vital to learning. They affirmed that there seems to be no more interest in students' learning, which might be why the enrolment of students reduces every year in the Colleges of Education. As a result of the loss of interest in the learning of Physics, students have developed a negative attitude towards the subject.

Studies in the past have attempted to find a lasting solution to this challenge with varying degrees of suggestions. Part of the suggested remedies was changing the

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teaching approaches employed by the teachers at the secondary schools. Meanwhile, what enhances students' interest in a subject could be the teacher's instructional strategies. When defining curricular priorities and pedagogical strategies, instructors should strive to promote discipline-based knowledge that ensures students move from novice to expert in a topic. The instructors teach domain-specific knowledge intending to assist students to skilfully organize the knowledge, and give chances for students to retrieve and use the knowledge in problem solving. Therefore, from a pedagogical standpoint, teachers understand what it means to be an expert in the topic and can identify the mechanisms that help students work toward acquiring competence and developing sustained interest.

There is no doubt that effective teaching strategies play a crucial role in enhancing students' academic achievement, raising interest in learning, and boosting confidence. Strategies like differentiated instruction, technology integration, and project-based learning can lead to better comprehension and retention of subject matter and the development of critical thinking. Efforts seem to be inclusive as to teaching strategies that could ultimately improve students' interest towards improved achievement in Physics to retain the students in the classroom.

One of such instructional strategy that is suspected to increase students' interest is the Cognitive Apprenticeship Instructional Strategy (CAIS). Cognitive apprenticeship was proposed by Brown *et al.*, (1989). It provides an opportunity for novices to observe how instructors or experts solve complex problems in an authentic context via the following steps:

- (a) **Modelling:** the experts demonstrate and explain their way of thinking for students to observe and understand;
- (b) **Coaching:** the students practice the methods, while the experts advise and correct;
- (c) **Scaffolding:** through increasing the complexity of problems and decreasing the level of assistance according to the student's progress, the experts progressively help the students successively approximate the objective of accomplishing a task independently;
- (d) **Articulation:** the students are given opportunities to articulate and clarify their way of thinking;
- (e) **Reflection:** the students compare their thoughts with those of experts and peers;
- (f) **Exploration:** the students manipulate and explore the learned skills or knowledge to promote their true understanding.

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Based on this teaching strategy, students can compare their problem-solving processes with those of an expert, another student, and ultimately, an internal cognitive model of expertise through the process of reflection. Analyzing past performances by both experts and novices and pointing out parallels and contrasts would be a reflection method. Reflection is to help students examine their past performances to comprehend and enhance expert conduct.

The cognitive apprenticeship model is a constructivist approach to teaching and learning based on the idea that learners should be actively engaged in their learning process. It is based on the idea that learners should learn by doing, and be actively involved in the activity. The core concept of this model was that learning involves the integration of the learner's cognitive skills with the knowledge, skills, and values of a mentor or master. The cognitive apprenticeship model suggests that learners should be actively involved in the learning process and that the role of the instructor is to provide support and guidance. The instructor should provide guidance on how to think about and solve problems, as well as provide feedback on the progress and performance of the learners. Employing a cognitive apprenticeship model encompasses the following three activities: Making processes visible to students; situating processes in real-world contexts, and varying tasks and information to foster transfer of learning to new and different situations.

There are equally certain challenges in developing academic interests in students most especially in Physics. Such challenges may include; limited teaching resources and opportunities, pressure to conform to expectations, the nature of the subject, inadequate exposure and awareness, competing interests and distractions, and self-doubt and uncertainties.

Research on students' interest in sciences is a broad and ongoing field of study. Numerous studies have been conducted to understand the factors that influence students' interest in mathematics and how it affects their learning outcomes. Peters-Burton *et al.*, (2015) examined how 19 secondary earth science and biology teachers' perceptions of inquiry, interest, motivation, and self-efficacy of teaching science were affected by a one-year professional development (PD) program based on a cognitive apprenticeship model of research experiences. A sample of 19 male and female in-service teachers were taught scientific thinking and inquiry skills using a cognitive

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apprenticeship paradigm. The findings showed that across every stage of the study, in-service male and female instructors maintained high levels of engagement and self-efficacy while also altering their views on inquiry. Teachers did not, however, alter their teaching of cognitive strategies in a long-term manner. Also, Olayanju et al., (2024) observed that the two models of cognitive apprenticeship (outside and inside school) had a significant impact on the interest of students in entrepreneurial skill development of PISTs in the two experimental groups.

Also, in a pre-test, and post-test quasi-experiment with a non-equivalent control group, Ogundola *et al.*, (2020) included students in intact classrooms in Ekiti State. All the 64 National Technical Certificate (NTC) II students pursuing fabrication and welding engineering craft practice made up the study's population and sample. There were 11 females and 15 males. The findings revealed that the mean achievement scores for males and females did not differ significantly. Conversely, Eze et al., (2020) where a pre-test, and post-test quasi-experimental method to investigate the effect of gender on students' academic achievement and retention in auto mechanic technology at technical colleges in Delta State, Nigeria. The study discovered that there was no significant difference in the interest and performance of male and female students taught auto mechanics technology using the cognitive apprenticeship teaching technique.

However, the study found that the gender-based differences in students' mean interest and retention scores were substantial. In a related development, Okotubu (2023) conducted a study motivated by a goal to boost male and female students' interest in automotive technology. The study sought to determine how the cognitive apprenticeship instructional technique affects students' interest in auto mechanics technology at Technical Colleges in Delta State. The study population consisted of 237 vocational II auto mechanic students from Delta State's six technical colleges. The study's sample size was 114 using a purposive sampling technique. The Auto Mechanic Interest Inventory (AMII) was utilized to collect data. The study found that students taught using the cognitive apprenticeship teaching approach were more interested in auto repair technology than students taught using the demonstration method. It also discovered that cognitive apprenticeship teaching does not differ by gender in terms of interest. Meanwhile, Collins (2005) has shown that the CAI model is carefully structured in the lesson, students will develop the capacity to apply the learned skills in new learning situations.

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Cognitive apprenticeship teaching has been confirmed to increase students' interest in technical-related subjects, there may therefore be a need to examine its influence on students' learning outcomes such as interest in Physics. Meanwhile, changing the teaching narratives involves evolving teaching strategies that directly impact student interests. It is expected that when the students' interest is ensured, there will be a propensity for them to enroll in Physics not only at the colleges of education but other tertiary institutions. This study was therefore set out using a comparative approach to examine the cognitive apprenticeship and students' interest in Physics at the secondary school level to leverage their sustained interest up till tertiary institution. Specifically, the study observed the distribution scores of male and female students' interests in Physics before the application of the Cognitive Apprenticeship Instructional Package (CAIP), examined the effect of the CAIP on secondary school students' interest in Physics, and, determined the effect of the package on male and female secondary school students' interest in Physics.

Statement of the Research Problem

The teaching and learning of Physics in secondary schools in Benue State, Nigeria, face numerous challenges, resulting in a widespread lack of interest among students. Despite its importance in understanding the natural world, Physics remains one of the most dreaded subjects in secondary schools, as students often perceive it as abstract, complex, and irrelevant to their everyday lives. Previous attempts to improve Physics education have seen little success.

Traditional teaching methods, which emphasize rote memorization and formulaic problem-solving, have failed to spark students' curiosity and enthusiasm for the subject. Consequently, there is a significant decline in students' interest in Physics, leading to poor academic performance and a shortage of qualified science graduates necessary for driving technological innovation and economic growth. The implications of this trend are extensive and concerning. The lack of interest in Physics at the Secondary School level creates a ripple effect, leading to the alarmingly low enrollment of students in Physics education programs at Colleges of Education throughout Nigeria. This, in turn, worsens the shortage of qualified Physics teachers, perpetuating a vicious cycle of decline in Physics education.

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The current situation is unsatisfactory, with Physics teachers struggling to make the subject relevant and engaging for their students. A pedagogical shift is therefore essential. The Cognitive Apprenticeship Instructional Strategy (CAIS) offers a promising solution. By modeling expert thinking, scaffolding learning, and encouraging reflective practice, CAIS has the potential to make Physics more accessible, interactive, and enjoyable for students.

Research has shown that CAIS can improve students' conceptual understanding, problem-solving skills, and motivation to learn Physics. However, its effectiveness in Benue State's secondary schools remains unexplored. This study seeks to investigate the effects of CAIS on interest in Physics among secondary school students in Benue State, to provide insights into the potential of this instructional strategy to revitalize Physics education in Nigeria and ultimately reverse the trend of low enrollment in Physics education programs.

Objectives of the Study

The following specific objectives guide the study:

1. Examine the mean interest scores of students taught Physics concepts using Cognitive Apprenticeship Instruction and those exposed to the conventional method in the Apa Local Government Area of Benue State.
2. Assess the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Physics concepts using Cognitive Apprenticeship Instruction and those exposed to the conventional method in the Apa Local Government Area of Benue State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the mean interest scores of male and female students in Physics before the intervention in the Apa Local Government Area of Benue State?
2. What are the mean interest scores of students taught Physics concepts using Cognitive Apprenticeship Instruction and those exposed to the conventional method in the Apa Local Government area of Benue State?
3. What are the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Physics concepts using Cognitive Apprenticeship Instruction in Apa Local Government area of Benue State?

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Hypotheses

Based on the research questions raised, the following hypotheses were formulated:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught Physics concepts using Cognitive Apprenticeship Instruction and those exposed to conventional methods in the Apa Local Government Area of Benue State.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Physics concepts using Cognitive Apprenticeship Instruction in the Apa Local Government Area of Benue State.

Methodology

The research designs adopted the non-equivalent pre-test, post-test, control group quasi-experimental, and survey. The population of the study consists of all Senior Secondary School class one (SS1) Physics students during the 2024/2025 academic session in Apa Local Government area of Benue State. The sample size of the study consists of 90 (Male = 44 & Female = 36) students selected from the target population using a purposive sampling technique. Two schools were purposively selected from the LGA. The basis for purposive selection was based on the availability of Physics teachers with a minimum of 5 years of teaching experience in Physics. One of the available arms of SSS I students was selected in each of the two schools using the random sampling technique. Each of the arms of students selected in their intact classes was randomly assigned to experimental groups A (Cognitive Apprenticeship) and control group B (Teacher Expository Teaching). Students in group A were taught using the Cognitive Apprenticeship Instructional Package (CAIP) developed by the researchers using the CAIS while students in their intact class using the Teacher Expository Teaching. One research instruments developed by the researchers were adopted for data collection for the study. An instrument titled Physics Students' Interest in Physics Questionnaire (PSIPQ). The PSIPQ consisted of carefully structured 4-point Likert items type that elicited the students' interest in Physics. The instruments were validated by science educators and tests and measurement experts from the Faculty of Education, Adekunle Ajasin University Akungba Akoko. The items in the instruments were thereafter modified based on the observations and comments of these experts. The instruments were pilot-tested by administering the instruments to a representative sample of 20 SSS II Physics students outside the population of the study. Cronbach's Alpha (α) for PSIPQ was 0.81. There were three stages involved in this research: the administration of the pre-test, the intervention stage, and the post-test stages. In the pre-test stage, PSIPQ was administered to the experimental and the control groups to

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ascertain the homogeneity of the respondents in terms of interest in Physics. The intervention was carried out by the researchers. The first week was for the administration of the pre-test. The treatment in all the groups covered three periods per week for four weeks. In the sixth week, a post-test which was PSIPQ was administered to the groups to determine the effect of the intervention on their interest in Physics. The research questions were answered using descriptive statistics of measures of frequency count, mean, and standard deviation while the hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean interest scores of male and female students in Physics before the intervention in Apa Local Government area of Benue State?

To answer the research question, responses of male and female students on interest in Physics prior to intervention were subjected to descriptive analysis and the results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Distribution of male and female Physics students' interest before the intervention using CAIS

		Group Pre-test on Interest in Physics		
		Total N	Mean	Standard Deviation
Gender Group A	Male	28	16.89	4.05
	Female	15	16.33	3.92
Gender Group B	Male	26	16.08	4.11
	Female	21	17.71	4.50

According to Table 1, male and female students in both experimental group A, and control group B in Physics had a similar interest in Physics (Group A; Male: $\bar{x} = 16.89$, Female: $\bar{x} = 16.33$), and (Group B: Male: $\bar{x} = 16.08$, Female: $\bar{x} = 17.71$). This revealed that Physics students' interest in Benue State is low and similar across the genders. This also infers that the students' entry characteristics into the experiment were homogenous and consistent across all groups.

Research Question 2: What are the mean interest scores of students taught Physics concepts using Cognitive Apprenticeship Instruction and those exposed to the conventional method in the Apa Local Government area of Benue State?

To address this research question, the pre-test and post-test students' interest in Physics in groups A and B were subjected to descriptive analysis and the results were presented in Table 2.

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Table 2

Mean and standard deviation of Physics students' interest in groups A and B when exposed to CAIS.

	Descriptive Statistics				
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean (\bar{x})	Std. Deviation
Group A Pre-test Interest	43	10.00	26.00	16.6977	3.96734
Group A Post-test Interest	43	32.00	48.00	40.8140	3.47272
Group B Pre-test Interest	47	8.00	26.00	16.8085	4.31700
Group B Post-test Interest	47	10.00	34.00	17.5745	4.62387

According to Table 2, the experimental group A students' post-test score ($\bar{x} = 40.8140$) is higher than the pre-test score ($\bar{x} = 16.6977$), whereas the control group B students' post-test score ($\bar{x} = 17.5745$) is comparable to the pre-test score ($\bar{x} = 16.8085$). This suggests that, when compared to students who were taught using the conventional method, students who were taught using the Cognitive Apprenticeship Instructional Package showed an improved interest in Physics and an increase in interest scores.

Research Question 3: What are the mean interest scores of male and female students taught Physics concepts using Cognitive Apprenticeship Instruction in Apa Local Government area of Benue State?

To address this research question, the post-test scores of male and female students' interests in Physics in groups A were subjected to descriptive analysis and the results were presented in Table 3.

Table 3

The post-test mean and standard deviation of male and female Physics students' interest in group A when exposed to CAIS

		Group A Post-test Interest		
		N	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation
Gender Group A	Male	28	41.11	3.41
	Female	15	40.27	3.63

According to Table 2, the post-test interest scores of the male ($\bar{x} = 40.27$) and female ($\bar{x} = 41.11$) students in experimental group A are comparable. This implies that there was no difference in the interest of male and female students who received instruction

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utilizing the Cognitive Apprenticeship Instructional Package, indicating that there is no gender bias in the Cognitive Apprenticeship Instructional Package at improving students' interest in Physics.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught Physics concepts using Cognitive Apprenticeship instruction and those exposed to conventional methods in Apa local government area of Benue State.

To test this hypothesis, the pre-test and post-test mean interest scores of students in the experimental group were subjected to t-test analysis and the results are presented in Table 4.

Table 4

The t-test analysis of students' interest scores in Physics using CAIP

Students' Interest	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	t	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Group A Pre-test	43	16.6977	3.96734	27.599	42	.000
Group A Post-test	43	40.8140	3.47272			

p<0.05

Table 3 shows the t-value as 27.599, which is extremely high. This indicates a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test interest scores being compared. The p-value of .000 also means that the probability of observing the difference (or more extreme) between the two groups by chance is extremely low (less than 0.1%). The extremely high t-value and very low p-value indicate a highly significant difference between the groups. In other words, the difference is statistically significant. Based on the t-test results, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant difference in the mean interest scores of students taught Physics concepts using Cognitive Apprenticeship instruction and those exposed to conventional methods in Apa local government area of Benue State is hereby rejected.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference in the Mean interest scores of male and female students taught Physics concepts using Cognitive Apprenticeship instruction in Apa local government area of Benue State.

To test this hypothesis, the post-test mean interest scores of male and female students in the experimental group were subjected to t-test analysis, and the results are presented in Table 4.

Table 5

The t-test analysis of male and female students' interest scores using CAIP

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Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	T	Df	Sig. (2-tailed)
Male	28	41.11	3.41	.738	27.210	.467
Female	15	40.27	3.63			

p<0.05

The t-test results from Table 5 indicate no statistically significant difference between male and female scores: t-value of .738, df: 27.210, Sig.: .046 greater than 0.05. This indicated no significant difference in the interest of male and female students in Physics when taught using CATS. In summary, the difference between male and female scores is not statistically significant. As such, the null hypothesis states that there is no significant difference in the Mean interest scores of male and female students taught Physics concepts using Cognitive Apprenticeship instruction in Apa local government area of Benue State. is hereby accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study which set out to examine how CAIP influenced students' interest in Physics suggested that when compared to students who were taught using the conventional method, students who were taught using the Cognitive Apprenticeship Instructional Package showed an improvement in their interest in Physics and an increase in interest scores. The finding corroborated Collins (2005) which showed that when the CAI model is carefully structured in the lesson, students will develop the capacity to apply the learned skills in new learning situations. This may tend to increase the interest of the students in studying Physics. It is therefore thoughtful that through cognitive modeling, students are exposed to higher-level thought processes while working with instructors and experts in cognitive apprenticeship methods. Students genuinely investigate novel concepts and come to conclusions by employing sophisticated reasoning techniques following the initial phases of assistance from teachers and specialists. Okotubu (2023) conducted a study motivated by a goal to boost male and female students' interest in automotive technology. The study sought to determine how the cognitive apprenticeship instructional technique affects students' interest in auto mechanics technology at technical colleges in Delta State. The study population consisted of 237 vocational II auto mechanic students from Delta State's six technical colleges. The study's sample size was 114. The purposive sampling technique was used to select two colleges among the six technical colleges. The Auto Mechanic Interest Inventory (AMII) was utilized to

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gather data. Three research experts validated the instrument. Cronbach Alpha was used to establish the reliability coefficient of the instrument, and a reliability coefficient of 0.81 was achieved. The study found that students taught using the cognitive apprenticeship teaching approach were more interested in auto repair technology than students taught using the demonstration method. It also discovered that cognitive apprenticeship teaching does not differ by gender in terms of interest. These findings were also in conformity with Olayanju et al., (2024) where it was observed that the two models of cognitive apprenticeship (outside and inside school) had a significant impact on the interest in entrepreneurial skill development of PISTs in the two experimental groups.

The findings of the study seeking to examine how CAIP influences male and female students' interest in Physics showed that there was no difference in the interest of male and female students who received instruction utilizing the Cognitive Apprenticeship Instructional Package, indicating that there is no gender bias in the cognitive apprenticeship Instructional Package at improving students' interest in Physics. the findings of this study were in line with Eze et al., (2020) where a pre-test, post-test quasi-experimental method to investigate the effect of gender on students' academic achievement and retention in auto mechanic technology at technical colleges in Delta State, Nigeria. The study discovered that there was no significant difference in the interest and performance of male and female students taught auto mechanics technology using the cognitive apprenticeship teaching technique. The findings of this study were at variance with the findings of Ogunlola et al., (2020) conducted a pre-test, post-test, non-equivalent control group quasi-experiment with students in intact classes. The population and sample consisted of all 64 National Technical Certificate (NTC) II students of fabrication and welding engineering craft practice in Ekiti State. There are 53 males and 11 females. Data was collected using two instruments: the fabrication and welding achievement test and the fabrication and welding interest inventory. It was found that the mean interest and retention scores of male and female students were significantly different. The findings also support Okotubu (2023) who found that students taught using the cognitive apprenticeship approach were more interested in auto repair technology than students taught using the demonstration method and that cognitive apprenticeship teaching does not differ by gender in terms of interest.

Conclusion

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Based on the analysis of data and the interpretation of the results of this study, it can be established that the Cognitive Apprenticeship Instructional Strategy (CAIS) is an effective teaching method that improves students' interest in Physics. It can further be concluded that CAIS is gender-neutral, as there was no significant difference in the interest of male and female students who received instruction using CAIS and CAIS is a better alternative to traditional teaching methods, such as the Teacher Demonstration Approach at increasing the enrolment of students in higher institutions as results of sustained interest in Physics from secondary schools.

Recommendations

Given the findings and conclusions reached in this study, it is hereby recommended that:

1. The Cognitive Apprenticeship Instructional Strategy (CAIS) should be adopted as a teaching method in Physics education, particularly in Benue State, to improve students' interest in Physics.
2. The Physics curriculum should be reviewed and aligned to incorporate CAIS, ensuring that it is integrated into the teaching and learning process.
3. The implementation of CAIS should be continuously monitored and evaluated to assess its effectiveness, identify areas for improvement, and make necessary adjustments.

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(Effect of Generative-Learning-Strategy on Achievement ... Tanko, K., Et al, 2025)

Effect of Generative-Learning-Strategy on Achievement in Probability Concept among Secondary School Mathematics Students in Sabon-Tasha Educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study investigated the Effect of Generative-Learning-Strategy on Achievement in probability concept among Secondary School Students in Sabon-Tasha educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria. The research design adopted for the study was quasi-experimental research design, specifically, pre-test, posttest experimental and control group design. The population of the study was 62,072 Secondary School class Two (SS II) Mathematics students in Sabon-Tashah Educational zone of Kaduna State. The sample of the study was 455 Mathematics students' drawn from four sample senior secondary schools through purposive sampling procedure. Two (2) research questions and corresponding null hypotheses guided the study. Probability Attitude Test (PAT) was used for data collection. The internal consistency of PAT was obtained using Kuder Richardson formula 20(KR-20), Hence, Reliability coefficients of 0.93 were obtained for the PAT. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions, while the null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. Results showed that Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) was more effective in improving students' academic achievement in Probability Concept than the Conventional Method of Teaching (CMT). The study concludes that the findings of this

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study demonstrate that the use of GLS significantly improves students' academic achievement probability concepts. GLS was also found to be gender friendly and the study recommended adequate training of teachers on the use of GLS for Nigerian Secondary Schools amongst others.

Keyword: Generative Learning Strategy, Attitude, Mathematics Concepts, Probability and Students

Introduction

Mathematics can be described as the study of space, time, sequence, pattern, structures, among others, in solving human problems. Ogbu (2020) opined that the high level of development of mathematics was assumed to have been sparked by the needs of the society and its competence is vital to everyone for meaningful understanding of things and situations. Anaduaka and Hassan (2017) viewed mathematics as the oldest field of study in the history of mankind and the most central component of human thought. Mathematics sharpens the mind, develops logical thinking and enhances the reasoning ability of an individual. Researchers, such as Cabe Roya (2010), Ogunleye and Babajide (2011) affirmed that the use of Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) is effective and results oriented. Hence, the use of Generative Learning Strategy as a means of improving students' achievement in mathematics through classroom activity aimed at enhancing students' greater comprehension and higher order thinking skills in mathematics is advocated.

Similarly, Adesoji (2008) defined students' achievement as the outcomes that reflect the extent to which an individual has attained a specific goal within instructional environments, particularly in schools, colleges, and universities. However, students' achievement should be viewed as a multifaceted construct encompassing various domains of learning. According to Okeke (2011), several criteria indicate students' achievement, including procedural and declarative knowledge acquired within an educational system. Consequently, there is a need to adopt Generative Learning Strategies to create a conducive and enriching environment that motivates, enhances attitudes, and improves students' achievement in the probability concept of mathematics at the senior secondary school level.

Gender as a factor needs to be investigated as one of the moderating variables in this study. School environment and educational facilities can make a great impact in terms of students' achievement in mathematics. This study therefore, was designed to investigate the effect of Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) on achievement

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in Probability Concepts among Secondary School Mathematics Students in Sabon-Tasha educational Zone, Kaduna State.

Statement of the Research Problem

The problem of poor attitude in mathematics has continued to resurface yearly in public examinations in Nigeria. The SSCE results released by WAEC and NECO have remained consistently poor and worrisome. The WAEC Chief Examiner's report identified probability concept as one of the students' areas of weaknesses. It further stated that the majority of the students attempted probability questions wrongly because of poor knowledge of the concept; inability to interpret problems involved the concept of probability, inability to read value from the problem which also involved the concept of probability. (WAEC, 2019; 2021 & 2022). Bababjide, 2011 and Amal & Elfateh, 2016). Their findings revealed that students exposed to Generative Learning Strategy performed better than their counterparts in the control group. Although a few studies on the use of Generative Learning Strategy have been carried out in the sciences in Nigeria, the extent of the use of Generative Learning Strategy has not been fully confirmed in the area of mathematics in Nigerian but elsewhere. Garba (2021) has shown that the use of probability concepts in teaching mathematics can improve students' academic achievement and retention in learning mathematics. This study therefore, is designed to examine the effect of Generative Learning Strategy on achievement of probability concept among Secondary School Mathematics students in Kaduna State.

Objectives of the study

The main purpose of this study was to examine the effect of Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) on achievement in Probability Concepts among Secondary School Mathematics Students in Sabon-Tasha educational Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria Specifically, the study sought to;

1. Determine the difference in the achievement of students taught probability using the Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) and those taught using the conventional teaching method in the Sabon-Tasha Educational Zone.
2. Investigate the difference in the achievement of male and female students taught probability using the Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) in the Sabon-Tasha Educational Zone.

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Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the difference in the achievement of students taught probability using the Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) and those exposed to conventional methods?
2. What is the difference in the achievement of male and female students taught probability using the Generative Learning Strategy (GLS)?

Null Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference in the achievement of students taught probability using Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) and those exposed to conventional methods in Sabon-Tashah Educational Zone.
2. There is no significant difference in the achievement of male and female students taught probability using Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) in Sabon-Tashah Educational Zone.

Research Design

The research design adopted for the study was quasi-experimental pretest posttest control group design. (Lauren Thomas, 2023) see quasi-experimental design as a useful tool in situations where true experiments cannot be used for ethical or practical reasons. This design is appropriate because the researcher assigned subjects to treatment and control conditions; but used intact classes to assign the groups so as to avoid the disruption of the normal class periods. The design was necessary also because it is appropriate for analyzing gain scores (i.e. the difference between pre-test and post-test scores) in addition to comparing scores. The layout of the design is shown below

EG → Q₁ → X₁ → Q₂ → Q₃: CG → Q₁ → - → Q₂ → Q₃

Where:

EG – Experimental Group

CG – Control Group

Q₁ – Represents the pre-test on the experimental group and Control group

Q₂ – Represent the post-test on the experimental group and Control group

X₁– Treatment for experimental group

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Q₃ – Retention test for experimental and control group

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised Sixty-two thousand and seventy-two (62,072) SS II students in all the 1,018 Government owned Senior Secondary Schools in Kaduna State. This comprises 29,057 male and 33,015 female SS II students (Kaduna State Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

The sample size of the study was 455 Senior Secondary II students drawn from four sampled schools (Government Senior Secondary School, Bagodo, Government Secondary School Kakuri, Government Secondary School Angwan Boro and Government Senior Secondary School, Narayi) within the study area. Four (4) schools from the educational zone (Kaduna South Local Government Area and Chikun South Local Government Area) that made up the study area were selected through random sampling method by balloting. This allowed for a fair chance of being selected.

Secondly, the four (4) schools were subjected to another round of balloting by picking from a container with four (4) papers was also tagged “YES” and others “NO” on squeezed pieces of paper for selection. Representatives of the four (4) Schools were allowed to pick on their behalf. The four (4) “YES” Schools were used for the research sample. Thirdly, two (2) schools out of the four (4) Schools were assigned to the experimental group (treatment group) while the last two (2) Schools formed the control group by random sampling (toss of coin).

The distribution of research subjects in their intact classes for this study is shown in Table 1:

Table 1: Sample Distribution

Group	Name of School	Male	Female	Total
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Experimental Group	GSS	Narayi	62	53	115
	GSS	Kakuri	67	51	118
Control Group	GSS	Bagodo	76	48	124
	GSS	U/Boro	57	41	98
Total			262	193	455

Instrumentation

The instruments that were used to collect data for the study was Probability Attitude Scale (PAS). Both instruments were constructed by the researcher and used as pre-test and post-test in the study. The PAS was of 20 items, 4-Options Multiple Choice Objective test based on the content of probability concept in in SS II Mathematics as shown in table of specification Probability Attitude Scale (PAS) was made up of two Sections: Section A contains Personal information and Section B contains Items and instruction for ticking the chosen response for each item. The PAS formed a 30 items Attitude Inventory developed by the researcher. It has a 4-point scale response. The responses are Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD).The respondents were expected to indicate the degree of their agreement and disagreement on a number of statements (positive or negative) equal cues about the units of study in probability concept.

Validity and Reliability of the Instruments

The PAS was validated by the experts in science education and Mathematics Education, Department of Science and Environmental Education, Faculty of Education, University of Abuja. Their validations were centered in terms of clarity of instruments, correct wordings of items, appropriateness and adequacy of the items in addressing the purpose and problem of the study. The experts' appraisal and comments were used to reform the items for the final package of the instrument used for the study. In measuring the reliability of the instruments for this study, the instruments: PAS were pilot tested using 15 SS II students of Government Secondary School Sabon-Tasha, Chikun LGA, Kaduna State who were part of the population but not part of the sample of the study. They were randomly selected. An hour was allowed for the test. The scripts were collated, marked and scored. Responses in PAS were also used to calculate the reliability coefficient of the PAS using Cronbach alpha procedures. The reliability coefficients for the PAS obtained was 0.92

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Procedure for Data Collection

The researcher personally visited the selected schools with letter of introduction collected from the Head of Department of Science and Environmental Education, University of Abuja, Abuja, Nigeria. The letter was given to the Principals and Head of Departments of the selected schools seeking permission to engage their students and mathematics teachers in a study. The researchers interacted with the students' and informed them of the purpose of the study and the benefits they are likely to gain from the study. Also, the consent form was issued to the participating students' and the teachers to indicate their willingness in the study in line with the standard of research practices.

The researcher trained the selected mathematics teachers as research assistants who touched the experimental group using GLS. The control groups were taught by mathematics teachers in the schools. The control group were taught without the use of GLS In the experimental group, the researcher grouped the students in the group heterogeneously based on their achievement in their terminal examination. The class consisted of five or six students in each group. The sitting arrangement was re-constructed in a semi- circular form to make it possible for the GLS learning and for the teacher to move across the groups. The seats were arranged for all the students to face the chalkboard. The students were assigned defined roles to two members of the group (group leader and the time keeper) while others served as secretary, in order to record what has been learnt in the group.

Method of Data Analysis

The six research questions were answered using Mean and Standard Deviation while the six null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 alpha level of significance using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA). The ANCOVA was appropriate for the study because it determined the differential effect of the treatment with the pretest scores as covariates to control the initial group difference. (comparing pretest scores with post-test scores to determine whether any significant difference occurs as a consequence of GLS and CMT). ANCOVA was appropriate for the study because it served as a procedure for increasing the precision due to extraneous variables that could have affected the external validity thus reducing error variance).

Answers to Research Questions

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Research Question One: What is the difference in the achievement of students taught probability using the Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) and those exposed to conventional methods?

To answer this research question, descriptive statistics was computed as recorded in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students’ achievement Pretest and Posttest Scores level by Learning Strategies (Experimental and control)

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean	Mean
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Gain	Difference
Experimental	233	24.72	1.93	30.00	3.91	5.28	3.21
Control	222	23.53	2.34	25.60	2.22	2.07	
Total	455	24.14	2.22	27.85	3.88		

Table 2 shows a mean achievement pretest level of 24.72 with a standard deviation of 1.93 for students taught probability concepts using generative learning Strategy and a Mean achievement Pretest level of 23.53 with a standard deviation of 2.34 for students taught using conventional method of teaching. As for the posttest, the table also shows a posttest mean achievement level of 30.00 with a standard deviation of 3.91 for students taught using generative learning strategy and a mean achievement level of 25.60 with a standard deviation of 2.22 for students taught using conventional method of teaching. The students taught probability concepts using generative learning strategy had a higher achievement mean gain level of 5.28 compared to their counterparts that were taught using conventional methods of teaching who had an achievement Mean gain level of 2.07. Students taught probability concepts using generative learning strategies had a higher achievement mean score in posttest than those taught using conventional methods of teaching probability concepts. The difference in mean achievement level of students taught using generative learning Strategy and those taught with conventional methods of teaching was 3.21. Hence there is a difference in students’ achievement to probability concepts when taught with GLS and when taught with CMT. Thus, those in experimental groups showed higher achievement than those in control groups.

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Research Question two: What is the difference in the achievement of male and female students taught probability using the Generative Learning Strategy (GLS)?

To answer this research question, descriptive statistics was computed as recorded in Table 3

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Students' achievement Pretest and Posttest Level by Gender

Gender	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain	Mean Difference
		Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
Male	262	21.6145	1.8425	29.1450	2.9894	7.53	0.38
Female	193	21.6373	1.8152	29.5440	3.2161	7.91	
Total	455	21.6242	1.8290	29.3142	3.0904		

Table 3 shows a Mean achievement Pretest level of 21.6145 with a Standard Deviation of 1.8425 for Male Students taught probability concepts using Generative Learning Strategy and a Mean achievement Pretest level of 21.6373 with a Standard Deviation of 1.8152 for Female Students taught using Generative Learning Strategy. The Posttest shows a Mean achievement level of 29.1450 with a Standard Deviation of 2.9894 for Male Students taught using generative learning Strategy and a Mean achievement of 29.5440 with a Standard Deviation of 3.2161 for Female Students taught using Generative Learning Strategy. This indicates that the Mean achievement level of Male and Female Students' taught probability concepts using generative learning Strategy was slightly different. This means that the Mean achievement level of Male and Female Students were not influenced by Students' gender. The difference in mean achievement level of male and students taught using generative learning strategy was 0.38

Test of Hypotheses

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the achievement of students taught probability using Generative Learning Strategy (GLS) and those exposed to conventional method in Sabon-Tashah Educational Zone:

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Table 4: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students' Tests Level by Generative Learning Strategy (Experimental and Control group)

Dependent Variable: Posttest Score

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	2205.869 ^a	2	1102.935	107.814	.000	S
Intercept	3058.765	1	3058.765	298.999	.000	S
Pretest	8.348	1	8.348	.816	.367	N.S
Attitude	2111.499	1	2111.499	206.402	.000	S
Error	4623.968	452	10.230			
Total	359752.000	455				
Corrected Total	6829.837	454				

a. R Squared = .323 (Adjusted R Squared = .320)

Table 4 shows the Analysis of Covariance test analysis carried out to determine whether students taught using GLS and those taught with CMT differed significantly in their attitude level in probability concepts. This test resulted in F-value 206.402 for the group (Experimental and Control group) is significant at .000 which is less than 0.05 ($p < .05$). Therefore, the null hypothesis stated was accepted. Thus, there is a significant difference in the achievement of students taught probability using GLS and those exposed to CMT. This implies that students taught with GLS had a higher attitude level than those that were taught with CMT.

HO₂: There is no significant difference in the mean attitude level of male and female students taught probability with GLS.

Table 5: Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) of Students' Test Level by Gender

Dependent Variable: Posttest Score

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.	Decision
Corrected Model	50.313 ^a	2	25.157	1.563	.211	N

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Intercept	3498.027	1	3498.027	217.340	.000	N.S
Pre	46.185	1	46.185	2.870	.091	N.S
Gender	7.225	1	7.225	.449	.503	N.S
Error	7274.821	452	16.095			
Total	367807.000	455				
Corrected Total	7325.134	454				

a. R Squared = .007 (Adjusted R Squared = .002)

Table 5 shows the Analysis of Covariance carried out to determine whether Male and Female Students taught probability concepts using GLS differed significantly in their attitude level in probability concepts. This test resulted in F-value .449 which is not significant at .503 which is above .001 ($p < 0.05$). The Null hypothesis as formulated was not rejected. This implies that there was no significant difference in the Mean attitude level of Male and Female Students taught probability concepts using GLS.

Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that the use of GLS significantly improves students' academic achievement probability concepts. Compared to the CTM, GLS proves to be more effective. This indicates that implementing GLS not only enhances students' performance but also positively influences their attitude toward probability concepts.

The effects of gender on mean attitude level, mean achievement score and mean retention score were not significant. Observed difference in attitude level, mean achievement score and retention score of students taught using GLS is due to chance not gender. However, contrary to conventional methods, GLS learning encourages learners to solve a particular problem or answer a central question using experience acquired from the GLS.

The GLS instruction helps learners to be actively involved in authentic, hands-on and natural learning in order to develop a new knowledge and apply the new knowledge to a new situation. Therefore, GLS is an appropriate strategy for teaching probability concepts.

Recommendations

On the basis of the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Since GLS is found to be an effective teaching strategy for improving student's mean achievement score, mean attitude score and mean retention score in

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- probability concepts, teachers should adopt it as a teaching strategy in Secondary Schools.
2. Bearing in mind the roles of workshops and seminars in the dissemination of knowledge and innovations, the researcher recommends that the Ministry of Education, MAN, STAN WAEC and JAMB should organize in-service training, workshops and seminars to equip teachers with necessary skills in the use of GLS.
 3. Authors and publishers of mathematics textbooks should include GLS in their texts for easy access for students and teachers and Curriculum planners also should include GLS in the Senior Secondary School mathematics Scheme for teachers and Students in order to enhance the participation, achievement, attitude and retention in students.
 4. Mathematics teachers should not introduce gender discrepancies when using GLS. They should as much as possible remove contents, instructional techniques and materials that may bring about gender differences in the teaching and learning of probability concepts.

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Application and Effectiveness of Artificial Intelligence Tools among Private Basic Schools' Teachers in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigated the application and effectiveness of artificial intelligence tools among private basic schools' teachers in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria. A correlation research design method was employed, the population of the study consists of all private basic schools' teachers during the 2024/2025 academic session in Ilorin west, Kwara state. A sample size of 200 teachers were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. A 10-item questionnaire (Artificial Intelligent Tools and Teachers' Effectiveness) on a four-point Likert scale was used to collect data. Two research questions and one hypothesis were generated and formulated to guide the study. The data obtained were analysed using mean and standard deviation on the research questions while Pearson product moment correlation Coefficient on hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The results showed a significant positive relationship between the application of artificial intelligence tools (AI) and teachers' effectiveness. The study concluded that AI can be a valuable tool for enhancing teachers' effectiveness in private basic schools. The findings of this study have implications for educational policymakers, school administrators, and teachers seeking to integrate AI into their instructional practices.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Teachers' Effectiveness, Private Basic Schools, Nigeria

Introduction

The integration of technology in education has become a significant aspect of modern teaching and learning. One of the most promising technologies in this regard is Artificial Intelligence (AI). AI refers to the development of computer systems that can

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perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as learning, problem-solving, and decision-making (Kurzweil, 2005).

In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the potential of AI to enhance teaching and learning in educational institutions. AI can be used to support teachers in various ways, such as automating administrative tasks, providing personalized feedback to students, and facilitating the development of adaptive learning systems (Baker, 2016).

Despite the potential benefits of AI in education, there is still a need for research on the effectiveness of AI in enhancing teachers' effectiveness. Teachers' effectiveness refers to the ability of teachers to facilitate student learning and achievement (Hattie, 2009). Effective teachers are those who are creating a supportive learning environment, providing clear instructions, and adapting their teaching to meet the needs of their students (Marzano, 2007).

In Nigeria, there is a growing need for effective teachers who can provide high-quality education to students. The country has a large population of students, and there is a shortage of qualified teachers in many schools (Federal Ministry of Education, 2017). The integration of AI in education could potentially help to address this challenge by providing teachers with the tools and resources they need to enhance their effectiveness.

This study aims to investigate the relationship between the application of AI and teachers' effectiveness in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria. The study will explore the ways in which AI tools can be used to support teachers in their work and examine the impact of AI on teachers' effectiveness.

Literature Review

Artificial Intelligence (AI)

Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to the development of computer systems that can perform tasks that typically require human intelligence, such as learning, problem-solving, and decision-making (Kurzweil, 2005). AI has been increasingly used in various fields, including education, to improve teaching and learning outcomes (Baker, 2016).

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In education, AI can be used to support teachers in various ways, such as automating administrative tasks, providing personalized feedback to students, and facilitating the development of adaptive learning systems (Baker, 2016). AI-powered tools can also help teachers to identify areas where students need extra support and provide targeted interventions to improve student learning outcomes (Dziuban et al., 2018). Oloyede, 2024, stated “In the academia, many of us traditionally relied on human research assistants and proofreaders to improve the quality of our work. However, with the use of AI, these roles are increasingly being complemented or even replaced by AI tools. This brings significant benefits in terms of efficiency, but it also raises questions about the need for policies to guide the use of AI within university.” AI tools can improve academic output by spotting errors, suggesting better phrasing and helping with complex analyses (Oloyede, 2024).

There are several types of AI, including:

- i. Narrow or Weak AI: Designed to perform a specific task, such as facial recognition or language translation.
- ii. General or Strong AI: Designed to perform any intellectual task that a human can, such as reasoning, problem-solving, and learning.
- iii. Super intelligence: Significantly more intelligent than the best human minds, potentially leading to exponential growth in technological advancements (Bostrom, 2014).

Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools that appropriate for teachers to use in teaching

1. Adaptive Learning Systems: These systems use AI to adjust the difficulty level of course materials based on individual students' performance. Examples include DreamBox, Curriculum Associates, and McGraw-Hill's ALEKS.
2. Virtual Teaching Assistants: These AI-powered tools can help teachers with tasks such as grading, providing feedback, and answering student questions. Examples include Georgia Tech's Jill Watson and Stanford's Rachel.
3. Intelligent Tutoring Systems: These systems use AI to provide one-on-one support to students, offering real-time feedback and guidance. Examples include Carnegie Learning's Cognitive Tutor and Pearson's Write To Learn.

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4. Natural Language Processing (NLP) Tools: These tools can help teachers analyze and provide feedback on student writing and communication. Examples include Turnitin's Feedback Studio and Grammarly's Writing Assistant.
5. AI-powered Learning Management Systems: These systems use AI to help teachers manage their courses, track student progress, and identify areas where students need extra support. Examples include Canvas, Blackboard, and Moodle.
6. Chatbots: These AI-powered tools can help teachers provide support to students outside of class, answering questions and providing guidance on course materials. Examples include IBM's Watson Assistant and Microsoft's Bot Framework.
7. AI-powered Assessment Tool: These tools can help teachers create and grade assessments, providing detailed feedback and analysis of student performance. Examples include ETS's AI-powered Assessment Platform and Pearson's AI-powered Testing Platform.
8. Personalized Learning Platforms: These platforms use AI to provide personalized learning recommendations to students, based on their individual strengths, weaknesses, and learning styles. Examples include Knewton's Adaptive Learning Platform and Dream Box's Math Platform.
9. AI-powered Classroom Management Tools: These tools can help teachers manage their classrooms, track student behavior, and identify areas where students need extra support. Examples include ClassDojo and Remind.
10. AI-powered Professional Development Tools: These tools can help teachers develop their skills and knowledge, providing personalized learning recommendations and feedback. Examples include IBM's Teacher Advisor and Microsoft's Educator Community

AI Applications

AI has various applications in education, including: Adaptive learning systems, intelligent tutoring systems, Automated grading and feedback, Natural language processing

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Benefits of AI

AI can benefit teachers' effectiveness in several ways, including:

- i. Automating administrative tasks and grading
- ii. Providing personalized feedback and assessment
- iii. Facilitating adaptive learning and instruction
- iv. Enhancing teacher-student relationships and communication

Teachers' Effectiveness

Teachers' effectiveness refers to the ability of teachers to facilitate student learning and achievement (Hattie, 2009). Effective teachers are those who are creating a supportive learning environment, providing clear instructions, and adapting their teaching to meet the needs of their students (Marzano, 2007).

Research has shown that teachers' effectiveness is a critical factor in determining student learning outcomes (Hattie, 2009). Effective teachers can improve student achievement, increase student motivation, and enhance student engagement (Marzano, 2007).

Private Basic Schools

Private basic schools refer to schools that provide basic education to students and are owned and operated by private individuals or organizations (National Bureau of Statistics, 2019). Private basic schools play an important role in providing education to students, particularly in areas where public schools may not be available or accessible (National Bureau of Statistics, 2019).

In Nigeria, private basic schools are becoming increasingly popular, particularly in urban areas (National Bureau of Statistics, 2019). However, there is a need for research on the effectiveness of private basic schools in Nigeria, particularly in terms of the quality of education provided (Adeyemi, 2018).

Private basic schools often have distinct characteristics, including:

- i. Autonomy in curriculum design and implementation
- ii. Flexibility in teaching methods and approaches

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- iii. Emphasis on academic excellence and achievement
- iv. Limited government regulation and oversight

Relationship between AI and Teachers' Effectiveness

Research has shown that AI can be a valuable tool for enhancing teachers' effectiveness (Baker, 2016). AI-powered tools can help teachers to automate administrative tasks, provide personalized feedback to students, and facilitate the development of adaptive learning systems (Baker, 2016).

In addition, AI can help teachers to identify areas where students need extra support and provide targeted interventions to improve student learning outcomes (Dziuban et al., 2018). AI can also help teachers to develop more effective teaching strategies, and to improve their overall teaching practice (Hartley, 2017).

However, there is a need for more research on the relationship between AI and teachers' effectiveness, particularly in the context of private basic schools in Nigeria (Adeyemi, 2018).

Factors: Several factors contribute to teachers' effectiveness, including:

- i. Teacher-student relationships
- ii. Instructional strategies
- iii. Classroom management
- iv. Feedback and assessment

Measures: Teachers' effectiveness can be measured using various methods, including:

- i. Student achievement data
- ii. Teacher evaluations
- iii. Classroom observations
- iv. Student surveys

Statement of the Research Problem

Despite the growing importance of technology in education, many private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria, are yet to fully harness the potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to enhance teachers' effectiveness. The lack of understanding of how

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AI can be used to support teaching and learning, coupled with the limited availability of AI-powered tools and resources, has hindered the effective integration of AI in these schools. As a result, teachers in these schools may not be able to provide high-quality education to their students, which can negatively impact student learning outcomes. Therefore, this study seeks to investigate the relationship between the application of AI and teachers' effectiveness in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria."

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the relationship between the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and teachers' effectiveness in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria. Specifically, this study aims to:

1. Examine the level of awareness and understanding of AI among teachers in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria.
2. Investigate the extent to which AI is being used to support teaching and learning in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria.
3. Determine the relationship between the application of AI and teachers' effectiveness in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the conduct of the study:

1. What is the level of AI tools awareness among teachers in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria?
2. What is the extent of AI tools utilization and teachers' effectiveness in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria?

Research hypothesis

The following hypothesis was formulated to guide the conduct of this study.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the use of AI tools and teachers' effectiveness in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria.

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Methodology

The study adopted correlation research design. The population of the study comprised the private basic schools in Ilorin west local government of Kwara state, the rationale for choosing correlation research survey was to establish if a significant relationship exists between the use of AI tools and teachers’ effectiveness in private basic schools in Ilorin west local government in Kwara state. Cohen and Manion (2009), correlation design aimed at determining the nature, degree and direction of relationship between variables or using the relationship for predictions. The population of the study consists of all private basic schools’ teachers during the 2024/2025 academic session in Ilorin west, Kwara state. A sample size of 200 teachers were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique.

Two research designed instruments namely ‘Artificial Intelligent Tools Questionnaire’ (AITQ) and Teachers’ Effectiveness Questionnaire’ (TEQ) were used for the study. The questionnaire was thoroughly assessed by the experts while the reliability index of 0.82 and 0.76 were obtained for the instruments using test-re-test method. The data obtained were analysed using mean and standard deviation for the research questions and Pearson product moment correlation coefficient for the research hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results:

Research Question 1: What is the level of AI tools awareness among teachers in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria?

Mean and Standard Deviation of the Level of AI among teachers in private basic schools Ilorin West Local government, Kwara State, Nigeria

Table 1

S/N	Teachers	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	Aware	160	3.51	0.64	High
2.	Not Aware	40	1.42	0.28	Low
	Total	200			

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Key: \bar{X} , 1.00-1.99 Low; 2.00-2.99 Moderate, 3.00-4.00 High

Table 1 explains the mean and standard deviation of the level of AI awareness among the teachers in the in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria. It was discovered that teachers that aware of AI tools had mean score of 3.51 while teachers that are not aware had 1.42 respectively. Therefore, the mean score of 3.51 of teachers that aware of AI tools clearly shows that the level of AI awareness in the private basic schools in Ilorin west local government in Kwara state, Nigeria was high.

Research Question 2: What is the extent of AI tools utilization and teachers' effectiveness in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria?

Mean and Standard Deviation of the Level of utilization of AI among teachers in private basic schools Ilorin West Local government, Kwara State, Nigeria

Table 2

S/N	Variables	N	\bar{X}	SD	Decision
1.	Lesson Plan	200	3.51	0.38	High
2.	Questions setting	200	3.42	0.36	High
Grand Mean			3.46	0.37	High

Key: \bar{X} , 1.00-1.99 Low; 2.00-2.99 Moderate, 3.00-4.00 High

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of the level of AI utilization among teachers in the in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria. It was discovered that lesson plan and questions setting with the use of AI tools had mean scores of 3.51 and 3.42 respectively as such is considered high. Therefore, the grand mean of 3.46 shows that the level of AI utilization among teachers in the in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria. was high.

Test of Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the use of AI tools and teachers' effectiveness in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria.

AI tools and teachers' effectiveness in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria.

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Table 3

Variable	N	\bar{X}	SD	r-value	p-value	Decision
AI Tools	200	2.61	0.073			
Teachers' Effectiveness	200	1.82	0.61	0.655	0.034	Ho₁ Rejected

P-value < .05

Table 3 shows the calculated r-value (0.655) while the p-value (0.034) is less than the significance level (0.05). Therefore, the null hypothesis (Ho) is rejected. This means that there was a significant relationship between AI tools and teachers' effectiveness in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria. The positive relationship indicates a positive relationship between the two variables, that is, the improvement in the use of AI in teaching and learning will also greatly improve the teachers' effectiveness. This is in line with the submission of Marzano (2007), effective teachers are those who are able to create a supportive learning environment, provide clear instructions, and adapt their teaching to meet the needs of their students. The finding supports the opinion of Baker (2016), that AI can be used to support teachers in various ways, such as automating administrative tasks, providing personalized feedback to students, and facilitating the development of adaptive learning systems.

Conclusion

A significant relationship existed between AI tools and teachers' effectiveness in private basic schools in Ilorin West, Kwara State, Nigeria. The study revealed that the level of AI awareness to the staff in private basic schools in Ilorin west local government, Kwara state was high and the level of utilization of AI tools by the teachers was also high therefore, the level of teachers' effectiveness in private basic schools in the Ilorin west local government was high. Achieving teachers' effectiveness private basic schools in

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Ilorin west local government, Kwara state can be traced to the effective use of AI tools in the process of teaching and learning.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. School administrators in private basic schools in Ilorin west local government, kwara state, should ensure that teachers make adequate use of artificial intelligent tools in order to achieve effectiveness in the school system.
2. School administrators in private basic schools in Ilorin west local government, kwara state, should sensitize teachers on the importance use of artificial intelligent tools in the teaching and learning process.

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Correlation between Self-Efficacy and Choice of Career among Colleges of Education Mathematics Students in Kano State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the relationship between self-efficacy and choice of career among Colleges of Education Mathematics students in Kano State, Nigeria. Three research questions with their corresponding hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study adopted a correlational research design. The population of the study was one hundred thirty-two NCE I Mathematics student-teachers as at 2019/2020 session. All the NCE I student-teachers participated in the study. Mathematics Student-Teachers Self-Efficacy Scale (MSTSES), adapted from the work of Usher and Pajares (2009), was the instrument used for the study. MSTSES was valid and reliable with a Cronbach Alpha of 0.84. Apart from demographic information, the instrument consists of 20 items designed based on the four sources of self-efficacy. The research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation. While the hypotheses were tested at the 0.05 level of significance and analyzed using Point-Biserial correlation and Pearson product moment correlation, based on the findings, it was concluded that student-teachers' self-efficacy was low, and there was no significant correlation between the student-teachers' self-efficacy and teaching careers. The study recommends that students' self-efficacy in Mathematics and a Mathematics teaching career should be considered before they were admitted into teacher education programs.

Keywords: Mathematics, Self-efficacy, Student-teachers, Mathematics Teaching Career.

Introduction

Despite the importance and numerous applications of Mathematics within and outside the context of science and technology, students-teachers have learning difficulties in the subject, which leads to low Mathematics ability and low self-efficacy among the students. Mathematics is the basic foundation for a good understanding of not only sciences and technologies but also social and management sciences. Unfortunately, an alarming rate of low achievement, negative attitude, anxiety, and poor skills and abilities among student-teachers has been observed. Mathematics in general is one of the most challenging subjects for almost every student in Nigeria. Many student-

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teachers in tertiary institutions or universities were admitted to study Mathematics as their last option, which was by necessity (Odiri 2020).

Student-teachers are teachers in training in either colleges of education or universities. Pre-service and in-service teachers are the two types of student-teachers. Pre-service student teachers are newly admitted into teacher training programs, and they have no teaching experience. While in-service teachers were already employed in the teaching system and re-admitted to further their study. This study referred to student-teachers that have no teaching experience and are newly admitted to pursue an NCE (National Certificate in Education) certificate in colleges of education. The colleges of education were among the teacher-training institutions responsible for training teachers (Awofala et al. 2020). The main purpose of the colleges of education is to produce non-graduate as well as well-grooming teachers that can teach in primary, junior, and some courses in senior secondary schools due to the insufficient number of Mathematics teachers (National Commission for Colleges of Education [NCCE] 2012). Unfortunately, looking at the student-teachers' results, one may wonder what they will teach as future teachers.

Self-efficacy theory is based on students' beliefs about their abilities to meet high levels of task difficulty in order to achieve specific goals (Bandura, 1994; Segarra, & Julià, 2022). "Belief is an individual's capability to organize and execute the course of action required to provide attainment," Bandura stated. Self-efficacy is the confidence or belief in an individual's capability to perform a given task successfully (Benaoni 2016). Self-efficacy is not a learned skill; it is concerned with students' beliefs about their abilities to mastermind and strategize skills, and abilities in challenging situations (Segarra & Julià, 2022).

Mathematics self-efficacy refers to students' beliefs and abilities regarding Mathematics as a subject (Kouli 2021). It is the student's assessment of what they are capable of doing mathematically. Ampofo (2019) stresses that students' self-efficacy in Mathematics indicates the students' competence and efficiency to perform mathematical tasks successfully, and Gao (2020) affirmed that student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics has a significant impact on their academic achievement. Self-efficacy defines students' emotional feelings, interest, and thinking toward their Mathematics learning (Prince 2017; Simamora et al., 2019).

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Existing literature indicates that students' self-efficacy in Mathematics is a serious issue that requires the attention of all educational stakeholders (Prince 2017; Xu & Qi 2019); otherwise, Mathematics education will collapse, as seen in Nigeria. Understanding self-efficacy and how it affects student learning and their problem-solving ability could enhance students' Mathematical ability, interest, self-esteem, academic achievement, and retention in Mathematics (Köseolu 2015; Recber et al., 2018; Ampofo 2019; Simamora et al., 2019; Gao 2020).

Implicating this theory into the current situation of teaching and learning Mathematics in Nigeria, it can be observed that the self-efficacy of Mathematics teachers in the country is very low because their success is assessed through their students' end results, while every year students achieve poorly in Mathematics national examinations. And research by Kouli (2021) revealed that the higher the Mathematics teachers' self-efficacy, the higher the students' academic achievement in Mathematics.

Linking the theory with mathematical ability, student-teachers' low Mathematics ability and skills are influenced by their lack of or low self-efficacy in Mathematics, which in turn affects their career as future Mathematics teachers. It has been noticed that there is a decline in student-teachers' mathematical ability, confidence, and academic achievement (Mman & Tudunkaya, 2019). Which is the result of low Mathematics self-efficacy among the student-teachers. Literature shows that there are four sources of self-efficacy (Usher & Pajares 2009): mastery experience, vicarious experience, social persuasion, and physiological and emotional state.

Mastery experience; some researchers called it performance experience because it deals with the students' performance or achievement in a certain mathematical task. Mastery experiences typically occur when students succeed or fail in a mathematical task; this allows students to determine their belief in their ability to perform better in their Mathematics courses (Kouli, 2021).

Vicarious experience typically refers to how students perceive the academic skills of career role models, teachers, parents, older students, or classmates (Usher & Pajares 2009). Students can develop Mathematics self-efficacy by seeing or observing someone who demonstrates Mathematics competency. Through vicarious experience, students learn from their relatives, which influences their self-efficacy beliefs (Gao 2020).

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Gao (2020) believes that social persuasion can affect mastery and vicarious experience as a source of self-efficacy. Students' interactions with others, such as parents, teachers, peers, and/or community members, influence their self-efficacy positively or negatively. Students with low self-efficacy in Mathematics can be affected through interaction with others that have a high level of Mathematics self-efficacy (Kouli 2021).

Physiological and emotional state is the fourth source of self-efficacy; when students physically and emotionally feel contented or satisfied with a given Mathematics task, this stimulates the students' self-efficacy toward the subject (Bandura 1994). Also, when students are upset psychologically with Mathematics anxiety, phobia, or pain while attempting to complete a mathematical task, this will stimulate the student's self-efficacy negatively.

Going by the reviewed literature, all four sources can affect student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics, as research has revealed (Peker 2016, Prince 2017, Reyes 2019, Kouli 2021). Mathematics teacher educators and researchers need to pay attention to student teachers' self-efficacy as they are the future Mathematics teachers. Also, Mathematics teacher educators need to be careful to display their passion for teaching and learning Mathematics as it relates to the student-teachers' self-efficacy in teaching the subject in the future.

Benaoui (2016) conducted a study on "The Impact of Self-Efficacy in Mathematics on Urban High School Graduates' Math Performance." The findings of the study showed that only two of the four sources of self-efficacy, performance experiences and physiological and emotional state, were found to be statistically significant factors that influence students' performance, while vicarious experiences and verbal persuasion were not significant. Unsal et al. (2016) conducted a study on "Analysis of Mathematics Teachers' Self-Efficacy Levels Concerning the Teaching Process." The study was conducted in Turkey during the second term of the 2015–2016 academic year. The researchers concluded that Mathematics teachers stated opinions on having high self-efficacy beliefs concerning the teaching process, and these opinions differed based on gender and year of service. Ampofo (2019) examined the relationship between pre-service teacher's perceived self-efficacy in teaching Mathematics and their achievement in Mathematics. A descriptive design was used for the study. The study's population was pre-service teachers, with a sample size of forty students from Kibi College of Education, 47.5% of whom were male and 52.5% of whom were female. Data was

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collected through a Mathematics self-efficacy scale (MSES) questionnaire and a Mathematics achievement test (MAT). The findings of the study showed a relationship between the pre-service teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and their achievement in Mathematics.

Hence, with the main goals of Mathematics educators being to improve students' mathematical ability, especially student-teachers, who will be the future Mathematics educators, this study aimed to investigate the influence of self-efficacy on student-teacher's careers in Mathematics teaching.

Statement of the Research Problem

In decade, most researches were conducted on Mathematics teachers' professionalism, content knowledge, and pedagogical skills, but little attention is given to aspects like self-efficacy and career choice that can directly or indirectly affect the effectiveness, efficiency, and sustainability of teaching and learning Mathematics, this become the basis of this study. Because the student-teachers' ability and beliefs stimulate their Mathematics learning and values, which allow the student-teachers to engage or not engage in the study of Mathematics.

Objectives of the Study

This research work was designed to attain the following objectives, i.e.,

1. Determine the level of student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics.
2. Find out the relationship between the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and their Mathematics teaching career.
3. Examine the relationship between Mathematics student teachers' self-efficacy and gender.

Research Questions

This research work was designed to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the mean score of the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics?
2. What is the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics teaching career?
3. Is there any difference in the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and gender?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were developed based on the research questions highlighted and tested at the 0.05 level of significance.

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- H₀₁: There is no significant relationship in the student-teachers' response between the sources of self-efficacy in Mathematics.
- H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between student-teachers' Mathematics self-efficacy and their career choices in Mathematics education.
- H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between student-teacher self-efficacy and gender differences.

Methodology

A correlational research design was adopted for the study because it focuses on the relationship between student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and the Mathematics teaching career. The population of the study consists of all level I00 (NCE I) student-teachers offering Mathematics as a teaching subject in Kano State's own colleges of education, a total of one hundred thirty-two (132) student-teachers as of the 2019/2020 academic session. All the population participate in the study. So, the sample size was one hundred thirty-two (132) Mathematics student-teachers, consisting of 75 males and 57 females. Census sampling technique was employed.

The instrument used for data collection was the Mathematics student-teacher self-efficacy scale (MSTSES). MSTSES was adapted from the work of Usher and Pajares (2009), validated by experts, where construct and face validity were emphasized in the validation assessment. The items were adjusted, and some were reconstructed based on the suggestions of the experts. The MSTSES was pilot tested for reliability purposes, and the internal consistency using Cronbach's alpha was found to be 0.84, which shows the MSTSES is valid and reliable.

The data collected were analyzed using the mean and standard deviation to answer the research question. The rule used to distinguish between an accepted and an unaccepted mean was the average of the four-point grading scale, which is 2.50. A mean score of 2.50 or higher is acceptable, while a score of less than 2.50 is not. While the hypotheses were tested using point-bi-serial and Pearson product moment correlation, SPSS software, version 22, was used for the analysis.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1

What is the mean score of the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics?

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**Table 1: Descriptive Statistics of the Student-teachers' Response on Self-efficacy.
 N=132**

Scales Items	Mean	SD	Decision
Mastery experience			
1 I make excellent grades on Mathematics tests.	1.57	0.65	Not Accepted
2 I have always been successful with Mathematics.	1.92	0.72	Not Accepted
3 Even when I study very hard, I perform poorly in Mathematics	1.59	0.83	Not Accepted
4 I got good grades in Mathematics on my last report card.	1.70	0.52	Not Accepted
5 I do well on math assignments.	1.57	0.65	Not Accepted
Vicarious Experience			
6 Seeing colloquies do well in Mathematics pushes me to do better.	1.76	0.72	Not Accepted
7 When I see how my Maths teacher solves a problem, I picture myself solving the problem in the same way.	1.84	0.73	Not Accepted
8 Seeing kids do better than me in Math encourage me to do better.	1.73	0.69	Not Accepted
9 When I see how another student solves a math problem, I can see myself solving the problem in the same way.	1.81	0.39	Not Accepted
10 I imagine myself working through challenging Maths problems successfully.	1.08	0.28	Not Accepted
Social Persuasion			
11 My math teachers have told that I am good at learning math.	1.41	0.55	Not Accepted
12 People have told me that I have a talent for math.	1.86	0.48	Not Accepted
13 Adults in my family have told me what a good math student I am.	1.43	0.55	Not Accepted
14 I have been praised for my ability in math.	1.65	0.63	Not Accepted
15 Other students have told me that I'm good at learning math.	1.59	0.68	Not Accepted
Physiological and Emotional State			
16 Just being in Maths class makes me feel stressed and nervous.	3.00	0.88	Accepted
17 Doing Maths work takes all of my energy.	1.16	0.44	Not Accepted
18 I start to feel stressed-out as soon as I begin my math work.	3.11	0.81	Accepted
19 My mind goes blank and I am unable to think clearly when doing Maths work.	2.35	0.85	Not Accepted
20 I get depressed when I think about learning Mathematics.	2.62	0.86	Accepted

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Table 1 shows the student-teacher’s responses to each of the four sources of self-efficacy in Mathematics. It is observed that the mean score of the responses in mastery experience, vicarious experience, and social experience is far below 2.50, and only in physiological and emotional state, the mean of three items accepted. This revealed that the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics is low.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship in the student-teachers’ response between the sources of self-efficacy in Mathematics.

Table 2: Point-Biserial Correlation of the Student-teachers Response between the Four Courses of Self-Efficacy. N=132

		Mastery Experience	Vicarious Experience	Social Persuasion	Physiological and Emotion State
Mastery Experience	r	1			
	Sig.				
Vicarious Experience	r	-.149	1		
	Sig.	.189			
Social Persuasion	r	.362*	-.348*	1	
	Sig.	.014	.017		
Physiological and Emotion State	r	.145	.293*	-.214	1
	Sig.	.196	.039	.101	

*significant correlation

The relationships between the student-teacher’s responses to the four sources of self-efficacy are shown in Table 2. The relationships between mastery and vicarious experiences is negative ($r(132)=-.149$; $\text{Sig}=.189$), indicating that $\text{Sig} > .05$; there is also no correlation between mastery and physiological or emotional state ($\text{Sig}=.196$), but there is a significant correlation between the student-teacher's response to mastery experience and social persuasion ($r = .362$; $\text{Sig}=.014$), indicating that $p < .05$. Another significant correlation is observed between vicarious experience and social persuasion ($r = -.348$; $\text{Sig}=.017$; and $r = -.293$; $\text{Sig} = .039$; respectively); this indicates that $P < .05$. Finally, there is no correlation between social persuasion and physiological or emotional state ($r = -.214$; $\text{Sig}=.101$), which implies that $\text{Sig} > .05$.

Research Question Two

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What is the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics teaching career?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics of the Student-Teachers Mathematics Self-Efficacy and Teaching Career.

Career Choice	N	Student-teachers' Self-Efficacy		Mean Diff.	Remark
		Mean	SD		
Mathematics Teaching Career.	31	37.50	3.89	.30	Insignificance
Other Careers.	101	37.80	2.77		

Table 3 shows the mean and standard deviation of student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics related to teaching career. According to the table, the number of student-teachers who chose Mathematics teaching as a career was thirty-one (31) with a mean of 37.50 with a standard deviation of 3.89. While one hundred and one (101) student-teachers with a mean of 37.80 and a 2.77 standard deviation reported that Mathematics teaching was not their career choice, a mean difference of 0.30 was found in favor of student-teachers who didn't choose Mathematics teaching as their career. However, the number of those whose Mathematics is not their career choice is larger than those who choose Mathematics teaching as their career.

Hypothesis 2

There is no significant relationship between student-teachers' Mathematics self-efficacy and their career choices in Mathematics education.

Table 4: Pearson Correlation between Student-teachers Self-Efficacy and their Career Choice.

Student-teachers'	N	Mean	SD	r	Sig.	Decision
Self-Efficacy	132	37.50	3.89	.039	.409	Accept Hypothesis
Teaching Career	132	37.80	2.77			

Pearson product moment correlation (PPMC) in Table 4 revealed that there is no relationship between student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and their choice of teaching career ($r = .039$, $\text{Sig.} = .409$), which indicates that $\text{Sig.} > .05$. Hence, the null hypothesis is accepted, stated that there is no relationship between student teachers' self-efficacy and their career choice.

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Research Question Three

Is there any significant difference in the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and gender?

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics of Student-teachers Self-Efficacy across Gender Differences.

Gender	N	Student-teachers Efficacy		Self-Mean Diff.	Decision
		Mean	SD		
Male	75	38.09	3.30	.78	Significance
Female	57	37.31	2.36		

Table 5 shows the mean and standard deviation of male and female student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics. A mean difference of 0.78 in favor of male student-teachers was recorded, and while the 2.36 standard deviation of the female student-teachers is less than that of the male 3.30, this shows there is a wide spread in the female responses.

Hypothesis 3

There is no significant relationship between student-teacher self-efficacy and gender differences.

Table 6: Pearson Correlation between Male and Female Student-teachers' Self-Efficacy in Mathematics

Gender	N	r	Sig.
Male	75	.183	.249
Female	57		

Table 6 shows the correlation between the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics across gender differences. The table revealed that there is no significant relationship between male and female student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics ($r=.183$, $Sig = .249$).

Discussion of Findings

The present study contradicts the finding of Benaoui (2016); in this study, it is found that there is no correlation between mastery and vicarious experience, mastery

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experience and physiological and emotional state, and also social persuasion and physiological and emotional state. While Benaoui found that mastery experiences and physiological and emotional states are statistically correlated and influence students' performance, Benaoui also found that vicarious experiences and social persuasion are not significantly related. In this study, it is found that vicarious experiences and social persuasion are significantly related. Anyway, Benaoui in his study correlate the sources of the self-efficacy with the students' achievement in Mathematics.

In the present study, it is found that there are no relationships between student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and Mathematics teaching career; this contradicts the conclusion of Unsal et al. (2016), who found that Mathematics teachers have high self-efficacy levels. The contradiction might be because of the student-teachers are not service teachers, and they are newly admitted students, they are not exposed to teaching.

The present study also observed that there is no significant relationship between male and female student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics, which contradicts the finding of Ampofo (2019), who found no gender differences in student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics. The contradiction might be due to the small number of female student-teachers available for the present study.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that student-teachers have low self-efficacy in Mathematics. There is no relationship between the student-teachers' self-efficacy in Mathematics and their choice of career. Finally, there is no relationship between student-teacher self-efficacy in Mathematics and gender.

Recommendations

1. The study recommends that students' self-efficacy in Mathematics and teaching Mathematics should be considered before they are admitted into any tertiary institution for education programs; this will help produce better future Mathematics teachers.
2. The study suggests that the government improve the welfare of the Mathematics teaching profession in order to pique the interest and attitude of student-teachers toward the profession.
3. Government, community, non-governmental organizations, and tertiary institution administrators should find a way to encourage females to pursue careers in Mathematics and to teach Mathematics.

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(Effects of Frequent Domestic Conflicts ... Aliero, B. U. Et. al. 2025)

Effects of Frequent Domestic Conflicts and Violence on Social Behaviour and Cognitive Development of School Children in Kwazo Academy Jega, Kebbi State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed the effects of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on social behavior and cognitive development of school children in Kwazo academy, Jega Kebbi State, Nigeria. Three objectives and research hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. Fifty five (55) pre-school children and seventy three (73) school age children out of the total population of 357 were identified as subject for the study. Observation, oral interview and continuous assessment record were used to assess their social behavior and cognitive development. The findings revealed among others that there was 39.0% prevalence of frequent domestic conflict and violence in the study area and there was significant effect of these tendencies on the social behaviours and cognitive development of both pre-school and school age children in the Kwazo academy, Jega. Based on these findings, it was recommended that parents and grown up family members should be enlightened on the effects of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on their children so as to minimize the rate of the prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in homes and its negative effects on the children.

Keywords: Domestic conflicts, Social behavior, violence, Cognitive development and Academy

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Introduction

The family, the basic unit of social life, forms the essential link between individuals and society. It is a system of accepted norms and procedures for fulfilling human needs (Amagon & Wakjissa, 2001). Families, whether nuclear, polygamous, or extended, provide for the rearing of children and meet various human needs (Adeniyi, 2003). Extended families, while geographically dispersed, come together in villages, potentially leading to conflicts (Anyakoha & Eluwa, 2008).

Domestic conflict, defined as misunderstandings among family members, is common. Domestic violence, an intentional use of physical abuse causing pain or injury, exacerbates these conflicts (Espion, 2008; Gilchrist & Graham, 2009). It includes behaviors like throwing objects, pushing, hitting, and threatening, perpetrated by one partner against another in an intimate relationship or parent-child context (Adeniyi, 2003). These conflicts manifest as anxiety, depression, isolation, and communication gaps (Cumming, 2006).

Children are profoundly affected by domestic violence, even if they are not direct victims. Parents often underestimate their children's awareness of these events (Laura, 2011). Children hear the fighting, see the injuries, and experience the emotional pain, impacting their cognitive growth (Laura, 2011).

Social behavior, conduct accepted within a society, is shaped within the family (Carpenter & Stacks, 2009). Children exposed to violence exhibit psychosomatic illnesses, depression, bed-wetting, and suicidal tendencies Adeniyi, E. I. (2003). Children aged one to six show internalizing and externalizing behavior problems, including depression, anxiety, hyperactivity, sleep disturbances, and poor concentration (Carpenter & Stacks, 2009).

Cognitive development, encompassing learning and problem-solving abilities, is influenced by observation and imitation (Anderson & Bushman in Reisberg, 2004). Children imitate behaviors they witness, and violence exposure affects their development (Anderson & Bushman in Reisberg, 2004). Pre-school and school-age children are particularly vulnerable to the effects of parental conflicts (Richard, 2011). They may act out, feel sad, become aggressive, or exhibit behavioral problems like frequent illness and isolation (Abraham, 2004).

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Primary school children (age, six to twelve) are in a critical cognitive development stage, characterized by intellectual curiosity and performance (Kitsman, 2007). Erickson, as cited in Snowman, McCown, & Biehler (2009), observed that children develop a sense of industry through achievement. However, domestic conflicts and violence can lead to

Inferiority complexes, impaired thinking, and poor problem-solving skills (Alexander, 2004).

Statement of the Research Problem

It is generally observed by the researchers that young children between the ages of three to ten years are generally falling victim to circumstances that happen among the family members. Most of their learning behaviour is through the daily practice of what they see happening around them. Children exposed to frequent domestic conflicts and violence do not have the foundations of safety and security that is normally provided by the family. As a result of that, the children experience desensitized to aggressive behaviour, poor anger management and problem solving skills and learn to engage in exploitative relationships (Adeniyi, 2003).

The researchers has observed and interacted with some parents, nursery and primary school teachers and care-givers that some pre-school and school-age children in nursery and primary school in the Kwazo academy, Jega develop a range of problems in school which include psychosomatic complaints, such as headaches or abdominal pain, as well as poor school performances are part of the general problems of children that come from conflict dominated homes. It has also been observed that these children do not have many friends or participate in outdoor activities; they do not have a sense of self-esteem and confidence. One of the researcher was also opportune to observe a role played by some children during an outdoor games in a primary school in Kebbi state and one of the pupils was asked to act as a father. He quickly declined to pick that role on the excuse that his father is very abusive and always fighting the mother. The statement by this pupil stated above caught the attention of the researchers and views of other researchers in relation to this topic has prompted this study to investigate the effects of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on social behaviour and cognitive development of pre-school and school age children in the Kwazo academy, Jega local government Kebbi state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the study:

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1. Ascertain the prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega
2. Identify the social behaviour of children from families with frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega
3. Assess the effects of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on cognitive development of school-age children in the Kwazo academy, Jega

Hypotheses:

1. There is no significant prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega
2. There is no significant difference in social behaviour of pre-school children brought up in homes with frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega
3. There is no significant effect of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on cognitive development of school-age children in the Kwazo academy, Jega

Methodology

Research Design

The research design for this study was survey research design. This design involves the gathering of data from accessible population at a particular period. According to Olayiwola (2007) survey research involves a clear definition of the problem, collection of relevant and adequate data, careful analysis and interpretation of the finding. A survey research design therefore was selected because it allows for the selection of sample from the total population having traits and characteristics of interest.

Population of the Study

The population of the study comprised children in Nursery and Primary Schools in Kwazo Academy, Jega during 2024/2025 academic session in Kebbi state.

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

A sample of 128 nursery and primary school children were selected from the study area. The researchers used random sampling to select the target classes for the study and proportionate sampling methods to select the respondents. This is because the number of pupils in the target classes of study is not uniform.

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Instrument for Data Collection

The instruments used for this study were oral interview, observation and children's continuous assessment records. The instrument is divided into four (4) sections. Section A is the bio-data of the respondents while Section B consist of 10 questionnaire items which were designed using the adapted assessment pattern of family violence by Boney and Sugar Man in Rathus and Silver (2003). This is used to interview the children in order to ascertain the prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega. Section C also consist of 10 items which served as a guide line in observing and identifying the social behaviours of children from families with frequent domestic conflicts and violence. To structure the observation guide the researchers adapted the social behaviour patterns of children as stated by Hurlock (2001). Section D also consists of 10 interview questions respectively and to assess the effects of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on cognitive development of pre-school and school age children, the questions were design using the nursery and primary school syllabus.

Validity of the Instrument

The items on the instruments for this study were given to experts in the field of Home Economics in the Department of Vocational and Technical Education, Adamu Augie College of Education Argungu to vet the content validity. The interview and observation items were also vetted by an expert in the field of family and child development to ensure that the instrument measures accurately what it is intended to measure. The corrected questionnaires were used for pilot study to ascertain the reliability coefficient of the instrument.

Reliability of the Instrument

The data collected from the pilot study was analyzed for the purpose of reliability coefficient. Consequently the Cronbach reliability level of .806 was obtained for the nursery school section and 0.919 was obtained for the primary school section. According to Spiegel and Stevens (1999) an instrument is considered reliable if its reliability coefficient lies between zero (0) and one (1), and that the closer the calculated reliability coefficient is to zero the less reliable is the instrument and the closer it is to one the more reliable is the instrument.

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Procedure for Data Collection

The researchers through the help of the headmaster, class teachers and care givers who were trained by the researchers interviewed the 128 children using the questionnaire items in section B. the researchers with the help of the class teachers during the interview selected the children one after the other who were identify as the subjects for the study. These children were used to answer the questions in section C and D, respectively. The researchers used direct and indirect method of observation to assess the social behaviour patterns of the children; this is to minimize the tendency of the children faking their behaviour. This was done using the guidelines in section C. The questionnaires in section D were administered to the children using oral test. The researchers graded them using their continuous assessment records and students coding sheets based on their performance and it lasted for six (6) weeks.

Procedure for Data Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using inferential statistics. All the null-hypotheses were tested using t-test at 0.05 level of significance. This is in line with Aloysin and John (2000) who explained that t-test is the most appropriate statistical tool to find out differences and effects among variables.

Presentation of Results

Hypothesis 1: *There is no significant prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega*

Table 1: One sample t-test of Prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega

Variables	N	Mean	t-Cal	t-Crit	DF	P
Prevalence	56	1.0546	2.081	1.96	54	0.000

Source: Fieldwork 2025

$t(127) 1.96, P < 0.05$

The test in Table 1, revealed that 56 children out of the total sample of 128 were identified from pre-school children and school age children. The observed t-calculated is 2.081 which is greater than the t-critical of 1.96 at the 54 degree of freedom and the probability level of significance observed in the test is 0.000 ($P < 0.05$). This indicates that there was significant prevalence of frequent domestic

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conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega was rejected.

Hypothesis 2: *There is no significant difference in social behaviours of pre-school children brought up in homes with frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega.*

Table 2: One sample t-test on social behaviours of pre-school children in the Kwazo academy, Jega

Variables	N	Mean	t-Cal	t-Crit	DF	P
Pre-school age children	53	-.25455	-1.308	2.01	51	0.000

Source: Fieldwork 2025

$t(54) 2.01, P < 0.05$

The test in Table 2, revealed that 53 students were identified for pre-school children. The observed t-calculated is -1.308 which is less than the t-critical of 2.01 at the 51 degree of freedom and the probability level of significance observed in the test is 0.000 ($P < 0.05$). This indicates that there was significant difference in the behaviours of the pre-school children. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant difference in social behaviours of pre-school children brought up in homes with frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega was therefore rejected.

Hypothesis 3: *There is no significant effect of frequent domestic conflicts and violent on cognitive development of school age children brought up in homes with frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega.*

Table 3: One sample t-test on effect of cognitive development of school age children in Kwazo academy, Jega

Variables	N	Mean	t-Cal	t-Crit	DF	P
school age children	71	-.24364	-2.281	2.01	69	0.000

Source: Fieldwork 2025

$t(72) 2.01, P < 0.05$

The test in Table 3, revealed that 710 school age children were identified. The observed t-calculated is -2.281 which is less than the t-critical of 2.01 at the 69 degree of freedom and the probability level of significance observed in the test is

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0.000 ($P < 0.05$). This indicates that there was significant difference in cognitive development of school age children. Therefore, the null hypothesis that there is no significant effect of frequent domestic conflicts and violence on cognitive development of school age children brought up in homes with frequent domestic conflicts and violence in the Kwazo academy, Jega was therefore rejected.

Discussion of Findings

The findings revealed in the test of null hypothesis that the probability level of significance observed in the test was 0.00 ($P < 0.05$). This shows that frequent domestic conflicts and violence had effects on school age children. The finding is in line with Laura (2011) who states that in many homes where domestic violence occurs, the parents are under the misconception that their children are unaware of the violence even if it has taken place in close proximity to the children. They may not witness the actual violence but they do hear the fighting, hear the screams and see the injuries. These children are also traumatized by the parent's emotional pain and suffering after the violence had taken place and this directly and indirectly have devastating effects on their cognitive growth. Witnessing domestic violence can lead children to develop an array of age-dependent and negative effect. Cumming, (2005) stated that children who witness violence in the home and children who are abused may display many similar psychological effects.

The school age children have significant difference in their cognitive development. This was further confirmed with Bandura in John (2008) who emphasizes that cognitive development and social behavior have important links with environment. His research program focused mainly on observational learning also called imitation or modeling, which is learning that occurs through observing what others do; for example, a young child might observe his parents yelling at each other in anger or treating other people with hostility, with his peers, the child may later act very aggressively. Bandura proposed that children cognitively represent the behavior of others and then sometimes adopted this behavior themselves. Elizabeth (2011) opines that when parents are in conflict situations, pre-school and school age children are seriously affected, while many parents think that they are keeping the conflict away from their children, the children notice tension in the home and it has a profound effect on their social behavior and cognitive development. Some children respond to parental conflict by acting out, violence behavior, increased anger and turning inward, isolation from parents and friends, while some may have trouble

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thinking, impaired thinking, abstract reasoning, poor problem solving skills and their memories affected.

Finally, the frequent domestic conflicts and violence on social behavior and cognitive development have effect on school age children in the Kwazo academy, Jega thereby affecting their behaviours, socially and cognitively.

Conclusion

From the findings it was discovered that prevalence of frequent domestic conflicts and violence in homes can be seen displayed among school age children. It could be deduced that frequent domestic conflicts and violence of homes in Kwazo academy, Jega has influence on a lot of children that stirred up violence in them right from their childhood. Parents should be aware of the fact that their actions can affect their children's future and violent act in the presence and around their children can affect their cognitive development.

Recommendations

1. Parents and grown up members of the family should be enlightened on the effects of frequent domestic conflicts and violence so as to minimize the rate of negative effect on the children's social behaviour and cognitive development.
2. Guidance and counseling unit should be built into the nursery and primary schools to curb and ameliorate whatever trauma the children of school age children had due to frequent domestic conflicts and violence.
3. Parents should be enlightened on their roles as good model to their children because children learn faster at their tender ages and also believe that what their parents do is the ultimate.

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Comparative Analysis between Awareness and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence Technology for Teaching and Research Activities among Public University Lecturers in South-West, Nigeria

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Abstract

The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in higher education is reshaping teaching and research methodologies. This study examines the level of awareness, utilization, and AI adoption among lecturers in public universities in Southwest Nigeria. Using a descriptive survey research design, data were collected from a representative sample of 525 lecturers across the selected institutions. Four research questions and two hypotheses were answered and tested at 0.05 level of significance respectively. Findings reveal a moderate to high utilization of AI tools for teaching and research, with ChatGPT (86.9%), Canvas (72.0%), and plagiarism checkers (62.1%) being the most frequently used for instructional purposes, while ChatGPT (86.7%), Canvas (75.2%), and Suite Assistant (66.7%) were prominent in research activities. Regression analysis established a significant relationship between lecturers' awareness of AI and its utilization for teaching ($\beta = 0.161$, $t = 3.620$, $p < 0.05$) and research ($\beta = 0.325$, $t = 7.250$, $p < 0.05$), indicating that increased awareness promotes higher AI adoption. The study recommend among others that the university management should procure the necessary digital resources to support seamless AI integration into teaching and research; and organize regular AI training workshops and professional development programs to improve lecturers' competence in AI adoption.

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Keyword: Artificial Intelligence, Awareness, AI Utilization, University Lecturers, Teaching, Research,

Introduction

Technological innovations, particularly Artificial Intelligence (AI), have rapidly transformed various sectors, including education. The impact of emerging technologies on teaching, learning, and research in higher education institutions worldwide cannot be overstated. The integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in higher education has significantly transformed teaching, research, and administrative processes globally. AI is referred to machines or software systems that is designed to perform tasks that traditionally require human intelligence, has revolutionized how institutions approach pedagogy, curriculum delivery, and academic research. Its application spans across diverse domains, including data analysis, personalized learning, grading automation, and academic research management (Davenport, Guha, Grewal, & Bressgott, 2020). Through adaptive learning technologies and AI-driven platforms, students can benefit from personalized learning experiences tailored to their individual needs, learning speeds, and preferences. AI-powered systems can assist lecturers in managing classroom activities, grading assignments, and evaluating students' progress in real-time.

In the global context, AI is increasingly seen as a critical tool for improving efficiency, reducing human error, and promoting productivity in higher education settings. AI-powered tools such as intelligent tutoring systems, automated grading software, plagiarism detection tools, and AI-driven research assistants have enhanced academic workflows, making education more efficient and research more innovative (Bond, Zawacki-Richter & Marin, 2021; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). In addition, AI has shown immense potential for research management, helping academics identify trends, conduct literature reviews, analyze complex data sets, and automate administrative tasks, thereby freeing up more time for creative and intellectual pursuits (Ibrahim & Oladimeji, 2023). These innovations have fostered an environment where teaching and research productivity are maximized, and contribute to the overall enhancement of higher education outcomes. Afolayan, Ogunleye and Olawale (2022) further averred that integration of AI into higher education institutions in the developed countries has resulted in notable improvements in teaching, learning, and research activities.

However, Ogunleye and Falade (2023) affirmed that factors such as institutional policies, infrastructural deficits and level of awareness among lecturers regarding

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emerging technologies has affected the adoption of AI in various institutions of learning in the developing nations of the world , especially, Nigeria. These challenges has affected the level of AI adoption in most universities in Nigeria for pedagogic experiences. The implication is that despite technological advancements, the adoption and integration of AI in higher education institutions in developing countries, such as Nigeria, have been relatively slow. While AI technologies have proven to be beneficial in various educational settings, the pace of their implementation in Nigerian universities remains sluggish, primarily due to several barriers. There are knowledge gaps in terms of awareness of potentials of AI and its adoption for teaching and research, as well as lack of professional development programmes and insufficient inclusion of AI training in university curricula might be some of the key factors hindering their adoption (Sharma, Banerjee & Mukherjee, 2021); which might account for the reasons why university lecturers are hesitant to embrace these technologies in their teaching and research practices.

Afolayan, Ogunleye and Olawale (2022) and Ogunleye and Falade (2023) further reiterated that the adoption of AI technologies is closely linked to factors such as institutional support, faculty readiness, and student engagement. Understanding the barriers to AI integration in Nigerian universities is critical for fostering a more inclusive and innovative educational environment. It is evident from the literature that AI has revolutionize higher education in the developing countries; and successful integration hinges on addressing the challenges facing its implementation in various universities in Nigeria (Bello, Umar & Abdullahi, 2023). AI holds the potential to not only to enhance teaching and learning, but also to provide solutions to some of the systemic challenges facing Nigerian higher education, such as overcrowded classrooms, inefficient grading systems, and limited access to quality learning resources (Olaleye & Sanusi, 2023).

Several empirical studies explored have substantiated the relationship between lecturers' awareness of information and communication technologies, however not on the domain of emerging technologies and utilization of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for teaching and research within Nigerian universities. Broader studies provide valuable insights into this correlation, however, specific research focusing exclusively on South-west Nigeria is limited. A study conducted by Ogunfowora, Akinrinade and Ajiboye (2022) on lecturers' awareness of AI and its relationship with their digital competence.

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The findings indicated a moderate level of AI awareness among lecturers and a positive correlation between AI awareness and digital competence. The study recommended targeted training programs to enhance AI literacy and equip lecturers with essential skills for effective AI integration in teaching activities.

Similarly, Fasola (2024) and Akinyemi and Adigun (2022) examined the awareness, perception, and utilization of AI tools among Library and Information Science (LIS) lecturers in Nigerian higher institutions. The study revealed a high degree of awareness and a positive perception towards AI tools, with commonly used applications including ChatGPT, Socrative, ChatPDF, Turnitin, and Gamma. Despite recognizing AI's potential benefits, actual usage was limited due to challenges such as rapid technological advancements, lack of infrastructure, and resistance to change. Olatunde-Aiyedun and Hamma (2023) assessed the proficiency levels of university lecturers in Nigeria regarding the use of AI features in presentation of software tools like MS PowerPoint, Canva, and Gamma. The study highlighted gaps in lecturers' proficiency and recommended targeted training programs to improve their skills, thereby enhancing teaching quality and student engagement. While these studies provide a general understanding of AI awareness and utilization among Nigerian university lecturers, there is a paucity of research specifically focusing on South-West Nigeria. Given the region's status as an educational hub, further empirical research is needed to assess the unique challenges and opportunities faced by lecturers in South-West Nigerian universities regarding AI integration in teaching and research.

The existing empirical literature suggests a positive correlation between lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies and their utilization of AI in teaching and research. However, actual usage is often hindered by challenges such as insufficient infrastructure, rapid technological changes, and resistance to adoption. Addressing these issues through targeted training programs and enhanced AI literacy initiatives is crucial for effective AI integration in Nigerian higher education. In the context of Southwest Nigerian universities, this study seeks to explore the level of awareness among lecturers regarding AI technologies and how this awareness correlates with their utilization of AI in teaching and research activities. By investigating these relationships, the study aims to uncover the underlying factors that either facilitate or hinder AI adoption. Specifically, the research will examine lecturers' awareness and how it correlates with its utilization.

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Statement of the Research Problem

Despite AI's widespread acceptance in the educational systems of developed countries, Nigerian universities lecturers seemed to lag in integrating AI for academic purposes (Oke & Olaleye, 2023). The slow adoption of AI is presumptuously due to related factors like low awareness of the technology, inadequate procuring of infrastructure facilities, and insufficient professional training for academic staff (Onwuagboke, Nnajiето, Nzeako & Umune, 2024). AI has demonstrated its potential to optimize admission processes, enhance research productivity, and support personalized learning, yet many Nigerian institutions continue to rely on traditional methods that hinder academic progress (Adebayo, Adewale & Jimoh, 2022). As the global academic community increasingly adopts AI-driven innovations, the need for Nigerian universities to adopt emerging technologies has become more urgent. However, the awareness and perception of AI remain under-researched, limiting its utilization for teaching and research purposes (Okolo, Aruleba & Obaido, 2023). This gap in knowledge and application of AI technologies is a barrier to improving the quality and global competitiveness of Nigerian universities. This study therefore seeks to investigate the awareness of AI among university lecturers in Southwest Nigeria and how these factors correlate with the use of AI in teaching and research.

Objectives of the Study

The primary objective of this study is to investigate comparative analysis between awareness and utilization of artificial intelligence technology for teaching and research activities among public university lecturers in South-west, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to:

1. Examine university lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies for teaching in public universities in Southwest Nigeria.
2. Investigate university lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies for research in public universities in Southwest Nigeria.
3. Examine university lecturers' level of utilization of emerging technologies for teaching in public universities in Southwest Nigeria.
4. Investigate university lecturers' level of utilization of emerging technologies for research in public universities in Southwest Nigeria.
5. Examine the relationship between lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies and their utilization of AI for teaching in Southwest Nigerian universities.

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6. Examine the relationship between lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies and their utilization of AI for research in Southwest Nigerian universities.

Research Questions

This study seeks to answer the following research questions:

1. What is the level of university lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies (AI) for teaching in public universities in Southwest Nigeria?
2. What is the level of university lecturers' awareness of emerging technologies (AI) for research in public universities in Southwest Nigeria?
3. What is the university lecturers' level of utilization of emerging technologies for teaching in public universities in Southwest Nigeria?
4. What is the university lecturers' level of utilization of emerging technologies for research in public universities in Southwest Nigeria?

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

- H₀₁:** There is no significant relationship between university lecturers' level of awareness of emerging technologies and the utilization of AI for teaching and research in public universities in Southwest Nigeria.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant relationship between university lecturers' level of awareness of emerging technologies and the utilization of AI for research in public universities in Southwest Nigeria.

Methodology

Population and Sampling Techniques

This study employs a descriptive research design of the cross-sectional survey type. The population comprised of all university lecturers in the public universities in Southwest Nigeria. The study focuses on six public universities in Southwest Nigeria, comprising three federal and three state-owned universities. The sampled Federal and State owned universities that participated in the study are: Lagos State {164(31.2%)}; Oyo State {193 (36.8%)} and Osun State {168(32.0%)}. A total of 525 lecturers were randomly sampled to capture a representative sample. These universities were selected based on their year of establishment and geographical distribution in the region.

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Instrumentation

A researcher-designed questionnaire titled “Awareness of AI as Correlate to Utilization” (AAICUQ) was used for data collection. The questionnaire consists of three sections: Section A contained demographic information based on the university ownership, gender, faculty, department, and area of specialization; Section B contained seven items on lecturers’ awareness of AI for teaching, and Section C contained also seven items on lecturers’ awareness of AI for research. The responses were measured using a 3-point scale: Aware (3), Partially Aware (2), Not Aware (1). The reliability of the instrument was tested using Cronbach Alpha, yielding a coefficient of 0.91 the average mean score, indicating high reliability index.

Data Collection and Analysis

The data collected was analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistics. The descriptive statistical tools used were frequency counts, percentages, and means to answer the study’s research questions, while Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient statistical tools was employed to test the relationship between lecturers’ awareness and their utilization of AI for teaching and research.

Research Question 1: What is the level of university lecturers’ awareness of emerging technologies (AI) for teaching in public universities in South-west Nigeria?

Table 1: Level of University Lecturers’ Awareness of Emerging Technologies (AI) for Teaching

No	Items on Teaching	Fully Aware (FA) %	Slightly Aware (SA) %	Not Aware (NA) %	Mean	SD
1	Research Rabbit	37.1	29.9	33.0	2.04	0.84
2	Chat PDF	54.9	27.4	17.7	2.37	0.77
3	Consensus AI	39.2	35.2	25.5	2.14	0.79
4	Education Co-pilot	35.2	32.8	32.0	2.03	0.82
5	Scispace	27.0	37.1	35.8	1.91	0.79
6	Semantic AI	35.0	32.0	33.0	2.02	0.83
7	Elicit AI	28.8	32.2	39.0	1.90	0.82

Mean Aggregate = 2.06, SD = 0.16

The results in Table 1 shows that the level of awareness of AI for teaching among lecturers. The analysed data revealed the mean scores for lecturers’ level of awareness of these AI technologies: Research Rabbit (2.04), Chat PDF (2.37), Consensus AI (2.14),

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Education Co-pilot (2.03), Scispace (1.91), Semantic AI (2.02) and Elicit AI (1.90) for teaching. The mean score was on average with mean aggregate value of 2.06, which was moderate based on the benchmark value of 2.0. This indicates that the level of awareness of AI technologies for teaching was moderate among the sampled university lecturers.

Research Question 2: What is the level of university lecturers’ awareness of emerging technologies (AI) for research in public universities in South-west Nigeria?

Table 2: Level of University Lecturers’ Awareness of Emerging Technologies (AI) for Research

No	Items on Research	Fully Aware (FA) %	Slightly Aware (SA) %	Not Aware (NA) %	Mean	SD
1	Suite Assistant	39.4	27.8	32.8	2.07	0.85
2	Chat	64.2	27.2	8.6	2.56	0.65
3	Copy AI	37.1	33.7	29.1	2.08	0.81
4	Sendstep AI	26.9	36.4	36.8	1.90	0.79
5	Canvas	43.4	35.4	21.1	2.22	0.77
6	Plagiarism Checkers	66.5	23.0	10.5	2.56	0.68
7	Gradescope	30.9	33.1	36.0	1.95	0.82

Mean Aggregate = 2.19, SD = 0.27

The results in Table 2 shows the level of awareness of AI for research among the university lecturers. The analysed data revealed the mean scores for lecturers’ level of awareness of these AI technologies: Suite Assistant (2.07), Chat (2.56), Copy AI (2.08), Sendstep AI (1.90), Canvas (2.22), Plagiarism Checkers (2.56) and Gradescope (1.95) for research related undertakings. The mean score was on average with mean aggregate value of 2.19, which was moderate based on the benchmark value of 2.0. This indicates that the level of awareness of AI technologies for research was moderate among the sampled lecturers. The mean aggregate of 2.19 indicates a high level of awareness among lecturers for AI tools used in research.

Research Question 3: What is the level of utilizing the available AI for teaching by lecturers in public universities in South-west Nigeria?

Table 3: Level of utilizing the available AI for Teaching by lecturers in public universities in south-west Nigeria

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S/ N	Items on Teaching	FU	%	OU	%	∑U	%	NU	%	X	SD
8	Elicit AI	150	28.6	192	36.6	342	65.9	183	34.9	1.94	.795
9	Suite Assistant	148	28.2	205	39.0	353	67.2	172	32.8	1.95	.780
10	Copy AI	164	31.2	172	32.8	336	64.0	189	36.0	1.95	.819
11	Sendstep AI	120	22.9	194	37.0	314	59.8	211	40.2	1.83	.776
12	Canvas	181	34.5	197	37.5	378	72.0	147	28.0	2.06	.789
13	ChatGPT	288	54.9	168	32.0	456	86.9	69	13.1	2.42	.712
14	Plagiarism checkers	143	27.2	183	34.9	326	62.1	199	37.9	1.89	.801

Key: Frequently Utilised (FU), Occasionally Utilised (OU), Never Utilised (NU), Sum of Utilization (∑U)

Mean aggregate = 2.01 SD = 0.20

Table 3 revealed lecturers' responses on the level of utilizing the available emerging technologies (AI) for research in public universities. The collapse of responses on FU and OU (∑U) shows level of utilizing the available AI tools: Elicit AI {342(65.9%)}; Suite Assistant {353(67.2%)}; Copy AI {336(64.0%)}; Sendstep AI {314(59.8%)}; Canvas {378(72.0%)}; ChatGPT {456(86.9%)}; and Plagiarism checkers {326(62.1%)}. The high frequency counts and percentages (ranging between 59.8% and 86.9%.) of the respondents utilizing the available AI technologies exemplified high frequency of using those emerging technologies (AI) in facilitating pedagogic experiences in the sampled universities. The mean aggregate 2.01 which is above the mean bench mark (2.0) affirms to utilizing the available emerging technologies (AI) for teaching by lecturers in public universities.

Research Question 4: What is the extent of using available AI tools for research by Lecturers in public universities in South-West Nigeria?

Table 4: Utilization of AI Tools for Research by Lecturers in Public Universities in South-West Nigeria

S/N	Items on Research	FU	%	OU	%	∑U	%	NU	%	X	SD
8	Elicit AI	160	30.2	185	34.9	345	65.7	180	34.3	.92	0.810
9	Suite Assistant	150	8.4	200	38.2	350	66.7	175	33.3	.93	.790
10	Copy AI	170	2.4	170	32.2	340	64.8	185	35.2	.94	0.830
11	Sendstep AI	130	4.6	190	36.2	320	61.0	210	39.0	.85	0.780
12	Canvas	190	5.9	195	37.2	395	75.2	130	24.8	.05	0.800
13	ChapGPT	280	2.8	175	33.3	455	86.7	70	13.7	.38	0.725
14	Plagiarism Checkers	150	8.3	185	35.1	335	63.8	190	36.2	.87	0.815

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Key: Frequently Utilized (FU), Occasionally Utilized (OU), Never Utilized (NU) Mean Aggregate = 2.02 | SD = 0.19

Table 4 presents the responses from lecturers in public universities in South-West Nigeria regarding the level of utilization of the available AI tools for research. The table shows a broad engagement with AI tools, with Likert responses: "Frequently Utilized" (FU) and "Occasionally Utilized" (OU) {collapsed as the "Sum of Utilization" (ΣU)} and "Never Utilised" (NU). The collapse of responses on FU and OU (ΣU) shows level of utilizing the available AI tools: Elicit AI {345(65.7%)}; Suite Assistant {350(66.7%)}; Copy AI {340(64.8%)}; Sendstep AI {320(61.0%)}; Canvas {395(75.2%)}; ChatGPT {455(86.7%)}; and Plagiarism checkers {335(63.8%)}. The high frequency counts and percentages (ranging between 64.8% and 86.7%) of the respondents utilizing the available AI technologies exemplified high frequency of using those emerging technologies (AI) in facilitating research undertakings in the sampled universities. The mean aggregate 2.02 which is above the mean bench mark (2.0) affirms to utilizing the available emerging technologies (AI) for research related tasks and purposes by lecturers in public universities. The results confirm that lecturers are actively engaging with AI technologies (**Elicit AI, Suite Assistant, Copy AI, Sendstep AI, Canvas, ChapGPT and Plagiarism Checkers**) for research related purposes.

Hypotheses Testing

H01: There is no significant relationship between university lecturers' level of awareness of emerging technologies and utilization of AI for teaching in South-west Nigeria.

Table 5: Relative Influence of Independent Variables on Dependent Variables

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
(Constant)	-3.446	1.654		-2.083
Awareness of AI	0.176	0.049	0.161	3.620

Table 5 the shows relative influence of independent variables (awareness) on dependent variables (AI utilization and adoption for teaching and research). The analysed data revealed that awareness of AI for teaching has a significant positive influence on the utilization of AI tools ($p < 0.05$). The beta value of 0.161 indicates a positive relationship between awareness and utilization.

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H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between university lecturers’ level of awareness of emerging technologies and utilization of AI for research in South-west Nigeria.

Table 6: Relationship between awareness of Emerging Technologies and Adoption of AI for Research

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients	Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta	
Awareness of emerging technologies	0.290	0.040	0.325	7.250

Dependent Variable: Frequency of AI adoption in research.

Table 6 shows the relationship that exists between awareness of emerging technologies and adoption of AI for research. The Table shows the beta value of 0.325 for the awareness of emerging technologies variable. The analysis reveals a significant positive relationship between university lecturers’ awareness of emerging technologies and their adoption of AI for research in Southwest Nigeria ($\beta = 0.325$, $t = 7.250$). This indicates that as awareness of emerging technologies increases, the frequency of AI adoption in research also rises. Given the high t-value, the relationship is statistically significant, suggesting that enhancing lecturers' awareness could promote greater AI utilization in research. This indicates that awareness has a positive predictive relationship with the adoption of AI tools. The findings suggest that the greater the awareness of emerging technologies, the more likely researchers are to adopt AI for research purposes. The results also show a statistically significant influence, with a p-value 7.250 greater than alpha value (0.05), reinforcing that awareness of emerging technologies has a meaningful impact on AI adoption in research.

Discussion of Findings

The study's findings reveal a growing adoption of Artificial Intelligence (AI) among lecturers in public universities in Southwest Nigeria. The results indicate a moderate to high level of AI utilization, particularly for teaching and research. Among the most frequently used AI tools for instructional purposes, ChatGPT (86.9%), Canvas (72.0%), and plagiarism checkers (62.1%) stood out, while ChatGPT (86.7%), Canvas (75.2%), and Suite Assistant (66.7%) were prominent in research activities. These findings align with existing literature, which emphasizes the increasing reliance on AI-driven tools for content delivery, assessment, and academic writing. Prior studies have shown that AI enhances pedagogical efficiency, supports personalized learning, and streamlines academic integrity monitoring (Bond et al., 2021; Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). The

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high adoption of generative AI tools like ChatGPT suggests that lecturers are leveraging these technologies for content creation, automated feedback, and knowledge enhancement (Ogunfowora, Akinrinade & Ajiboye, 2022), which is consistent with the broader trend of AI integration in education (Ogunleye & Falade, 2023).

The study further established a significant relationship between lecturers' awareness of AI and its utilization for teaching ($\beta = 0.161$, $t = 3.620$, $p < 0.05$) and research ($\beta = 0.325$, $t = 7.250$, $p < 0.05$), reinforcing the idea that increased awareness leads to higher adoption. This finding supports that awareness significantly impact technology adoption; and faculty members with greater exposure to AI are more likely to integrate AI-enhanced learning strategies into their instructional and research activities (Olaleye & Sanusi, 2023). While the increasing use of AI tools is evident, barriers such as inadequate institutional support, ethical concerns, and limited digital infrastructure continue to hinder full-scale adoption. The challenges identified in this study align with the findings of Afolayan, Ogunleye and Olawale (2022), who highlighted the infrastructural and skill-based limitations affecting AI implementation in Nigerian universities.

As AI continues to redefine higher education, institutions must prioritize structured AI training and digital literacy programs to enhance lecturers' awareness and competency. Research indicates that targeted AI workshops and institutional guidelines can bridge knowledge gaps and encourage responsible AI adoption (Afolayan, Ogunleye & Olawale, 2022; Ogunleye & Falade 2023). Furthermore, policy frameworks must address ethical concerns related to AI-generated content, particularly in academic writing and research. Studies have warned against the potential risks of over-reliance on AI in scholarly work, raising issues related to authorship, originality, and data integrity (Davenport, Guha, Grewal, & Bressgott, 2020). Given these concerns, it is essential for universities to implement clear ethical guidelines and responsible AI-use policies to maintain academic standards.

The findings also highlight the importance of external support, including government funding and private sector collaboration, to facilitate AI adoption in higher education. Similar initiatives in developed nations have accelerated AI-driven innovation through strategic investments in education technology (Olatunde-Aiyedun & Hama, 2023). Nigerian universities can benefit from similar partnerships, enabling the integration of

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AI solutions tailored to various academic disciplines (Luckin, 2018). By improving AI infrastructure, expanding training opportunities, and fostering interdisciplinary collaborations (Olaleye & Sanusi, 2023), institutions can fully leverage AI's transformative potential in teaching and research while ensuring ethical and sustainable implementation.

Conclusion

The study revealed that university lecturers in Southwest Nigeria are increasingly integrating Artificial Intelligence (AI) into their teaching and research activities. Tools such as ChatGPT, Canvas, and plagiarism checkers were found to be the most frequently used for instructional purposes, while ChatGPT, Canvas, and Suite Assistant were dominant in research activities. The findings indicate a significant relationship between lecturers' awareness of AI and its utilization, suggesting that higher levels of awareness lead to increased adoption of AI tools in academic work. Despite this growing adoption, several challenges were identified, including inadequate digital infrastructure, limited institutional support, ethical concerns, and the absence of clear policies on AI usage. These barriers hinder the seamless integration of AI in higher education. The study emphasizes the need for structured AI training programs, institutional guidelines on ethical AI use, and increased investment in AI-compatible digital resources. The study underscores the increasing role of AI in shaping academic activities among university lecturers in Southwest Nigeria. The strong link between AI awareness and its utilization suggests that targeted interventions, such as training and policy development, can further enhance AI adoption in higher education. While lecturers have begun integrating AI tools into their teaching and research, addressing infrastructural gaps and ethical concerns remains crucial for sustainable implementation. Collaboration between universities, policymakers, and stakeholders is essential in fostering a supportive environment for AI-driven innovation in academia.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Management in various universities in Nigeria should organize regular AI training sessions, seminars and workshops to enhance lecturers' understanding and effective use of AI for teaching and research. Also, lecturers should make efforts to attend professional training programmes to expose them to hands-on experiences.

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2. Various universities in Nigeria should invest in stable internet connectivity, AI-compatible software, and necessary digital resources to support seamless AI integration.
3. AI tools such as ChatGPT, plagiarism checkers, and Canvas should be systematically incorporated into academic activities while ensuring ethical usage.
4. Universities management in Nigeria should establish guidelines on AI ethics, data privacy, and responsible usage to address concerns about academic integrity and intellectual property.
5. Partnerships with tech companies, policymakers, and funding bodies should be encouraged in fostering and supporting AI-driven research and interdisciplinary innovation.
6. The use of AI tools should be encouraged by academics to meet the unique needs of different academic disciplines, and ensuring relevance and effectiveness in diverse fields.
7. Government, institutions, and private sector stakeholders should provide financial support to enhance AI accessibility, research, and innovation in higher education.

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Assessment of Internet Facilities usage on Reading Culture among Wesley High School Students in Otukpo, Benue State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study assessed internet facilities usage on reading culture among Wesley high school students in Otukpo, Benue state, Nigeria. Three objectives guided the study. The research design adopted was a survey research design. The population of the study comprised of 278 SS2 and SS3 students of the school studied in 2023/2024 academic session. The sampling technique used was a complete census. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire titled: "Impact of Internet Facilities on Student's Reading Culture Questionnaire (IIFSRCQ)". The questionnaire was subjected to face and content validity. The reliability score of the questionnaire was 87.53 Cronbach Alpha Value. Data collected were analyzed using frequency counts, simple percentages and mean scores. The findings showed that majority of the students make use of the internet to study, prepare for examinations, write assignments, and chatting with friends, among others. Making the students active in class, distracting their reading, and exposing them to unimportant articles and write-ups were among the perceived impact. The study recommended that Management of secondary schools should organize seminars aimed at teaching the students the right use of the internet to improve their reading culture, among other things.

Keywords: Reading, Reading Culture, Internet, impact, Student.

Introduction

Reading is the springboard of any literacy program. It is one of the oldest habits of human civilization and has remained the passion of the greatest personalities of all times. According to Nnadozie and Egwim (2010), reading is a complex skill requiring the coordination of several inter related sources of information. It is the art of interpreting printed and written words, and the most effective process of conscious learning, which influences the extent and accuracy of information as well as the attitudes, morals, beliefs, judgement and action of individuals (Edeole & Adejoke, 2016).

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However, due to the attitude of individuals who rarely pick a book or magazine to read, there is a serious decline in reading culture. The same applies to the schoolchild for whom reading has come to mean a thing of spare time. Considering the place of creative thinking in reading, it becomes very important for one to develop the rudiments of reading and the culture of reading always. The importance of reading culture cannot be overemphasized because it is crucial for both personal and academic success. Furthermore, it is an aid to language development, socialization and civilization.

The development of good reading culture is important because society has realized the importance of information and effective communication for the survival and exploitation of their environment. Moreover, the development of reading and reading culture are basic skills, which society must confer on its students as part of their childhood education. Unfortunately, there are problems inherent in the development of proper reading culture among students because of some technological innovations. One of the technological innovations is the Internet. The Internet can be broadly defined as a worldwide network of computers communicating through an approved protocol. The Internet according to Kumar and Kaur in Jibrin, Musa and Shittu (2017), has an unlimited wealth of information resources that are readily available and easily accessible for people to use worldwide and simultaneously. Internet is a veritable tool in learning, teaching and research if effectively used. However, it has been observed that owing to this technological innovation, reading culture is being threatened, especially, among teens and secondary school students (Yusuf, 2015).

In Nigerian society today, while technology is slowly taking a steady control over individual lives, the reading culture among secondary school students is fast vanishing. Today, students rather than read to acquire new knowledge prefer to spend hours unending, surfing the net, playing with funky handsets, chatting and passing non-stop short message services (SMSs), thereby making reading a book or any other information resource in a quiet or peaceful corner of a library or home an archaic idea. The declining interest in reading among our children (especially those in secondary schools) compared to increase in hours spent on the Internet has become a cause for alarm and a challenge to all and something needs to be done to change the scenario. However, assuming or concluding that Internet use is the cause of the declining reading culture can be better regarded as an assumption until empirically proven. It is against this backdrop that the current study is assessing internet facilities usage

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on reading culture among Wesley high school students in Otukpo, Benue state, Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The rapid advancement of internet technology has transformed how students access and engage with information. While the internet provides vast resources that can enhance learning, its usage also raises concerns about its impact on students' reading culture. In Wesley High School, Otukpo, Benue State, there is growing concern that students may be shifting from traditional reading habits, such as reading textbooks, novels, and academic materials, to spending more time on social media, online gaming, and entertainment websites. Despite the availability of internet facilities in the school and among students, little is known about how these resources are being utilized and whether they contribute positively or negatively to students' reading culture. Some researchers argue that the internet can enhance reading habits through access to e-books, online journals, and educational blogs, while others believe that it distracts students and reduces their engagement with academic texts (Musa & Shittu, 2017; Yusuf, 2017). This study seeks to assess the usage of internet facilities and its impact on the reading culture of students in Wesley High School Otukpo, Benue State, Nigeria. Specifically, it aims to determine whether internet access promotes or hinders reading habits, identify the types of online content students engage with, and explore possible ways to enhance the positive effects of internet usage on reading culture. Addressing this issue is essential to ensuring that the internet serves as a tool for academic growth rather than a distraction from meaningful reading practices.

Research objectives

The study is guided by the following objectives, which involve, to:

1. Find out if students of Wesley high school Otukpo make use of the Internet facilities
2. Determine the students' reasons for their use of the Internet facilities
3. Investigate the perceived impact of the Internet facilities by the students on their reading culture

Research questions

1. Do students of Wesley high school Otukpo make use of the Internet facilities?
2. What are the students' reasons for their use of the Internet facilities?

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3. What is the perceived impact of the Internet facilities by the students on their reading culture?

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the students' reasons for use of internet facilities and students on their reading culture

Literature review

Since the advent of ICT, the subject of the students' reading culture has attracted a major concern. According to Yusuf (2015), this major concern is because of the need to keep the schoolchild active and able to cope with the demands of the present day. In the same vein, Saka, Bitagi, and Garba (2012) pointed out that inculcating a reading culture should be introduced at an early age among children. This is because reading and reading culture develop over a prolonged period and an early promotion will be able to mold them into lifelong readers. The challenge is therefore to ingrain the culture of reading in children so that it is as important as sports and other hobbies. Perhaps then, the impact of negative media will be directly reduced. Furthermore, Yani (2003) observed that reading culture of Nigerians is a matter of concern in our educational and national development, stating further that in a developing country like Nigeria, the concept of reading culture should not be relegated to the background.

Fundamentally, the major way to improve the reading culture of students is through a well-equipped school library. Topo, as cited in Strong (2014) affirmed that the need today is the thoughtful integration of book reading with high technology, as it will reverse the decline in book reading among children and adults. In addition, Yusuf (2007) asserted that equipping school libraries is the first practical step in these efforts. This is because books and other information resources are the most suitable medium through which knowledge is transmitted from generation to generation.

Nonetheless, Kristy (as cited in Kolawole, 2005) reported that the prevalence of poor reading skills varies, and believed the consequential effect to include poor grades for students and difficulty trying to find or advance to a good job for adults. Saka, Bitagi and Garba (2012) in their submission were of the view that the majority of students read to pass examinations and to do assignments. The implication being that absence of examinations and assignments creates a distance between students and their books, while shifting their attention and energy to the net for frivolities. As to what these students prefer, the study of Chen, Hsiao, Chern and Chen (as cited in Almasi,

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Machumu & Zhu, 2017) reported a growing increase in the use of the Internet, which is gradually eroding reading culture among secondary school students.

The authors, however, observed that the students use the Internet also for activities related to schoolwork as well as more General activities, believing that Internet-based activities in schools may have several impacts on students` life at schools and thereafter. Besides, various studies have reported that the use of the internet can have benefits on the educational achievement of students.

Considering the influence of the use of the Internet on student learning performance or other outcomes, the studies of Davis (2001), Widyanto and Griffiths (2006), Odaci and Kalkkan (2010), and Odaci (2011) reported that it has either a negative influence or no significant influence. Furthermore, Young (as cited in Amasi et al., 2017) suggested that excessive internet usage among students have negative effects on students` academic success.

The studies of Olatokun (2008) and Nwagwu, Adekannbi and Bello (2008) reported that students chiefly utilize the Internet for academic purposes, such as preparation for assignments and examinations, rather than for leisure purposes. Though some students use the Internet much more than their school libraries, they also find the Internet as a source of general knowledge since it assists them in their reading habits as well as improving their academic performances.

Tarimo and Kavishe (2017), believed that by providing Internet access and enhancing its usage in schools, a chance to improve students` learning through access to the huge amount of information that is accessible on the internet is guaranteed.

Chen and Fu (2009) stated that the Internet has brought unparalleled opportunities to students on one hand and a major concern for parents on the other hand. This is because while online searching for information helps to boost examination scores and performances in assignments given to students, using the internet mainly for socializing and gaming results in poor reading habit and poor performance in examinations, general academic achievements as well as poor personal development. Since some internet use may seriously distract students, affect their reading habit and generally distort their academic achievements, students should employ effective use of the Internet.

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In the same vein, the studies of Adedotun (as cited in Yebowaah, 2018); Akande and Bamise (2017) reported that access to information brought about by the use of the Internet can influence the academic performance of the secondary school students. Also, Sahin, Balta and Ercan (2010) and Yebowaah (2018) believed that the use of credible Internet resources is of greater importance for academic activity, especially in high-class courses which require an academic review of the literature. This is not different from the belief of Kim (as cited in Yebowaah, 2018) who asserted that Internet use for educational purpose is the heart of adolescent academic achievement, as it helps students to broaden their academic knowledge, research and assignments by accessing information worldwide as well as enhances easy communication to the academic community.

On what needs to be done to avoid the negative influence of the Internet on the students, Chen *et al* as cited in Almasi, Machumu & Zhu (2017) noted that Internet usage is of benefit to students but believed that its negative use involves pornography addiction and excessive chat among secondary students, which have relatively negative effects on their academic success and life after school. In the same vein, Fuchs and Woessmann (2004); Kuhlemeier and Hemker (2007) believed that the Internet is used in daily life in educational settings; and as a result, its usage among secondary school students should be channeled appropriately to yield academic success.

Downes (2002) noted that if secondary-education teachers are to tailor their instruction to the needs of all students, they need to develop an understanding of the extent to which incoming students have access to and make use of the Internet at home. Campagna (as cited in Almasi *et al.*, 2017) emphasized that teachers should encourage students to come up with techniques for reading independently, which is one of the outcomes of reading habit.

In the same vein, Ngoumandjoka (as cited in Yebowaah, 2018) found that the Internet is not mostly used for academic purpose rather for recreational activities. The authors further buttressed that though students are more into the use of the Internet, in reality, they are using it mainly for non-academic purposes like emailing, gaming and social networking, which has contributed greatly to the decline in their reading culture. This brings to the fore the controversy among empirical studies on the influence of internet use on the academic performance and reading culture of secondary school students.

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Based on the literature review, it is clear that the Internet has serious effects on students and their reading culture. Students are so vulnerable to becoming addicted to the Internet to the extent that they do their homework not with their efforts but with complete dependence on Internet resources. This is to say that the influence of the Internet is in two faces, either negative or positive.

However, it would be inappropriate to conclude on the face the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State belong to. A critical look at available literature has revealed a gap in this respect, which forms the fulcrum of this research.

Methodology

The study was purely a descriptive survey because of the given large number of different sub-sets of the population involved. Thus, a descriptive survey design was adopted for the study owing to its usefulness in the field of computer Science. The population of the study was 278, which comprised senior secondary 2 and 3 classes (SS2 & SS3) in 2023/2024 academic session. Furthermore, the 278 students were sampled using the complete census sampling technique. Data was collected using a structured questionnaire titled: “Impact of Internet Facilities on Student’s Reading Culture Questionnaire (IIFSRCQ)”. The questionnaire was validated using face and content validation. The research instrument was validated by an expert in measurement and evaluation from the department of mathematics and Statistics in Federal University of Health Sciences Otukpo Benue State. Also, the instrument was distributed in Jesus College Otukpo Benue State for Pilot test among SS2 and SS3 students. A total of 50 copies of questionnaire was distributed to the students and retrieved. The data was analyzed using Cronbach Alpha. The overall Cronbach alpha value for the instrument was 87.53 which was found strong and reliable. Therefore, the instrument was used for the study. The items in the questionnaire consist of close-ended questions using four (4)-point scale of Strongly Agree (SA) = 4, Agree (A) = 3, Disagree (D) = 2 and Strongly Disagree (SD) = 1. The data collected were analyzed using frequency counts, simple percentages and mean scores. A mid-point of 2.5 was taken as the acceptance criterion for the positive response. This implied that questionnaire items with a mean score of 2.5 and above denote “agreed” while questionnaire items with a mean score below 2.5 denote “disagreed”. Presentation of the result was done using the frequency tables.

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Presentation of Results

This section deals with the analysis of the outcomes of the data collected. A total of 278 copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents but 275 copies were completed, returned and found useful for analysis. The presentation follows the order of the research objectives.

Research Objective 1: To find out if students of Wesley High school Otukpo make use of the Internet.

Table 1: Responses of the Students on the Use of Internet Facilities (N = 275)

S/N	Item statement	Yes	%	No	%
1	Do you make use of the Internet?	267	97.1	8	2.9

Source: Researcher's Field Survey

Table 1 shows the responses of the students on the use of the Internet. The result shows that the majority of the respondents 267(97.1%) indicated the use of the Internet, while few of the respondents that constitute 8(2.9%) indicated the non-use of the Internet. The result implies that students in Otukpo Local Government Area make use of the Internet.

This finding corroborates with the earlier studies carried out by Olatokun (2008), Tarimo and Kavishe (2017), which revealed the high use of the Internet among youths and secondary school students.

Research objective 2: To determine the students' reasons for their use of the Internet Facilities.

Table 2: Students' Reasons for Use of the Internet (N = 275)

S/N	Item Statement	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	I use the Internet for study purposes	75	120	18	62	2.76	Agreed
2	To prepare for examinations	114	126	12	20	3.21	Agreed
3	To do my assignments	92	51	90	42	2.70	Agreed
4	To chat with friends	114	96	35	30	3.07	Agreed
5	To watch movies	126	36	68	45	2.88	Agreed
6	To get information	91	114	40	30	2.97	Agreed

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7	To meet new friends	101	114	40	20	3.08	Agreed
8	To improve my reading habit	25	20	86	114	1.73	Disagreed
9	To improve my grades in school	35	50	96	94	2.09	Disagreed
10	To be like others	83	61	48	83	2.52	Agreed

Source: *Researcher's Field Survey*

Key: SA – Strongly Agreed; A – Agreed; D – Disagreed; SD – Strongly Disagreed

Table 2 showed the responses to the reasons for the use of the Internet by the students of Wesley High School Otukpo Benue State. From the analysis, majority of the students agreed with the following reasons for their use of the Internet: for studying purposes (2.76), to prepare for examinations (3.21), to do my assignments (2.70), to chat with friends (3.07), to see movies (2.88), to get information (2.97), to meet new friends (3.08) and to be like others (2.52). However, few respondents that constitute 1.73 and 2.09, respectively, indicated the use of the Internet to improve their reading habit and improve their grades in school.

Research Objective 3: To investigate perceived impact of the Internet facilities on the reading culture of the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State.

S/N	Item Statements	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Decision
1	It enhances my reading ability	20	15	173	67	1.96	Disagreed
2	It makes me active in class	77	138	40	20	2.99	Agreed
3	It increases my reading attention span	20	30	126	99	1.89	Disagreed
4	It helps me to have a better understanding of what I am reading	80	165	10	20	3.11	Agreed
5	Chatting with friends keeps me awake to read in the night	102	138	25	10	3.21	Agreed

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6	Internet articles motivate me to read	63	132	30	50	2.76	Agreed
7	The Internet distracts my reading	113	117	30	15	3.19	Agreed
8	The Internet exposes me to unimportant articles and write-ups	200	30	15	30	3.25	Agreed

Source: Researcher’s Field Survey

Key: SA – Strongly Agreed; A – Agreed; D – Disagreed; SD – Strongly Disagreed

Table 3 presents responses gotten on the perceived impact of the Internet on the reading culture of the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State. The result shows that out of the eight perceived impact investigated, six were agreed by the majority of the respondents that constitute 2.99, 3.11, 3.21, 2.76, 3.19, and 3.45, mean scores respectively. These impacts agreed by the respondents on item statements 2, 4, 5, 6, 7, and 8, include it makes me active in class, it helps me to have a better understanding of what I am reading, chatting with friends keep me awake to read in the night, Internet articles motivate me to read, the Internet distracts my reading and the Internet exposes me to unimportant articles and write-ups. Furthermore, majority of the respondents disagreed with item statements 1 and 3, which present that, it enhances my reading ability (1.96), and it increases my reading attention span.

Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between the students’ reasons for use of internet facilities and students on their reading culture

Statement	N	df	Mean	S.D	R	P-Value	Decision
Students’ Reasons for Use of the Internet	275		3.0000	.60302			
students reading culture	275	274	3.1667	.71774	.210	0.512	Not Significant

***p-value is significant at <=0.05, df: degree of freedom, S.d: standard deviation, R; relationship,*

The result showed the relationship between reasons for the use of internet facilities and reading culture of students. The result showed the mean and standard deviation

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of the variables. Students' reasons for use of internet facilities: 3.00(0.603) and students reading culture is 3.167(0.718). The degree of freedom is 274. The showed that the relationship between students' reasons for use of internet facilities is linear and weak $R = 0.210 \times 100 = 21\%$. In the same vein, the result further showed that there is no significant relationship between students' reasons for use of internet facilities and their reading culture as the p -value = 0.512. Since the P -value > 0.05, the hypothesis which state that there is no significant relationship between students' reasons for use of internet facilities and students reading culture is accepted.

Discussion of findings

The result showed that students in Otukpo Local Government Area make use of internet facilities. The finding corroborates with the earlier studies carried out by Olatokun (2008), Tarimo and Kavishe (2017), which revealed the high use of the Internet among youths and secondary school students. This is because majority of the students has a mobile device with internet facilities, also majority of the schools has internet enable e-library in the school premises. Also, the results showed that students of Wesley High school Otukpo Benue State make use of the Internet for numerous purposes aside to improve their reading habit and grades in school. Consequently, preparation for examinations had the highest mean score of 3.21. The finding of this study in this regard partially corroborates with the work of Luambano and Nawe (2004), which found the use of the Internet by students particularly for academic purposes as hugely influenced by their teachers who give them assignments requiring the use of the Internet. Thus, the studies revealed that students will only use the Internet if work given to them by their teachers requires them to use Internet facilities. In the same vein, the finding has shown different perceived impact of the Internet on the reading culture of the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State. Some of the impacts are positive, such as making them active in class, understand what they are reading, keep them awake to read in the night, and motivates them to read.

However, the negative impacts include the use of the internet distracting their reading, expose them to unimportant articles and write-ups, fails to enhance their reading ability, and failure to increase their reading attention. With these findings, one can deduce that the negative impacts of the Internet outweigh its positive impacts in the case of students of Wesley High Otukpo, Benue State. This study corroborates the earlier works of Davis (2001), Widyanto and Griffiths (2006), Odaci and Kalkkan (2010), and Odaci (2011), which reported that the use of the Internet by the students

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has either a negative impact or no significant impact on student learning performance or other outcomes.

The authors believed that if these young users are educated, they will use the Internet more for educational information resources rather than leisure or entertainment purposes, which will invariably improve their studying and reading culture. The findings of the study also corroborate with the study of Luambano and Nawe (2004), which investigated the use of the Internet by students of University of Dares Salaam and revealed that many of the students were not using the Internet for issues on education but for communication purposes such e-mailing and Face booking.

The study further showed that some students were using Internet services for pornographic viewing, which is an obvious misuse of Internet facility in an academic background, which negatively affects their reading culture and overall academic performance. The negative influence of the Internet as revealed by the above studies may be attributed to the findings of Manda (2005) that majority of students are not aware that Internet is a veritable tool for searching online academic information but rather jump into the Internet for other frivolous purposes.

Finally, the result showed that there is no significant relationship between students' reasons for use of internet facilities and their reading culture. The implication of this finding is due to the fact students reasons for use internet facilities is not necessarily because of academic purposes but may be for pleasure and socialization such as the use of social media platforms. The result is supported by Luambano and Nawe (2004), which found the use of the Internet facilities by students is not necessarily for academic purposes but for socialization and pleasure while just few uses internet facilities for academic purposes through their teacher's instructions.

Conclusion

A critical look at the Internet could make one believe that it is a blessing to our generation. However, many students are becoming addicted to the Internet as they spend more time playing games or just surfing the net without any particular reasons. Consequently, the time they spend on studying is automatically reduced, which in turn causes lower academic achievement, which could all be attributed to poor reading culture.

Findings of the study have shown that the students make use of the Internet for different reasons. These reasons include for studying purposes, to prepare for

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examinations, to do their assignments, to chat with friends, to watch movies, to get information, to meet new friends, and to be like others. However, the influence of the use of the Internet is various, which include making them active in class, helping them to have a better understanding of what they are reading, chatting with friends keeping them awake to read in the night, Internet articles motivating them to read, the Internet distracting their reading, as well as exposing them to unimportant articles and write-ups.

Based on the findings, the study concludes that the use of the Internet amidst some positive impacts negatively influences the reading culture of the students of Wesley High School, Otukpo Benue State, Nigeria.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made to ensure that the use of the Internet positively influences students' reading culture:

1. Management of secondary schools should organize seminars aimed at teaching the students the right use of the Internet to improve their reading culture.
2. Teachers in secondary schools should give assignments to students that will stimulate effective use of the Internet for academic purposes and improvement of reading culture.
3. School authorities and parents should closely monitor the Internet sites their students and wards visit to ensure that the utilization of the educational sites is encouraged.
4. There should be a law stipulating the age limit of the utilization of some Internet sites that are detrimental to the reading culture of the secondary school populace.
5. Secondary school students should be provided with adequate guidance on how to promote their reading culture through the appropriate use of the Internet.
6. Establishing, equipping and proper maintenance of school libraries as a means of improving the reading culture of the secondary school students should be highly considered and made a priority for all secondary schools

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Qualitative Study on Integration of Multiple-Strategies for Effective Implementation of STEAM Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined Qualitative study on integration of multiple-strategies for effective STEAM instructional approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria. The study adopted Qualitative Research Method Specifically Systematics Literature Review. Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) are the vehicles for technological advancement and national development. STEAM is essential for the socio-economic development of any nation, including Nigeria, since it is aimed at meeting the aspirations of the individual and the society. Science and Technology have become the major ingredients of economic and national advancement it influences every aspect of our lives. They are centrals to our welfare as individuals and society at large. The position and prestige of a Nation in world politics depends on the extent to which the country advances in STEAM. STEAM are activities embarked by man in search of basic needs for survival on the planet such as food, shelter and clothing. It's on this note that the paper examined some impactful pedagogical approaches in STEAM, among which include: Anchored Instruction, Reggio Emilia Approach, Predict-Observe-Explain Instruction, Ethno-Science Instruction and Conceptual Change Approach. It was concluded that these approaches enhance effective teaching and learning. Finally, the paper suggested among others, that STEAM teachers should incorporate these approaches in teaching of Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) at secondary school level of Education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Identification. Impactful, Pedagogical Approaches, STEAM

Introduction

Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) are the only vehicles for technological advancement and national development Suleman (2010). Science and Technology have become the major ingredients of economic and national advancement. Science and Technology influence every aspect of our lives. They are centrals to our welfare as individuals and society at large. The position and prestige of a Nation in world politics depends on the extent to which the country advances in Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics. Omosewo (2006) defines Science as an activity which results into a testable, falsifiable and veritable body of knowledge. It accelerates the pace of change in the world by providing the foundation for wealth and development and brings improvement to the quality of life. STEAM is activities embark by man in search of basic needs for survival on the planet such as food, shelter and clothing. It is as old as man himself and meant for him to practice Lestari and Fitriani (2016).

The knowledge of Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) is relevant and applicable in all areas of life endeavors, without knowledge of STEAM, life on the planets would be miserable and primitive. For instance, the production of essential human needs such as soap of all kinds, creams, drinks, petroleum and its bi-products, clothing, drugs and household utensils and chemicals for preservations of food items as well as textiles are all a product of principles of science chemistry. While the productions and supply of energy from different sources, means of transportation, and communication as well as the inventions of machines and materials that make life comfortable and enjoyable as well as what makes work easier and faster are all products of the basic knowledge and principles of technological Physics. The knowledge of Biology is applicable in medicine, physiology and anatomy to preserve and save lives. The knowledge of Agriculture gives way for the production of food and animals which serve as meat and sources of protein as well as raw materials for industries.

The National Policy on Education (NPE) (2013), emphasized the importance of science and technology education at all levels of schooling, at the primary school level the objective of science education is to lay a sound knowledge in scientific and reflective thinking. There was inculcation of literacy and numeracy and the study of science and introductory technology. At the secondary school level, the aim is for the preparation of students for useful living in the society and for higher education. The

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objective of the science policy is to equip students with adequate scientific knowledge to live effectively in modern age of science and technology. To achieve this, integrated science is offered as a core subject at basic level (from primary one to the Junior Secondary School three) and science subjects (physics, chemistry biology) as parts of core subjects and technical subjects at the Senior Secondary School (SSS) level. At the higher education level the aim is the development of higher level manpower. Government policy at this level is that course content of science and technology is with professional career and it must reflect the national requirement through consultation among Universities (Babajide, 2015). Despite the importance of Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) in national development, the research works carried out by Omosewo (2001), Wokocha (2002), Olaniyi (2004), Adesoji (2008), Sulieman (2010) and Adeniran (2011), it has been stated that methods of instruction affect the performance of students in sciences and other related subjects. Hence, this study focuses on identifying some impactful pedagogical approaches in Science Technology, Engineering, Arts and Mathematics (STEAM) and other related subject for effective teaching and learning.

Integration of Anchored Strategy for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Anchor instructional approach is one of the application models of constructivist approach, is a learning approach, which prescribes that all learning activities should be organized around a story, problem or case that is called anchor. This approach also provides the students with the opportunity to apply the information they have gained on different real-life cases and thus serves as a bridge between school life and real life. The materials within the border of programmes basing on anchor learning are generally technology-based and they contribute to students' success in a positive manner. Anchored instruction is a technology-based learning approach which stresses the importance of placing learning within a meaningful, problem-solving context. A form of situated learning, anchored instruction uses context-- stories or micro--- to situate the learning and application of knowledge. In other words, the learning is contextualized to provide students with realistic roles that serve to enhance the learning process.

Anchored instruction is a framework for learning that emphasizes complex problem solving in integrated learning contexts. Integrated learning contexts take on the form of drawing realistic connections, making learning meaningful for students, and

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forming connections within and between content domains. An anchored instruction activity supports learning opportunities that relate to and extend thinking to other content areas.

Learning and teaching activities are designed around an "anchor" which is often a story, adventure, or situation that includes a problem or issue to be resolved and that is of interest to the students. The "anchoring" refers to the bonding of the content within a realistic and authentic context: Anchored modules typically embed all of the information need— embedded data or hints are used as scaffolding— to solve the problem, making it easier to manage in environments with limited time or limited resources. Apart from creating specific contexts and scenarios, anchored instruction is also considered as an important approach to active learning which in particular stresses the importance of active involvement of learners, either mentally or physically, to achieve meaningful learning (Hativa 2000).

Pedagogical Foundations of Anchored Strategy for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

The Group of Vanderbilt Cognition and Technology (CTGV) first developed anchor learning in 1990 under the leadership of John Bransford. Although many people have been contributing to the theory and research of anchor learning, the leader of this theory is Bransford. It evolved from the idea put forward by situated cognition which highlights the situated nature, that is, context specific feature of knowledge (Brown et al. 1989).

Anchor learning, one of the application models of constructivist approach, is a learning approach, which prescribes that all learning activities should be organized around a story, problem or case that is called anchor. This approach also provides the students with the opportunity to apply the information they have gained on different real life cases and thus serves as a bridge between school life and real life. The materials within the border of programmes basing on anchor learning are generally technology-based and they contribute to students' success in a positive manner.

Application of anchored Strategy for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

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The primary application of anchored instruction has been to elementary reading, language arts and mathematics skills. The CLGV has developed a set of interactive videodisc programs called the 'Jasper Woodbury Problem Solving Series'. These programs involve adventures in which mathematical concepts are used to solve problems. It's applicable in a variety of problems. Whitehead claimed that learning environment produced memorized knowledge. On the other hand, anchor teaching is based on researching in laboratory and class, and thus tries to help the knowledge to be less memorized than the knowledge gained by means of traditional class activities such as remembering and exercise. This fundamental principle is a good example of structures' learning that emphasized the importance of inclusive learning. The techniques that help anchor teaching to be used effectively are target structures, students' active participation, content, applicability, awareness and cognitive apprenticeship.

Steps of implementing anchor Strategy in Classroom for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Bottge, (2002) identified seven steps to be considered when implementing an anchored learning in class, the following are steps to be followed when design anchored class; Choosing a field of study, Defining an anchor, Introducing the anchor, Discussing the anchor, Establishing groups and research questions and Running the research

Integration of Reggio Emilia Strategy for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Reggio Emilia Approach is a cooperative or interactive approach in which pupils do the learning by themselves and assist each other when the necessary materials are provided. It is a child-centered learning approach which involves children interacting with each other in the classroom and sharing ideas with one another. It also involves bringing in another teacher (instructor) to teach with the class teacher, thus enhancing efficiency. Reggio Emilia approach is an early childhood education which originated in Italy in 1945 after World War II.

In Reggio Emilia approach, classroom work is based on building the cognitive, social, language, creative and physical skills that empower pupils to gain and own learning experiences. Each child in the class has an opportunity to share, observe, play, learn and construct ideas on his/her own by visiting sites of interest provided in the

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corners of class- room which are full of open-ended materials like stones, sticks, bottle caps, blocks of many varieties and brain flatness in a collaborative approach. Children use their senses to explore and direct their educational experiences. They are given the freedom to select pre-prepared activities to work with. This means that they make incorrect attempts to solve a game or puzzle as classrooms are devised to be an ex- tension of children’s world. It is a pedagogy which focus-es on preschool and primary education. It was first developed in 1945 by psychologist Loris Malaguzzi and parents in the surrounding area of Reggio Emilia in Italy where the philosophy gets its name. They believed that children would benefit from a new and progressive way of learning (Owulabi, 2017).

The Reggio Emilia approach believes that children are capable individual that comes to school with wealth of experiences and knowledge and hence should be supported to communicate their ideas in a variety of ways. To the proponents, young children are powerful, active, and competent architects of their own growth, on the basis of their own particular experiences and level of consciousness. In a classroom where all resources and materials are thought provoking and inviting, the children are inspired to think critically and it provides children with a lot of learning opportunities that encourage them to explore, discover and solve problems on their own.

Reggio Emilia approach strongly believes that children learn through interaction with friends, parents, teachers as well as interactions with the learning environment. According to Kelemen, (2013), REA approach is committed to create learning conditions that encourage and facilitate the child to build his own power of thinking through the incorporation of the whole of expressive, communicative, and cognitive.

Pedagogical Foundation of Reggio Emilia Strategy for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

The Reggio Emilia Approach derives its name from its place of origin, Reggio Emilia, a city located in Emilia Romagna in Northern Italy. Shortly after the Second World War, Loris Malaguzzi, a young teacher and the founder of this educational approach, joined forces with the parents of this region to provide care for young children. They felt that it is in the early years of development that children form who they are as individuals. This led to the creation of a program based on: the principles of respect, responsibility, and community; the value of exploration and discovery; a supportive and enriching environment; and the interests of the children through a self-guided

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curriculum. Originally inspired by the need of women to return to the workforce, over the last 50 years, this educational philosophy has caught the attention of early childhood educators worldwide.

Reggio Emilia is a town in the northern part of Italy. This area is the richest and most developed area of Italy with its population of four million people. This area is also the most-developed area of Italy which provides the social aid the most (Cited in Aslan, 2007 from Cadwell, 1997). This approach was supported by Louris Malaguzzi in Reggio Emilia city and emerged in preschool education institutions with the participation of families living in the area (Pekdogan, 2012). After the World War II, some families in the village of Villa Cella in Reggio Amilila town of Italy wanted to build a school for their kids and start the building of schools with the money they obtained by selling the tanks, trucks and horses remaining from the war. Reggio Emilia Municipal School was opened with the support of Malaguzzi and the families in question. With this approach, the city of Reggio Emilia was started to be mentioned as "the golden standard" in early childhood education (Pekdogan, 2012).

Application of Reggio Emilia Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Arseven, (2014) viewed Reggio Emilia as an alternative approach for educating children and generally it has the qualities of constructivist education generally. This approach, which aims for children to solve the problems he encounters himself, is also centered on children and family, society and teachers take part in this approach. It is necessary for a child to participate in activities himself and take part actively. Children growing up according to the Reggio Emilia approach become individuals with high self-confidence, improved personalities, improved production level who are acting in solidarity.

Reggio Emilia Approach is a method or approach to education, especially for young children. REA is different from other approaches. REA is committed to "create learning conditions that will encourage and facilitate the child to build up the strength of thinking itself through the incorporation of the whole of expressive, communicative, and cognitive" (Vecchi, 2010).

Children are encouraged to describe their understanding through one of the symbolic languages, including drawing, sculpture, dramatic playing, and writing. They work together to solve the problems that arise. The teacher facilitates and then observes

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the debate over the extent to which the child can solve the problem. Revising the drawings or ideas are performed if necessary, and the teachers let the children repeating the activity and modify each other's work for a collective purpose to be a better understanding of the topic. Teachers are involved in the exploration and evaluation process and pay attention to all children development outcomes in resolving problems based on their understanding.

Predict-Observe-Explain (POE) Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

The POE learning model is a learning model with the knowledge development process, which begins with predicting solution over a problem, and then it goes with conducting experiment to prove the prediction, and finally it ends with explaining the result of experiment (White and Gystone, 2006). Kearney (2002) claims that POE learning model is a learning method, which involves the students to predict and discuss considerations for their prediction, to observe directly, and to compare the result obtained to their former prediction. This learning method makes the instruction more exciting and improves the conceptual mastery of the students.

Meanwhile, Tuckerman (2007) argues that POE learning model is a technique to ensure that the students articulate their former ideas with activities that lead them to understanding. The phases of the POE learning model include the following: (1) the students are introduced to a situation so that they are able to make predictions based on their experience; (2) the students are requested to make predictions and give reasons for their predictions; (3) the students do activity observations; (4) the students explain the differences between what they predict and the results of their predictions; and (5) the students are requested to propose new ideas to explain their understanding.

Predict-Observe Explain instructional strategy is a form of deductive reasoning, that is, reasoning from predictions to observation and it is significant in allowing learners to engage in learning tasks in small groups rather than the traditional teacher-led whole class environment. It allows learners to work at their own paces gives them the opportunity to go back and edit their initial responses and take control of the demonstrations. It makes learners to be autonomous and to thoroughly discuss and reflect on their predictions, reasons and observations. The observation phase of the

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instructional strategy is crucial and its effectiveness provides the feedback to learners on their predictions.

In regard to science learning, teachers can involve students to make hypotheses, investigate, and analyze data to develop students' thinking (Wardani, 2017). One model of learning that is capable of developing students' thinking optimally is Predict, Observe and Explain (POE) learning model. POE learning models can include ways that can be taken by a teacher to assist students in improving the understanding of the concept and their psychomotor. POE learning model engages students in predicting a phenomenon, observations through demonstrations or experiments, and finally explain the results of the demonstration as well as their hypothesis. By doing this way, acquired knowledge will be preserved in students' memory and increase students' science processing skills (Zulaeha, Darmadi & Werdhiana, 2014). To make an active teaching-learning process, students need to be able to clearly express themselves in written form and verbal form.

Pedagogical Foundation of POE Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Learning with a constructivist approach requires the use of various strategies and techniques. POE is one of the strategies included in this approach. This strategy is characterized by the steps of estimating, verifying predictions, defining observations, comparing and explaining predictions with observations, revealing students' prior knowledge, and allowing them to find alternative solutions to complex problems (Köse et al., 2003). It was first developed by Champagne, Klopfer, and Anderson in 1979 to measure the thinking skills of first-year physics students at the University of Pittsburgh. It was later given the name POE by White and Gunston in (1992).

The Predict-Observe-Explain instructional strategy has been described as a relatively new approach to the teaching of science (Zuziwe, 2006). Champagne, Klopfer and Anderson (1979) were the first to design the strategy as –Demonstrate-Observe – Explain (DOE). This strategy was initially used to probe the thinking of first year Physics students at the University of Pittsburgh. Gunstone and White reworked the DOE into Predict-Observe-Explain model (POE) in 1981.

The POE learning model can be used to recognize the initial ideas of students, to give information to the teacher about the students' thinking, to generate discussion, and to motivate them to investigate concepts (White and Gustone, 1992). The roles of the

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teacher in the POE learning method are as a motivator and a facilitator. As a motivator, the teacher is expected to be able to stimulate the students to solve problems through the following measures: (1) proposing relevant, challenging, and curious problems for the students, (2) trying to get the students cognitively active in each phase of the POE learning model; and (3) developing interaction among the students through questions and answers and discussions.

Stages of POE Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

The Process of Predict-Observe-Explain Instructional Strategy consists of three procedural steps of prediction, observation and explanation phases. The Predict—Observe—Explain steps of Gunstone and White (1998) are:

Prediction Phase: Learners are presented with some questions to which they are expected to supply answers (predictions). They are also to give and discuss reasons for their predictions. It is a process to make a prediction toward a problem given by the teacher. In making the prediction, the students have thoughts the reasons why they make such a prediction. In this process, they are given an extensive freedom to arrange their prediction including its reasons. Therefore, the teacher should not limit the students' thoughts so that they produce many ideas and concepts. In this prediction process, the teacher can also understand the misconceptions made by the students. This is important for the teacher to help the students to develop right concepts.

Observation Phase: This is an experimentation phase where learners verify their predictions.

Activities here include reading textual materials and performing experiments in order to observe the real life situations or events in the laboratory. It is a process to investigate and observe what happens. In other words, the students are asked to do experiments to examine the prediction righteousness that they deliver. In this phase, the students do investigation or experiment to examine the prediction that they convey. The students observe what happens, and the most important thing in this measure is confirmation on their prediction.

Explanation Phase: Learners explain their observations and compare them with their initial predictions. Conceptual changes occur here and new knowledge or ideas

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are generated. There is rejection, acceptance or modification of learners' initial predictions as the case may be. It is a process to give explanation mainly the ones about the conformity between the prediction and the result of experiment of the observation phase. If the result of prediction is suitable with that of observation and after they obtain explanations about their prediction righteousness, the students will be more convinced about their concepts. However, when their prediction is false, the students can look for explanation why their prediction is not right. The students will experience the change of concepts from the false to the right ones. In this regard, they can learn from the mistake, and learning things from mistake will not be easily vanished or forgettable.

Integration of Ethno-Science Instructional Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Ethno-science instructional strategy involves the organization of instruction based on diverse cultural context. The strategy requires the teacher to draw analogy and explanations from traditional culture while focusing on the basic science needed by students in the society. Ethno-science instructional strategy according to Abonyi (2014) involves the teacher designing practical models of integration of indigenous and cosmopolitan knowledge systems with a view to achieving a balanced process of development and change. Ethno-science learning can transform teacher centered learning into centered on students as a contextual and meaningful learning (Sumarni, 2018).

Ethno-science is an interdisciplinary science that combines human and cultural anthropology with science education. The study of the scientific knowledge that is gained by examining the local knowledge that is contained in the culture of a community or ethnic group. Local awareness is derived from local communities' thought and ideas about daily life, including customs, beliefs and views on the world (Lestari & Fitriani, 2016). Ethno-science, rooted in students' lives, is a type of contextual experience (Setiawan et al., 2017). Ethno-science will allow students to investigate the facts and phenomena present in society and be integrated with scientific knowledge (Melyasari et al., 2018). Ethno-science can captivate learners because it's connected to their own regional identity. Ethno-science may also encourage knowledge and preserve local culture (Supriyadi & Nurvitasari, 2019). Ethno-science can make it easier for students to dig facts and phenomena that exist in society and can be integrated with science (Khoiri et al., 2019).

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Pedagogical Foundation of Ethno-science Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Ethno-science is a term and study that came into anthropological theory in the 1960s. Often referred to as "indigenous knowledge," it introduces a perspective based on native perceptions. Ethno-science looks at the intricacies of the connection between culture and its surrounding environment (Abonyi, 2002). The term ethno-science according to Okwara & Upu, 2017 refers to the materials, ideas, beliefs and technology in a given society or environment, that derive from the past and present cultural practices and traditions. It is knowledge that is indigenous to a particular people.

Snow (1972) reported that the integration of indigenous knowledge and ethno-scientific approaches into contemporary frameworks for instructions began around 1960 to 1965 with the works of Carl Hime, a supervising teacher for science and math at Many Farms High School, Many Farms, Arizona, United States of America. The emphasis in introducing Ethno-science at Many Farms then, was on life and ecological-environmental aspect of science.

The implementation of the ethno-scientific teaching approach is therefore based on the recommendations for teaching science by the Science for All Movement (UNESCO, 1991) which are:

- i. The content, language, symbols, designs, and purpose of the curriculum should be linked to day-to-day experiences and goals of the children;
- ii. Theory should be linked to practice, human purpose, the quality of life, and in-school experience to out-of-school experience; and
- iii. Teaching and learning should begin from the beliefs, interests, and learning skills that students bring to the classroom and should help each of them extend and revise their ability and understanding (Hiwatig, 2008).

Application of Ethno-Science Instructional Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Ethno-science instruction is applicable in science teaching, technology, elementary reading and arts. Ethno-science instruction is similar to the modified lecture method in terms of contents, basic instructional objectives, and mode of evaluation. The only

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differences are in the instructional activities and materials in which teachers in the ethno-science instruction group make use of additional information from common local beliefs and sayings stating their cultural meanings and relating them to science concepts being taught and learnt while also assessing and obtaining additional information from the learners and allowing them form their own opinion on the concept. Learners would also be allowed to utilize additional instructional materials reflecting local beliefs and expressions.

Conceptual Change Instructional Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Conceptual change instructional strategy is an instructional strategy in which the teacher acts as a facilitator by asking thought-provoking questions, conducting experiments, and leading guided discussions that help students think about constructing scientifically valid ideas. More specifically, it is a strategy that assists the student in distinguishing earlier conceptions and newly introduced scientific concepts, as well as how they impact each other as the learner quietly works out his ideas from the former idea and the newly introduced concept.

Conceptual change teaching as a learning approach that alters an existing conception, such as a belief, idea, or way of thinking. Conceptual change differs from other types of learning procedures in that it involves a shift or restructure of existing information and beliefs. Learning for conceptual change is more than just learning new facts or skills. An existing conception is significantly altered or even replaced in conceptual change, and this becomes the conceptual framework that students use to solve problems, explain phenomena, and function in their reality.

Conceptual change methodology, which is developed based on constructive approach and widely used in teaching-learning activities recently, considers students' previous knowledge and plans teaching activities based on this (Canpolat & Pınarbaşı, 2002; Dhindsa & Anderson, 2004; DiSessa, 2002; Mason, 2002; Uzuntiryaki, Çakır & Geban, 2001; Yürük, 2000). Conceptual change methodology represents an alternative approach that encourages students' to change their ideas from misconceptions to scientific correct facts (Broughton et al., 2010; Canpolat & Pınarbaşı, 2002).

Conceptual change approach that is commonly used in education recently takes students' previous knowledge into account and education program is planned based

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on these (Canpolat & Pınarbaşı, 2002; DiSessa, 2002; Dhindsa & Anderson, 2004; Mason, 2002; Uzuntiryaki et al., 2001; Yürük, 2000).

Pedagogical Foundation of Conceptual Change Approach for Effective STEAM Instructional Approach at Secondary School Level of Education in Nigeria

Conceptual change approach was proposed by Posner, Strike, Hewson, and Gertzog in 1982. Posner et al. in Özdemir and Clark (2007), described four necessary conditions (dissatisfaction, intelligibility, plausibility, and fruitfulness). Posner et al. in Özdemir and Clark (2007) proposed a model of conceptual change, which had four conditions, taking into cognizance the four conditions such as:

- i. Learners must become dissatisfied with their existing conceptions - they must have experiences, which lead them to lose confidence in the ability of their current conception to solve problems,
- ii. The new conceptions must be intelligible - the student must be able to understand sufficiently how experience can be structured by the new concept,
- iii. The new conceptions must appear plausible - any new concept adopted must at least appear to have the ability to solve the problems generated by its predecessors and,
- iv. The new conceptions must be fruitful - it should have the capacity to open up new areas of inquiry.

Conclusion

This study adopted a qualitative research method particularly systematic literature review on integration of multiple-strategies for effective STEAM instructional approach at secondary school level of education in Nigeria. The pedagogical approaches highlighted implement conceptual change in science teaching, emphasizing teaching for critical thinking and problem solving, encouraging teaching for transfer of learning, enriching socio-cultural learning, providing equal access for all participants in science.

Suggestions

In line with the review of the study, it is suggested that science teachers should:

1. Incorporate the used of Anchored Instruction as teaching strategy in teaching STEM.

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2. Reggio Emilia, Predict Observe Explain, Conceptual Change should also be used in teaching for easy understanding of STEM concepts.
3. Ethno-Science Instructional Approaches is a promising strategy for effective teaching and learning of STEM, it should be adopted.
4. Conceptual Instructional Approach is a very good approach to be adopted by STEAM teachers in Nigerian secondary schools for better understanding of concepts.

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Qualitative Study on Curriculum and Technological Trends in Smart Education at Secondary School Level-of-Education in Nigeria: A systematic Review

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Abstract

The paper systematically reviewed curriculum and technological trends in smart education at secondary school level-of-education in Nigeria. It therefore discussed the concept of smart education. In view of the growing recognition and adoption of smart education globally, Artificial intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT) block chain and cloud computing technologies have been deliberated among other several curriculum and technological trends associated with smart education at secondary school level-of-education. It highlighted smart education framework for possible practice and some considerations for effective integration of smart education at secondary school level. Also, the paper concluded that there are several surmountable challenges that may affect the effective integration of smart education at secondary schools in Nigeria including inadequate smart education infrastructures at secondary schools level-of-education and finally among others, it was suggested that opportunities for secondary school teachers and students to attend training aimed at providing relevant ICT skills and knowledge to enable them function effectively should be provided.

Keyword: Smart education, curriculum trends, Smart technology

Introduction

Information Technologies will continue to pervasively transform educational practices around the world. Information Technology (IT) has received considerable attention in education and recognized as one of the most important modern innovation that transformed the teaching and learning process (Haliru & Aliyu, 2023). Various nations are at various pace in technology integration into education system with advanced nations having attained remarkable progress and therefore able to keep

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pace with technological advancement. Efforts to educate citizens and prepare them for the 21st century gave birth to Smart Education (SM) project globally. While some countries (Malaysia, Singapore, Finland, UAE etc.) have already developed and implemented smart education, others are at fluid stage of the project. Smart education aimed to develop individuals into future global citizens by utilizing information technologies to provide 21st century qualities, competencies and responsibilities. Smart education embraces technologies to provide self-learning mode where each students can learn at their speed. It is new paradigm aims at creating smart learners through smart schools. Salem, Mikhalkina and Nikitaeva (2019) see smart education as interdisciplinary area, encompassing many aspects of the educational technologies that cover instruction, training, teaching, learning, pedagogy, communication and collaboration.

Smart Education is a new educational perspective on teaching and learning that redefines the new role of teachers and learners in the learning process and thus seeks to supplant traditional practices which failed to optimize learning for each individual learner. Smart learning environment as technology element of smart education is catalyst for adoption of smart pedagogies. In the view of Zhu and He in Zhu, Sun and Riezebos (2016) the essence of smarter education is to create intelligent environments by using smart technologies, so that smart pedagogies can be facilitated as to provide personalized learning services and empower learners to develop talents of wisdom that have better value orientation, higher thinking quality, and stronger conduct ability.

Implementing technology-facilitated form of education such as SE requires understanding and consideration of basic features, purposes and principles of smart technologies. Smart education take place in smart schools which by their organizational and infrastructural settings take account of individuality and personalized learning. Implementing smart education has to go along way with digitalization of educational landscape.

Concept of Smart Education

The term "smart" according Salem, Mikhalkina and Nikitaeva (2019) is often associated with the technological aspect and the emergence of smart technologies in education, including smart board, smart screens, smart course and a wide range of tools combined in the concept of "smart technologies. Smart education is a new

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educational paradigm that is based on all relevant perspectives, embraces the future as well as the past, and provides clear guidelines for intelligent education in a smarter world (Zhu, Sun & Riezebos, 2016). With increasing role of technologies in education, smart technologies provide many opportunities for accessing content, communication and collaboration in a smart environment. Smart education is the process of optimally managing human, economic and technological resources from educational institutions and research centres (Nwankwo & Mkpa, 2023). Smart education is therefore technology- enhanced, resource-enriched and self-directed form of learning. Smart education involves a comprehensive modernization of all educational processes, as well as methods and technologies used into this process (Salem, Mikhalkina & Nikitaeva, 2019). Smart education can be seen as the education that makes use of smart technologies to shift the educational paradigm in the future. Modernization of educational processes requires proactive engagement with smart learning technologies.

Technology refers to practical application of knowledge for the benefit of people. In the context of education, relevant technologies include such physical things as personal computers and handheld devices as well as non-physical things such as algorithms used to mine data from large data-sets and use findings to make adjustments in terms of information representation and delivery as well as in terms of assessment and evaluation (Spector, 2016). Both teachers and students stand to benefit from smart learning technology. Teachers can use smartphones, tablets and laptops to generate their lessons. Accessibility and affordability have been facilitated by smart technology. Technology plays an important role in availability and accessibility of learning contents including for disabled students (Palanivel, 2020). One of the important characteristic of smart learning technology is “support for learning. To this end, Spector (2016) asserted that Smart learning technologies do need to exhibit support for learning, either directly or through support for instructional design processes intended to promote learning. Idea of learning that is engaging, effective, and efficient should be the focus. Moreover, technologies that empower learners, instructors, or instructional designers by adapting to their needs and situations can be considered smart learning technologies. From foregoing, a technology must possess the features of adaptability and intelligence for to be considered smart learning technology. Adaptability means that the technology has the ability to detect relevant details of the situation and then select, modify and deploy an appropriate response.

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Curriculum and Technological Trends in Smart Education at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Smart technologies are the driving forces of smart education ideology. Advancement in technology has powerful and promising impact on education and mode of instruction. Technology has redefined the roles of major actors in education industry including teachers and students. Today's generation of learners are digital natives and thus require integration of technology into their daily lives both in school and beyond. In this regard, Palanivel (2020) stated that intelligent technologies, such as cloud computing, learning analytics, Big Data, IoT, wearable technology etc., promote the emergence of smart education. Some of the emerging technologies germane to smart education are discussed below:

Artificial Intelligence (AI) at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

AI has remarkably change the educational landscape globally. AI enables the creation of computerized machinery to mimic human behavior and certain psychological features. With AI in education many barriers associated with traditional education are beginning to give way for a more robust, student-centric mode of delivery of education. AI technology can scale easily, quickly and facilitate a one-on-one interface with a learner (Palanivel, 2020).

Block chain Technology at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Security and quality of information and all important transaction is key in any industry. Block chain enables protection of digital transaction in a smart education. Block chain help to minimize threat to security of records, prevent alteration and unauthorized access. The most common use of this technology is for providing authentic records of students' credentials and competences.

Big Data Technology at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Big data has transformed education from traditional to smart system. Like other smart learning technologies, big data platform can offer both a data archival and advanced analytics to the challenges in education. Big data analytics can be applied to all of the areas of student enrollment, student management, and reporting with advanced research. The advantages of using Big Data in education are reliability, flexibility and efficiency (Palanivel, 2020).

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Cloud Computing Technology at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

As smart technology, cloud computing enables storage, management and processing of data using network of internet-hosted computers instead of local sever or personal computer. Palanivel (2020) identifies the following role of cloud computing in smart education: Creating a flexible, unified and open platform for education information; sharing of educational resources among developers, teachers and students; and alleviating the information gap between different areas of today's education.

Some of the advantages of cloud computing system include reduced cost, wide access to educational contents, enhanced teaching and learning, openness to new technologies, offline usage among others.

Data Science Technology at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

The data science model understand the problem domain and the data, preparation of the data, mining of the data and evaluation of the discovered knowledge. For analysis, it give rise to new important methodological developments in smart education. The development requires experts from educational science and data science.

Machine Learning Technology at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Machine Learning (ML) technology is a subset of AI. ML applications designed to benefit the education community, such as learning analytics, content analytics, scheduling algorithms, grading systems, cognitive psychology and active learning and experimental design. ML has the potential to improve student engagement, create clearer communication channels between teachers and students, and develop less biased grading systems.

Internet of Thing (IoT) at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

IoT is described as an ecosystem of connected things coupled with sensors, that capture information in their environment, store, process and analyze either at the device itself or in the cloud or remotely to create value. IoT provides opportunity for improving the quality learning and efficiency of administrative tasks in education. Smart campus, smart classroom, digital content, smart examination, remote learning, campus safety are among other results of IoT (Planivel, 2020). Similarly IoT

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has given rise to a number of applications an IoT-powered appliances for smart education. For instance smart lightning and smart heating can be ensure efficient energy consumption and control of the cooling systems of smart classrooms.

Learning Analytics Technology at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

This aspect of smart technology plays crucial role in smart education. Learning analytics is defined as the use of educational data and educational models to predict the progress and performance of students, and the ability to take action on that information (Palanivel, 2020). This technology improves and optimizes the learning capabilities. This analytics technology can be used to find the educational sentiments of students and what subjects they should learn to reach their desired level of competence.

Smart Education Framework for Practice at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Smart education practice requires smart learning environment that promote efficient and effective learning. Smart Education redefines the role of teachers and learners in education. As such new skills and capabilities are key to this new educational perspective. The adoption of new pedagogies to transform practice at scale requires connections between pedagogy and technology, underpinned by knowledge of how to bring about change (Shoikova, Nikolov & Kovatcheva, 2017). The three essential elements that underpinned smart education framework proposed by in Zhu, Sun and Riezebos (2016) are as follows: Teaching Presence, Technology and Learner presence, respectively.

Teaching Presence at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

This describes the teaching role in a smart education system as instructional design, facilitation and direct instruction, and technological support. Teaching presence refers to student-centred, personalized, and collaborative pedagogical models to design learning in technology-facilitated environments, facilitating the learning process by promoting interactions and providing feedback/direct instructions, and supporting learners to use technologies (Zhu, Sun & Riezebos, 2016).

The three major components of teaching presence are *instructional design, facilitation and direct instruction, and technological support.*

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Instructional design. This involves setting up learning objectives, organizing learning activities, and providing rules and guidance in a technology-facilitated environment. Technology use in education has led to emergence of new instructional approaches characterized as student-centric, personalized and collaborative. Students' active participation is central to student-centred approach to teaching. With smart technologies, Smart education helped to overcome barriers in traditional practice such as meeting the individual differences by way of personalized learning paths (Web-based learning system). Collaboration is on the notion of the knowledge building community where the focus is on problem solving and collective knowledge building rather than passing on knowledge.

Facilitation and direct instruction: unlike in traditional setting, in the smart education environment the teacher assume the new responsibilities of facilitator and encourage participation among the students. The teacher also provides intellectual and scholarly leadership and share their subject matter knowledge with students" (Anderson et al., 2001).

Technological support. Teachers are required to provide technical support to the students. For teachers to function effectively they have to competent enough to support the learners to achieve the goal of smart education. Digital divides among students from high-tech and low-tech homes further make this imperative.

Learner presence at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Succinctly put, learner presence refers to proactive role a learner plays in the learning process. Zhu, Sun and Riezebos (2016) conceptualize learner presence in the smart education framework as consisting of three major components: *autonomous learner, collaborative learner* and *an efficient technology user*.

Autonomous learner. Individuality is key to smart education and learners require a match between their personal talents and interests and learning experiences provided for optimal learning. Proactive participation is promoted by personal abilities, desires and interests.

Collaborative learner. Although individuality is dominant factor in technology-facilitated learning setting, collaboration plays important role as it help students to

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learn from each other. Collaborative learners acquire skills such teamwork and role identification among others.

Efficient technology user. For optimal learning to occur in the smart education environment, learners should be able use technology for specific learning purpose. Digital skills play fundamental role for learners to efficiently interact with smart technologies.

Facilitating the integration of Smart Education at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Smart education is an embryonic project in Nigeria with smart schools being set up in every state in the country. The universal Basic Education Commission had recently signed a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) with Korean international Commission Agency to kick-start the project in Nigeria. As new education practice, implementation of smart education is not without flaws. Some of the considerations for effective integration of smart education in the country are discussed below:

Development of highly trained teachers at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Smart education redefines the role of teachers. The interaction between internet of things (IoT) and learners is facilitated by competent teachers with relevant technological and pedagogical knowledge and skills. Education system in Nigeria has been plagued by inadequate trained teachers which affect the implementation of any programme. To this end, Haliru and Aliyu (2023) stated that teachers grappled with problem of lack of adequate training on how to function effectively using the new technologies. Smart education requires trained teachers that can operate smart technologies such as smart board and smart phones, tablet in order to facilitate learning and interaction in smart learning environment. Both smart educators and learners must develop digital skills for optimum participation in smart education.

Equally important are the related concepts of computer self-efficacy and computer literacy. While the former implies judgment of one's capability to use computer the later refers to one's ability to execute assigned tasks with computer. Both computer self-efficacy and literacy have significant impact on teachers' and students' computer usage in technology-enhanced learning environment.

Provision of sustainable technological infrastructure at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Smart schools are uniquely different from conventional schools in terms of provision of smart technologies. Smart devices- smart board/interactive white board, smart table, mobile technologies (tablet, laptop) and video conferencing are associated infrastructure available in smart classrooms. No one is able to use and enjoy the benefits of electronic devices and information technologies unless connected with internet (Idris & Benjamin, 2022). Poor or lack internet connectivity and irregular power supply are among major setbacks to technology integration in education in Nigeria. There is a plethora of smart technologies to create the environment for learning to happen. Such technologies require reliable connectivity and electricity to function and facilitate learning.

Adequate funding is key to success at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Procurement of ICT infrastructures and their regular maintenance and replacement of malfunctioned ones as well as internet subscriptions justify a need for funds successful functioning of smart schools. Nwankwo and Mpka (2023) stated that government has to make funds available for the equipment and manpower required for the implementation of smart schools.

Formulation of policy framework at secondary school level of education in Nigeria

Policies serve important purpose not only in education but all aspects of human endeavor. Government should formulate policies to guide and regulate the implementation of smart education in the country. It is through these policies that personnel development and recruitment can be controlled and regulated.

Conclusion

Smart education hold a promising future for secondary school level of education in Nigeria. It is a form of education that can be best described as technology-enhanced, resource-enriched and self-directed learning. The emergence of smart education was

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facilitated by irresistible advancement of technologies and their wide spread application particularly in educational sector. Smart education has become an integral part of initiatives to improve the quality of secondary education in Nigeria. This educational practice has long been operational in some developed countries, it appears to be new and relatively recent innovation in developing countries. There are several surmountable challenges that may affect the implementation of smart education in secondary schools in Nigeria and other developing countries. One fundamental issue is that of inadequate smart education infrastructures in secondary schools which government must give priority in order to achieve the desired results.

Suggestions

1. There should be opportunities for secondary school teachers and students to attend training aimed at providing relevant ICT skills and knowledge to enable them function effectively in smart schools;
2. There should be synergy between government and private organization in order to make funds available for provision of needed equipment, facilities and services, internet connectivity and electricity inclusive; and
3. Functional policy framework to regulate and facilitate this new perspective of education is needed.

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(Investigating the Effects of Field Trip-Based-Instruction ... Adamu, B., Et., al. 2025)

Investigating the Effects of Field-Trip-Based-Instruction On Biology Learning Outcomes: A Systematic Review

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Abstract

This study systematically reviewed researches that investigate the effects of field trips experiences on student's learning outcomes in biology. Peer-reviewed papers were searched using a variety of databases including (Google, Google scholar, Academia, Ask the public, conferences, journals, online library, and electronic journals). Using a protocol as bases of inclusion and exclusion. Any research article conducted on the effect of field trip on any of the students learning outcome variables (achievement, performance, retention, attitudes, motivation, and interest) in any Biology topic is considered. The inclusion criteria are that: only articles from 2009-2024 that examine the effect of field trip and any of the variables. Therefore any article before 2009 or did not study at least one of the variables was excluded. A total of 16 articles were selected and used for this study. The result indicates that field trip affects students learning outcomes In all the variables. The review suggests that all biology teachers should use field trip into their instruction, in order to improve student understanding of complex and abstract biology concepts.

Keywords; Field Trips, Biology Teaching, Students Learning Outcomes

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Introduction

Leaving the school premises is a social experience and one, which provides a change of tempo and scenery for students. School field trips are one of the basic elements in biology education and with the help of field trips students can learn biology, make observations in a better way and make learning more meaningful (Abdul, et al, 2015). Field-trip is a method of teaching that involves taking the students on an excursion outside the classroom for the purpose of making relevant observation necessary for understanding of the topic under study. Often times such trips/excursions enable student to obtain scientific, technological and vocational information (Akinbobola, et al, 2010). According to Ilori (2010), Field trips are aids that teacher uses to arouse the interest of the learner thereby enabling the learner to gain direct experience. Omeodu, et al, (2018) also pointed out that field trips exposes students to new experiences and can increase interest and engagement in science regardless of prior interest in a topic. However, during field trips, learners sharpen their skills of observations, perception and objective report of observations by utilizing all their senses Shakil, et al (2011).

Biology is a science of life concerned with the characteristics of living things, their forms, functions and relationship with one another and with their environment among others Bello, (2016). It is a unique branch of natural sciences, however, like other natural sciences; it is concerned with the search for in-depth understanding of natural phenomena and events Nnorom, (2015). Biology also remains to hold a distinctive place in the school curriculum. This is because the basic understanding of biology is required for study in a variety of disciplines such as Medicine, Agriculture, Pharmacy, Microbiology, Biochemistry, and Psychology, among others. It goes without saying that no student planning to pursue these courses of study can do without Biology. However, Due to immense benefits of the subject (Biology) to both individual and societal development, the federal government of Nigeria in the national policy on education, (2014). Made Biology a core Science subject at senior secondary school (SSS). The objectives of Biology programme are; i) adequate laboratory and field skills in biology ii) Meaningful and relevant knowledge in biology. iii) Ability to apply scientific knowledge in everyday Life in matters of personal and Community health and agriculture. iv) Reasonable functional scientific attitude and emphasis of content and context of syllabus is place on. v) Field study guide discovery/ Biology as inquiry Thus from the above objectives, an outdoor strategy such as field trip has been recommended

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by FME for its implementation for accomplishments of Biology objectives in the secondary School in Nigeria.

Many systematic literature review were conducted in the field trip and students learning. Some of the reviews carried out by previous researchers include; a review of research in the field trip and their value in education which examine the importance of science field trips and educational tools to connects the students to classroom concepts (Behrendt, et al 2014). Also, Cathryn (2010), conducted a systematic review on the use and implementation of science field trips. Relatedly, Prather (1989) systematically reviewed the value of field trip in science instruction. These reviews channel effort toward examining the impact of field trip in promoting student learning.

However, despite the effort put by previous reviews, intensive review of the existing literature revealed no systematic review was carried out specifically on investigating the effect of field trips based instruction in biology learning outcomes. Also, the reviews conducted by previous reviewers did not involve major parameter that shows methodology and the actual processes the researchers follow in their empirical researches.

This review therefore, aim at retrieving the empirical studies carried out on effect of field trips based instruction strategy with reference to biology only covering a period of 15 years (2009-2024) to enable the researcher include all accessible and relevant articles published on impact factor journals. It will also enable the researcher to present a comprehensive outlook on the literature and state of art about field trip and learning of biology.

Research objectives

1. To determine the distribution of research on field trips in biology by country and educational level.
2. To identify the research designs and instruments used to assess the impact of field trips on biology learning outcomes.
3. To describe the different learning outcome examined by the researchers when assessing the impact of field trips on biology learning.
4. To identify the key limitations found in research reviewed on field trips in biology learning

Research Questions

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In the most specific terms, the review answered the following research questions:

1. What is the distribution of research on field trip in biology by country, and by educational level?
2. What research design and instruments were used by researchers in assessing field trip on students learning outcomes in biology?
3. What are the learning outcomes examine by researchers in assessing field trip on students learning outcomes in biology?
4. What are the limitations of the researches reviewed on field trips in biology learning?

Methodology

The review searched relevant literature using keywords “field trip”, “field trip and biology”, “field trip in biology and achievement”, “field trip in biology and performance”, “field trip in biology and interest”, “field trip in biology and Retention,” “field trip in biology and attitude”, “field in biology and motivation. The search engine and database used include: goggle, goggle scholar, research gate, ask the public, ERIC, E-library, journals, conference and electronic journal. The result of these was 102 articles.

Study Selection

The selected study were limited to students learning outcomes (performance, achievement, attitude, motivation, interest, retention) in biology which brought the no of article to 61, the duration was restricted to fifteen years from 2009 to 2024 .see fig 1.this cut down the no of article to 20. Therefore, any study before 2009 is excluded.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The inclusion and exclusion criteria were place to make sure that the selected studies were relevant and appropriate to answer the questions. Table 1 below described the inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Table 1: Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria.

<u>Inclusion criteria</u>	<u>Exclusion criteria</u>
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1. Full text article.	Incomplete article.
2. Any studies conducted from 2009 to 2024.	Studies conducted before 2009.
3. Manuscripts written in English	Any other language other than English.
4. Reference journals	Non reference journals, articles, books, thesis
5. Studies on field trip and any of performance, achievement, motivation, retention, interest or attitude in biology.	Studies not include field trip and any other variables from inclusion criteria.

Source (field work, 2025)

After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, a total number of 20 articles were found to be suitable for inclusion in this review. The articles were analyzed in and discussed in accordance with the research questions.

Framework Analysis

The framework of the results from the review was tabulated using thirteen items/element and used as data for analysis, discussions of findings. The items are Serial number, Author, Year. Title, Type of Publication, Location, Knowledge Domain, Educational level, Methodology, Sample, Instrument, Independent variables, Limitation, and findings

Quality Assessment

To get an authentic and qualitative data about the effects of field trips on learning outcomes only complete and full text available articles published in peer review journal were selected and reviewed. The journals were mostly from reputable ones. Therefore the findings from these articles are expected to be of high accuracy and precision.

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S/N	Author	Year	Location	Title	Knowledge Domain	level	Methodology	Sample	In
1	Egwu, S.O & Okigbo, E.C	2021	Nigeria	Effect of field trip on secondary school students achievement in ecology in Anambra state	Ecology	Sec. sch.	Quasi Experimental	148	BA Te
2	Ezechi, N.G.	2018	Nigeria	Influence of field trip in teaching and learning of biology	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Survey Design	100	Quest
3	Ugwu, C.B.A.		Nigeria	Enhancing student's interest and achievement in senior secondary school in biology through field trip teaching approach	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	100	Test
4	Shuvra, D.			Effect of field trip on students' academic performance in biology	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	200	Test
5	Nnenna, G.E.		Nigeria	Field trips; A viable tool for students Achievement in biology	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Survey Design	391	Quest
6	Sandip, M.		India	Attitude towards field excursion in biological science and achievement at higher secondary school	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Survey Design	289	Test
7	Mahmud, et al.	2022	Nigeria	Impact of field trip on the retention and academic performance in ecology, among sec. sch. Students I zaria, kaduna state.	Ecology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	200	Test
8	Bwanhot, E.S.	2021	Nigeria	Impact of field trip on academic performance of secondary school students in ecology concept in kaduna state.	Ecology	Sec. Sch.	Experimental Design		Test
9	Zumyil, C.F., & Toma, M.A.	2022	Nigeria	Effect of field trip instructional strategies on students interest and achievement in ecology in plateau central zone, Nigeria.	Ecology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	106	Test
10	Obineke, C.J &		Nigeria	Effect of two modes of field trip method on students' achievement in senior secondary school in ecology in Nsukka local government area, enugu state	Ecology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	120	Test
11	Gormez, I.	2014	Turkey	Effect of field trip oriented instruction on ninth grade in students' achievement in animal diversity unit, continuing and academic motivation	Animal diversity	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	87	Test
12	Ajaja, O.P	2010		Effect of field trip on learning outcome In biology	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Experimental Design	100	Test
13	Anita, et al.	2018	Indonesia	The influence of field trip on high school students scientific literacy and attitude towards science in ecosystem concept	Ecosystem	University			
14	Usman, A.	2020	Nigeria	Effect of field trip instructional strategy on	Ecology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi Experimental	71	Test 8

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15	Denen, D. U. & Isah, S.A.	2019	Nigeria	students interest in ecology in nasarawa state, Nigeria. Effect of field trip instructional strategy on ss1 student interest and achievement in ecological concept in dutsin-ma LGA katsina state	Ecological concepts	Sec. Sch.	Quasi experimental	82	test
16	Nurhasnah, N., et al.	2019	Indonesia	Effectiveness of field trip in biology towards students increased concern for biodiversity Values	Biology	Sec. Sch.	Quasi experiment	96	Test

Source (field work, 2024)

Research Question One; what is the distribution of research on field trip in biology by country, educational level and the knowledge domain?

Table 3, 4, and 5 presented the distribution of research on field trip in biology by country, educational level and the knowledge domain respectively.

Table 3: Frequency of the studies by countries

Country	Frequency (f)	Studies
Nigeria	12	[1],[2],[3],[4],[5],[7],[8],[9],[10],[12],[14],[15]
India	1	[6]
Indonesia	2	[13],[16]
Turkey	1	[1]

Source (field work, 2024)

Table 3: indicated to a total of four countries where the empirical studies were carried out were involved in the review. Nigeria recorded the highest frequency of twelve (12) studies

Figure 2: Distribution of Field Trip Researches in Biology by Country

Table 4: Frequency of Studies by Educational Level

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Educational level	Frequency	Studies
Secondary	15	
University	1	

Of the 16 articles reviewed, 15 studies were conducted with secondary school biology students as the participants while 1 study were conducted with university students

Research Question Two; what research design and instruments were used by researchers in assessing field trip on students learning outcomes in biology?

Table 5: Frequency of Studies by Research Design

Research design	Frequency	Studies
Quasi experimental design	11	[2][5][6][8][12]
Experimental design	2	[8][12]
Survey	3	[2][5][5]

of the table above, 11 articles uses quasi experimental design, 3 uses survey while 2 uses experimental design.

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Table 6: Frequency of Studies By instruments

Instrument	Frequency	Studies
Test	14	[2], [5]
Questionnaire	2	[2],

The table above indicates that almost all the empirical studies reviewed uses test as their instruments for data collection.

Research Question Three; what are the learning outcomes examine by researchers in assessing field trip on students learning outcomes in biology?

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Table 7: Frequency of Studies by Learning Outcomes

Learning Outcomes Measured	Frequency	Studies
Achievement	8	[1][3][5][6][9][10][11][14][15]
Performance	4	[2][4][7][8]
Interest	4	[3][14][15][16]
Motivation	2	[11][16]
Retention	1	[7]
Attitude	2	[12][13]

Of the table above the result indicates that the learning outcomes achievement has the highest frequency of 8 studies, followed by interest and performance with 4-4 studies, motivation and attitudes has 2-2 while retention has only 1 study.

Research Question Three; what are the limitations of the studies?

Study	Limitation
1.	Carried out in one region , Focuses only on one topic
2.	Small sample size, Conducted in a region, Focuses only on one topic
3.	Small sample size, Limited scope Conducted in one region
4.	Focuses only on one topic
5.	Conducted in one region
6.	Limited scope, Focuses only on one topic
7.	Conducted in one region; Focuses only on one topic
8.	Sample size is too small, Conducted in one region
9.	Small sample size, Focuses only on one topic
10.	Conducted in one region Focus in only one topic
11.	Small sample size, conducted in one region, focuses only on one topic
12.	Small sample size, captured only one region, focuses only on one topic
13.	Small sample size carried out in one region, focuses only on one topic
14.	Small sample size, restricted in one region
15.	Small sample size, carried out in one region
16.	Limited scope

Source (field work, 2024)

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Discussion of findings

The findings of this systematic review were discussed based on research questions. The 16 peer-reviewed articles, demonstrates a notable concentration of research on field trips within the Nigerian educational context, particularly at secondary school level. Methodologically, the reviewed studies exhibit a preference for quasi-experimental designs and test instruments. The primary learning outcomes investigated were cognitive in nature, specifically academic achievement and knowledge retention.

Conclusion:

This systematic review reveals a strong positive association between field trips based-instructions and several biology learning outcomes. Consistent findings indicate that field trips can significantly increase student academic achievements, improve students' knowledge retention, interest, performance, motivation, and student's attitude towards learning biology. Furthermore a significant portion of the reviewed studies was conducted in secondary school setting, limiting the generality of findings to university students. Additionally, Limited research beyond Nigeria and secondary schools, along with the need for more methodologies, more than just test scores, and a broader assessment of learning outcomes shows clear directions for future research on field trips.

Suggestions for Further Studies:

1. All biology teachers should use field trip into their instruction, in order to improve student understanding of complex and abstract biology concepts.
2. Future research should prioritize conducting studies in university settings, research designs other than quasi experimental and test scores for instrumentation.

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(Unraveling the Past, Shaping the Future: A Qualitative study on ... Saidu, A., Et., al. 2025)

Unraveling the Past, Shaping the Future: A Qualitative Study on Historical Development of Colleges of Education in Oyo State (1980-2020)

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Abstract

This study examined the historical development of colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria, from 1980 to 2020 by revealing the evolution, enrollment of students, growth of staff and challenges of the colleges of education in Oyo State. The study employed a historical research design. Also, an interview schedule and a researchers' designed questionnaire titled "Questionnaire on Historical Analysis of Colleges of Education in Oyo State Nigeria" (QHACED) with a reliability co-efficient of 0.85 were the instruments used for data collection. The population for this study comprised of 238 stakeholders of all the colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria. Both the qualitative and quantitative data analysis techniques were employed in the study. It was revealed that the trends of staffing at the colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria between 1980 and 2020 were fluctuating as upward and downward movements of staffing reflected. Also, challenges facing colleges of education in Oyo State were revealed which include; inconsistency and inadequate funding, vandalism of infrastructure, constant staff resignation among others. It was therefore recommended that government should ensure that a clear staffing policy for both academic and non-academic is implemented with clear criteria for recruitment of staff for different colleges in the state. The study's conclusion offer valuable insights for educators, policymakers and researchers seeking to enhance educational outcomes in Nigeria and similar contexts.

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Keywords: Historical Analysis; Teacher Education; Colleges of Education; Past; Future

Introduction

Education is the greatest instrument that man has devised for his progress and it is a dynamic tool for change. This is why successive Nigerian governments have placed much emphasis on the development of the individual as a means to national development. Education stems out to be the sure means of developing an individual's potential. The potency of education is more evident in its globalization trends which are imbued with instrumental values of nurturing productive citizens for sustainable development (Olayanju, 2012).

The fact remains that teaching and learning depend on teachers because there can be no meaningful socio-economic and political development in any country without teachers. It is teachers' numbers, quality, and devotion that test the effectiveness of all educational arrangements, development, and growth. Even the educational planners may have the best educational policies, designs, and the government may vote the largest sum of its revenue to education, but the ultimate realisation of any set of aims for education depends on the teacher. It is the teacher who will ultimately be responsible translating educational policies into action and practice. Ukeje (1996) supported this fact when he stated that education unlocks the door to modernization and it is the teachers who hold the key to that door.

According to Afe (2015), the realisation of educational objectives depends on the quality and quantity of the available teaching manpower. This can be influenced by the availability of adequate training and retraining programmes for those about to teach and those already teaching respectively. Hence, the efficiency of teacher training should be the main determining factor in the success or failure of education to meet the country's needs. The training encompasses the knowledge of the policies and procedures designed to equip prospective teachers with the knowledge, attitudes, and skills they require to perform their tasks effectively in the classroom, school, and wider community.

Teacher education refers to the preparation of teachers towards the attainment of attitudes, skills, and knowledge considered desirable to make them efficient and effective in their work, according to the needs of a given society at any point in time. It

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includes training and education occurring at teacher training institutions such as College of Education before the commencement of service (pre-service) and during service (in-service or on-the-job). Every society requires adequate human and material resources to improve its social organisation, preserve the culture, enhance economic development, and reform the political structures (Oke, 2019). Education is often seen as a prerequisite for quality manpower development and the creation of wealth, a sure path to success in life and service to humanity. Thus, teachers have an important role to play to adequately preparing the young for their roles in society to achieve the set national objectives.

Abdullahi (2006) stressed that education is the bedrock of the economic development of any nation. The achievement of this depends largely on the quality of the teacher education in the country. The National Policy on Education Section 8, Sub-section 70 (a) pointed out that “Teacher education programme will continue to be given a major emphasis in all our educational planning and development because no educational system can rise above the quality of its teacher” (FGN, 2013, p.33). The statement implies that teachers should be properly trained to achieve excellence. This means that the quality of teachers in the system determines the quality of the educational system of any nation in the world.

Adewuyi and Ogunwuyi (2002) opined that teacher education is the provision of professional education and specialised training within a specified period for the preparation of individuals who intend to develop and nurture young ones into responsible and productive citizens. It is informed by the fact that teaching is an all-purpose profession that stimulates the development of the mental, physical, and emotional powers of students. Such educated citizens would be sensitive and equipped with the skills and attitudes necessary for co-existence, environmental management, and a democratic process.

The heartbeat of manpower development and training for prudent use and sustenance of resources in nation-building is teacher education. Teacher education, being inextricably linked with general education and social goals, is constantly caught up in the series of dilemmas derivable from educational expansion, political, technological development, and social change. The prevailing crisis in Nigerian education and its society as typified by unemployment, poverty, corruption, crime, indiscipline, and

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underutilization of capacities in all facets of human life and national development, could be ascribed to the neglect of teacher education and the pitiable plight of the teachers. All these conflictual relationships precipitated poverty-induced hardships across all segments of the Nigerian community. What structurally becomes important in achieving the nation's quest for a self-reliant society, imbued with a vibrant economy and productive citizenry, is to put in place a comprehensive teacher education programme.

Literature Review

Oyo State is located in the South-west geo-political zone of Nigeria. it is one of the three states carved out of the former Western State of Nigeria in 1976. Oyo State consists of 33 Local Governments and 29 Local Council Development Areas. Local Government Areas are Afijio, Akinyele, Atiba, Atisbo, Egbeda, Ibadan North, Ibadan North-East, Ibadan North-West, Ibadan South-East, Ibadan South West, Ibarapa Central, Ibarapa East, Ibarapa North, Ido, Irepo, Iseyin, Itesiwaju, Iwajowa, Kajola, Lagelu, Ogbomoso North, Ogbomoso South, Ogo-Oluwa, Olorunsogo, Oluyole, Ona-Ara, Oorelope, Oriire, Oyo East, Oyo West, Saki East, Saki West and Surulere. The Local Council Development Areas (LCDAs) are: Aare Latosa, Afijio West, Ajorosun, Akinyele East, Akinyele South, Akinyele West, Akorede, Araromi, Atisbo South, Ibadan East, Ibadan South East, Ibadan West, Ibarapa North-East, Ibarapa North-West, Ifeloju, Iganna, Inukan, Irepodun, Iseyin South, Iwa, Lagelu North, Ogbomoso Central, Ogbomoso South-West, Ogo-oluwa West, Oke 'badan, Omi Apata, Surulere North, Surulere South, Wewe (<https://old.oyostate.gov.ng/about-oyostate>) With a total land area of 28,454 square kilometers, Oyo State is home to nearly 5 million people, mostly Yoruba, but also other migratory communities. Ogun State borders it to the south, Kwara State borders it to the north, Ogun State and the Republic of Benin border it to the west, and Osun State borders it to the east. The terrain is composed of old hard rocks and dome-shaped hills that climb gradually from 500 meters above sea level in the south to 1,219 meters above sea level in the north. As of 2006, the population of Oyo was 5591589 million based on the Nigeria 2006 Census with a Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of 29.8. Presently, the state is headed by a Governor, Engr. Oluwaseyi Abiodun Makinde.

Teacher Education at the early stage of the missionary period started with a few African converts who were taught how to teach and were gradually incorporated into the teaching activities in the Church after Sunday services, sometimes during the week.

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Early schools started as boarding types as missionaries opened schools in their church premises, where selected students were trained as evangelist teachers (Boyi, 2014). In 1859, the CMS showed leadership when it established a teacher training institution in Abeokuta. This was later relocated to Lagos in 1896 after the missionaries were expelled from Abeokuta due to some disagreements between the missionaries and the local population authorities most of whom were not very receptive to the new religion and the education being introduced by the missionaries. The preponderance of British presence and security assurance in Lagos influenced the decision to relocate to Lagos (Boyi, 2014).

Subsequently, the institution was moved to Oyo which became St. Andrew's College, Oyo. The Southern Baptist Mission started a Theological College at Ogbomoso in 1753. This was changed to Baptist College and incorporated teacher training courses in 1897. The College was later moved to Shaki and then to Iwo as a teachers' College. In 1905, the Wesleyan Methodist Missionary Society funded an institution for the training of Catechists and teachers in Ibadan for like a purpose to cater for students from Niger (Ukeje, 1996). It opened with four students. The number of students had risen to twenty by 1918 and the institution became known as the Wesley College, Ibadan.

In Oyo State, the first teacher training institution known as Grade II Teachers' College was established in 1896 and was later upgraded by the government of the Late Chief Bola Ige of Oyo State during the second republic in September 1980 to St. Andrew's College of Education, Oyo and later Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo. In other words, Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo is an offshoot of the St. Andrew's College of Education, Oyo which was upgraded to a College of Education Campus under the then Oyo State College of Education, Ila-Orangun in 1980. Thus, at various times, the College had been known as St. Andrew's College of Education, Oyo, Oyo State College of Education, Oyo, and now Emmanuel Alayande College of Education, Oyo in 2008 in memory of the renowned educationist and an Andrian, Rev. Canon Emmanuel Alayande without affecting the core mandate as stipulated in the College Enabling Law. Federal College of Education (Special), Oyo was also created in the year 1977 (<https://eacoed.edu.ng/about-us>)

Following the publication of the National Policy on Education (1998), the policy articulated the dream of having a Nigeria Certificate of Education (NCE) as the minimum qualification for entry into the teaching profession. This dream was realized

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by the establishment of the National Commission for Colleges of Education (NCCE) by enabling Decree No.3 of April 1989. Furthermore, the then Military Head of State, General Abdulsalam Abubakar welcomed the need to license private investors in the provision of higher education in Nigeria, and as a result of this, more private colleges of education were established in Nigeria, particularly in Oyo State. Private investors also played their part in establishing more colleges to support the government-owned and to create room for more student enrollment.

Objectives of the Study

The main purpose of this study is to trace the historical development of colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria from 1980 to 2020. Specifically, the study intends to:

- i Trace the historical antecedents of colleges of education in Oyo State Nigeria before 1980
- ii Trace the trends in the area of staffing in the colleges of education in Oyo State Nigeria from 1980 to 2020
- iii Assess the trends of students' enrolment in the colleges of education in Oyo State Nigeria from 1980 to 2020
- iv assess the major challenges faced by the colleges of education in Oyo State Nigeria from 1980 to 2020

Research Questions

The following questions were raised.

- 1.What were the historical antecedents of colleges of education in Oyo State?
- 2.What was the trend of staffing in the colleges of education in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020?
- 3.What were the trends of students' enrolment in the colleges of education in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020?
- 4.What were the major challenges the colleges of education faced in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020?

Methodology

In this study, historical research method was employed. A historical research method is considered appropriate for this study because the study is purely historical.

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Historical research is a systematic method in which the researcher investigates past events to have a better understanding of the past and the present and have a reliable prediction of the future to shape it for the better (Alabi, 2021). The population of this study comprised of all the stakeholders of all the seven (7) colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria. The stakeholders are categorised into three using stratified sampling techniques. These include, the policymakers (officials of the Ministry and principal officials), implementers (Lecturers) and beneficiaries (students). Purposive sampling technique was used to select seven (7) Provosts, seven (7) Deputy Provosts Administration, seven (7) Deputy Provosts Academic, seven (7) Registrars, seven (7) Librarian, seven (7) Bursars and seven (7) Directors of works from each of the seven (7) colleges of education which is equal to forty-nine (49) principal officials. Also, 140 lecturers, seven (7) officials from the Oyo State Ministry of Tertiary Education and 42 students were selected to make a total number of 238 respondents for this study. A researchers' designed questionnaire with the reliability coefficient of 0.85, official documents and pro forma were used for data collection in this study while the data collected were analysed using the thematic analysis, the descriptive statistics of percentage and bar chart were explored to answer the research questions raised.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: *What were the historical antecedents of colleges of education in Oyo State?*

The historical antecedents of colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria are deeply rooted in the actions and inactions of missionary bodies, colonial masters and indigenous people's movements towards formal education. In the 19th century, the missionary bodies like Wesleyan Methodist Society, Church Missionary Society (CMS), Baptist Mission and so on found there ways in Nigeria for evangelism. However, for their message to be appreciated there was need to teach people how to read and write, hence the establishment of schools. The curricula for the schools included religious education, basic reading, and writing as well as simple arithmetic. By late 19th and early 20th century, missionary schools started practicing some trends of teacher training in apprentice manner. Therefore, In the past, the training of teachers was mostly done on the job and many of them rise from student-teachers under the supervision of a more experienced teacher. Also, in 1925, the colonial government set Phelps-Stokes Commission of 1925. Among the outcomes of this commission was the call for improvement of the teacher training institution to enhance the quality of

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education available in the colony. After the Second World War, the colonial government started establishing government owned teacher training colleges in the 1930s and the 1940s. Several teacher training institutions were established during this period in Oyo State. In 1970s, Nigeria experienced a colossal expansion in her educational system and this led to the establishment of specialized institutions that offered training for teachers exclusively and also, the government of Oyo State later upgraded most of the existing teacher training institutions into full-fledge colleges of education. These colleges were meant to give higher qualifications like the Nigerian Certificate in Education (NCE) which is a basic requirement for teaching in Nigerian schools.

Research Question 2: *What was the trend of staffing in the colleges of education in Oyo State between 1980 and 2020?*

The trends of staffing in colleges of education in Oyo State between 1980 and 2020 evolved significantly, reflecting changes in educational policies, funding and demand for specialized teaching personnel. The trend of academic and non-academic staffing of colleges of education in Oyo State was summarized in the Table 1:

Table 1: Trend of Academic and Non-academic Staffing in the Colleges of Education in Oyo State: 1980-2020

Years	Staff Recruitment		Total	% Increment
	Academic	Non-Academic		
1980-1982	58	61	119	-
1983-1985	101	92	193	62.18
1986-1988	120	124	244	26.42
1989-1991	215	249	464	90.16
1992-1994	302	321	623	34.27
1995-1997	411	432	843	35.31
1998-2001	512	560	1,072	27.16
2002-2004	562	591	1,153	7.56
2005-2007	601	710	1,311	13.70
2008-2011	819	1,190	2,009	53.24
2012-2014	839	1, 218	2,057	2.39
2015-2017	860	1,347	2,207	7.29
2018-2021	894	1,322	2,216	0.41

Source: Field work (2024)

Figure 1: Bar Chart Showing Trends of Academic and Non-academic Staff in the Colleges of Education in Oyo State between 1980 and 2020

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The table and the chart above indicate that a total of 199 staff members were in the colleges between 1980 and 1982. However, there was a massive increase of 62.18% between the year 1983 and 1985. Between 1986 and 1988, the colleges staffing trend was downward with 26.42% increment compared to previous years of 62.18%. However, the staffing trend witnessed its biggest increment till date in the years 1989-1991 with 90.16% total increments compared to previous years. This is largely due to creation of more teacher training schools in Oyo State. By 1992 to 1994, there is only 34.27% increment, which indicate downward trend compared to the previous years' massive increment. Also, 1995-1997 saw almost identical increment in the trend of staffing compared to previous years with 35.31% increment.

The transition of the Nigeria government from military to democracy did not affect peoples' interest in academic with the trend in staffing still relatively unchanged between 1998 and 2001 with 27.16% increment compared to previous years. However, there was a massive decline in the trends of colleges of education in Oyo State staffing in 2002 to 2004. This might be due to more emphasis being place on University Education which affected enrolment of students and subsequently affect employment of staff. 2002-2004 only witnessed 7.56% increment, 2005-2007 with 13.70 increment witnessed, however, there was a sharp increase in 2008-2011 with 53.24% increment. The increment experienced in 2008-2011 was as a result of establishment of more private colleges of education.

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More so, since 2012, the colleges of education staffing trends have been minimal increment with only 2.39% increment between 2012 and 2014, 7.29% increment between 2015 and 2017, 0.41% increment between 2018 and 2021 while the most recent staffing figures between 2022 and 2024 is 2,339 which is only 5.55% increment compared to previous years. In conclusion, there have been inconsistent in the trends of staff recruitment among colleges of education in Oyo State.

Research Question 3: *What were the trends of students’ enrolment in the colleges of education in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020?*

Between 1980 and 2020, the trends of students’ enrolment in colleges of education across the nation reflect educational and socio-economic growth of the nation. In Oyo State and across the country, prior to the establishment of Joint Admission and Matriculation Board (JAMB), Institutions which include University, Polytechnic and Colleges of Education have a specified and standardized way of conducting their own internal admission examination and enroll students who meet their requirements. However, the policies to standardized and harmonized the education system of the country have led to JAMB conducting standardized examinations with colleges of education having a specified cut of marks for students.

Also, apart from internally conducted examinations by the colleges of education, there are other requirements that candidates must have before being consider for admission. Among them are (a) completion of secondary school education with a minimum of number of credits in relevant subjects, most especially, English and Mathematics. Table 2 below reveals students’ enrolment trends in Colleges of Education in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020.

Table 2: Trends of Students’ Enrolment in Colleges of Education in Oyo State, Nigeria.

Academic Session	Numbers of Students		Students Enrolment within 3 Years	Percentage Increment Over Previous Years
	Male	Female		
1980-1982	498	109	607	-
1983-1985	604	206	810	33.44
1986-1988	891	451	1,342	65.68

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1989-1991	1,412	844	2,256	68.11
1992-1994	1,738	1,008	2,746	21.72
1995-1997	2,451	1,612	4,063	47.96
1998-2001	5,682	3,810	9,492	133.62
2002-2004	6,198	4,322	10,520	10.83
2005-2007	7,856	5,041	12,897	22.59
2008-2011	8,221	5,518	13,739	6.53
2012-2014	8,044	5,001	13,045	-5.05
2015-2017	7,921	4,981	12,902	-1.09
2018-2021	7,341	6,012	13,353	3.49

Source: Field work (2024)

Figure 2: Bar Chart Showing Trends of Student’s Enrolment in the Colleges of Education in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020

Table 3 shows the pattern of students’ enrolment within 3years interval. The students’ enrolment was 607 between 1980 and 1982, while there was 33.44% increment in the years 1983 to 1985. Years 1986-1988 and 1989-1991 saw massive upward increment in the numbers of students’ enrolment with 65.68% and 68.11% increment within the six years’ interval. The massive increment within these years might be as a result of appreciation of academic by the populace and the massive opportunities attached to teacher trainings. Within the year 1992 and 1994, the students’ enrolment trend falls compared to previous six years with only 21.72 increment while 1995 and 1997, the enrolment of 4,063 students shows 47.96% increment to previous years. Between 1998

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and 2001, colleges of education in Oyo State experienced massive increment in the number of students' enrolment. 133.62% increment coincided with President Obasanjo's policy of free primary education and establishment of more colleges of education. Between 2002 and 2004, the trend experienced another massive fall in students' enrolment compared to previous years. The waves of enrolment experienced between 1998 and 2001 reduced a little which affect staff recruitment across colleges of education. Only, 10.83% increment was experienced between the year 2002 and 2004.

The establishment of new colleges of education between 2003 and 2005 spark another wave of enrolment trend experienced between 2005 and 2007 with 12,897 new enrolments', making 22.59% increment compared to previous years. However, the waves came down back between 2008 and 2011 with only 6.53 increment in the number of new enrolments compare to previous years (2005-2007). Between 2012-2014 and 2015-2017, the students' enrolment experienced a massive negative trend, where there was -5.05% in number of enrolments between 2012 and 2014 and -1.09% between 2015 and 2017. According to the study finding, this is largely due to the fact, students are now more interested in University Education, Entrepreneur and other activities that they believe will fetch them more money. The negative experienced during this six year highlighted the challenges of unemployment among NCE graduates and also, poor remuneration being paid to employed NCE graduates. Between 2018 and 2021, there was slight increment compared to negative trend experienced in the previous six years, with 13,353 new enrolments which was 3.49% increment compared to previous three years (2015-2017). The trend highlighted above a high level of inconsistency in students' enrolment in the colleges of education in Oyo State especially between 1980 and 2020.

Research Question 4: *What were the major challenges the colleges of education faced in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020?*

The respondents' responses to the interview highlighted that major challenges faced by colleges of education in Oyo State from 1980 to 2020 were diverse and impacted the quality of education and development of the institutions. Most of these challenges include;

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1. Poor Interest of Local Communities from Onset: 72% of the respondents made mention that one major challenge was the initial lack of interest from local communities in Oyo State. Many communities viewed universities as more prestigious, leading to low enrolment and limited local support for the colleges of education. This hindered the institutions' growth and development during the early years."

2. Poor Emphasis Placed on Colleges of Education by Government Compared to Universities: Also, 63% of the respondents believe that colleges of education in Oyo State faced neglect, as the government prioritized Universities. The lower importance given to teacher training colleges affected their funding, development, and overall visibility, making it difficult for them to compete or thrive on the same level."

3. Inconsistent and Inadequate Funding: 79% of the respondents pointed out that inconsistent and inadequate funding was a persistent issue. Colleges of education in Oyo State often struggled to maintain basic infrastructure, hire qualified staff, and improve educational resources. This financial instability limited their capacity to offer quality education."

4. Poor Remuneration of Graduate Teachers by Employers: 61% of the respondents believe that graduate teachers from these colleges poor remuneration upon employment is another challenge that continues to affect enrolment and quality. Many found the pay inadequate for their qualifications, leading to dissatisfaction, demotivation, and an overall decline in the prestige of teaching as a profession."

5. Religious Crises in Local Communities: 29% of the respondents also pointed out that at some point, religious crises also posed significant challenges, particularly in communities where tensions flared. These conflicts affected the smooth operation of the colleges, disrupting academic activities and affecting student enrolment and staff retention.

6. Vandalism of Infrastructure: Vandalism of infrastructure is another important challenge pointed out by 43% of the respondent. They said that colleges suffered from the destruction of educational facilities, which led to a decline in the quality of education provided. This further discouraged investment in the sector, worsening the already fragile situation.

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7. Constant Staff Resignation Due to Poor Pay: Finally, 80% of the provosts asserted that constant staff resignation, driven by poor pay, created instability in the colleges of education. Many skilled educators sought better opportunities elsewhere, leaving the institutions understaffed and affecting the quality of education and administrative efficiency.

Discussion of Findings

The finding of the study revealed that the trend of staffing at the colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria between 1980 and 2020 were fluctuating as upward and downward movements of staffing reflected. This was due to a lot of reasons such as strategic interventions towards improving the quality of education as well as addressing the shortage of qualified teachers in the Nigerian society. This is related to a study of Fagbemiye (2001) which submitted that several challenges characterized Nigeria post-independence educational system, one of which was the concern for the quality teachers who could provide quality education for the growing school system. The Nigerian government, realizing this need provided a high priority for the setting up of teacher training centres like colleges of education. These institutions were expected to churn out well qualified teachers to teach the post primary and secondary education. Also, in the same period the government tried to enhance the quality of education by providing teachers with important pedagogical competencies enabling them to meet the challenges of a rapidly changing educational environment (Okebukola, 2002).

Another factor that affected staffing was the increase in demand of specialized teachers. This was due to the complexity of education system in Nigeria therefore teachers with techniques in specialized areas like science, technology, and vocational education were needed. But insufficient funding and unsystematic policies on recruitment generates disparities in staffing practices which are actual thorns in this situation in many colleges of education (Ajayi, 2017).

More so, this study findings show that there are fluctuations on the student enrolment in the colleges of education in Oyo State from the year 1980 to 2020. The reason behind this inconsistency was a change in the general economic situation, changes in government policies regarding education and the development of new forms of higher education institutions. This is in line with the finding of the study of Olaniyan and Okemakinde (2008) which asserted that in the past, some families could not be able to afford to pay the fees required to take their children to colleges of education hence low

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intakes. On the other hand, when there was improved economic development, there was an improvement in enrolments since families were better of economically to pay for their children's education.

Recommendations

1. Important policy measures such as scholarships, career advancement schemes and professional development for intending teachers should be formulated. This will encourage enrollment into teacher education programmes.
2. The government should also ensure that a clear staffing policy for both academic and non-academic is implemented with clear criteria for recruitment of staff for different colleges.
3. More so, there should be provision of enough funds to support the development of physical infrastructure and policies to be implemented by different colleges as part of physical infrastructure policies.

Conclusion

This historical analysis of colleges of education in Oyo State, Nigeria (1980-2020) has unraveled the complex dynamics that shaped the development of teacher education in the state. The study revealed the significant role of government policies on enrolment rate, staffing, capacity building as well as challenges facing colleges of education in the state. As Nigeria continues to navigate the complexities of 21st-century education, this study highlights the importance of understanding the historical context of teacher education. By unraveling the past and shaping the future, colleges of education in Oyo State can continue to play a vital role in producing qualified educators and driving educational excellence.

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Assessment of Information and Communication Technology Competence among English Language Lecturers in Polytechnics and Colleges of Education in Northwest, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study assessed the Information and Communication Technology competencies between English Language lecturers of Colleges of Education and Polytechnics in North-west Nigeria. One of the objectives of the study is to determine the difference in the level of ICT competencies between English lecturers from federal Colleges of Education and polytechnics in North West, Nigeria. Descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. A population of 432 (284 male, 148 female) English language lecturers from Polytechnics and Colleges of Education during 2024/2025 academic session in the North-West Nigeria. A sample size of 91 (62 male, 29 female) was selected from the tagged population using stratified sampling technique and proportionate sampling procedure. A 4-point rating scale questionnaire tagged: ICT Competencies among English Lecturers (ICTCAEL) with validity and reliability index of 0.91 was used as instrument for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer two research questions while t-test statistics was used to test two null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The study revealed that, for the ICT competencies, there is no significant difference exists between English lecturers in federal colleges of education and polytechnics in North West zone, Nigeria. Both have substantial knowledge on the use of computers, email, and internet. The study also revealed that there was significant difference in the ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in the area of study and the difference is on the favour of male lecturers. The study concluded that majority of English lecturers in colleges of education and polytechnics have competencies on most of the ICT tools like power point presentation Microsoft word/excel, email, social media, overhead projector, internet. Other skills are language laboratory, sound system and radio/television assisted instructions. It was recommended that lecturers should be encouraged to be computer literate through organizing regular conferences, seminars, and workshops.

Keywords: Information and Communication Technology, Competences, English Language Lecturers, Colleges of Education, Polytechnics

Introduction

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) competence is the ability to use a variety of computer applications for varied purposes. Consequently, one of the main predictors of integrating ICT in teaching is teachers' computer proficiency (Ahmed , Qasem, & Power, 2020). The level of competency and knowledge of ICT skills among teachers is different in view of digital technology that exists in varied and wide scope (Wong & Khadijah 2018). Some educators are quick to master the knowledge and technology skills that exist while there are also educators who are still trying to master the most basic technology such as email, students file management system, internet and office productivity software (Wong & Khadijah 2018). The ICT competencies are related with teachers' knowledge and technical training that how to use and maintain ICT equipment and software. These competencies involve the skills to operate modern technologies such as computer, internet etc (Husain, 2010). Regrettably, the majority of developing countries have not been able to successfully investigate the potential applications of computers in their educational systems. It is generally agreed that Nigeria, in particular, was one of the countries that was slow to adopt the use of computers for communication and other purposes (Ogunsola & Aboyade, 2005). Therefore, there is an ongoing need to research, develop, and discuss teachers' professional development and use of digital teaching tools (Amhag, Hellstrom, & Stigmar, 2019).

The introduction of ICT into tertiary institutions has significantly altered the way education is delivered; it paves the way for a new pedagogical approach in which students are expected to play a more active role than in the past (i.e. getting more involved in the teaching and learning process, being active participants of knowledge creation rather than passive recipients of knowledge) (Adamu, Baba, Musa, Goni, Mohammed, & Yohanna, 2020). The incorporation of information technology into the classroom is crucial for ensuring the quality of learning. There are significant benefits to incorporating ICT into the teaching and learning process. Initially, students would become familiar with ICT, since all jobs in today's society depend on ICT (Comfort & Onaigho, 2015). ICT helps facilitate his transaction between producers and users by keeping the students updated and enhancing teachers capacity and ability fostering live contact between the teacher and the student through email, chalk session, e-

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learning, web-based learning including internet, intranet, extranet, CD-ROM, TV and audio-videotape. (Anu, Kapil, Sameer, & Seems 2011)

Statement of the Research Problem

Academic and research communities in Nigeria will soon be required to fully adopt ICTs in order to survive in their respective endeavors as a result of the current trend in technological development. Teachers in the developing world must transform their methods of imparting knowledge and encouraging research through the acquisition of ICTs skills, particularly Internet proficiency (Adamu et al., 2020; Adisa et al., 2018; Comfort & Onaigho, 2015). Therefore the main aim of this study is to investigate lecturers' competencies on the use of ICT tools in Tertiary institutions in North-western Nigeria with particular reference to Colleges of Education and Polytechnics.

Despite the significant expansion in the use of ICTs in several fields, including education, the competency of lecturers and the use of ICT tools at tertiary institutions in North-Western Nigeria, particularly Polytechnics and Colleges of Education, remains a serious issue. This is due to the fact that the beginnings of the teaching and learning by competencies method may be traced to the societal developments of recent decades (Basilotta-Gómez-Pablos et al., 2022). Therefore, digital competence has assumed a prominent position in the educational setting, becoming one of the most important skills that lecturers must possess in the modern world (Basilotta-Gómez-Pablos et al., 2022; Zhao et al., 2021). Consequently, active-duty lecturers should learn relevant skills to meet the newly increased teaching standards and make adjustments to accommodate the new teaching environment (Gilakjani, 2017).

The objective of Nigeria's tertiary institutions is to produce highly skilled workers for the many economic sectors of the country. It is anticipated to contribute to national development by strengthening and diversifying its programs to meet the nation's high manpower needs and by incorporating national regiments into the professional course curriculum. These objectives could be achieved through effective teaching, research and other allied academic activities (Emmanuel et al., 2022). For teachers of tertiary institutions to carry out their jobs efficiently and effectively especially in this age of knowledge-based technology and globalization, the use of information and communication technology (ICT) becomes imperative recognizing the significance of

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ICT in the development of skills, talents, and competencies for effective development, the National Policy on Education (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2018) stipulates that it should be incorporated at all levels of education in Nigeria (Emmanuel et al., 2022). Lecturers' competencies in the utilization of ICT tools boost their research productivity. It also boosts their significance in the academic sphere through intellectual contributions. Therefore, information and communication technology (ICT) can play an important role in tertiary institutions in North-Western zone Nigeria. Despite geographical constraints, ICT can provide higher education in rural places in an easily accessible and learning environment. It is critical to therefore investigate how ICT may be used in higher education. North-Western Nigerian states with educational disadvantages can benefit from leveraging the global information network to boost their higher education sector and make better use of current ICT resources. Access to worldwide resources (e-journals, databases, etc.) is made possible by information and communication technology, which strengthens higher education as a whole.

However, Apagu & Wakili, (2015) opined that, the majority of research on ICT in education focuses on the availability of ICT facilities and perspectives of ICT use in national institutions. Researchers place less emphasis on competencies and the prudent use of available ICT tools on the ground. Given the country's economic, social, and political situation, as well as the acceptability of western education in general, particularly in the northern part of the country, therefore, it is questionable whether the lecturers have the necessary ICT competencies to utilize ICT. In the absence of these skills, the enormous amount of money spent on the acquisition of ICT equipment would be a monumental waste, and the learning, teaching, and research objectives of these institutions will not be accomplished. In the light of this, the research aimed at investigating the lecturers' competencies and the use of ICT tools in tertiary institutions in North-Western Nigeria, with a focus on Polytechnics and Colleges of Education.

Objectives of the Study

The purpose of the study was to assess Information and Communication Technology competencies among English Language Lecturers of Colleges of Education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria. Specifically, the study tried to

1. Determine the difference in the level of ICT competencies between English Language Lecturers in federal colleges of education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria.

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2. Find out the difference in the level of ICT competencies between male and female English Language Lecturers in colleges of education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria.

Research Questions

The research addressed the following questions:

1. What is the difference in the level of ICT competencies between English Language Lecturers in federal colleges of education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria?
2. What is the difference in the level of ICT competencies between male and female English Language Lecturers in colleges of education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria?

Null Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses were formulated in the study. They included:

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the level of ICT competencies between English Language Lecturers from federal colleges of education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference in the level of ICT competencies between male and female English Language Lecturers in colleges of education and Polytechnics in Northwest, Nigeria.

Methodology

Descriptive survey design was adopted with population of 432 (284 male, 148 female) English language lecturers from Federal Polytechnics and Colleges of Education in the North-West Nigeria. A sample size of 91 (62 male, 29 female) was selected using stratified sampling technique and proportionate sampling procedure. A 4-points rating scale questionnaire titled: ICT Competencies among English Lecturers (ICTCAEL) was used as instrument for data collection. Face to face method of instrument distribution with the help of 5 research assistants was used for data collection. The data collected for analysis was in form of nominal scale converted to interval scale where the most desired value attracts 4 points and the least desired attracts 1 point. The total value of a respondent was arrived at by adding the value of a respondent to each questionnaire item. Mean and

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standard deviation were used to answer research questions while t-test statistics was used to test all hypotheses using SPSS at 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Results

Research Question 1: What is the difference of ICT competencies between English Language lecturers in federal colleges of education and polytechnics in North West of Nigeria?

To answer this research question, the data collected from 51 federal colleges of education English lecturers and 40 from federal polytechnics has been used. Therefore, to find out the difference in their ICT competencies mean and standard deviation was calculated and result presented in table 1 below:

Table 1: Mean and Standard Deviation for difference of ICT competencies between federal colleges of education and federal polytechnics English lecturers in North West Nigeria

Institution	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	MD
Federal COE	51	46.43	8.32	3
Federal Poly	40	43.43	6.69	

Fieldwork 2024

Table 1 displayed the mean and standard deviation of lecturers from federal colleges of education and federal polytechnics in North West Nigeria. The mean score and standard deviation in respect of lecturers from federal colleges of education are 46.43 and 8.23. For lecturers from federal polytechnics the mean is 43.43 and standard deviation is 6.69. Their mean difference is 3. The lecturers from federal colleges of education recorded higher mean than their counterpart from federal polytechnics. This shows that there is difference of ICT competence between the groups. However, to know whether it is significance, it is only the data was subjected to t-test independent sample analysis.

Research Question 2: What is the difference of ICT competencies between male and female English language lecturers in the North West Nigeria?

To answer this research question, the data collected from 62 male lecturers and 29 female English lecturers was used to find out the difference in their of ICT

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competencies. The mean and standard deviation as well as mean difference was calculated and result presented in 2 below:

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation for difference of ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in colleges of educations and polytechnics in North West Nigeria

Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	MD
Male	62	47.33	7.70	
Female	29	43.88	7.77	3.45

Fieldwork 2024

Table 2 revealed the mean score of 47.33 and standard deviation of 7.70 for male lecturers while for female, the mean value stands at 43.88 with standard deviation of 7.77. The mean difference was 3.45 in favour of male lecturers. This shows that there was difference of the ICT competence between the genders. However, to know whether the difference is significant it is only when the data was subjected to t-test analysis.

Ho₁: There is no significant difference in the ICT competencies between English lecturers in federal colleges of education and polytechnics in North West of Nigeria.

To test null hypothesis 1, t-test independent sample was ran to find out mean difference in the ICT competencies between English lecturers from federal colleges of education and polytechnics in North West Nigeria. The result was presented in the Table 3 below:

Table 3: T-test Analysis of difference in the ICT competencies between English Language lecturers in federal colleges of education and polytechnics in North West Nigeria

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-Value	p-value	Decision
Federal COE	51	46.43	8.324				
Fed. Polytechnics	40	43.43	6.694	89	1.860	0.07	Retained

Fieldwork 2024

Table 3 showed the t-test statistical analysis on the difference of ICT competencies between English lecturers in federal colleges of education and polytechnics in the area of study. The result revealed the mean value of 46.43 with standard deviation of 8.324 for lecturers from colleges of education while lecturers from polytechnics had mean

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value of 43.43 and standard deviation of 6.694 at degree of freedom of 89 with p-value of 0.07. The p-value obtained is greater than the level of significant 0.05 set for the study. Therefore, null hypothesis was retained and this means that there was no significant difference of ICT competencies between English Language lecturers in federal colleges of education and federal polytechnics in North West Nigeria.

Ho₂: There is no significant difference of ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in tertiary institution in North West of Nigeria.

To test null hypothesis 2, t-test for independent sample on difference in the ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in colleges of education and polytechnics in North West Nigeria was ran and presented in Table 4 below:

Table 4: T-test Analysis of difference of ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in colleges of education and polytechnics in North West Nigeria

Groups	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Df	t-Value	p-value	Decision
Male	62	47.33	7.70420	229	3.04	0.03	Rejected
Female	29	43.88	7.76786				

Fieldwork 2024

Table 4 contained the t-test statistics on independent samples for the difference in the ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in colleges of education and polytechnics in North West Nigeria. The analysis revealed the mean values of 47.33 and 43.88 for male and female with standard deviation of 7.70420 and 7.76786 at degree of freedom of 229. The t-value was 3.02 and p-value was 0.03. The p-value obtained was less than the less the level of significant 0.05 set for the study. Therefore, going by decision rule, the null hypothesis was rejected. Hence, it was concluded that there exist significant difference of ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in colleges of education and polytechnics in North West of Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

The study shows that for the ICT competencies, no significant difference exists between English lecturers in federal colleges of education and polytechnics in North West,

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Nigeria. Both of them have substantial knowledge on use of computers, email, internet, social network etc. This finding is not in agreement with work of Adeoluwa, & Ogunmodede, (2018) who investigated on the lecturers' competency and utilisation of ICT facilities in the delivery of accounting lecturers in tertiary institutions in Ekiti State. Their finding shows that the use of ICT facilities depends on the level of competency of lecturers. This helps them to increase their efficacy in classroom teaching, research and publications. Thus, lecturers who are competent in the use of ICT tools can easily download new materials from the internet which can be used for lecture preparation and teaching.

The study revealed that there is significant difference in the ICT competencies between male and female English lecturers in the area of study. This finding disagree with Ahmed, et'al (2020) who conducted a study aimed at exploring South Yemeni EFL tertiary teachers' attitude towards implementing ICTs in their English Language teaching. Their findings revealed that English as Foreign Language (EFL) teachers of the concerned universities held positive attitudes towards using ICTs in their teaching of English and there is no significant difference in teachers' attitudes that can be attributed to gender, academic level or computer competence.

Conclusion

It is the conclusion of the study that the majority of English lecturers in federal college of education and polytechnic have competencies on most of the ICT tools like power point presentation Microsoft word/excel, email, social media, overhead projector and internet. Other skills are language laboratory, sound system and radio/television assisted instructions.

Recommendations

Based on the findings it was recommended that;

1. Lecturers should be encouraged to be computer literate through organizing regular conferences, seminars, and workshops. Similarly, they should be encouraged to develop good attitude toward use of ICT tools for teaching and research work.

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2. The managements of colleges of education and polytechnics should make provisions for e-learning facilities as well as capacity building in the use of facilities in their institutions. Hence, special interest should be on female lecturers to enhance their level of competencies.

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Assessing the Integration of Digital Tools and Barriers on Access to Quality Education among Internally Displaced Children in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study evaluates the role of digital tools and barriers in accessing quality education among internally displaced children (IDCs) in Benue State, Nigeria. A descriptive survey design was employed, with a population of 68,076 school-age IDCs across six Local Government Areas. A sample of 384 participants was selected using multistage sampling. Data were collected using a validated structured questionnaire, Integration of Digital Tools and Barriers on Access to Quality Education among Internally Displaced Children Questionnaire (IDTBAQEIDCQ), which achieved a reliability coefficient of 0.89. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used for analysis. Findings indicate that digital tools; such as mobile learning apps, online video platforms, e-books, and educational websites significantly enhance access to and quality of education for IDCs. However, barriers like unreliable internet access, high device costs, limited electricity, low teacher digital literacy, and poor learning environments hinder effective technology adoption. The study highlights the need to integrate technology to address educational gaps for displaced learners. Key recommendations include scaling up successful digital platforms, improving infrastructure, and enhancing teacher training in digital literacy. These measures are critical to ensuring equitable and effective education for IDCs in Benue State.

Keywords: Assessment, Quality Education, Barriers, Internally Displaced Persons & Technology Tools

Introduction

Access to quality education is a significant challenge for internally displaced children (IDCs), especially in regions experiencing conflict, natural disasters, and other forms

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of instability. In Nigeria, the situation is particularly dire due to ongoing insurgencies, communal clashes, and farmer-herder conflicts, which have displaced millions, including a large number of children (Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre [IDMC], 2022). Benue State, located in North-Central Nigeria, has been heavily impacted by these crises, resulting in a sharp increase in internally displaced persons (IDPs), with children forming a significant portion of this population (National Emergency Management Agency [NEMA], 2021). Although the government and various non-governmental organizations (NGOs) have made efforts to provide educational opportunities for these children, substantial barriers remain, particularly at the post-primary education level.

Additionally, post-primary education is a critical stage in the development of children, as it equips them with essential skills for economic productivity and social integration (United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization [UNESCO], 2020). However, IDCs in Benue State face numerous obstacles, including insufficient infrastructure, a shortage of qualified teachers, and limited access to learning materials (Okeke & Eze, 2021). These challenges are further compounded by the psychological trauma associated with displacement, which often negatively impacts their ability to learn effectively (Save the Children, 2021).

In recent years, technological tools have emerged as potential solutions to improve access to quality education, especially in resource-limited settings. Digital platforms, mobile learning applications, and online resources have demonstrated the ability to enhance educational access, improve learning outcomes, and offer personalized learning experiences (West & Chew, 2014). However, the use of technology in education for IDCs is not without its challenges. Barriers such as limited access to electricity, low digital literacy among teachers and students, and the high cost of technological devices have been identified as significant obstacles (United Nations Children's Fund [UNICEF], 2020). Additionally, the unique needs of IDCs, including their psychosocial well-being and the transient nature of their living conditions, require a tailored approach to integrating technology into their education (Agu & Okeke, 2023).

Ultimately, this study provides a crucial examination of technological tools and barriers in facilitating access to quality education for internally displaced children (IDCs) in post-primary education in Benue State. By comparing this finding with existing literature, several key insights and gaps become evident. Omale, Abduljabbar, and Dauda (2022) address the urgent need to bridge educational gaps for IDCs through

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targeted interventions during emergencies. Their work emphasizes the necessity of tailored strategies to support displaced students but does not delve deeply into the specific technological tools and barriers that could address these gaps. Ambe-Uva (2012) also discusses the potential of open and distance learning as a means to uphold the right to education for displaced populations in Nigeria. This perspective is valuable but primarily focuses on higher-level educational solutions rather than the practical, on-the-ground impact of technological tools and barriers in post-primary education settings for IDCs.

The gap identified by this study is the need for a focused examination of how technological tools and barriers specifically impact the educational experiences and outcomes of IDCs in post-primary education in Benue State. While existing studies provide a general understanding of technology's role and the challenges faced by displaced populations, they do not offer a detailed assessment of how technological interventions can be tailored to the unique needs of IDCs in this specific educational context. This research aims to bridge this gap by providing a nuanced analysis of technological tools and barriers and offering actionable insights to develop more effective strategies for leveraging technology to enhance access to quality education for IDCs in Benue State.

While there is a growing body of research on the use of technology in education, there is limited focus on role of technological tools and barriers in improving access to quality education for IDCs, particularly at the post-primary level in conflict-affected regions like Benue State. Existing studies have primarily concentrated on primary education or general IDP populations, leaving a gap in understanding the specific challenges and opportunities at the post-primary level (Obiakor & Maltby, 2020). This study aims to address this gap by evaluating the role of technological tools in meeting the educational needs of IDCs in Benue State, while also identifying the barriers that hinder their effective implementation.

In conclusion, assessing the role of technological tools and barriers in facilitating access to quality education for internally displaced children in post-primary education in Benue State is both timely and critical. As the global community continues to address the challenges of displacement and educational inequality, this study offers a unique opportunity to explore innovative solutions that can transform the educational landscape for IDCs, contributing to their holistic development and future prospects.

Statement of the Problem

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This study addresses the pressing issue of internal displacement, with a specific focus on the vulnerable demographic of internally displaced children (IDCs) in Nigeria, particularly in Benue State. The unique challenges faced by IDCs include limited access to educational resources and difficulties in maintaining a consistent learning environment due to forced relocations and the resultant instability. The majority of these displaced children are denied a secure, inclusive, and quality education, exacerbating the short- and long-term consequences of their displacement (Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre [IDMC], 2020). Existing barriers, such as a lack of teaching capacity, limited funding, ongoing insecurity, social tensions, and discrimination, further compound the challenges faced by education systems in low-income and fragile contexts (IDMC, 2020).

Recognizing the potential of technology to address these issues, the study acknowledges the growing interest in adopting technology in Nigeria's education sector. Technological interventions, such as online learning platforms, mobile applications, and digital educational resources, have shown promise in enhancing educational access for marginalized populations, including IDCs. The study aligns with the perspective presented by the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR, 2023), which views technology as a valuable tool for driving inclusion in education among displaced populations, transcending geographical constraints and bridging gaps created by displacement.

Despite numerous studies on internally displaced persons (IDPs), none have explored the influence of technological tools and barriers in facilitating access to quality education for internally displaced children in post-primary education in Benue State. Additionally, there is a lack of standardized structures, well-articulated plans, and procedures in Nigeria to address digital educational needs in emergencies. Given the contemporary and ongoing nature of this issue, a research gap has emerged, prompting this study to fill the void.

This study, therefore, seeks to assess the role of technological tools and barriers in facilitating access to quality education for internally displaced children in post-primary education in Benue State. By doing so, it aims to provide actionable insights into how technology can be effectively leveraged to address the unique educational challenges faced by IDCs, while also identifying the barriers that hinder its successful implementation. The findings of this study will contribute to the development of

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targeted strategies to improve educational outcomes for this vulnerable group, ultimately promoting inclusivity and equity in education.

Purpose of the Study

The aim of this research is to examine the role of digital tools and barriers in accessing quality education among internally displaced children (IDCs) in Benue State, Nigeria. The specific objectives guiding the study are to:

- a) Ascertain the specific technological tools and platforms that has been most effective in facilitating access to and improving the quality of education for IDPs in Benue State?
- b) Find out the main challenges and barriers hindering the effective use of technology to facilitate access to quality education for IDPs in Benue State?

Research Questions

The following research questions were set out to guide the study:

- 1) What are the specific technological tools and platforms that have most effectively facilitated access to and enhanced the quality of education for IDPs in Benue State?
- 2) What are the main challenges and barriers hindering the effective use of technology to facilitate access to quality education for IDPs in Benue State?

Methodology

The research design for this study adopted a descriptive survey design to systematically collect and analyze data on the experiences of internally displaced children (IDCs) in post-primary schools across Benue State.

This design was appropriate for assessing the impact of technology on access to quality education without manipulating variables (Nworgu, 2015). The study was conducted in Benue State, focusing on three major IDP camps: Abagena (Makurdi), Gbajimba (Guma), and Anyiin (Logo).

These areas were selected due to their high concentration of displaced persons and evident challenges in accessing quality education. The population consisted of 68,076 school-age IDCs (35,460 males and 32,616 females) across six Local Government Areas

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(LGAs) in Benue State, based on data from the Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM) Round 11 (March 2023) and the Biometric Registration Progress Report (July 2024). A sample of 384 school-age IDCs was selected using a multistage sampling technique. First, proportional stratified sampling determined the sample from each camp: Makurdi (124), Guma (146), and Logo (113). Within each camp, stratification by gender was applied based on a 52:48 male-to-female ratio. Finally, simple random sampling was employed within each gender stratum to ensure equal selection chances.

A structured questionnaire titled *Impact of Technology in Facilitating Access to Quality Education for Internally Displaced Children Questionnaire (ITFAQEIDCQ)*, adapted from Balogun (2005), was used. The instrument consisted of two sections: Section A (demographics) and Section B (25 items grouped into five thematic clusters). Responses were rated using a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (4) to Strongly Disagree (1). Experts in measurement and evaluation validated the instrument for clarity and relevance. Following validation, a pilot test with 20 participants was conducted outside the study area. Cronbach's Alpha yielded reliability coefficients ranging from 0.70 to 0.79 across clusters, with an overall reliability coefficient of 0.89. Data were collected using a direct delivery-and-retrieval method by the researcher and three trained assistants. Clear instructions were provided, and responses were retrieved immediately to minimize non-response and ensure data integrity. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to analyze the research questions, with a mean score of 2.50 or higher indicating a high extent of agreement.

Presentation of Results

This provides concise summary of the data analysis conducted following the administration of the research instrument. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were employed to analyze respondents' responses. These measures facilitated informed decision-making regarding the outcomes of the study.

Descriptive Analysis

Table 1: The demographic description of respondents:

Age	Frequency	Percent
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11-13	54	14.1
14-16	186	48.4
17-19	144	37.5
Total	384	100.0
Gender		
Male	196	51.0
Female	188	49.0
Total	384	100.0
Class Level		
JSS1-3	250	65.1
SS1-3	134	34.9
Total	384	100.0
Duration in the IDP camp		
Less than one year	27	7.0
1-2 years	330	85.9
More than 2 years	27	7.0
Total	384	100.0

Source: Field survey data (2024)

Table 1 provides a demographic overview of a sample population (N = 384) with variables categorized by age, gender, class level, and duration of stay in an IDP camp in Benue State.

Age Distribution

The age range of 14-16 years comprises the majority (48.4%) of the population, followed by 17-19 years (37.5%), while 11-13 years accounts for the smallest proportion (14.1%). This suggests that the population is predominantly adolescents in middle-to-late teenage years, likely indicative of the targeted group for the study.

Gender Distribution

The gender ratio is nearly balanced, with males constituting 51.0% and females 49.0%. The near parity ensures gender representation in the study, allowing for potentially unbiased gender-specific analysis.

Class Level Distribution

A significant portion of the participants (65.1%) are in Junior Secondary School (JSS 1-3), while 34.9% are in Senior Secondary School (SS 1-3). This distribution highlights

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the dominance of younger secondary school students, which might influence the type of interventions or programs implemented.

Years spent in the IDP Camp

Most participants (85.9%) have stayed in the camp for 1-2 years, with only 7.0% each having stayed less than a year or more than two years. This indicates a relatively recent displacement, as the majority have spent a moderate duration in the camp. It reflects the likely ongoing impact of displacement on education and other life domains.

Research Question 1: What are the specific technological tools and platforms that have most effectively facilitated access to and enhanced the quality of education for IDPs in Benue State?

To answer this research question, the responses of the students were subjected to descriptive analysis and the results were presented in table 2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Specific Technological Tools and Platforms that have most Effectively Facilitated Access to and Enhanced the Quality of Education for IDPs

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=383	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	Mobile learning apps (e.g., Google Classroom, Edmodo) have been effective in improving my access to education.		2.83	0.61	Agreed
2.	Online video platforms (e.g., YouTube, Zoom) have significantly enhanced my understanding of the subjects taught.		2.96	0.86	Agreed
3.	The use of e-books and digital libraries has improved the quality of my learning experience compared to printed books.		2.53	0.69	Agreed
4.	Educational websites (e.g., Khan Academy) have provided me with quality resources for learning.		2.62	0.89	Agreed
5.	Using computers or tablets has been effective in improving my learning outcomes compared to traditional tools.		2.65	0.89	Agreed
	Grand Mean		2.72	0.78	Below Average

Source: Field survey data (2024)

Decision $\bar{X} \geq 2.5$ Above Average

Table 2 displays the specific technological tools and platforms that have most effectively facilitated access to and enhanced the quality of education for IDPs in Benue State. All

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item statements recorded mean scores above the established cut-off mean of 2.50, indicating agreement across all categories. With a grand mean of 2.72 and a standard deviation of 0.78, the findings suggest that technological tools and platforms, such as mobile learning apps, online video platforms, e-books, digital libraries, and educational websites, have positively contributed to improving access to and the quality of education for IDPs.

Research Question 2: What are the main challenges and barriers hindering the effective use of technology to facilitate access to quality education for IDPs in Benue State?

To answer this research question, the responses of the students were subjected to descriptive analysis and the results were presented in table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of the Main Challenges and Barriers Hindering the Effective Use of Technology to Facilitate Access to Quality Education for IDPs

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=383	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	Lack of reliable internet access is a major challenge to using technology for my education.		2.95	0.72	Agreed
2.	The high cost of technological devices (e.g., tablets, laptops) hinders my access to education.		3.28	0.59	Agreed
3.	Limited availability of electricity affects my ability to effectively use technology for learning.		3.33	0.60	Agreed
4.	Poor digital literacy among teachers has negatively impacted the quality of education I receive.		2.88	1.06	Agreed
5.	The learning environment in the IDP camp makes it challenging to focus on technology-based education.		2.89	1.01	Agreed
	Grand Mean		3.07	0.80	Below Average

Source: Field survey data (2024)

Decision $\bar{X} \geq 2.5$ Above Average

Table 5 reveals the main challenges and barriers hindering the effective use of technology to facilitate access to quality education for IDPs in Benue State. All item statements recorded mean scores above the established cut-off mean of 2.50, indicating agreement across all categories. With a grand mean of 3.07 and a standard deviation of 0.80, the findings suggest that challenges such as lack of reliable internet access, the high cost of technological devices, limited availability of electricity, poor

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digital literacy among teachers, and the learning environment in IDP camps have negatively impacted the effective use of technology for educational purposes.

Discussion of Findings

The result of research question one showed that technological tools and platforms, such as mobile learning apps, online video platforms, e-books, digital libraries, and educational websites, have positively contributed to improving access to and the quality of education for IDPs. The positive impact of technological tools and platforms on education for IDPs could be attributed to their accessibility, cost-effectiveness, and ability to deliver diverse, multimedia-rich resources that address varied learning needs. The findings of this align with Munoto, Meini and Satriana (2021), who demonstrated that mobile learning applications improve student responses and motivation, making them a feasible tool for enhancing learning outcomes. Furthermore, the finding agreed with Oyelere and Suhonen (2016), which demonstrated how mobile learning applications like MobileEdu effectively provide access to quality education in Nigeria. Lastly, the study resonates with Dahlstrom, Walker and Dziuban (2013), who found that mobile devices allow students to access educational materials anytime and anywhere, bridging gaps in access to learning resources. This finding implies that the adoption of digital tools and online learning systems can improve access to education for IDP children, offering them equitable and inclusive opportunities for quality learning.

The outcome of research question two revealed that challenges such as lack of reliable internet access, the high cost of technological devices, limited availability of electricity, poor digital literacy among teachers, and the learning environment in IDP camps have negatively impacted the effective use of technology for educational purposes. This result may be attributed to systemic infrastructural deficiencies, socio-economic barriers, and inadequate teacher training in digital literacy within IDP camps. The findings correspond with Adeoye, Adanikin, and Adanikin, (2020), who identified unstable power supply and the high cost of data as barriers to e-learning in Nigeria. Furthermore, the results are consistent with Ubi and Ofre (2021) who opined that poor internet connectivity and the lack of digital tools prevented rural students from participating in government-provided e-learning initiatives. Similarly, Akinrinola, Adebayo, Onakpoya and Nwaozuru, (2020), reported that teachers' limited technical expertise poses a challenge to effective e-learning facilitation. The implication of this finding is that addressing infrastructural deficits, reducing technology costs, and

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improving teacher digital literacy are critical for enhancing the effective use of technology in education within IDP camps.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the positive contributions of technological tools and platforms—such as mobile learning apps, online video platforms, e-books, digital libraries, and educational websites—in enhancing access to and improving the quality of education for internally displaced persons (IDP) children in Benue State. These technologies have provided flexible learning opportunities and enriched educational content, making learning more engaging and accessible. However, significant challenges persist, including unreliable internet access, high costs of technological devices, limited electricity supply, low digital literacy among teachers, and unfavorable learning environments within IDP camps. Addressing these barriers is essential to fully harness the potential of technology in creating equitable and effective educational opportunities for displaced children.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that:

1. Stakeholders should evaluate and scale up the use of platforms such as e-learning modules, interactive educational software, and localized digital libraries that have demonstrated success in improving access and quality.
2. School administrators, in collaboration with government and NGOs, should address infrastructural challenges such as internet connectivity, reliable electricity supply, and the affordability of devices by establishing solar-powered computer labs, providing offline digital tools, and seeking partnerships to secure necessary resources for IDP schools.

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Qualitative Study on Ensemble Learning-Based-Predictive Model on Classification of Churn for Business Propensity in Nigeria

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Abstract

The modern business environment is changing rapidly that companies are always looking for new ways to boost sales and profitability. A popular and successful approach is predictive analytics, which uses machine learning algorithms to estimate sales leads and their likelihood of conversion. This instrument has changed the way sales methods are used, making them more successful and efficient at generating revenue. Recognizing customer churn as a critical issue implies understanding that when customers leave a business at a higher rate than desired, it indicates deeper problems or challenges within the organization. The features that are associated with the classification of churn among customers were identified following which relevant data was collected from an online repository provided online by Kaggle. The predictive model for the classification of churn among customers was simulated using the holdout method based on three simulation runs for an ensemble learning model XGBoost. The results of the study showed that the ensemble methods adopted, the XGBoost classifier proved to have the best overall performance having 100% accuracy through the three simulation respectively. However, it was observed that as the proportion of the training datasets increased, the performance of the machine learning classifiers improved. The features that are most important to the classification of churn among customers include: type of customer

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contract, tenure of using service, satisfaction level of customer support, online security service, device protection service, payment methods, and streaming services.

Keywords: customer churn, classification, supervised learning, unsupervised learning, ensemble modeling,

Introduction

The number of clients in every business is growing daily in our day, and customers have multiple options in every area, including financial, governmental, and organizational ones. The primary focus of this study is the banking industry's forecast of client attrition. One issue facing the banking industry is customer churn, which occurs when businesses are unable to retain their clientele for a variety of shifting reasons, including better services at lower prices, bank location, etc. Therefore In today's market, it is more expensive to acquire new consumers than it is to keep existing ones, thus maintaining positive relationships with current ones is essential (Aman, Jigyasa & Manish ,2024; Adrin & Fadaralia, 2020). By combining multiple models, ensemble learning techniques can leverage the strengths of individual models while mitigating their weaknesses, thereby improving predictive accuracy and robustness (Yağcı, 2022). Moreover, ensemble learning methods can handle diverse types of data and modelling techniques, enabling a more comprehensive analysis of factors influencing prediction. Ensemble Modelling is widely used in various ensemble learning tasks, including classification, regression, and clustering. It has been shown to improve predictive performance, reduce variance, and increase model robustness compared to single-model approaches. However, ensemble modelling requires careful tuning of hyper parameters, selection of diverse base models, and consideration of computational resources to achieve optimal results (Joolfoo, *et al*, 2020; Gore, Chibber, Bhasin & Melita, 2023). As mentioned earlier, analyzing customer behavior serves as the basis for predicting customers who might churn, which is important for many reasons. One reason is that for companies who rely on subscription-based income, it can make a big difference on whether they can keep a steady income level or if they need to make changes to their services to keep customers (Lalwani, Mishra, Chadha, & Sethi, 2022). Another reason is that, compared to retaining customers, attracting new ones is costlier and firms can save money by retaining their existing customer base (de Lima Lemos, Silva, & Tabak, 2022).

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In the world of commercial enterprises, achieving financial success is closely tied to customer management. This means not only acquiring new customers but also minimizing customer churn, as these factors together contribute to a business's overall performance (Habes, Altairey, & Ismail, 2024; Mali, Runwal, Shah, Raut & Hire 2023). Many studies have considered the subject matter of the development of predictive models required for the classification of customer churn from various dimensions but many have not considered the importance of features on the performance of predictive models. Also, it has been observed that many studies were limited to the use of a single simulation run for development whereas multiple simulation runs of varying proportions of training and testing datasets can provide better insights into the performance of predictive models thereby providing more optimal solutions. There is a need for the identification of the features that are likely to improve the performance of the classification of customer churn thereby mitigating the onset of churn among customers using ensemble learning algorithms, hence this study.

Review of Related Literature

Sindikubwabo and Ndengo (2023), applied an ensemble of ensemble learning to the prediction of churn among customers in the banking sector. The study collected data containing information about churn among customers from an online repository provided by Kaggle. The data contained information about 14 features from 10000 customer records. The study performed a single simulation run consisting of 80% for training and 20% for testing the models. The results revealed that kNN showed the best performance with an accuracy of 86.5% among the ensemble learning algorithms however the overall best performance was achieved ranfom forest algorithm with an accuracy of 87.4%. The study failed to consider the impact of feature selection and varying proportion of training and testing datasets selected during simulation on the performance of the model.

de Lima Lemos, Silva, and Tabak (2022), worked on the application of ensemble learning alkgorithms to the determination of customers who were likely to churn. The study collected data containing information about 35 attributes from 500,000 customers which was subjected to a number of data preprocessing tasks with equal distribution of churners and non-churners. The study adopted the use of decision trees (DT), K-nearest neighbours (kNN), logistic regression (LR), support vector machines (SVM) and random forest for the classification of customer churn based on the collected

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dataset using 10-fold cross validation approach. The results revealed that the best performance was achieved using random forest algorithm with an accuracy of 82.8%. The study did not consider how the size of training dataset can affect the performance of the predictive models since it was limited to a single simulation run.

Dhangar and Anad (2021), assessed the performance of the application of ensemble learning to the prediction of customer churn. The study performed an exhaustive review of literature covering the various algorithms and tool adopted for the development of predictive models required for assessing customer churn. The study collected data from 7045 client records containing information about 21 features. The study adopted a single simulation run for the assessment of logistic regression, Gaussian naïve Bayes, support vector machines and random forest. The results revealed that the best performance was achieved using random forest algorithm with an accuracy of 87%. The study was limited to a single simulation run and did not consider the impact of the selection of relevant features on the performance of ensemble learning algorithms.

Methodology

Collection of Data

The dataset used in this study was collected from the publicly accessible repository that is provided by Kaggle online via the Internet. It is a public dataset that has been made available for educational and research purposes and is available via <https://www.kaggle.com/blastchar/telco-customerchurn>. The dataset consists of information about a set of features that was collected from 1870 non-churner records and 5173 churner records making a total of 7043 records.

Table 1: Demographic information of customers

FEATURE NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATA LABEL
GENDER	Customer's gender	Male, Female
SENIOR CITIZEN	Is customer an elder?	Yes, No
PARTNER	Has a partner (or spouse)	Yes, No
DEPENDENTS	Has dependents (Child)	Yes, No.

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Table 1 shows a description of the demographic information of the customers which is composed of four (4) features. The features include: gender, been a senior citizen, having a partner (or spouse) and having dependents (child). The gender of the customer was identified as a binary value with values Male and Female however the other three features were identified as binary value with values Yes and No.

Table 2: Service-based information of customers

FEATURE NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATA LABEL
PHONE	Use phone?	Yes, No
MULTIPLE LINES	Have multiple lines?	Yes, No, NPS
INTERNET	Use Internet?	DSL, Fiber Optic, No
ONLINE SECURITY	Use online security?	Yes, No, FPS
ONLINE BACKUP	Use online backup?	Yes, No, FPS
DEVICE PROTECTION	Use device protection?	Yes, No, FPS
TECHNICAL SUPPORT	Provided technical support?	Yes, No, FPS
STREAMING TV	Streams TV?	Yes, No, FPS
STREAMING MOVIES	Streams Movies?	Yes, No, FPS

Table 2 shows the description of the service-based information of the customers which was composed of nine (9) features. The features include knowledge of phone use, having multiple phone lines, using Internet, using online security, using online backup, using device protection, receiving technical support, TV and movie streaming. All the features were represented as categorical data such that the use of phone is binary while the rest are ternary. The use of Internet was represented as either: direct service line (DSL), fiber optic and no while the remaining features were represented as: yes, no and no phone service.

Table 3 shows a description of the account-based information of the customers which is composed of seven (7) features. Some of the features are numeric while others are categorical. The features with numeric data include: customer ID, monthly charges, total amount charged, and time spent using service. The categorical features include: contract represented as monthly, biennial, and yearly; using paper billing was represented as Yes and No while method of payment was presented as: electronic check, mailed check, bank transfer and credit card.

Table 3: Account information of customers

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FEATURE NAME	DESCRIPTION	DATA LABEL
PHONE	Use phone?	Yes, No
MULTIPLE LINES	Have multiple lines?	Yes, No, NPS
INTERNET	Use Internet?	DSL, Fiber Optic, No
ONLINE SECURITY	Use online security?	Yes, No, FPS
ONLINE BACKUP	Use online backup?	Yes, No, FPS
DEVICE PROTECTION	Use device protection?	Yes, No, FPS
TECHNICAL SUPPORT	Provided technical support?	Yes, No, FPS
STREAMING TV	Streams TV?	Yes, No, FPS
STREAMING MOVIES	Streams Movies?	Yes, No, FPS

Model Simulation

To develop the predictive model that was required for the classification of churn among customers the dataset collected for this study was fed to a few ensemble learning and ensemble learning algorithms using the holdout method. The dataset was split into two parts, namely: training and testing dataset such that the training dataset was used to build the model while the testing dataset was used to validate the performance of the predictive model. The simulation was performed using 3 simulation runs of varying proportions of the training and testing datasets following which the models were compared based on several performance evaluation metrics. The results of the simulation and evaluation of the predictive models was represented using a diagram called confusion matrix. The evaluation of the performance of the predictive models was done based on the testing dataset and not the training dataset.

Presentation of Result

Results of the Simulation of Predictive Model

This section presents the results of the application of the ensemble learning algorithms, XGBoost classifier. The model simulation was conducted by splitting the dataset into two parts, train and test dataset using five simulations such that 60/40, 70/30, and 80/20 percent of the dataset was adopted for training/testing the predictive model. Table 6 shows the number of records that were adopted for each simulation that were considered in this study. As stated earlier, the train datasets were used to build the predictive model while the test data were used to evaluate the performance of the predictive model based on a number of performance evaluation metrics.

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In simulation 1, 60% of the dataset was adopted for training and 40% was adopted for testing such that the train data consisted of 3753 no churn records and 472 churn record while the test data consisted of 1421 no churn and 1397 churn records. In simulation 2, 70% of the dataset was adopted for training and 30% was adopted for testing such that the train data consisted of 4103 no churn records and 827 churn record while the test data consisted of 1071 diabetes present and 1042 churn records. In simulation 3, 80% of the dataset was adopted for training and 20% was adopted for testing such that the train data consisted of 4473 no churn records and 1161 churn record while the test data consisted of 701 no churn present and 708 churn.

Table 4: Description of the number of records adopted for training and testing predictive model across three simulations.

SIMULATION#	TRAIN DATA			TEST DATA			
	No churn	Churn	Total	No churn	Churn	Total	
SIMULATION (60/40)	1	3753	472	4225	1421	1397	2818
SIMULATION (70/30)	2	4103	827	4930	1071	1042	2113
SIMULATION (80/20)	3	4473	1161	5634	701	708	1409

Results of the Evaluation of the Predictive Model

This section presents the results of the evaluation of the predictive model that were generated across the three simulations based on the ensemble learning technique that was adopted in this study. The results are presented for each simulation following which the results of the performance of the algorithm was presented.

Evaluation of predictive models in simulation 1

As stated earlier, simulation 1 was validated using a dataset that was composed of 40% of the dataset and consisted of 1421 Non-churn and 1397 Churn records. Figure 3 shows the confusion matrices that were used to interpret the results of the evaluation of each predictive model developed in simulation 1 based on the test dataset. Using XGBoost classifier, it was observed that all 1421 Non-churn records were correctly classified and all 1397 Churn records were correctly classified owing to an accuracy of 100%.

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Figure 3: Confusion matrices for the evaluation of XGBoost for simulation 1.

Evaluation of predictive models in simulation 2

As stated earlier, simulation 2 was validated using a dataset that was composed of 30% of the dataset and consisted of 1071 Non-churn and 1042 Churn records. Figure 4 shows the confusion matrices that were used to interpret the results of the evaluation of each predictive model developed in simulation 2 based on the test dataset. Using XGBoost classifier, it was observed that all 1071 Non-churn records were correctly classified and all 1042 Churn records were correctly classified owing to an accuracy of 100

Figure 4: Confusion matrix for the evaluation XGBoost for simulation 2.

Evaluation of predictive models in simulation 3

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As stated earlier, simulation 3 was validated using a dataset that was composed of 20% of the dataset and consisted of 701 Non-churn and 708 Churn records. Figure 5 shows the confusion matrices that were used to interpret the results of the evaluation of each predictive model developed in simulation 3 based on the test dataset. Using XGBoost classifier, it was observed that all 701 Non-churn records were correctly classified and all 708 Churn records were correctly classified owing to an accuracy of 100

Figure 5: Confusion matrix for the evaluation of XGBoost, for simulation 3.

Discussion of Results

This section presents the discussion of the results of the various analyses that were performed in this study for the development of a predictive model required for the classification of churn among customers. The results of the study showed that the ensemble method adopted, the XGBoost classifier proved to have the best overall performance among throughout the simulations. However, it was observed that as the proportion of the training dataset increased, the performance of the machine learning classifiers improved.

It was revealed in this study that the ensemble learning algorithm selected in this study showed very good performance in the classification of churn. The results of this study showed better performance than that of the study conducted by Malik, Runwal, Shah, Raut, and Hire (2023) which had an accuracy of 90.3% using Light GBM classifier and in the study by Sindikubwabo and Ndengo (2023) who showed an accuracy of 87.4% using random forest classifier and in the study by de Lima Lemos, Silva, and Tabak (2022), who showed an accuracy of 82.8%. However, the results of this study supported the view promoted in the study by Adrin and Fadaralika (2020) and Dhangar and Anad

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(2021) regarding their view concerning the effectiveness of ensemble models for development of predictive models. Table 7 presents the summary of the results of the evaluation of the performance of the ensemble learning approaches considered in this study.

SIMULATIO N# (TEST RECORDS)	ALGORI THM	CORRECT RECORDS	ACCURACY (%)	PRECISION		RECALL		F1-SCORE	
				No Churn	Chur n	No Churn	Churn	No Churn	Churn
SIMULATIO N 1 (2818 RECORDS)	XGBoost	2818	100.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
SIMULATIO N 2 (2113 RECORDS)	XGBoost	2113	100.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000
SIMULATIO N 3 (1409 RECORDS)	XGBoost	1409	100.00	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000	1.000

Conclusion

The study identified that each feature had a relative importance to one another regarding their usefulness in the classification of churn. However, it was observed that the information provided by the mutual information metric seemed to be more reliable compared to the information provided by the Pearson's correlation since this is focused on assessing linear relationship which is hardly the case in medical data. The study concluded that ensemble learning models proved effective in the development of predictive models for the classification of churn among customers. The study revealed that the most important feature was the service-based information. Also, it was observed that the XGBoost classifier showed the best performance.

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Assessment of Parents' Socio-Economic Status on Academic Achievement among Secondary School Students in Niger State, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study investigated Parents socio-economic status as a factor on Academic Achievement of secondary schools in Niger State, Nigeria. The study looked at effects of parents' socio-economic status on academic achievement of students' secondary schools. The study used ex-post factor method, in which groups with qualities that already existed are compared, in 150 schools with a population of (373,529) students, out of which 384 participants were drawn as sample size using multi stage technique. The instruments used include Kuppuswamy classification of socio-economic status and End of year examination scores tagged, (KCSESEYESQ). The instrument was pilot tested among 50 students in different location and the reliability of KCSESEYESQ was 0.81 obtained through test re-test method. To direct the course of investigation, six objectives, and questions were set to guide the study, six research hypotheses were also tested to guide the conduct of the study. T-test and ANOVA statistics were used to test the hypotheses, with a significant level of 0.05. The Findings revealed that parents' socio-economic status (finance) have a significant effect on the academic achievement of secondary schools students in Niger State. In conclusion, the findings indicated that parents 'income, educational background and occupational status all significantly affects students' academic achievement. Based on the findings, it was recommended that parents should support educational pursuits of their children financially, academically and experience wise, Government to employed qualified teachers and posted to teach in rural and urban areas, lastly scholarship assistance can be initiated to facilitate education among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Key words: Parents, Socio-economic status, students, Academic, Achievement

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Introduction

Academic achievement of students remains an issue of great interest to educationists, psychologist and stakeholders, as it remains the means of distinguishing successful students from unsuccessful ones. It is a means of assessing the extent to which learning has taken place in students and is intended to improve their life and the nation at large. The issue of low academic achievement at the secondary level seeks for serious concern since it takes its origin from the lower level that is responsible for the training of both middle and high-level man-power for the country. Therefore, under-achievement at this level will be a disaster for the country. Presently, some employers of labour are already lamenting about the low quality of our undergraduates. Many now prefer graduates from foreign universities, such as Asia, UK, USA and neighboring African countries. In a study (Eyong, David and Umoh 2014), it was stated that there had been a reported incidence of under-achievement among students in secondary schools as evidenced by poor outing of WAEC results, which for years had been the standard measurement of academic achievement.

Despite these laudable efforts, it is unfortunate to find some students irrespective of their intelligent quotient (IQ) still considered under achievers. This indicates that the factors responsible for their under-academic achievement are due to teaching methodology, the nature of curriculum and the inability to cover the syllabus, among others. Therefore, there is the need to look at the factors related to students' psychosocial and cognitive attributes that may have some effects on their socio-economic status on academic achievement, since they are psychosocial beings.

The researcher deems this as an important vacuum to research into. A lot of factors have contributed to poor academic achievement of students. According to literatures academic achievement is a product of a number of factors operating within the individual and outside him. Broadly speaking, the main factor which influences academic achievement is the parents' socio-economic status. It can also be added that it has now been fairly established that the emotional factors, most particularly anxiety, environmental factors and levels of aspiration, largely determine one's academic achievement, which this study is not set out to investigate. A major factor that determines students' academic achievement is parents' socio-economic status.

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Socio-Economic Status (SES) According to American Psychological Association (APA), socio-economic status is commonly conceptualized as the social standing or class of an individual or group, and it is often measured as a combination of education, income and occupation. In the present study, a student SES is identified by the information provided by the questionnaire about the students' parents' academic and professional qualifications, income and occupational affiliations. Parental education and socio-economic supports are very important ingredients in students' academic achievement. The finding of studies has indicated that the academic achievement of students is contingent upon parents' socio-economic condition. For instance, Li and Qiu (2018) state that family socioeconomic status has a greater impact on the total effect of children's academic achievement. This means that parental socio-economic status is a vital factor that affects the academic achievement of students significantly. Studies have also shown that the academic achievement of students is directly proportional to parental income, education and occupation of their parent. Pant, (2020) in a study revealed that majority of students of low SES has poor academic achievement.

That is why it is right to say that the high socio-economic status of parents plays a fundamental and crucial role in the enhancement of children's academic achievement. So, differences have been observed between those students who come from different financial status and different parental educational levels. The students belonging to higher socio-economic backgrounds will achieve academically better than those with low socio-economic backgrounds. This is the general over-view of the majority, but the same assertion mostly is true as related studies pointed out those students who mostly come from deprived socio-economic and educational backgrounds achieve academically and relatively better than those coming from higher socio-economic and educational background. This trend or phenomena is referred to as educational elasticity.

Academic achievement refers to the outcome of education and the extent to which a student, teacher or institution has achieved the educational goals. It is commonly measured by examinations or continuous assessment. Academic achievement focuses on particular learning in a particular setting, which is defined by examination scores, teachers' grades and percentiles in academic subjects. School successes depend upon the ability of students to qualify in such examinations. For present study, academic achievement is defined as the cumulative grade obtained by students in the end of final examinations conducted by the schools during the year May/ June 2021/2022. This

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study is aimed at assessing the effects of parents' socio-economic status on academic achievement among the secondary school students in Niger state.

Socio-economic status (SES) is an economics and sociological combined total measure of a person's work experience and of an individual's or family's economic and social position in relation to others based on income, education and occupation. When analyzing a family's SES, the household income, earners' education and occupation are examined, as well as combined income, among individuals, when their own attributes are assessed. According to Mladenka, Ana, Ivana and Merima, (2017). Parental socio-economic status is a multidimensional concept of social importance for the growth and development, health outcomes and education of the children. Its definition generally refers to the amount of parental income, their employment status and level of education. Socio-economic status is typically broken into three categories (high SES, middle SES and low SES) to describe the three areas a family or an individual may fall into. When placing a family or an individual into one of these categories, any or all of the three variables (income, education and occupation) can be assessed (Saifi and Mehood, 2011).

Income refers to wages, salaries, profits, rents and any flow of earning received. It can also come in the form of unemployment or workers' compensation, social security, pensions, interests or dividends, royalties, trusts, alimony, or other government, public or family financial assistance. Income can be looked at in two terms, relative and absolute. Absolute income, as theorized by the economist John Maynard Keynes, is the relationship in which as income increases, so will consumption, but not at the same rate. Relative income dictates a person or family's savings and consumption based on the family's income in relation to others. Income was most strongly associated to all indicators; the association remained statistically significant when adjusting to other indicators. Alexander, Stefan and Ingemar (2017). Low income families focus on meeting immediate needs and do not accumulate wealth that could be passed on to future generations, thus increasing inequality. Families with higher and expendable income can accumulate wealth and focus on meeting immediate needs while being able to consume and enjoy luxuries and weather crises.

Researchers have claimed that the economic status of parents influences the academic achievement of the students. It was argued that parental economic status and education play a vital role in the learning achievement of their children. Parents of a

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medium socioeconomic class found to be more conscious about the future carrier of their children (Thomson, 2018)

Occupational prestige, as one component of SES, encompasses both income and educational attainment. Occupational status reflects the educational attainment required to obtain the job and income levels that vary with different jobs and within ranks of occupations. Additionally, it shows achievement in the skills required for the job. Occupational status measures social position by describing job characteristic, decision making ability and control and psychological demands on the job. Occupations are ranked by the census (among other organizations) and opinion polls from the general population are surveyed. Some of the most prestigious occupations are physicians and surgeons, lawyers, chemical and biomedical engineers, university professors and communications analysts. These jobs, considered to be grouped in the high SES

Classification, provide more challenging work and greater control over working conditions but require more ability. The job with lower rankings include food preparation workers, counter attendants, bartenders and helpers, dishwashers, janitors, maids and housekeepers, vehicle cleaners and parking lot attendants. The jobs that are less valued also offer significantly lower wages and often are more laborious, very hazardous and provide less autonomy. Occupation is the most difficult factor to measure because so many exist and there are so many competing scales. Many scales rank occupations based on the level of skill involved, from unskilled manual labor t professional or use a combined measure using the education level needed and the income involved (Afifa, Kusum, Anamika, Kamlesh and Manohar, 2015). From the above explanation, it can be interpreted that the majority of researchers agree that income, education and occupation together best represent SES, while some others feel that changes in family structure should also be considered. With the definition of SES more clearly defined, it is now important to discuss the effect of SES on students' cognitive abilities and academic success. Several researchers have found that SES affects students' stabilities.

Another important issues concerning students' socio-economic background is whether it is defined by the characteristics of their fatherism, their motherism or some combination of both. Traditionally, studies of the effects of social background on educational outcomes have measured social class or socio-economic status by father's occupation. This assumes that the class position of the family is determined by the

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occupation of the adult male and female occupation is largely irrelevant. Since the mid-1970s, the traditional view has come under attack from feminists, who argue, justifiably, that women's occupations are relevant to both their own social and economic position and that of their families. In the context of post-war years, the traditional procedure was more understandable. Men were viewed as 'the provider', 'the head of the house hold' or 'main breadwinner' and the proportion of married women in the work force was considerably lower than it is today. Given the present situation of high proportions of married women in the labour force, 'career women' and increasing numbers of house husband, the traditional procedure is less attractive than it once was (Amogne, 2015).

An important aspect of disadvantage is family structure. It is often believed that students living in one parent or blended families do less well at school than students from more traditional nuclear families. The detrimental effects of family disrupt found on the social mobility is most through education. There is little doubt that it is desirable to monitor differences in educational outcome between types of family structures. It is also true that the type of family a student comes from is relevant to the measurement of parental occupation and education. However, it is not clear if family structure comes under the rubrics of socio-economic background or is a distinct source of educational disadvantage (Chioma, Bernadethe and Joseph, 2017). The researchers, after studying the above literature on socio-economic status level, resolved to present the literature on academic achievement.

Statement of the Problem

It has been notice for quite some times the dwindling nature of student's academic of secondary school students in Niger State. This was attributed to daily poor academic among students overtime. There is therefore the need to nip this challenge at the bud before it becomes a source of serious concerned to both the state and the national at large. Academic achievement will be jeopardized because students cannot accomplish academic tasks, and had difficulty meeting educational and career goals. In the long run, there is the possibility of students dropping out from schools. Therefore, the present study precisely seeks to investigate under academic achievement against influence of parents' socio-economic status levels as a factor on academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger state, Nigeria.

Objectives of the Study

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The objective of this study includes the followings:

1. To ascertain whether parents' income affects high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
2. To evaluate effect of parents' educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
3. To measure the parents' level of employment influence on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
4. To determine the difference between Parents' income and educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
5. To determine the difference between Parents' educational background and level of employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
6. To determine the interactive effect of Parents' income, educational background and level of employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Research Questions

The following questions are raised:-

1. What are the effects of parents' income on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State?
2. What are the effects of parents' educational background effect on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State?
3. What are the levels of parents' employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State?
4. What is the difference between Parents' income and Educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State?
5. What is the level of Parents' Educational background and Employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State?

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6. What is the level of interactive effect between Parents' income, Educational background and level of Employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State?

Research Hypotheses

This will test the following empirical hypotheses:-

- H₀₁: There is no significant difference effect of parents' income on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
- H₀₂: There is no significant effect difference of parents' educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
- H₀₃: There is no significant difference effect in parents' employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
- H₀₄: There is no significant difference effect of parents' income and educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
- H₀₅: There is no significant difference effect of parents' educational background and levels of employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.
- H₀₆: There is no significant difference in interactive effect of parents' income, educational background and employment on high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools student in Niger State.

Methodology

Research Design

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The research design for this study is ex-post-facto method in which groups with qualities that already exist are compared on dependent variables. Also known as “after the fact” research, an ex-post facto design is considered quasi-experimental because the subjects are not randomly assigned. They are grouped based on particular characteristics or traits. Assigning subjects to different groups is based on whichever variable is of interest to the researcher. Ex-post-facto research in education has permitted investigations of the effects of variables, such as home background, father’s absence, early experiences, disabilities, teacher competence and others that are beyond the control of educators. In some instances, ex-post-facto research has discovered relationships or raised questions that can later be investigated more systematically in well-controlled experimental studies.

Population of the Study

The population for this study consisted of over one hundred and fifty (150) secondary schools with an estimated numbers of three hundred and seventy three thousand, five hundred and twenty nine (373, 529) students in Niger State.

Sample Size

Based on the estimated population of this study, which is (n=373,529), in line with Baron and Kenny in Otuwa, (2019), 384 sample is adequate for a population of 1,000,000 and above. This is aligned with size believing that the six secondary schools will have more than such population. The study however, will administer a total of (537) questionnaire throughout the six secondary schools. The 40% increase in questionnaire is in line with non-response attitude of respondents (Alex 2022) and Nigeria’s attitudes of poor response rate to questionnaire (Murthy 2022). Out of over one hundred and fifty (150) secondary schools in Niger State; six (6) secondary schools are randomly selected according to the state geo-political zones.

Sampling Techniques

Multi stage cluster sampling is a more complex form of cluster sample, which contains two or more stages in sample selection. According to Pritha, (2021) Multi-stage sampling, or multistage cluster sampling, you draw a sample from a population using smaller groups (units) at each stage. It’s often used to collect data from a large, geographically spread group of people in a national survey. All the SS 111 students’ population of selected secondary schools in Niger State 2021/2020 was captured in

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this study, using Multi-stage sample. The first stage was using Cluster sampling technique to randomly select out fifteen (15) schools. This was done simply by writing the names of the whole schools each on separate sheets of paper, folded and a research assistant was asked to pick out a name after shaking the container where fifteen (15) different names were picked out. When it was opened, it contained the names of fifteen (15) schools. The second stage is also using the clustery sampling technique to select nine (9) schools out of the above fifteen (15) schools. The same process of clustery sampling was carried out picking nine (9) schools. The third stage is also using same the clustery sampling technique to select six (6) schools. Following the same clustery sampling technique. The fourth stage is to use stratified random sampling technique to select study sample size which from the population of the six (6) schools. This is done through the use of the students' class list from the exams office where every third name on the list was selected.

Data Collection Instrument

The data collection instruments using one adapted Questionnaire and examination generated scores, these are:-

Kuppuswamy Classification of Socio-Economic Status (Scale)

The Kuppuswamy Classification of Socio-economic Status was proposed by Kuppuswamy B. (1976). The adapted instrument was used to measures the SES of urban population. The instrument is to elicit for parents' socio-economic status data through the students. It's divided into three (3) sections based on the status of individuals, namely Section A Education, Section B Occupation and Section C Income of the household or family. Number of test items:- It contains 24 items shared within the three sections. Section A ten (10) items, section B seven (7) items and section C seven (7) items.

End of the Year Examination Scores

The end of the year examination scores is an internal assessment set and marked by the teachers. The scores obtained by examinees as results from a teacher made examination questions to mark the coverage of syllabus and end of the term or school

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calendar in secondary schools. In this study, EYES would be used to measure the students' academic achievement, through transforming the scores generated using Z scores statistical method. It's the means through which academic achievement will be measure in this study.

Pilot Testing

In this study, a pilot test would be carried out using the test re-test method. The purpose of conducting a pilot testing is to ascertain if respondents would encounter any difficulty in completing the instruments used in this study. The data collected are used to calculate the reliabilities value of the instruments with the aid of SPSS. Cronbach's Alpha reliability coefficient for each of the instrument will be shown. Test re-test reliability would be computed to examine the suitability of the instrument that is sought through a test re-test. Fifty (50) students from G.S.S Minna (Father "O" Connell) would be used in this testing.

Data Collection Procedure

A letter of introduction from the Department of Counselling Psychology would be presented at the office of the Principals of the selected secondary schools in Niger State. This is to grant the researcher access to collect the required data by administering the questionnaire to the selected respondents.

Data Analysis Procedure

The computation and organization of data will be done with SPSS software. However, the data will be transferred to and run on stata package for analysis. Hypotheses 1 and 2 will tested using ANOVA and Hypotheses 3 using regression analysis at the 0.05 level of significance.

Presentation of Result

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in effect of parents' income on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

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Table 1: One-way analysis of variance on the difference in the effect of Parents' income on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Parent income	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	321.762	2	160.881	1.349	.261
Within Groups	44380.414	372	119.302		
Total	44702.176	374			

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A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to investigate potential difference in the effect of parents' income on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State. The analysis revealed that there was no statistically significant difference in academic achievement among secondary school students based on their parents' income levels, $F(2, 372) = 1.349$, $p = .261$. The between-groups sum of squares was 321.762, and the within-groups sum of squares was 44380.414, resulting in a total sum of squares of 44702.176. The mean square for between-groups was 160.881, and the mean square for within-groups was 119.302. These findings indicates that, at the 0.05 significance level, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the effect of parents' income on academic achievement is not significantly different across high, moderate, and low income levels among secondary school students in Niger State.

H_{02} : There is no significant difference effect of parents' educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Table 2: One-way analysis of variance on the difference effect of Parents' educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Parent Educational Background	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	333.940	2	166.970	1.400	.248
Within Groups	44368.236	372	119.269		
Total	44702.176	374			

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A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine the difference in the effect of parents' educational background effect on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State. The analysis indicated that there was no statistically significant difference in academic achievement among secondary school students based on their parents' educational qualifications, $F(2, 372) = 1.400$, $p = .248$. The between-groups sum of squares was 333.940, and the within-groups sum of squares was 44368.236, resulting in a total sum of squares of 44702.176. The mean square for between-groups was 166.970, and the mean square for within-groups was 119.269. At the 0.05 significance level, the p-value of .248 suggests that there is no significant difference in academic achievement based on parents' educational qualification levels.

H_{03} : There is no significant difference effect of parents' employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Table 3: One-way analysis of variance on the difference effect of Parents' employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Parent Employment	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	333.830	2	166.970	1.300	.256
Within Groups	44259.328	372	118.279		
Total	44593.158	374			

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A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to investigate difference in the effect of parents' employment on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State. The analysis revealed that there was no statistically significant difference in academic achievement among secondary school students based on their parents' employment levels, $F(2, 372) = 1.300$, $p = .256$. The between-groups sum of squares was 333.830, and the within-

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groups sum of squares was 44259.328, leading to a total sum of squares of 44593.158. The mean square for between-groups was 166.970, and the mean square for within-groups was 118.279. At the conventional 0.05 significance level, the p-value of .256 indicates that there is no significant difference in academic achievement among students with varying levels of parents' income.

H₀₄: There is no significant difference effect of parents' income and educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Table 4: Multivariate Analysis of Variance on the effects of Parents' educational background and employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Effect		Value	F	Df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta Sq
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.987	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Wilks' Lambda	.013	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Hotelling's Trace	74.354	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Roy's Largest Root	74.354	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
Qualification	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Occupation	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Qualification * Occupation	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000

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A multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was conducted to examine the effects of parents' educational background and employment on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State. The analysis revealed significant effects for the Intercept, indicating that the model as a whole is statistically significant, with Wilks' showing substantial effect sizes (Pillai's Trace = .987, F = 3829.228, p < .001, partial eta squared = .987). However, the main

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effects of parents' educational background and employment, as well as their interaction, were found to be non-significant. Pillai's Trace for parents' educational background and employment, and the interaction term all yielded values of 0, indicating no significant effect on the academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State.

H₀₅: There is no significant difference effect of parents' educational background and employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students in Niger State.

Table 5: Multivariate Analysis of Variance on the effects of parents' income and educational background on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students

Effect		Value	F	df	Error	Sig.	Partial Eta
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.987	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Wilks' Lambda	.013	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Hotelling's Trace	74.354	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Roy's Largest Root	74.354	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
Income	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Qualification	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Income *Qualification	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000

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A multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was conducted to examine the effects of parents' income and educational background on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools student in Niger State. C with Wilks' showing substantial effect sizes (Pillai's Trace = .987, F = 3829.228, p < .001, partial eta squared = .987). However, the main effects of parents' income and educational background, as well as their interaction, were found to be non-significant. Pillai's Trace for parents' income and educational background, and their interaction all yielded

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values of 0, indicating no significant effect on the academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools student in Niger State.

H₀₆: There is no significant interactive effect of parents' income, educational background and employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools student in Niger State.

Table 6: Multivariate analysis of variance on the effects of parents' income, educational background and employment on high, moderate and low levels academic achievement among secondary schools students

Effect		Value	F	df	Error df	Sig.	Partial Eta S.
Intercept	Pillai's Trace	.987	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Wilks' Lambda	.013	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Hotelling's Trace	74.354	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
	Roy's Largest Root	74.354	3829.228 ^b	2.000	103.000	.000	.987
INCOME	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
QUALIFICATIO N	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Occupation	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Income * Qualification	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Income * Occupation	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Qualification * Occupation	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000
Income * Qualification * Occupation	Pillai's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	.000	.	.
	Wilks' Lambda	1.000	. ^b	.000	103.500	.	.
	Hotelling's Trace	.000	. ^b	.000	2.000	.	.
	Roy's Largest Root	.000	.000 ^b	2.000	102.000	1.000	.000

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A multivariate analysis of variance (MANOVA) was conducted to examine the effects of parents' income, educational background and employment on academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools students in Niger State. The analysis revealed a significant effect for the Intercept, indicating that the model as a whole is statistically significant, with Wilks' showing substantial effect sizes (Pillai's Trace = .987, $F = 3829.228$, $p < .001$, partial eta squared = .987). However, the main effects of parents' income, educational background and employment, and all of their interactions were found to be non-significant. Pillai's Trace for parents' income, educational background and employment, and all interaction terms yielded values of 0, indicating no significant effect on the academic achievement from high, moderate and low levels among secondary schools student.

Discussion of Findings

From the analysis data, the study revealed that, at the 0.05 significance level, there is insufficient evidence to reject the null hypothesis, indicating that the effect of parents' income on academic achievement is not significantly different across high, moderate, and low income levels among secondary school students in Niger State. This is in line with study of Chioma, Bernedeth & Joseph (2017) who asserted that the students response on the effect of parental income on students' academic performance showed that greater academic achievement for a student was attained by those students from financially buoyant families (Mean(Mean \pm SD = 2.97 ± 0.88 , $X^2 = 11.991$, $P = 0.007$). However, 29.7% of the students strongly disagreed. This implies that parents with small income can only take care of a small percentage of a child's education, such as to pay school fees while the child is deprived of basic needs such as text books, school uniforms and sandals, which essence make the students' performance in school very low.

The study also revealed that the analysis indicated there was no statistically significant difference in academic achievement among secondary school students based on their parents' educational qualifications. This study is contrary to Amogne (2015) whose study revealed that parents' educational level has a strong association with academic performance of students. Students from educationally and better off families scored high results in their regional exams than their counterparts.

Furthermore, the analysis revealed that there was no statistically significant difference in academic achievement among secondary school students based on their parents'

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employment levels, this finding is at variance with Chioma, et al. (2017) opined that the study showed that parents' involvement in children schools activities matters most than their financial status in uplifting their children's academic performance in the school. Parental involvement in the education of their children not only improve their academic performance but also enhance other aspect of the lives of students such as motivation, improve behaviour, better communication skills as well as positive attitude toward school.

Also The analysis revealed significant effects for the Intercept, indicating that the model as a whole is statistically significant, with Wilks' showing substantial effect sizes (Pillai's Trace = .987, $F = 3829.228$, $p < .001$, partial eta squared = .987). This finding is in line with Musangu and Ghazali (2017) whose study findings revealed a positive relationship between all the three variables of socio-economic status and academic performance of Secondary School students in the Western Province of the Republic of Zambia. Hence, parents' income carried strong influence on the academic performance of Secondary School students (beta =0.879). The effect of parents' level of education on the academic performance was second (beta =0.758) while occupation had the least influence (beta=0.65).

Furthermore, the analysis of the finding revealed a significant effect for the Intercept, indicating that the model as a whole is statistically significant, with Wilks' showing substantial effect sizes (Pillai's Trace = .987, $F = 3829.228$, $p < .001$, partial eta squared = .987). However, the main effects of parents' income and educational background, as well as their interaction, were found to be non-significant. This finding of this study also contradicted the study by Masangu and Ghazali (2017) and Amogne (2015). The result of the analysis revealed that the socio-economic status of parents (particularly affects their educational level and occupational status) has a strong association with the academic performance of students. Students from educationally and better of this off families scored higher results in their regional examination than their counterparts

Lastly, the study also The analysis revealed a significant effect for the Intercept, indicating that the model as a whole is statistically significant, with Wilks' showing substantial effect sizes (Pillai's Trace = .987, $F = 3829.228$, $p < .001$, partial eta squared = .987). However, the main effects of parents' income, educational background and employment, and all of their interactions were found to be non-significant. This finding also contradicted the study finding by Ovansa (2015 drawn

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from the analysis that parents' socio-economic status influences the academic performance of students. this explained why it was recommended that government should introduce scholarship scheme to assist less privilege students and provide basic social amenities in public schools.

Conclusion

The findings of this current investigation revealed that parents' socio-economic status (finance) have a significant effect on the academic achievement of secondary schools students in Niger State.

Recommendations

It has been established from the study that Parents socio-economic status plays an important role influencing secondary school students' academic achievement. Therefore:

1. Parents should support the educational pursuit of their children both financially, academically, and experience wise etc.
2. Government should ensure that qualify teachers were sent to rural areas to teach in secondary schools.
3. Scholarship assistance can be initiated in secondary schools to assist the good and less privilege students achieve their educational dreams.
4. Parents should spend quality times with student to assist them with school work
5. Parents should ensure that school needs such as recommended text books, uniforms and school fees are provided and paid as at when due.
6. Parents can provide the students with extramural teacher to teach them at home during weeks and vacations

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Assessment of Machine Learning-Based-Predictive-Model on Academic Performance Classification among Computer Science Students in Tai Solarin University of Education Ogun State Nigeria.

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Abstract

Accurately predicting students' academic performance is essential for improved educational outcomes and individualized learning. While helpful, traditional assessment techniques frequently overlook the complex variables affecting performance, such as engagement metrics and socioeconomic background. This study explores the development of a predictive model using an ensemble of machine learning algorithms to classify students' academic performance in higher institutions. By leveraging data collected from Department of Computer Science, Tai Solarin University of Education records, relevant features were selected using the mutual information method. The model was formulated and simulated using two machine learning algorithms such as Naïve Bayes (NB) and Decision Trees (DT) in the Google CoLaboratory environment. The model's predictive accuracy was evaluated based on key performance metrics, including accuracy, precision, and F-measure. This study demonstrates the effectiveness of machine learning techniques in identifying a student's performance early with NB having 100% accuracy, allowing for timely interventions and improved resource allocation. Moreover, it contributes to evidence-based decision-making in educational institutions, helping to optimize learning experiences and boost student retention rates.

Keyword: *Academic performance, Classification, machine learning, Naïve Bayes, Decision Trees*

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Introduction

In educational institutions, understanding and predicting student performance play a crucial role in facilitating personalized learning, early intervention, and academic success (Deda, 2021). Traditionally, educators have relied on various assessment methods, such as exams, quizzes, and assignments, to evaluate student performance. While these methods offer valuable insights into students' understanding and progress, they often provide only a snapshot of their academic abilities and may not capture the complex interplay of factors influencing performance (kumar, 2019)

Machine learning (ML) techniques offer promising avenues for analyzing large volumes of educational data and uncovering patterns that may be difficult to discern through manual analysis alone (Romeo, 2020). By leveraging ML algorithms, researchers and educators can develop predictive models capable of classifying student performance based on various input variables, such as demographic information, previous academic records, and engagement metrics (Albeiki et. al., 2012) These models have the potential to enhance educational outcomes by identifying at-risk students (karalar, 2021) tailoring instructional interventions, and optimizing resource allocation (Ramaswami et al. 2019).

Machine learning approaches offer several advantages over predictive models based on a single machine learning algorithm (karalar, 2021) By combining multiple models, machine learning techniques can leverage the strengths of individual models while mitigating their weaknesses, thereby improving predictive accuracy and robustness (Hussain, 2023). Moreover, machine learning methods can handle diverse types of data and modelling techniques, enabling a more comprehensive analysis of factors influencing prediction. Ensemble modelling is widely used in various machine learning tasks, including classification, regression, and clustering. It has been shown to improve predictive performance, reduce variance, and increase model robustness compared to single-model approaches. However, ensemble modelling requires careful tuning of hyperparameters, selection of diverse base models, and consideration of computational resources to achieve optimal results. ires careful

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tuning of hyperparameters, selection of diverse base models, and consideration of computational resources to achieve optimal results.

Institutions of higher learning are currently facing the challenging task of attracting new students who can effectively meet their diverse academic demands. With these demands come the need for those institutions to develop strategies that can enhance students' learning experiences at various educational levels. Predicting the academic success at an early stage would allow academic institutions to develop specific enrolment guidelines while avoiding poor performance. Traditional methods of assessing student performance, such as standardized tests and course grades, have several limitations. These methods often rely on summative assessments that provide retrospective insights into students' abilities but offer limited predictive power regarding future performance. Moreover, traditional assessments may not capture the full spectrum of students' skills, knowledge, and competencies, leading to incomplete or biased evaluations. Furthermore, traditional methods may overlook non-academic factors that influence student performance, such as socio-economic background, motivation, learning style, and mental health. Failing to account for these factors can result in inaccurate predictions and missed opportunities for intervention. Additionally, traditional assessments are often labour-intensive, time-consuming, and subject to human biases, making them less scalable and efficient for large-scale predictive modelling tasks.

This research addresses this gap by developing a predictive model using an ensemble of machine learning algorithms which can be used to classify the academic performance of students in higher institutions based on information about features associated with influencing academic performance.

Predicting student performance holds significant implications for both students and educational institutions. For students, early identification of academic challenges can lead to timely support interventions, personalized learning experiences, and improved outcomes. By identifying struggling students early on, educators can provide targeted interventions, such as tutoring, counseling, or additional resources, to address academic difficulties and prevent dropout.

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Review of Related Literature

Hussain and Khan (2023), worked on the development of a student performance estimator using machine learning algorithms. The dataset considered in the study consisted of 90,000 secondary school student records consisting of information about features however all confidential information were removed from the dataset. The study adopted the use of generative algorithm for the selection of relevant features which are most important in the determination of students' performance. The study adopted the use of kNN and decision trees algorithm for the development of the predictive model required for estimating students' academic performance. The results showed that the use of feature selection of relevant features improved the performance of machine learning algorithms. Decision trees algorithm showed better performance by achieving an accuracy of 96.64%. The study was limited to the use of dataset collected from secondary school students.

Baashar, *et al.*, (2022) worked on the assessment of the application of AI models for the assessment of the academic performance of postgraduate students in Malaysia. The study identified the various features that are associated with the prediction of students' academic performance such as: demographic information, program name, program structure, sponsorship, attendance and final CGPA. The model simulation involved the use of the holdout method based on the use of 90% for training and 10% for testing which was fed to artificial neural network (ANN), support vector machines (SVM), decision trees (DT), and Gaussian process regression. The results revealed that the best performance was achieved using ANN with an R^2 value of 0.89 and mean squared error (MSE) of 0.080. The study was limited to a regression task as it was focused on estimating the value of the students' CGPA and data collected from postgraduate students.

Yağcı (2022), worked on the application of machine learning algorithms to the prediction of the academic performance of Turkish students. The study collected data about students taking a course in a Turkish university consisting of mid-term exam grades, department data and faculty data were used for predicting

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the final grade of the course. The study fed the dataset to a number of machine learning algorithms, namely: kNN, SVM, logistic regression (LR), random forest (RF) and naïve Bayes (NB). The results of the study revealed that the best performance was achieved using random forest with an accuracy of 74.6%. The study concluded that the ensemble model performed better than other machine learning algorithms. The study was limited to the prediction of the performance of student taking a particular course based on the comparative analysis of machine learning algorithms.

Owosu-Boadu, Nti, Nyarko-Boateng, Aning, & Boafo (2021) worked on the assessment of the academic performance of students in Ghana using machine learning algorithms. The study collected data from third year students of three secondary schools located in Ghana based on a number of identified features. The features included demographic features such as gender, nationalit, place of birth, level, class group, topic, term, relation to guardian, class participation, library visits, involvement in group discussions, parent survey responses, parent satisfaction and student absence days. The model was formulated using kNN, DT, ANN, RF, SVM, LR and AdaBoost. The results revealed that random forest (RF) showed the best performance among all the selected algorithms with an accuracy of 82%. The results concluded that ensemble models performed better than machine learning algorithms. The study was limited to data collected from secondary schools.

Methodology

Relevant data containing information about the features that are associated with the assessment of the academic performance of students was collected from the departmental records. Table 1 provides a description of the features that were considered for the classification of academic performance. The features in the dataset collected were subjected to feature selection using the mutual information method. The ensemble model for the classification of academic performance was formulated using a number of machine learning algorithms based on information about the features. Predictive models were simulated by using the holdout method based on 5 simulation runs for each machine learning

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algorithm such that the training dataset was used to build the model using the Google CoLaboratory; a Python jupyter notebook for Gmail users. The models were evaluated using on a number of performance metrics, namely: accuracy, true positive (TP) rate, false positive (FP) rate, precision and f-measure based on the test dataset.

Table 1: Identification of features associated with academic performance

CLASS OF VARIABLE	NAME	LABEL VALUES
SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC INFORMATION	Gender	Categorical (Male, Female)
	Age at Admission	Numeric – Integer type
	State of Origin	Categorical
UTME RESULTS	English	Numeric – Integer Type
	Mathematics	Numeric – Integer Type
	Chemistry	Numeric – Integer Type
	Physics	Numeric – Integer Type
	English	Numeric – Integer type
	Mathematics	Numeric – Integer type
	Chemistry	Numeric – Integer type
O'LEVEL RESULTS (SSCE)	Physics	Numeric – Integer type
	Biology	Numeric – Integer type
	Agricultural Science	Numeric – Integer type
	Geography	Numeric – Integer type
	Economics	Numeric – Integer type
	Further Mathematics	Numeric – Integer type
	Technical Drawing	Numeric – Integer type
100 LEVEL RESULTS	First Semester CGPA	Numeric – Float type
	Second Semester CGPA	Numeric – Float type

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TARGET CLASS	Graduating Class of Degree	Categorical (First Class, Second Class Lower, Third Class Lower)
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Presentation of Results

The results of the exploration of the numerical and categorical features within the dataset was presented using appropriate tools such as tables, bar charts and box plots. Afterwards, the results of the transformation of the categorical string-type valued features into numeric types was presented alongside the assessment of the feature importance of the features. Finally, the results of the simulation and evaluation of the comparative analysis of the adoption of the machine learning and machine learning models was determined based on a number of performance evaluation metrics.

Figure 1: Screenshot of visualization of contents of the collected dataset.

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Figure 1 shows a screenshot of the description of the datasets showing the values of the features that were identified in the dataset collected for the purpose of this study. According to the figure, it was shown that majority of the features were stored using numeric values while the features: gender and state were stored as categorical string type values

Figure.2: Visualization of heatmap of feature-feature intercorrelation.

Figure 2 displays the value of the correlation of the features with respect to one another such that darker colours reflect higher correlation while light colours reflect lower correlations. Also, red colours signified negative correlation and blue colour signified positive correlation. However, since the focus of the study is on the association between the features and the classification of academic performance among students, the values displayed in the last row which was called *cgpa_final* was considered. The values in the cell of the last row shows the correlation of the features with respect to the classification of the academic performance of students. On the other hand, figure 6 shows the graphical plot of feature importance in decreasing order based on the mutual information

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metric. As shown in figure 6, the mutual information revealed the amount of information about the classification of academic performance among students that can be explained by each feature identified in the dataset based on the information collected about them in the dataset. Table 2 gives a summary of the ranking of features based on the value of their Pearson's correlation and mutual information.

Table 2: Identification of Feature Importance

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S/N	PEARSON'S CORRELATION		MUTUAL INFORMATION	
	Feature Name	Value	Feature Name	Value
1	CGPA 100 Level First	0.8000	CGPA 100 Level First	0.459060
2	CGPA 100 Level Second	0.7800	CGPA 100 Level Second	0.404737
3	UTME-English	-0.3900	UTME-English	0.193618
4	UTME-Chemistry	-0.3300	SSCE-Physics	0.147297
5	UTME-Mathematics	-0.2700	UTME-Chemistry	0.134541
6	UTME-Physics	-0.2500	UTME-Physics	0.068669
7	SSCE-Further Maths	-0.2400	SSCE-Further Maths	0.041710
8	SSCE-Biology	0.2000	SSCE-Mathematics	0.021190
9	SSCE-Economics	0.1700	SSCE-Agric	0.00000
10	SSCE-Physics	0.1500	SSCE-Tech Drawing	0.00000
11	Age at Admission	0.1400	SSCE-Economics	0.00000
12	SSCE-Mathematics	0.1400	SSCE-Geography	0.00000
13	Gender	-0.1400	Age at Admission	0.00000
14	SSCE-Tech Drawing	-0.1400	SSCE-Biology	0.00000
15	SSCE-Chemistry	-0.0940	Gender	0.00000
16	SSCE-Agric	0.0870	SSCE-English	0.00000
17	State	-0.0670	UTME-Mathematics	0.00000
18	SSCE-Geography	-0.0250	State	0.00000
19	SSCE-English	0.0092	SSCE-Chemistry	0.00000

According to the Pearson's correlation coefficient, it was revealed that the two most important features were *CGPA 100 Level First* and *CGPA 100 Level Second* both with positive correlation, followed by *UTME-English*, *UTME-Chemistry*, *UTME-Mathematics*, *UTME-Physics*, and *SSCE-Further Maths* all with negative correlation, followed by *SSCE-Biology*, *SSCE-Economics*, *SSCE-Physics*, *Age at Admission*, and *SSCE-Mathematics* with positive correlation. Features with the least correlation include: *Gender*, *SSCE-Tech Drawing*, and *SSCE-Chemistry* with negative correlation followed by *SSCE-Agric* with positive correlation followed by *State*, and *SSCE-Geography* with negative correlation and the least correlation was found in *SSCE-English* with positive correlation.

Discussion of findings

This section presents the results of the evaluation of the predictive models that were generated across the five simulations based on the machine learning and ensemble modeling techniques that were adopted in this study. The results are

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presented for each simulation following which the results of the performance of the algorithms were presented.

Results of the Simulation of Predictive Model

This section presents the results of the application of the three machine learning algorithms, namely: naïve Bayes (NB), support vector machines (SVC) and decision trees (DT) classifiers. The model simulation was conducted by splitting the dataset into two parts, train and test dataset using five simulations such that 50/50, 60/40, 70/30, 80/20 and 90/10 percent of the dataset was adopted for training/testing the predictive model. Table 4.2 shows the number of records that were adopted for each simulation that were considered in this study. As stated earlier, the train datasets were used to build the predictive model while the test data were used to evaluate the performance of the predictive models based on a number of performance evaluation metrics.

Table 3. Description of the number of records adopted for training and testing predictive models across five simulations

SIMULATION#	TRAIN DATA					TEST DATA				
	2.1	2.2	First	Third	Total	2.1	2.2	First	Third	Total
SIMULATION 1 (50/50)	28	19	3	11	61	15	12	9	14	50
SIMULATION 2 (60/40)	32	21	4	14	71	11	7	11	11	40
SIMULATION 3 (70/30)	37	26	2	16	81	6	8	9	7	30
SIMULATION 4 (80/20)	42	31	3	15	91	5	6	4	5	20
SIMULATION 5 (90/10)	49	38	4	20	101	1	4	2	3	10

Figure 3 shows the confusion matrices that were used to interpret the results of the evaluation of the three machine learning models adopted in simulation 1 based on the test dataset. Using NB classifier, it was observed that all 15 actual second-class lower records were correctly classified, all 12 actual second-class

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lower records were correctly classified, all 9 actual first-class records were correctly classified and all 14 actual third-class records were correctly classified owing to an accuracy of 100.0%.

Figure 3: Confusion matrices for the evaluation of naïve Bayes (left), and decision trees (right) for simulation 1.

Figure 4 shows the confusion matrices that were used to interpret the results of the evaluation of both machine learning models adopted in simulation 2 based on the test dataset. Using NB classifier, it was observed that all 11 actual second-class lower records were correctly classified, all 7 actual second-class lower records were correctly classified, all 11 actual first-class records were correctly classified and all 11 actual third-class records were correctly classified owing to an accuracy of 100.0%.

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Figure 4: Confusion matrices for the evaluation of naïve Bayes (left), and decision trees (right) for simulation 2.

Figure 5 shows the confusion matrices that were used to interpret the results of the evaluation of both machine learning models adopted in simulation 3 based on the test dataset. Using NB classifier, it was observed that all 6 actual second-class lower records were correctly classified, all 8 actual second-class lower records were correctly classified, all 9 actual first-class records were correctly classified and all 7 actual third-class records were correctly classified owing to an accuracy of 100.0%.

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Figure 5: Confusion matrices for the evaluation of naïve Bayes (left) and decision trees (right) for simulation 3.

Figure 6 shows the confusion matrices that were used to interpret the results of the evaluation of both machine learning models adopted in simulation 4 based on the test dataset. Using NB classifier, it was observed that all 5 actual second-class lower records were correctly classified, all 6 actual second-class lower records were correctly classified, all 4 actual first-class records were correctly classified and all 5 actual third-class records were correctly classified owing to an accuracy of 100.0%.

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Figure 6: Confusion matrices for the evaluation of naïve Bayes (left) and decision trees (right) for simulation 4.

Figure 7 shows the confusion matrices that were used to interpret the results of the evaluation of both machine learning models adopted in simulation 2 based on the test dataset. Using NB classifier, it was observed that all 1 actual second-class lower records were correctly classified, all 4 actual second-class lower records were correctly classified, all 2 actual first-class records were correctly classified and all 3 actual third-class records were correctly classified owing to an accuracy of 100.0%.

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Figure 7: Confusion matrices for the evaluation of naïve Bayes (left) and decision trees (right) for simulation 5.

Table 4: Results of the evaluation of the predictive models across five simulations based on performance metrics.

Simulation#	Algorithm	Correct Records	Accuracy (%)	Precision				Recall				F1-Score			
				2.1	2.2	First	Third	2.1	2.2	First	Third	2.1	2.2	First	Third
Simulation 1	NB	50	100.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	SVC	50	100.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	DT	44	88.0	0.80	0.91	0.89	0.93	0.80	0.83	0.89	1.00	0.80	0.87	0.89	0.97
	NB	40	100.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00

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Simulation 2	SVC	40	100.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	DT	32	80.0	0.70	0.64	1.00	0.91	0.64	1.00	0.73	0.91	0.67	0.78	0.84	0.91
Simulation 3	NB	30	100.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	SVC	30	100.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	DT	25	80.0	0.75	0.78	1.00	0.78	0.50	0.88	0.89	1.00	0.60	0.82	0.94	0.88
Simulation 4	NB	20	100.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	SVC	20	100.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	DT	18	90.0	0.80	0.83	1.00	1.00	0.80	0.83	1.00	1.00	0.80	0.83	1.00	1.00
Simulation 5	NB	10	100.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	SVC	10	100.0	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
	DT	9	90.0	0.50	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	0.75	1.00	1.00	0.67	0.86	1.00	1.00

Conclusion

The study examined the performance of three machine learning algorithms: Naïve Bayes, Support Vector Machine and Decision Tree, in classification and predicting the performance of students the datasets were obtained from the Department of Computer Science Tai Solarin University of Education. The model simulation was conducted by splitting the dataset into two parts, train and test dataset using five simulations such that 50/50, 60/40, 70/30, 80/20 and 90/10 percent of the dataset was adopted for training/testing the predictive model. The study concluded that machine learning models are very effective in the classification of the academic performance of students, especially the naïve Bayes and Support Vector classifiers that outperformed the Decision Tree with 100% accuracy respectively.

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Impact of Technology-Enhanced-Tools on Access to Quality Education among Internally Displaced Post-Primary Education Children in Benue State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of technology-enhanced-tools on access to quality education among internally displaced post-primary education children in Benue State, Nigeria. The study population comprises 68,076 school-age children during the 2024/2025 academic session from six Local Government Areas in Benue State, Nigeria, with a sample of 384 participants selected through multistage sampling. Data were collected using a validated structured questionnaire, Technology-Enhanced-Tools on Access to Quality Education among Internally Displaced Children Questionnaire (TETAQEIDCQ), which achieved a reliability coefficient of 0.89. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used for analysis. Findings reveal that technology-enhanced tools significantly improve access to quality education and positively influence learning outcomes among internally displaced post-primary education children in Benue State, Nigeria. The study highlights the importance of integrating technology to bridge educational gaps for displaced learners. Recommendations include enhancing digital infrastructure, providing teacher training, and implementing policies that support equitable access to educational technology for IDP children.

Keywords: Assessment, Education, Impact, Internally Displaced Persons & Technology

Introduction

At the end of 2019, it is estimated that 45.7 million people were internally displaced by conflict and violence. Close to 20 million of the people internally displaced by conflict and violence are children (IDMC, 2020). A United Nations Educational and Scientific Organization (UNESCO, 2023) report also indicates that Nigeria is still home to about 20 million out-of-school children, with persons with disabilities occupying a sizeable

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percentage. United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF, 2015) reported that 800,000 children in Nigeria are affected by the Boko Haram insurgency, with 19 out of 42 camps lacking educational access as of June 2015 (Global Educational Monitoring Report [GEMR], 2016). The UN Secretary-General Ban Ki-moon, in the 2015 General Assembly, revealed that over 60 million people globally are displaced, impacting children who lose educational opportunities, some coerced into becoming child soldiers (National Emergency Management Agency [NEMA], 2015). The National Emergency Management Agency (NEMA) reported in 2015 that 2.5 million people, with 1.2 million school-age children, were displaced in northern Nigeria due to Boko Haram attacks, with 56% being children under 18 and over half under 5 years old (NEMA, 2015).

The global phenomenon of internal displacement has led to a significant number of children facing disruptions in their education, stemming from forced relocations and the resultant instability. Among these affected populations, Internally Displaced Persons (IDP) children are particularly vulnerable, often experiencing limited access to educational resources and facing challenges in maintaining a consistent learning environment. The vast majority of children internally displaced are denied a secure, inclusive, and quality education, along with the numerous short- and long-term benefits it provides. Obviously, barriers such as a lack of good teaching capacity, limited funding, ongoing insecurity, social tensions and discrimination compound with education systems in low-income and fragile contexts which are already overstretched (Internal Displacement Monitoring Centre [IDMC], 2020).

Consequently, the integration of technology into education has emerged as a potential catalyst for addressing these issues. With the growing interest in the adoption of technology in Nigeria's education sector, the use of technology for teaching and learning has proven to be an enabler of equitable education for persons with disabilities, learners from disadvantaged backgrounds, learners living in rural locations, and women and girls of marginalized groups (Thisdaylive, 2023).

In recent years, various technological interventions, such as online learning platforms, mobile applications, and digital educational resources, have been implemented to enhance educational access for marginalized populations, including IDP children. UNHCR (2016) in their study on the technology as an enabler for equity and inclusion in education sees technology as a veritable tool to drive inclusion in education among refugees. These tools offer the prospect of delivering quality educational content

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regardless of geographical constraints, potentially bridging the gap created by displacement.

However, the impact of technology on educational outcomes for IDP children is a complex interplay of opportunities and challenges. On the positive side, technology can provide flexible learning environments, personalized instruction, and opportunities for remote collaboration. Yet, challenges such as limited infrastructure, digital literacy gaps, and the potential exacerbation of existing inequalities need to be critically examined.

Ultimately, this study provides a crucial examination of how technology impacts the accessibility and quality of post-primary education for internally displaced children (IDP) in Benue State. By comparing our findings with existing literature, several key insights and gaps become evident. Uzodinma, Njoku, and Ejiofor (2024) explore the broader role of technology in enhancing educational outcomes across various levels in Nigeria, highlighting its potential to improve learning experiences. Their findings underscore the importance of integrating technology into educational settings but do not specifically focus on the unique challenges faced by IDP children in post-primary education.

Similarly, Omale, Abduljabbar, and Dauda (2022) address the urgent need to bridge educational gaps for IDP children through targeted interventions during emergencies. Their work emphasizes the necessity of tailored strategies to support displaced students but does not delve deeply into the specific technological solutions that could address these gaps. Ambe-Uva (2012) also discusses the potential of open and distance learning as a means to uphold the right to education for displaced populations in Nigeria. This perspective is valuable but primarily focuses on higher-level educational solutions rather than the practical, on-the-ground impact of technology in post-primary education settings for IDP children.

The gap identified by this study is the need for a focused examination of how technology specifically impacts the educational experiences and outcomes of IDP children in post-primary education in Benue State. While existing studies provide a general understanding of technology's role and the challenges faced by displaced populations, they do not offer a detailed assessment of how technological interventions can be tailored to the unique needs of IDP children in this specific educational context. This

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research aims to bridge this gap by providing a nuanced analysis of technological impacts and offering actionable insights to develop more effective strategies for leveraging technology to enhance access to quality education for IDP children in Benue State.

Statement of the Problem

This study addresses the pressing issue of internal displacement, with a specific focus on the vulnerable demographic of IDP children in Nigeria, particularly in Benue State. The unique challenges faced by IDP children include limited access to educational resources and difficulties in maintaining a consistent learning environment due to forced relocations and the resultant instability. The majority of these displaced children are denied a secure, inclusive, and quality education, exacerbating the short- and long-term consequences of their displacement (IDMC, 2020). Existing barriers, such as a lack of teaching capacity, limited funding, ongoing insecurity, social tensions, and discrimination, further compound the challenges faced by education systems in low-income and fragile contexts (IDMC, 2020). Recognizing the potential of technology to address these issues, the study acknowledges the growing interest in adopting technology in Nigeria's education sector. Technological interventions, such as online learning platforms, mobile applications, and digital educational resources, have shown promise in enhancing educational access for marginalized populations, including IDP children. The study aligns with the perspective presented by (United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees [UNHCR], 2023), which views technology as a valuable tool for driving inclusion in education among refugees, transcending geographical constraints and bridging gaps created by displacement. Despite numerous studies on IDPs, none have explored the impact of technology on the educational outcomes of IDP children. Additionally, there is a lack of standardized structures, well-articulated plans, and procedures in Nigeria to address digital educational needs in emergencies. Given the contemporary and ongoing nature of this issue, a research gap has emerged, prompting this study to fill the void.

Purpose of the Study

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The aim of this research is to scrutinize the technology-enhanced-tools on access to quality education among internally displaced post-primary education children in Benue State, Nigeria. The specific objectives guiding the study are to:

- a) Assess the impact of technology-enhanced-tools on access to quality education among Internally Displaced post-basic children in Benue State.
- b) Examine the impact of technology-enhanced-tools compared to traditional method on access to quality education among Internally Displaced post-basic children in Benue State.

Research Questions

The following research questions will be set out to guide the study:

- 1) What is the impact of technology-enhanced-tools on access to quality education among Internally Displaced post-basic children in Benue State?
- 2) What is the impact of technology-enhanced-tools compared to traditional method on access to quality education among Internally Displaced post-basic children in Benue State?

Methodology

The research design for this study adopted a descriptive survey design to systematically collect and analyze data on the experiences of internally displaced children (IDCs) in post-primary schools across Benue State.

This design was appropriate for assessing the impact of technology on access to quality education without manipulating variables (Nworgu, 2015). The study was conducted in Benue State, focusing on three major IDP camps: Abagena (Makurdi), Gbajimba (Guma), and Anyiin (Logo).

These areas were selected due to their high concentration of displaced persons and evident challenges in accessing quality education. The population consisted of 68,076 school-age IDCs (35,460 males and 32,616 females) across six Local Government Areas (LGAs) in Benue State, based on data from the Displacement Tracking Matrix (DTM) Round 11 (March 2023) and the Biometric Registration Progress Report (July 2024). A sample of 384 school-age IDCs was selected using a multistage sampling technique.

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First, proportional stratified sampling determined the sample from each camp: Makurdi (124), Guma (146), and Logo (113). Within each camp, stratification by gender was applied based on a 52:48 male-to-female ratio. Finally, simple random sampling was employed within each gender stratum to ensure equal selection chances.

A structured questionnaire titled *Impact of Technology-Enhanced-Tools on Access to Quality Education among Internally Displaced Children Questionnaire (TETAQEIDCQ)*, adapted from Balogun (2005), was used. The instrument consisted of two sections: Section A (demographics) and Section B (25 items grouped into five thematic clusters). Responses were rated using a four-point Likert scale ranging from Strongly Agree (4) to Strongly Disagree (1).

Experts in measurement and evaluation validated the instrument for clarity and relevance. Following validation, a pilot test with 20 participants was conducted outside the study area. Cronbach's Alpha yielded reliability coefficients ranging from 0.70 to 0.79 across clusters, with an overall reliability coefficient of 0.89. Data were collected using a direct delivery-and-retrieval method by the researcher and three trained assistants. Clear instructions were provided, and responses were retrieved immediately to minimize non-response and ensure data integrity. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were used to analyze the research questions, with a mean score of 2.50 or higher indicating a high extent of agreement.

Presentation of Results

This provides concise summary of the data analysis conducted following the administration of the research instrument. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were employed to analyze respondents' responses. These measures facilitated informed decision-making regarding the outcomes of the study.

Descriptive Analysis

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Table 1: The demographic description of respondents:

Age	Frequency	Percent
11-13	54	14.1
14-16	186	48.4
17-19	144	37.5
Total	384	100.0
Gender		
Male	196	51.0
Female	188	49.0
Total	384	100.0
Class Level		
JSS1-3	250	65.1
SS1-3	134	34.9
Total	384	100.0
Duration in the IDP camp		
Less than one year	27	7.0
1-2 years	330	85.9
More than 2 years	27	7.0
Total	384	100.0

Source: Field survey data (2024)

Table 1 provides a demographic overview of a sample population (N = 384) with variables categorized by age, gender, class level, and duration of stay in an IDP camp in Benue State.

Age Distribution

The age range of 14-16 years comprises the majority (48.4%) of the population, followed by 17-19 years (37.5%), while 11-13 years accounts for the smallest proportion (14.1%). This suggests that the population is predominantly adolescents in middle-to-late teenage years, likely indicative of the targeted group for the study.

Gender Distribution

The gender ratio is nearly balanced, with males constituting 51.0% and females 49.0%. The near parity ensures gender representation in the study, allowing for potentially unbiased gender-specific analysis.

Class Level Distribution

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A significant portion of the participants (65.1%) are in Junior Secondary School (JSS 1-3), while 34.9% are in Senior Secondary School (SS 1-3). This distribution highlights the dominance of younger secondary school students, which might influence the type of interventions or programs implemented.

Years spent in the IDP Camp

Most participants (85.9%) have stayed in the camp for 1-2 years, with only 7.0% each having stayed less than a year or more than two years. This indicates a relatively recent displacement, as the majority have spent a moderate duration in the camp. It reflects the likely ongoing impact of displacement on education and other life domains.

Research Question 1: What is the impact of technology-enhanced-tools on access to quality education among Internally Displaced post-basic children in Benue State?

To answer this research question, the responses of the students were subjected to descriptive analysis and the results were presented in table 2.

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Technology's Role in Increasing Access to Education for IDP Children in Benue State

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=383	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	Technology has improved my access to educational materials.		2.77	0.57	Agreed
2.	The use of online learning platforms has made it easier for me to attend classes.		2.88	0.66	Agreed
3.	I find it easier to continue my education despite being displaced due to access to technology.		3.00	0.78	Agreed
4.	Technology has facilitated my connection with teachers beyond the classroom, though access remains significantly limited		3.20	0.67	Agreed
5.	My access to educational resources has increased due to digital tools like computers or tablets.		2.93	0.90	Agreed
	Grand Mean		2.96	0.72	Below Average

Source: Field survey data (2024)

Decision $\bar{X} \geq 2.5$ Above Average

Table 2 illustrates the role of technology in increasing access to education for IDP children in Benue State. All item statements have mean scores above the established cut-off mean of 2.50, indicating agreement across all categories. With a grand mean of

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2.96 and a standard deviation of 0.72, the findings suggest that technology has played a significant role in enhancing access to education for IDP children in Benue State.

Research Question 2: What is the impact of technology-enhanced-tools compared to traditional method on access to quality education among Internally Displaced post-basic children in Benue State?

To answer this research question, the responses of the students were subjected to descriptive analysis and the results were presented in table 3.

Table 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Technology Impact on the Quality of Education Received by IDP Children in Benue State Compared to Traditional Methods

S/N	ITEM STATEMENT	N=383	MEAN	SD	REMARK
1.	The use of technology has improved the quality of education I receive compared to traditional classroom methods.		2.98	0.89	Agreed
2.	Learning with digital tools (e.g., computers, tablets) provides a better understanding of the topics taught compared to traditional textbooks.		3.23	0.56	Agreed
3.	Technology has made learning more interactive and engaging compared to conventional classroom activities.		3.23	0.74	Agreed
4.	The quality of feedback I receive from teachers is better when using technology compared to traditional methods.		3.00	0.81	Agreed
5.	Online resources have provided me with access to more varied and up-to-date content compared to traditional methods.		2.72	0.87	Agreed
	Grand Mean		3.03	0.77	Below Average

Source: Field survey data (2024)

Decision $\bar{X} \geq 2.5$ Above Average

Table 3 illustrates the extent to which technology has impacted the quality of education received by IDP children in Benue State compared to traditional methods. All item statements recorded mean scores above the established cut-off mean of 2.50, indicating agreement across all categories. With a grand mean of 3.03 and a standard deviation of 0.77, the findings suggest that technology has positively influenced the quality of education for IDP children.

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Discussion of Findings

The result of research question one revealed that technology has played a significant role in enhancing access to education for IDP children in Benue State. The rise in remote learning opportunities for IDP children in Benue State could be attributed to the growing availability of digital tools and online platforms. The outcome of the study was found to be similar with that of Oyelere, Suhonen, and Shonola (2016) which emphasized the role of technology in facilitating distance learning by providing students in remote areas with access to quality education through online courses and virtual classrooms. The result also concurred with that of Alimi, Babalola, Aladesusi, Issa, and Omolafe (2022), which opined that assistive technology is a vital tool in making learning accessible and meaningful for children with disabilities in Nigeria. The finding further agreed with that of Ripat and Woodgate (2017), which reported that assistive technology plays a significant role in overcoming academic challenges and enhancing the performance of children with disabilities. The implication of this finding is that the use of digital tools and assistive technologies can bridge educational gaps for IDP children in Benue State, providing them with better access to quality learning opportunities.

The finding of research question two showed that technology has positively influenced the quality of education for IDP children. The positive influence of technology on the quality of education for IDP children could be attributed to the increasing integration of digital resources in educational delivery. The findings of the study align with Baytak, Tarman, and Ayas (2011), who emphasized that the integration of technology into classrooms creates a more enjoyable, interactive, and meaningful learning environment for students. Similarly, the result resonates with Bulut and Delen (2011), who highlighted that information and communication technology positively impacts students' achievements in mathematics and science. Additionally, the finding corresponds with Herron (2010), who demonstrated that technology-based math lessons foster student engagement and retention through hands-on activities. Finally, it concurs with Courduff (2011), who reported that incorporating technology in special education supports students in achieving individual educational goals and enhances academic outcomes.

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Conclusion

In conclusion, this study highlights the significant role of technology in enhancing access to education for internally displaced persons (IDP) children in Benue State. The findings demonstrate that digital tools and platforms have expanded educational opportunities, making learning more accessible for displaced children. Additionally, technology has positively influenced the quality of education, offering improved instructional resources and fostering better learning outcomes. These results underscore the potential of technology to bridge educational gaps for IDP children, contributing to a more equitable and effective learning environment.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the researcher recommends that:

1. Government and NGOs should prioritize initiatives that enhance access to education through mobile learning apps, offline educational content, and community-based technology hubs tailored to the needs of IDP children.
2. Educational policymakers should implement hybrid models that combine technology and traditional teaching, ensuring that technological tools complement rather than replace face-to-face interaction for enhanced learning outcomes.

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EFFECT OF POSITIVE REINFORCEMENT COUNSELLING TECHNIQUE ON AGGRESSION AMONG POST-BASIC STUDENTS IN KANO METROPOLIS, KANO STATE

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of positive reinforcement counselling technique on aggression among post-basic students in Kano Metropolis. The study employed a quasi-experimental research design specifically, pretest post-test non randomized control group design. Two objectives guided the study while two null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance. The population of the study consists of seventy six (76) students with aggression while the sample of thirty (30) were purposely drawn from two public secondary schools in kano metropolis, kano state. Data collection instrument titled 'Aggression Behaviour Scale' was employed for the study. The instrument was validated and attained content validation while reliability was obtained using split half method yielding reliability coefficient of 0.65. The data collected was analyzed using paired sample t-test. The finding reveals that positive reinforcement technique has significant effect on physical and in this study is effective counselling tool for addressing the physical and verbal dimensions of aggression among post-basic students. Based on the findings, counsellors are recommended to utilise positive reinforcement counselling technique on students found with symptoms of aggression.

Keywords: Aggression, Positive Reinforcement, Post-Basic

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Introduction

Aggression is a worrisome phenomenon as many schools seem to have a significant number of students with aggression especially among secondary students. The stress that students face, can make them aggressive and when they get aggressive, they won't be able to concentrate, also students lose the ability to concentrate on their lessons or classes as they will always concentrate on what is annoying them causing social withdrawal and isolation. Aggression is an action or conduct that is intended to cause harm, either physically, verbally, relational or instrumentally, to self or other person. Aggression may also be seen as any action with the intent to harm others resulting to injury or pain, the behaviour can manifest in different ways which includes physical, verbal, relational, and instrumental. The physical aggression are behaviours that causes physical harm to others characterized by hitting, biting, kicking, and also use of objects or weapons. Verbal aggression may be seen as communication verbally that can harm people through the use of words, tone and manner, it is characterized by insult, persistent criticism, threats, and name calling. Thus, aggression negatively affects the academic performance of the students, failure due to poor performance, peer rejection to the students who exhibit the symptoms of the behaviour, therefore contributing to lower grades. Additionally, victimized students of such behavior may experience anxiety, social isolation and withdrawal.

Aggression behaviour involves conflict between individuals of equal level". Whenever the term aggressive is used to describe a student's behavior, images of physical injury to another automatically come to mind. Aggressive behavior doesn't just violate social boundaries. It can also affect relationships and even have professional or legal consequences. Recognizing the ways aggression shows up in your life can help you take steps toward addressing it, along with anger and any other emotions that might play a part (Naoreen et al.2018). Aggression has been reported by Van (2017) to be a prevailing anti-social act affecting individuals on a daily basis. It is a negative stimulus to another person as it pertains to the intention of harming that person (with the expectation that the aversive stimulus will reach its destination). School violence and aggressive tendencies have become a social problem especially among secondary school students in the contemporary world.

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According to Kjærviik, and Bushman (2021) aggressive behaviour is an intentional act to cause harm to another person. This could be expressed more overtly, such as physically hitting someone, in verbal or relational contexts, and also as violence, bullying, and more like covert action, such as lying and stealing. Therefore, designing effective, reliable and empirically based classroom interventions is important to improve the academic performance and social development of students who manifest aggression characteristics. In this regard, counselling intervention may be one of the ways to assist such students, specifically using positive reinforcement and the role-play counselling technique in this study.

However, positive reinforcement is a counselling technique that encourages desired behaviours by providing reward following a behaviour. It also focuses on encouraging students by offering incentives to spur them on when they do well academically or demonstrate positive behavior which may also be in form of comment, clapping, hug, and a smile. In the context of post-basic school, positive reinforcement involves acknowledging and rewarding instances of positive behaviour, such as cooperation, empathy, sharing, and conflict resolution. For example, a teacher poses question to the students and receives a correct answer from them, it should be followed with a clap to strengthen further responses.

Meanwhile, most school administrators and teachers applied variety of disciplinary measures to tackle the problem of aggression among students in school. Nakpodia (2010) reported that such conventional approach measures include, kneeling down, head knocks, ear pulling, slapping, manual work, sweeping and tidying the school environment, sending out of class, writing impositions, flogging, suspension, expulsion and reporting to the police among others.

Statement of the Problem

Aggression is a disturbing issue that could place students, the school and even parents at risk. In kano metropolis, aggression among students especially at the post-basic stage is increasingly spreading due to their exposure to crime activities exhibited in the environment in which they found themselves. Therefore, the aggressors causing harm to themselves, and their peers and victims of such behaviour develop fear of going to school, feeling uncomfortable within the school environment and lack full

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concentration to the learning process. Consequently, aggression disrupts the enabling learning environment needed for optimal and meaningful activities for both the aggressor and the victim. Thus, the victims are stressed, saddled with school phobia, low self-concepts, full of anxiety and dejection, diminished interest in school activities among others, while the aggressor on his part develops inferiority complex and a sense of irrelevance.

Experience of the researcher has shown that students with symptoms of aggression in classroom are found with behaviours of bullying their colleagues, name calling, hitting others and smashing doors. Therefore, the negative consequence of these behaviours may distract the peaceful atmosphere of the classroom thereby making teaching and learning so difficult to accomplish. Hence, may invariably, lead to poor academic performance/achievement and poor social relationship. Additionally, students might exhibit different forms of aggression which include physical and verbal. Physical aggression is an act that is done with the intention to harm or cause pain to others physically and characterized by symptoms of hitting, punching, kicking and slapping. Verbal aggression is a behaviour that is exhibited verbally through the use of tone, abuse or harsh words which might cause harm. Hence, students who exhibit verbal aggression are found with the symptoms of calling names, bullying and teasing.

Consequently, parents and teachers are concerned with why such students behave aggressively, they resort to measures such as beating, kneeling down, and suspension from school, sending out of classroom, seeping school compound and the likes. Thus, despite all measures taken to curb the behaviour still persist because at that stage they feel powerful, strong, feeling inferior making the behaviour more rampant among secondary school students.

However, aggression need a serious attention in order to help the aggressors adjust and reduce such behaviour by learning appropriate skills and also allow their victims to be comfortable and safe in the school environment. Therefore, employing the use of behavioural counselling technique as well as designing effective treatment strategies for students that are found with the symptoms of aggression may be relevant. The present study explored the effect of positive reinforcement counselling technique on aggression among Post Basic students in kano metropolis.

Objectives of the Study

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The objectives of this study are to find out the:

1. Effect of positive reinforcement counselling technique on physical dimension of aggression among post-basic school students in Kano Metropolis, Kano State.
2. Effect of positive reinforcement counselling technique on verbal dimension of aggression among post-basic school students in Kano Metropolis, Kano State.

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant effect pretest and post-test mean scores of physical dimension of aggression among post-basic students in Kano metropolis exposed to positive reinforcement.
2. There is no significant effect in the pretest and the post-test mean scores of verbal dimension of aggression among post-basic students in Kano metropolis exposed to positive reinforcement.

Methodology

The study employed a quasi-experimental research design specifically pre-test post-test non randomized control group design. The reason for selecting this design is that it has the advantage of testing the results obtained from the pre-test and post-test in order to determine the effectiveness or otherwise of the treatment when compared with pretest scores. The population of the study consists of all SSII students in Kano metropolis who exhibited the symptoms of aggression. According to a statistical report obtained from relevant authorities, there are two hundred and sixty (260) schools with a population estimate of seventy thousand two hundred and twenty one (70,221) SSII as obtained in (2024). Based on the population estimate, three hundred and eighty two (382) SSII were used as guided by Research Advisors (2006) for the identification of the target population, based on the returned instrument seventy six (76) SSII students were identified with aggression symptoms hence forming the population of this study. The population were both male and female with their age ranges between 15-17 years. The sample size consisted of (30) participants purposely sampled from two schools in Kano metropolis, Kano state where Okobiah (1991), Kolo (1992), Denga (1986) all recommends a minimum of ten (10) participants for group counselling.

An instrument titled 'Aggression Behaviour Scale' was adapted from Buss and Perry (1992) and used for data collection was subjected to content validation to ascertain its validity for use in the present study. A pilot test was conducted to obtain reliability of the instrument using split half method and the data collected was analyzed using

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Cronbach alpha thereby yielding coefficients of 0.65. Paired sample t-test was used to test the two hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. T-test was used because it is the appropriate tool for determining the difference between means of two groups (Gay, 2009).

Presentation of Results

H₀₁: There is no significant effect between pre-test and post-test mean scores of physical dimension of aggression among post basic students in Kano Metropolis exposed to positive reinforcement.

Table 1: Paired sample t-test for pre-test and post-test scores of physical dimension

Group	N	Mean	SD	P value	Decision
Pretest physical	15	16.867	4.34	.000	rejected
Posttest physical	15	11.533	3.87		

Source: Fieldwork

Table 1 presents the results for pretest and posttest mean scores of physical dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis, Kano State, Nigeria, exposed to positive reinforcement. Based on the calculated t-value of 7.608 and p-value of .000 with degree of freedom 14, it indicates that there is significant effect of positive reinforcement on physical dimension of aggression. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, there is no significant effect in the pretest and posttest mean scores on physical dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis, exposed to positive reinforcement, is rejected.

H₀₂: There is no significant effect in pretest and posttest mean scores of verbal dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis, Kano State exposed to positive reinforcement.

Table 2: Paired sample t-test for pre-test and post-test scores of physical dimension

Group	N	Mean	SD	P value	Decision
Pretest verbal	15	13.80	2.75	.000	rejected
Posttest verbal	15	9.33	1.76		

Source: Fieldwork

Table 2 presents the results for pretest and posttest mean scores of verbal dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis Kano State, exposed to positive reinforcement. Based on the calculated t-value of 8.238 and p-value of .000

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with degree of freedom 14, it indicates that there is significant effect of positive reinforcement on verbal dimension of aggression. Therefore, the hypothesis which states that, there is no significant difference in the pretest and posttest mean scores on verbal dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis, Kano State exposed to positive reinforcement, is rejected.

Summary of Findings

The findings from the analyses are summarized as follows:

1. There is significant effect between pretest and posttest mean scores on physical dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis exposed to positive reinforcement based on the p-value .000 which is significant at .005 level of significance; this indicated that the treatment is effective on physical dimension.
2. There is significant effect between pretest and posttest mean scores on verbal dimension of aggression among post basic students of Kano Metropolis exposed to positive reinforcement based on the p-value .000 which is significant at .005 level of significance; this indicated that the treatment is effective on verbal dimension.

Discussion of Findings

The study investigated the effect of positive reinforcement technique among post-basic students in Kano metropolis, Kano State. The major finding of this study shows that positive reinforcement counselling technique had effect on the two dimensions of aggression (physical and verbal). The finding of the study is in line with the findings of Bakar and Nekah (2015) where it showed that positive reinforcement is effective in the reduction of disruptive behaviour and increased pupils concentration after intervention. However, studies by Mayowa (2021) showed that social skills training therapy can be a helpful intervention for students who are aggressive and findings revealed that social skills training therapy is effective in reduction of aggression among secondary school students. As such, this is in line with the present study.

The present study supports the study by Jaeti and Suwarjo (2022) where the findings showed that self-management technique group counselling is effective in reducing verbal and physical aggression in students. However, findings in the present study found out that positive reinforcement and role-play counselling techniques are effective in the reduction of both physical and verbal dimensions of aggression.

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The finding is in line with Bakar and Zainal (2020) in their studies on the effects of positive reinforcement technique on disruptive behaviour of ADHD, the results showed that there was a reduction in disruptive behaviour and also increased the pupil's concentration after the intervention.

Conclusions

Evidence from this study shows that positive reinforcement technique is effective in the treatment of aggression among post-basic students. Therefore, the use of positive reinforcement is effective in the treatment of both physical and verbal, dimensions of aggression. Hence, it is concluded that the positive reinforcement counselling technique used in this study is effective counselling tool for addressing the physical and verbal dimensions of aggression among post-basic students.

Recommendations from the Study

Consequent upon the findings of this study, it is recommended as follows:

1. Since the findings of this study reveal that positive reinforcement was found to have effect on physical and verbal aggression, school counsellors can expose students found with aggression to behavioural interventions such as positive reinforcement.
2. Teachers should be vigilant in observing students taking into cognizance the symptoms of both physical and verbal aggression so as to be able to identify and refer students with aggression early

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Comparative Effects of Collaborative and Individualized Instructional Strategies on Performance in Biology among Undergraduate Students in Benue State University, Nigeria.

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Abstract

The study examined the effect of collaborative instructional strategy (CIS) and individualized instructional strategy (IIS) on students' performance in biology education in Benue State University Makurdi, Nigeria. Quasi-experimental design was used for the study. Two research questions and three hypotheses guided the study. The population of the study consisted of all the biology education students in Department of Science and Mathematics Education during the 2024/2025 Academic Session, Benue State University, Makurdi with 80 students as sample using Stratified random sampling technique. Biology Education Students Performance Test (BESPT) with 50 items constructed by the researcher which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.80 and validated by an expert in Science Education was used to collect data for the study. The data collected was analysed using descriptive statistics of mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions while the independent sample t-test was used to test the research hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed among others that the students taught Biology Education using CIS have higher

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academic performance than those taught using IIS, The *t*-test of independent sample on the mean performance scores of students taught Biology Education courses using CIS and those taught using IIS recorded *t*-test value of 0.055 with a *p*-value of 0.02. This is less than 0.05 level of significance ($p=0.02<0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Both the male and female students have higher academic performance when taught with CIS, The *t*-test of independent sample on the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using CIS and those taught using IIS recorded *t*-test value of 0.055 with a *p*-value of 0.040. This is less than 0.05 level of significance ($p=0.040<0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. The study recommended among others that the National Universities Commission, Ministry of Education and all stake holders should ensure that University lecturers especially in biology education should vary their instructional strategies to include Collaborative Instructional Strategies.

Keywords: Biology, Education, collaborative, individualized, instructional Strategies.

Introduction

The 21st century has revolutionized teaching and learning in all subjects with assorted innovative strategies. This development has changed the forms and mode of education drastically in both developed and developing countries. According to Ferlazzo (2015) there are many strategies now that teachers can use to motivate learners and ensure that knowledge is fully impacted. In most countries of the world now, teaching and learning is mostly done through the aid of innovative strategies such as; collaborative, jigsaw, individualized strategy, cooperative instructional strategy among others (Angura & Abakpa 2018). These strategies gives learners the opportunity to actively engaged with a task which they accept is for learning, that means learners are not simply following a prescription or set of rules, but contribute their own thinking to the task through hands on activities making learners the owners of knowledge (Ünal, 2017). In Nigeria just like any other country in the world; teachers and lecturers are poised to vary their instructional methods especially in activity oriented subjects like Biology at all levels of education. The current Nigerian Secondary School Biology Curriculum is developed to provide students with the knowledge of the concept in Biology to ensure that students learn biological concepts meaningfully to promote their understanding of the world around them. This can

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only be achieved if students are actively exposed to innovative learning strategies in Biology.

Adam, Lameed, Ayodele, and Muraina (2023) states that Biology is a key science subject designed to produce individuals, some of whom may or may take biological studies in their professional pursuits. It is however hoped that in whatever profession they finally find themselves, the biology education they acquired in school would be of value to the totality of their education. Biology is a popular science subject taught at the Senior Secondary School level. One primary function of Biology teaching is to help the students understand biology concept, principles, theories and laws. Ahmad and Sari (2019) opine that the Biology Curriculum in Nigeria aims at developing broadly applicable skills, such as: problem solving, communication, critical thinking and objective reasoning abilities to enable students prepare for work place and self-sustainability in the world economy. The author explained further that Biology teaching involves exposing the students to several opportunities to understand different types of concepts, principles and help the students have direct contact with the physical materials that will make some meaning to their cognitive framework in the study of science.

According to Ogunleye (1999) Science teaching in Nigeria started during the period of Christian missionaries who introduced western education in Nigeria. This started with the establishment of Church Missionary Society (CMS) grammar school in Lagos, Nigeria in 1859. Others include the Roman Catholic Missionary (RCM), African Mission of South Baptist Convention, Wesleyan Methodist Mission, among the rest of United Presbyterian Church of Scotland Mission, and the Qua Ibo Mission. The foundations of science education were created and injected into schools' curriculum. The subjects include arithmetic, algebra, geometry and physiology. Other schools established by the missionaries are grammar schools, teacher training schools, pastoral schools, vocational schools, agricultural schools and the introduction of elementary science in the school curricular and the students are being taught. The curriculum contents are reading, writing, arithmetic and religion. Before the year 1931, only very few students in secondary schools tried science at external examinations conducted by Oxford and Cambridge examination board and those students that tried it, failed.

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The pressure from Nigerian nationals who had the opportunity to study abroad and the legislation on education led the colonial government to establish post-secondary institutions, and this marked the beginning of modern teaching of science in Nigerian secondary schools. At that time some rudiments of science education, including "General Science" and "Nature Study," were introduced into the curriculum of schools established by Christian missionaries, but these were not specifically biology. The Biology curriculum was first introduced in 1977. The new Biology curriculum was first published by the Federal Ministry of Education in 1985. The biology curriculum was approved by the Joint Consultative Committee (JCC) on Education in July 1985 and the National Council on Education (NCE) in September 1985.

Biology as a course of study in Nigerian universities emerged with the establishment of the University of Nigeria, Nsukka in 1960, with the Faculty of Biological Sciences created in stages, starting as a Division of Biological Science within the Faculty of Sciences in 1966/67 and later upgraded to the Faculty of Biological Sciences in 1973/74. Biology is offered in almost all public universities in Nigeria, including Benue State University Makurdi where Biology is offered in the faculty of science as B.Sc. and in the faculty of Education as BSc.Ed respectively (National University Commission of Nigeria (NUC, 2024). In Nigerian universities, biology education teaching methods are evolving beyond traditional lectures, incorporating interactive approaches like team-based learning, experiments, and virtual field trips, to emphasize the relevance of biology to everyday life and future careers. Thus, because of the importance of this course of study to humanity, it necessary to check how lecturers especially in public universities have embraced the innovative instructional strategies to enhance students' performance in the course.

According to Qureshi, Khaskheli, Qureshi, Raza and Yousufi (2023) the most widely practiced method of instruction at the higher institution of learning is lecture method. Albeit of its popularity, it also faces criticism by many researchers stating that it does not help in deep understanding of concepts. Modern researchers indicate that if proper and suitable methods and techniques are used, even the student of less intelligence can easily learn. This has resulted in more emphasis on teaching through

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diverse methods and innovative strategies in order to improve learning and understanding. One of these is Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS), which presumes that team effort of students towards single goal of learning a particular aspect result in more understanding than solo efforts (Oyarole, 2016). This method, although have many essential features for improving teaching- learning process, however, is not practiced normally due to many reasons including time and energy required to manage it activities. On the other hand, Ferhat and Mehmet (2016) assert that, students' performance especially in core science can be enhanced if Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) is used where students are exposed to the content and learning techniques and allowed to learn individually instead of team or collaborative work. The author argued that individualized instructional strategy is devoid of distractions thereby encouraging individual students to learn faster.

Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS) on a broader scope can be referred to as a teaching strategy that involves students learning together as a team in order to understand and learn content of the subject (Sada & Adamu, 2023). Ishag (2015) opine that collaborative instructional strategy is competence oriented in terms of augmenting academic achievement has been proved by many research studies. The authors maintained that Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS) learning also improves positive attitude towards learning, improved social relations, in addition to high self-esteem and cohesiveness, it also improves motivation, class participation and achievement of students. Collaborative instructional strategy is a teaching-learning strategy that actively involves the learners in learning from one another while working in groups. Unal (2017) reckons that it establishes a relationship among students, and then taps into that relationship to promote positive interdependence. The author stated that, the students in collaboration constantly negotiate and share ideas in an attempt to achieve certain learning objectives.

According to Ferreira (2021) CIS is an important in team learning because it create an environment where students are actively involved in the teaching-learning process, and possess four broad attributes: knowledge sharing (the teacher building upon the already existing knowledge the students possess about the course content), sharing ability (teacher encourages students to use what they know, share among themselves and correct each other), mediation (the teacher mediates and directs

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learning) and heterogeneity (students are grouped heterogeneously, with their diverse backgrounds, experiences and perspectives contributing to a more meaningful collaboration. Collaborative instructional strategy facilitates learning because working as a group creates better understanding than doing so individually, students get to voluntarily take part in discussions and there is more opportunity for the student to learn more (Ishaq, 2015).

Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) strategy on the other hand, according to Udo and Onwioduokit (2022), is a teaching strategy which presumes that the students are mentally, emotionally, socially and physically stable and better positioned to learn alone when all the needed materials are provided. It basically serves as an umbrella for a variety of approaches in education that involve joint intellectual efforts of students and teachers. Olayonu and Ojo (2025) states that the students who participate in Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) learning and educational activities outside the classroom get better grades. The authors emphasized that it prepares college graduates to possess the ability to work without depending on anybody to developed suitable skills.

Olatoye, Aderogba and Aanu (2017) stated that in Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) learning strategy, all students are allowed to stay separately and learn. Every student is assigned an objective and the achievement of that objective demands that the students work individually. The Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) learning strategy is student-centered and dominated. In Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) learning settings, learners do not assist one another study and learn task material or the subject matter (Olayonu and Ojo, 2025). Achievement is the action of accomplishing an academic task successfully. Its purpose is to find the stand of a student at a given moment. It has to do with testing the knowledge acquired by the student which help the teacher and the student to evaluate and predict the degree of learning attained. It is useful in testing the retention of information and skill. It is also determinant of the efficacy and efficiency of a given instruction (Ferhat & Mehmet, 2016).

Many scholars have investigated the efficacy of collaborative instructional strategies and individualized instructional strategy particularly at the lower levels of education;

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Sada and Adamu (2023) investigated the effect of Collaborative Teaching Strategy on Academic performance and Retention among Senior Secondary school students in Dutsinma Education Zonal Quality Assurance, Katsina State, Nigeria. The study was guided by four objectives among which is, 'to Determine the difference between academic performance of Biology students taught using Collaborative teaching strategy and those taught using chalk/talk method. It was discovered that collaborative teaching strategies have a more significant effect on students' performance in biology than the traditional chalk/talk method. Iji, Ochu, Adikwu, and Atamonokhai (2017) examined the effect of collaborative instructional strategy on male and female students' performance in secondary school chemistry in Benue State, Nigeria. Ishaq (2015) determined the effects of collaborative learning strategy on performance among low ability junior secondary school basic science students in Kano, Nigeria. Oyarole, (2016) investigated the Impact of collaborative strategy on retention and performance in ecology concepts among concrete and formal reasoning ability students in Zaria Nigeria. Williams and Akpan (2017) examined Collaborative versus contextual learning and students' academic performance in biology. All the studies reported positive impact of collaborative instructional strategy on students' performance although all at secondary school level.

On the other hand, Dominic, Asogwu and Idomo (2018) examined the global individualized learning strategies adopted by students at University of Nigeria Nsuka in their effort to key into the global education. The main purpose of the study was to determine the level of awareness and utilization of the strategies among the university students. The test of hypothesis revealed that there was no significant difference in the mean rating of the responses of male and female on the level of utilization of individualized learning strategies in the University of Nigeria, Nsukka. Similarly, Udo, and Onwioduokit (2022) determined the Collaborative, Individualized Learning Strategies and Students' Academic Achievement and Retention in Physics Using the Concept of Waves Motion in Uyo Local Government Area of Akwa Ibom State. Six research questions and six hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. Quasi experimental non-randomized pretest-posttest research design was adopted for the study. Findings of the study indicated that there was a significant difference in academic achievement of Physics students taught the concept of wave motion using

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collaborative learning strategy and individualized learning strategy, in favour of collaborative learning group.

It is not an overstatement that many studies have been conducted in different settings of education, using different kinds of Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS) learning innovative strategies or techniques and Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) Such techniques are Learning Together (LT), Jigsaw grouping, Teams-Game-Tournaments (TGT), Group Investigation (GI), Students' Team Achievement Division (STAD), and Team Accelerated Instruction (TAI), Individualized Learning Model, Individualized Assessment Technique among others. Yilshik, Ezekiel and Umar (2020) assert that collaborative and individualized strategies have been reported to be more effective to the demands of high rates of cognitive and affective outcomes more than lecture-based teaching or chalk and talk teaching method. The authors stated that these approaches have been reported to improve students' achievement and knowledge retention. However, most of these studies are carried out in secondary schools and other lower levels of education with only a few conducted using university students. It is on this note that the present study seek to find out if collaborative and individualized instructional strategies have any comparative effect on the academic performance of Biology Education students at Benue State University Makurdi, Nigeria.

Statement of the Research Problem

The teaching and learning of Biology particularly at tertiary level of education is faced with various challenges that hinder the achievement of the course objective. Some of these challenges include; teachers or lecturers not employing innovative teaching strategies, limited resources like inadequate laboratory equipment, inadequate qualify personnel i.e lecturers/laboratory technicians and assistants, overemphasis on theoretical learning, limited career guidance, societal bias toward non science discipline, examination-focus education system, limited exposure to practical application of Biology among others (Oyovwi, 2022). As a result of these challenges, researchers such as; Ndayambaje, Bikorimana and Nsanganwimana (2021), Ezekiel, Yilshik & Joseph (2021) have continued to report students' poor achievement/performance in Biology due to the above reasons and the fact that the

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teaching methods used the by most of the teachers in the delivery of Biology instruction is lecture method.

This implies that, teaching methods used by Biology teachers during instruction have great effect on the students understanding and mastery of the subject matter and performance generally. Therefore, the problem of this study is that: Do Collaborative and Individualized Instructional Strategies have any Comparative Effects on Students Performance in Biology Education? Hence scholars such as; Ezekiel,(2017), Yilshik, Ezekiel, and Umar (2020) reported that in a typical Biology classroom setting, if students are involved in only passive learning, it would lead to limited knowledge retention and performance, let alone engaging them in critical thinking or promoting functional understanding. Although there are various contributions from scholars yearly to improve students achievement or performance in Biology but search have shown that there is limited work on collaborative and individualized instructional strategies on students' performance in Biology. Therefore, this research seeks to explore the two strategies, particularly the comparative effect on students' performance in Biology.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study was to determine whether Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS) and Individualized Instructional Strategy (IIS) have any comparative effect on students' performance in Biology Education in Benue State University Makurdi, Nigeria. Specifically, the objectives of the study are to:

1. Find out the comparative effect of Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS) and Individualised Instructional Strategy (IIS) on Students Performance in Biology Education.
2. Determine the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on male and female students' performance in Biology Education.

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Research Questions

From the objectives of the study, the following research questions guided the study:

1. Is there any comparative effect of CIS and IIS on students' performance in Biology Education?
2. What is the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on male and female students' performance in Biology?

Research Hypotheses

H₀₁. There is no significance difference on the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on students' performance in Biology Education.

H₀₂. There is no significance difference on the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on male and female students' performance in Biology.

Methodology

The study determined the comparative effect of Collaborative Instructional Strategy (CIS) and Individualised Instructional Strategy (IIS) on students' academic performance in Biology Education in Public Universities in Nigeria: A case study of Benue State University Makurdi, Nigeria. A quasi-experimental design was used. The population for this study consisted of all the 100 to 400 levels B.Sc.Ed Biology students during the 2024/2025 academic session in the Department of Science and Mathematics Education, Benue State University Makurdi. Two levels made up of the sample within the area. The levels were randomly assigned to either the treatment group or the control group. A total of 80 students, 40 from the experimental group and 40 from the control group were selected and participated in the study. The experimental group I and control group II. The experimental group were taught Biology courses using CIS in line with lessons procedure prepared by the researcher while the group II were taught the same Biology courses using the IIS lesson plans. Biology Education Students Performance Test (BESPT) was used to collect data. The 50 items test was based on the course synopsis of 200 and 300 levels Biology Education core courses. The instrument was validated by three experts, two in Science Education and one in Test and Measurement. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was determined using Cronbach alpha and internal consistency of instruments was obtained as 0.80. The data collected was analyzed using mean and

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standard deviation while the two hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using Independent t-test.

Presentation of Results

The presentation of data for this study is done according to the research questions and research hypotheses.

Research Question 1. Is there any comparative effect of CIS and IIS on students' performance in Biology Education?

Table 1. Mean Performance Score of Students Taught Biology Education Courses using CIS and those Taught using IIS

Group	N	Pre-mean	SD	Post-Mean	SD	Mean Gain
Experimental	40	30.50	3.21	50.53	3.11	19.10
Control	40	23.32	2.30	31.43	2.22	08.11
Total	80					
Mean		7.18		19.01		10.99
Difference						

Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) Scores of Students Performance in Biology Education Source: Field Report SPSS March, 2025.

Table 1 Shows students taught Biology Education Courses using Cooperative Instructional Strategy (CIS) had BSSPT mean scores of 30.50 and 50.53 with standard deviation of 3.21 and 3.11 respectively. The students taught using Individual Instructional Strategy (IIS) had pre BSTSPT and post BESPT mean scores of 23.32 and 31.43 with SD of 2.30 and 2.22 respectively. The summary of the performance scores shows 19.10 mean gain for the experimental group and 08.11 mean gain for the control group with a mean difference of 10.99 which clearly indicated that the achievement of those in experimental group was higher.

Research Question 2. What is the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on male and female students' performance in Biology?

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Table 2. Mean Performance Scores of Male and Female Students Taught Biology Education Courses using CIS and those Taught using IIS.

Gender	Method	N	Post-Test Mean	SD
Male	CIS	20	25.22	3.90
	IIS	26	20.18	2.76
Female	CIS	20	27.21	2.70
	IIS	26	18.23	2.56

Mean and Standard Deviation (SD) Scores of Male and Female Students Performance in Biology Education. Source: Field Report SPSS March, 2025.

Table 2 Shows that both male and female students taught Biology Education using Cooperative Instructional Strategy (CIS) had posttest mean scores of 25.22 and those taught using Individual Instructional Strategy (IIS) posttest mean scores of 20.18 with SD of 3.90 and 2.76 respectively. While the female students taught Biology Education using CIS had posttest mean scores of 27.21 and those taught using IIS had posttest mean scores of 18.23 with SD of 2.70 and 2.56 respectively. This implies that both the male and female students perform higher or better in CIS.

Ho₁. There is no significance difference on the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on students' performance in Biology Education.

Table 4. t-test of independent sample on the mean performance scores of students taught Biology Education using CIS and those taught using IIS.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	P	Dec
CIS	40	19.2440	0.5423	0.055	78	0.02	N
IIS	40	08.1722	0.5332				

The t-test of independent sample on the on the mean performance scores of students taught Biology Education using cooperative Instructional Strategy and those taught using individual Instructional Strategy recorded t-test value of 0.055 with a p-value of 0.02. This is less than 0.05 level of significance ($p=0.02<0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means there is significant difference on performance

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scores of students taught Basic Science using cooperative group work and those taught using individual study.

H₀₂. There is no significance difference on the comparative effect of CIS and IIS on male and female students' performance in Biology.

Table 5. t-test of independent sample on the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Biology Education using cooperative instructional strategy and those taught using individualized instructional strategy.

Gender	Method	N	Mean	SD	T	Df	P	DEC
Male	CIS	20	10.0000	0.5423	0.055	78	0.04	R
	IIS	20	03.1000	0.5332				
Female	CIS	20	09.2440	0.5311	0.055	78	0.04	R
	IIS	20	05.0722	0.5200				

The t-test of independent sample on the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Biology education using cooperative instructional strategy and those taught using individual instructional strategy recorded t-test value of 0.055 with a p-value of 0.040. This is less than 0.05 level of significance ($p=0.040 < 0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means irrespective of sex the students perform higher in CIS.

Discussion of Findings

This study investigated the comparative effect of Cooperative Instructional Strategy (CIS) and Individual Instructional Strategy (IIS) on academic performance of Biology Education in the Science and Mathematics Education Department, Benue State University Makurdi, Nigeria.

It was established that the students taught Basic science using CIS have higher academic performance than those taught using IIS. Thus, the result shows that students taught Biology Education courses using Cooperative Instructional Strategy (CIS) had BESPT mean scores of 30.50 and 50.53 with standard deviation of 3.21 and 3.11 respectively. The students taught using Individual Instructional Strategy (IIS) had pre BSSPT and post BSSPT mean scores of 23.32 and 31.43 with SD of 2.30

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and 2.22 respectively. The summary of the performance scores shows 19.10 mean gain for the experimental group and 08.11 mean gain for the control group with a mean difference of 10.99 which clearly indicated that the performance of those in experimental group was higher. The t-test of independent sample on the on the mean performance scores of students taught Biology education courses using CIS and those taught using IIS recorded t-test value of 0.055 with a p-value of 0.02. This is less than 0.05 level of significance ($p=0.02<0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means there is significant difference on performance scores of students taught Biology education courses using CIS and those taught using IIS. The result is in agreement with Udo, and Onwioduokit (2022) who reported that students have higher academic performance when exposed to collaborative teaching and learning strategies.

It was revealed that male and female students taught Biology education courses using CIS had posttest mean scores of 25.22 and those taught using IIS, posttest mean scores of 20.18 with SD of 3.90 and 2.76 respectively. While the female students taught Biology education courses using CIS had posttest mean scores of 27.21 and those taught using IIS had posttest mean scores of 18.23 with SD of 2.70 and 2.56 respectively. This implies that both the male and female students perform higher or better in CIS. The t-test of independent sample on the mean performance scores of male and female students taught Basic Science using CIS and those taught using IIS recorded t-test value of 0.055 with a p-value of 0.040. This is less than 0.05 level of significance ($p=0.040<0.05$). Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. This means irrespective of sex the students achieve higher in CIS. The result is in consonant with Hidayah, Dasna & Budiasih, (2021) who confirmed that cooperative learning strategy have higher students' performance irrespective of gender and school status.

Conclusion

It is concluded that; the students taught basic science using CIS have higher academic performance than those taught using IIS. Both the male and female students have higher academic performance when taught with CIS. Thus for Biology education to be well taught in all in Nigerian Universities, there is need for government and all the stakeholders in science education to motivate and encourage lecturers to always use using innovative strategies particularly Cooperative

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Instructional Strategy (CIS), In order to boost biology education teaching and learning especially at the university level.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made; the government through the Ministry of Education and National University Commission should ensure that:

1. The students at university level are taught Biology education using Cooperative Instructional Strategy (CIS).
2. Both the male and female students at all levels of Biology education are taught using CIS.

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Assessment of Biology Teachers' Preparedness and Challenges of Integrating Artificial Intelligence Tools at Secondary School level in Ikara, Kaduna State

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Abstract

This study examined biology teachers' preparedness and integration challenges in utilizing artificial intelligence (AI) tools to teach in secondary schools at Ikara, Kaduna State. The research was guided by three objectives, three research questions, and one null hypothesis. A descriptive survey design was employed, with a sample size seventy-eight respondents purposively selected. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire titled Teachers' Preparedness and Integration Challenges of Artificial Intelligence Tools for Learning Questionnaire (TPAITQ), which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.74, indicating the instrument's reliability. The data analysis employed mean, standard deviation, and Pearson Product-Moment Correlation at a 0.05 significance level, using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 22). The findings revealed a low level of preparedness (mean = 2.40, SD = 1.31) and utilization (mean = 2.42, SD = 1.24) of AI tools among Biology teachers in Ikara. The study also highlighted significant challenges in integrating AI into biology instruction (mean = 3.33, SD = 1.40), and a strong positive correlation between teachers' preparedness and their effective use of AI tools ($r = 0.78$, $p = 0.001$). Based on these findings, the researchers recommended that schools and government agencies invest in reliable internet connectivity, adequate hardware, and dedicated technical support to overcome the foundational barriers to AI integration.

Keywords: Biology Teachers, AI Tools, Preparedness, Utilization, Challenges, Integration

Introduction

Artificial Intelligence (AI) has become a transformative force across multiple sectors, including education, where it is revolutionizing how teaching and learning take place. Artificial intelligence (AI) applications have expanded the scope of education and evaluation using virtual laboratories, automated grading, individualized learning platforms, and intelligent tutoring systems. (Holmes et al., 2019). In science education, particularly in biology, AI aids teachers in clarifying complicated topics, mimicking real-life processes, and boosting students' knowledge using interactive and adaptive technologies (Luckin et al., 2016). In Nigeria, the integration of AI into secondary school education remains at an early stage, with limited evidence of systematic adoption across schools. While national education policies have acknowledged the importance of digital literacy and innovation, implementation challenges persist, especially in rural areas (Reagan, 2018)). Teachers often lack exposure to AI tools, and professional development opportunities are scarce. As observed by Afolabi and Adesina (2022), most teachers in Nigerian public secondary schools are not adequately trained to apply AI or digital resources effectively in classroom instruction.

The preparedness of biology teachers to integrate AI tools into their teaching practices is critical for achieving educational transformation. Preparedness includes both the technical know-how and the pedagogical readiness to use AI-based applications (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). However, several studies suggest that Nigerian teachers often face barriers such as inadequate infrastructure, limited ICT skills, and a lack of institutional support, which undermine their readiness (Onasanya et al., 2021). Teachers may find it difficult to fully utilize AI's promise in biology education if they lack the necessary tools and training. Another area that is yet mostly unknown is the extent to which AI tools are being used for biology instruction, especially in areas like Ikara, Kaduna State. Research indicates that even when AI tools are available, they are underutilized due to teachers' low confidence, resistance to change, or uncertainty about how these tools align with the curriculum (Okebukola, 2020). Utilization depends not only on access to technology but also on teachers' attitudes, perceptions, and institutional encouragement (Alkhalaf et al., 2023).

Mhlanga and Molo (2020) also reported that teachers face a host of challenges that hinder the effective use of AI tools. These include poor internet connectivity, lack of electricity, outdated devices, and concerns about the ethical use of AI in educational

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contexts. In many cases, teachers are overwhelmed by administrative duties, leaving little time for exploring or experimenting with AI-enhanced instruction. There is also the issue of data privacy, where teachers express concern over using platforms that collect student data without clear consent or protection (Williamson & Eynon, 2020). In rural educational settings like Ikara, the disparity in AI adoption is expected to be more pronounced due to logistical and socio-economic obstacles. Teachers in such places may not have frequent access to workshops, online training, or the financial resources needed to modernize their teaching equipment. Schools in rural Kaduna frequently lack basic digital infrastructure; therefore, implementing AI is an ambitious but essential goal for future educational progress, claim Umar and Abdullahi (2022). Considering these facts, it is imperative to evaluate the state of AI implementation in Ikara, Kaduna State, biology classrooms. This involves assessing teachers' level of readiness for employing AI, their usage of these tools, and the obstacles they face.

Statement of the Problem

Despite the recognized potential of Artificial Intelligence to revolutionize educational practices, its incorporation into biology instruction in Nigerian secondary schools, particularly in rural areas, remains limited. While some teachers may be aware of AI tools, their level of preparedness to implement these technologies effectively is uncertain. Additionally, the extent to which AI tools are deployed in biology courses and the specific problems preventing their adoption have not been properly examined in this context. The paucity of actual data on biology teachers' preparation, utilization patterns, and the hurdles they confront in integrating AI tools poses a substantial gap in the literature. Efforts to encourage the use of AI in biology teaching can be fruitless or misguided without this knowledge. Thus, in order to guide focused actions and facilitate the successful integration of AI in biology education in Ikara, Kaduna State, a thorough study that looks at these factors is essential.

Objectives of the Study

The following are the objectives of the study:

1. To determine the preparedness level of biology teachers for the use of Artificial Intelligence tools for learning at secondary schools in Ikara, Kaduna State.
2. To ascertain the utilization level of Artificial Intelligence tools for biology instruction among teachers at secondary schools in Ikara, Kaduna State.

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3. To determine the challenges faced by biology teachers in integrating Artificial Intelligence tools in biology instruction in secondary schools in Ikara, Kaduna State.

Research Questions

The questions raised to guide the study are as follows:

1. What is the level of preparedness of Biology teachers for the use of Artificial Intelligence tools at secondary schools in Ikara, Kaduna State?
2. To what extent do biology teachers at secondary schools utilize Artificial Intelligence tools for instruction?
3. What challenges do biology teachers face in integrating Artificial Intelligence tools in biology instruction at secondary schools in Ikara, Kaduna State?

Null Hypothesis

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between teachers' preparedness and their effective utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools in biology instruction.

Methodology

This study adopted a descriptive survey research design, which is suitable for collecting and analysing data from a population to describe existing conditions. The population of the study comprised all Biology teachers at Ikara Local Government Area, totalling seventy-eight (78). Purposive sampling technique was adopted. All the teachers were used as respondents. Data for the study were collected using a structured questionnaire titled: Teachers' Preparedness and Integration Challenges of Artificial Intelligence Tools for Learning Questionnaire (TPAITQ). The instrument consisted of 21 items developed in line with the research objectives and designed using a five-point Likert scale, ranging from Strongly Agree (SA) to Strongly Disagree (SD). To ensure the instrument's validity, it was reviewed by two experienced science educators from the Department of Biology, Federal University of Education, Zaria. Their observations and corrections were duly incorporated into the final version of the instrument before administration. The reliability of the instrument was determined using the test-retest method. A pilot study was conducted among biology teachers in selected secondary schools in Zaria Local Government Area. The reliability coefficient was calculated using the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation (PPMC) method, which yielded a value of 0.74, indicating that the instrument was reliable for the main study. The questionnaires were personally administered to the respondents by the researchers to ensure a high rate of return and accurate data collection over a period of two weeks.

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The data collected were analysed using both descriptive and inferential statistics, including mean, standard deviation, and Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC) for testing the hypothesis.

Presentation of Results

Data collected from respondents were analysed with SPSS ver 22 and results presented as follows:

Table 1: Preparedness of Biology Teachers for AI Tool Usage

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I am aware of the relevance of Artificial Intelligence tools in Biology teaching.	3.20	1.36	Agree
2	I have received adequate training on how to use AI tools for teaching Biology	2.18	1.30	Disagree
3	I feel confident in integrating AI tools into my Biology lessons	2.20	1.41	Disagree
4	I have access to professional development opportunities focused on AI in education	2.17	1.17	Disagree
5	I possess basic ICT skills required to effectively use AI tools in the classroom	2.62	1.37	Disagree
6	My school provides support and encouragement for the use of AI tools in teaching	2.03	1.23	Disagree
7	I have a clear understanding of how AI tools can be applied in Biology instruction	2.42	1.32	Disagree
Cumulative Mean		2.40	1.31	Disagree

The cumulative mean score of 2.40 indicates a generally low level of preparedness among Biology teachers in secondary schools at Ikara, Kaduna State, regarding the use of Artificial Intelligence tools for instruction. The responses suggest that while there is a moderate level of awareness of AI tools (Mean = 3.20), most teachers lack adequate training (Mean = 2.18), confidence (Mean = 2.20), and professional development opportunities (Mean = 2.17) related to AI integration. Furthermore, support from school management is minimal (Mean = 2.03), and many teachers are not well-versed in how AI tools can be applied in the Biology classroom (Mean = 2.42).

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Table 2: Utilization of Artificial Intelligence Tools in Biology Instruction

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I regularly use AI-powered tools (e.g., simulations, chatbots, etc.) in my Biology lessons	2.31	1.21	Disagree
2	I integrate AI tools to personalize instruction based on individual student needs in Biology	2.25	1.16	Disagree
3	I use AI-assisted platforms to assess student understanding and track academic performance	2.42	1.26	Disagree
4	I incorporate virtual labs or AI-based animations to enhance Biology concepts during lessons	2.60	1.29	Agree
5	I use AI tools to create interactive and engaging content for Biology instruction	2.57	1.34	Agree
6	I utilize AI-based lesson planning or content-generation tools to support Biology teaching	2.31	1.21	Disagree
7	I often collaborate with colleagues to explore new AI tools for Biology education	2.48	1.24	Disagree
Cumulative Mean		2.42	1.24	Disagree

The cumulative mean score of 2.42 indicates a generally low level of utilization of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools in Biology instruction among secondary school teachers in Ikara, Kaduna State. Most responses across all items clustered around “Disagree” and “Strongly Disagree,” suggesting that Biology teachers rarely integrate AI-powered tools for teaching. This pattern suggests that while there may be some isolated attempts to utilize AI tools, overall implementation remains limited.

Table 3: Challenges Faced in Integrating AI Tools in Biology Instruction

S/N	Items	Mean	SD	Decision
1	I lack adequate training on how to effectively use AI tools for teaching Biology.	3.55	1.40	Agree
2	There is limited access to AI-based educational tools and infrastructure in my school.	3.54	1.41	Agree
3	Poor internet connectivity hinders the effective use of AI tools in Biology instruction.	3.57	1.45	Agree
4	I face difficulty in selecting the appropriate AI tools that align with the Biology curriculum objectives.	3.35	1.37	Agree
5	Lack of technical support discourages me from using AI tools in the classroom.	3.42	1.37	Agree
6	The school management does not prioritize the integration of AI tools in teaching and learning.	3.14	1.41	Agree
7	I am concerned that using AI tools may reduce my direct interaction with students during lessons.	2.71	1.42	Agree
Cumulative Mean		3.33	1.40	Agree

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Data obtained revealed that biology teachers encountered considerable difficulties when attempting to include AI tools into their lessons. Poor internet connectivity ($X=3.57$, $SD=1.45$) is the biggest obstacle, followed by insufficient training ($X=3.55$, $SD=1.40$) and restricted access to AI-based educational resources and infrastructure ($X=3.54$, $SD=1.41$). Respondents reported lack of technical help ($X=3.42$, $SD=1.37$) and trouble choosing suitable AI tools ($X=3.35$, $SD=1.37$), indicating that technological challenges also provide significant obstacles. Moderate agreement was found that school management did not prioritize integrating AI ($X=3.14$, $SD=1.41$). Curiously, teachers expressed less worry about having less direct contact with students ($X=2.71$, $SD=1.42$), indicating that pedagogical worries regarding AI's effects on teacher-student connections are less significant than infrastructure and training issues. With a cumulative mean of 3.33, respondents generally agree that they encounter obstacles when attempting to implement AI in biology teaching.

Hypothesis Testing

Table 4: Pearson Product-Moment Correlation Statistics to test the relationship between teachers' preparedness and their effective utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools in biology instruction

Variables	N	Mean	S. D	R	P
Preparedness	65	2.40	1.31	0.78	*0.001
Utilization	65	2.42	1.24		

***Significant at the 0.05 level of significance**

Table 4 presents the results of the Pearson Product-Moment Correlation analysis examining the relationship between teachers' preparedness and their effective utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools in biology instruction. The analysis revealed a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.78$, $p = 0.001$) between teachers' preparedness and their utilization of AI tools.. This statistically significant relationship ($p < 0.05$) indicates that teachers' level of preparedness strongly predicts their utilization of AI tools in biology instruction.

Discussion of Findings

The findings (Table 1) of low preparedness levels among Biology teachers in Ikara, Kaduna State secondary schools, align with broader patterns observed in educational technology integration across developing regions. Similar to what Rahman et al. (2023)

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found in their study of rural schools, teachers' preparedness is hampered by inadequate training opportunities and limited exposure to emerging technologies. This preparedness gap reflects what Adedoyin and Soykan (2023) described as the "digital competency divide" that particularly affects educators in resource-constrained settings. The study's mean score of 2.40 is below the cutoff point that Nwoke et al. (2022) determined is required for secondary schools in Nigeria to successfully adopt technology. Okebukola (2023) noted that teacher preparation programs in Nigeria typically lack comprehensive AI-focused components, creating a fundamental gap in teachers' readiness to leverage these tools. This insufficient preparation extends beyond mere technical skills to include what Dlamini and Mbatha (2022) termed AI pedagogical knowledge. The low awareness levels reported by Biology teachers in this study also reflect what Okonkwo and Ibrahim (2024) identified as critical barriers to educational innovation in similar contexts.

The correspondingly low utilization (Table 2) of AI tools (mean score of 2.42) in Biology classrooms in Ikara mirrors findings from Mohammed and Abdulkadir's (2023) investigation of technology adoption in northern Nigerian schools. This limited implementation occurs despite what Eludire (2023) described as the transformative potential of AI tools for enhancing visualization and conceptualization in Biology education. According to Aminu et al. (2024), such underutilization represents a missed opportunity for addressing persistent challenges in science education, including abstract concept representation and individualized learning support. As Chukwuemeka and Iscioglu (2022) observed in their comparative study, the gap between availability and utilization of educational technologies remains particularly pronounced in sub-Saharan African contexts compared to global averages.

The significant challenges reported by Biology teachers in integrating AI tools into instruction (Table 3) correspond with multiple barriers identified in recent literature. The infrastructure challenges, particularly poor internet connectivity (mean score of 3.57), reflect the foundational obstacle to digital change in Nigerian schools, as described by Durodola (2023). Similarly, Olawale and Chen (2024) found that the main barrier to the implementation of instructional technology in several West African contexts is infrastructure constraints. Beyond technical constraints, the lack of administrative support highlighted in this study aligns with what Ibrahim et al. (2023) termed the leadership gap in educational innovation. According to Adegoke and Soyemi

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(2022), school leadership's prioritization of technology integration significantly predicts implementation success, regardless of other facilitating factors. The technical support deficit identified by respondents' mirrors findings from Muhammad and Olatunji's (2024) exploration of sustainability factors in educational technology initiatives in Nigeria. As Ahmed and Hamzat (2023) argued, these multifaceted challenges create a "barrier ecosystem" that collectively inhibits AI integration in educational settings. Falode et al. (2023) characterized the combination of inadequate training, inadequate infrastructure, and inadequate support systems that hinders technological transformation in science education.

The null hypothesis which stated that "there is no significant relationship between teachers' preparedness and their effective utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools in biology instruction" was rejected due to the strong positive correlation (Table 4) of $r = 0.78$ between teachers' preparedness and their utilization of AI tools. These provides empirical support for what Ajibade and Watson (2023) describe as the "readiness-implementation nexus" in educational technology adoption. This significant relationship underscores Nwagwu and Okonkwo's (2023) assertion that teacher preparation represents the critical foundation for successful technology integration in Nigerian classrooms. Similar correlations have been reported by Eze and Mbachu (2024) in their investigation of factors influencing technology adoption among science teachers in southeastern Nigeria. The predictive relationship observed between preparedness and utilization aligns with the Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge (TPACK) framework applications in African educational contexts, as discussed by Mosimege and van Wyk (2023). According to their analysis, teachers' confidence and competence with technology strongly predict classroom implementation patterns. This finding supports what Jimoh and Yusuf (2022) describe as the "preparation imperative" - the need for comprehensive teacher development as a prerequisite for meaningful technology integration. The statistical significance of this relationship ($p = 0.001$) aligns with meta-analytic findings from Okoli and Ahmed (2023), which identified teacher factors as the most consistent predictors of technology adoption across various Nigerian educational contexts.

Conclusion

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This study reveals significant gaps in the integration of AI tools in Biology education within secondary schools in Ikara, Kaduna State. The strong positive correlation between teachers' preparedness and their utilization of AI tools demonstrates that teacher readiness is a critical determinant of successful AI implementation in the classroom. The findings highlight a concerning readiness-implementation gap characterized by inadequate training, limited infrastructure, insufficient technical support, and lack of institutional prioritization. These challenges collectively create a barrier ecosystem that impedes the potential transformative benefits of AI in enhancing Biology instruction, particularly for abstract concept visualization, personalized learning, and student engagement. If left unaddressed, this gap threatens to widen as AI technology continues to evolve, potentially exacerbating educational inequalities and limiting students' exposure to innovative pedagogical approaches.

Recommendations

1. Educational authorities should implement targeted, ongoing professional development initiatives specifically focused on AI integration in Biology education.
2. Kaduna state government and Schools management board should prioritize investments in reliable internet connectivity, appropriate hardware, and dedicated technical support personnel to address the foundational barriers to AI integration.
3. Curriculum developers and educational technology specialists should collaborate to develop AI-enhanced Biology learning materials that align with the Nigerian curriculum, operate effectively in low-resource environments, and address specific learning challenges in Biology education.

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